

Identifying Key Factors to Facilitate the Successful Implementation of Medical Shared Decision-Making in Scotland: A Mixed Methods Approach

Abbie McGuire-Meiklem

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Division of Psychology

School of Education and Social Sciences, University of the West of Scotland

Supervisory Team:

Dr Elizabeth Boyle, Dr Melody Terras, Dr Joanne Ingram

Declaration of Authenticity

I declare that, except where explicit reference is made to the contribution of others, that this thesis is the result of my own work and has not been submitted for any other degree at the University of the West of Scotland or any other institution.

Abbie McGuire-Meiklem

Published Work and Presentations

1. McGuire, A. (2019, March). Shared decision making: the future of healthcare. In *The British Psychological Society Undergraduate Conference 2019*.
 - Conference paper on topic of thesis i.e. shared decision-making and decision aids.
2. McGuire, A., (2019). Tackling Societal Challenges in Health. *UWS Learning, Teaching & Research Conference*. Conference Poster.
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Common Abbreviations

UWS – University of the West of Scotland

SDM – Shared decision-making

DA – Decision aid

NHS – National Health Service

TPB – Theory of Planned Behaviour

TTM – Transtheoretical Model

ENGAGE – Engagement

SAT – Satisfaction

OV – Outcome variable

READINESS – Readiness to change

DECISION – Decisional needs

ED LEVEL – Education level

EMPLOY – Employment status

AWARE – Awareness of SDM

TREATMENT – Made a treatment decision

ATT – Attendance at a medical appointment

INT – Intention

MPRCQ2 – Multidimensional Pain Readiness to Change Questionnaire

CPAQ – Chronic Pain Assessment Questionnaire

DNAQ – Decisional Needs Assessment Questionnaire

NICE – National Institute for Health and Care Excellence

SDM-Q-9 – Shared Decision-Making Questionnaire

IPDASi – International Patient Decision Aid Standards

Abstract

Shared decision-making (SDM) is a practice in which patients and clinicians work in partnership to choose treatments, management packages, support packages, or tests based on the patient's informed preferences as well as clinical evidence. SDM was a critically important element of the 2016 Scottish model of healthcare quality. However, whilst the aim of the Scottish Government was that SDM should be standard practice in healthcare within Scotland, with decision aids (DAs) used to assist the SDM process, successful implementation of SDM and DAs is patchy and not currently the norm within the UK, with no known literature or review for Scotland and its individual health system.

Thus, the overall aim of the research reported in this thesis was to identify key factors that will facilitate the successful implementation of medical SDM in Scotland. Where previous research on SDM had focused on healthcare professionals, the thesis made an important contribution to knowledge by focusing specifically on patients' attitudes to and engagement with SDM. Conducting this research within Scotland also further contributes original knowledge, where previous research has focused on the UK as a whole, despite the differences in how health is delivered in its individual nations.

A multiphase mixed methods design was employed, consisting of two qualitative studies (studies 1 and 4) utilising semi-structured interviews and two quantitative studies (studies 2 and 3) via online surveys. Study 1 investigated the implementation of SDM and DAs in NHS Scotland using thematic analysis of interviews with members of Scottish NHS boards (n=9), with participants suggesting while SDM is successfully practiced, barriers such as lack of time, auditing and awareness need to be addressed, with recommendations provided for both these issues and the effective design and implementation of DAs. This was followed by two online surveys to identify predictors of both acceptance of SDM for individuals with chronic pain (study 2; n=195) and engagement with SDM for the Scottish general population (study 3; n=210). While both studies identified useful predictors to assist in delivering SDM effectively with both populations, it was clear that effective measures of SDM need to be identified, such as the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) utilised in study 3. Finally, experiences and attitudes towards SDM were investigated through thematic analysis of interviews with both members of the Scottish general population and individuals with chronic pain (n=24). Despite overall positive attitudes towards SDM, participants' experiences suggest that SDM is inconsistently implemented between healthcare professionals, geographical locations and healthcare departments. Recommendations were provided for training and education for healthcare professionals to achieve a wider standard of implementation.

The qualitative findings demonstrate despite positive attitudes towards SDM from both healthcare professionals and patients, the reports from professionals on successful implementation of SDM did not align with patient experiences. Recommendations were identified for provider training and education on SDM, as well as for the design and implementation of DAs to support SDM. In addition, effective and standardised audits of SDM also need to be implemented in order to adequately assess SDM implementation. The quantitative findings identify factors which were important for individuals with chronic pain to predict their acceptance of SDM, alongside factors which were important for members of the Scottish general population in predicting their engagement SDM. Importantly, awareness (study 2) and knowledge of SDM (studies 2 and 3) for patients indicates a need for training and education in SDM also with patients, not just for healthcare professionals. These studies also further highlighted the need for appropriate academic measures of SDM, such as the TPB.

To summarise, both the qualitative and quantitative findings in the thesis highlighted key factors that will facilitate the successful implementation of medical SDM in Scotland. Thus, healthcare professionals in Scotland, and perhaps even outside Scotland, should aim to implement and incorporate these key factors moving forward to successfully implement medical SDM in Scotland. The findings were discussed in relation to the research aims, previous literature, practical implications and ideas for future research were also proposed.

Chapter 1: Introduction

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1.1 Overview

Shared decision-making (SDM) is a critically important element of the new model of healthcare quality (Scottish Government, 2016; G. Smith, 2024). SDM amongst other benefits, promotes self-management and independence, and by giving patients a full understanding of their problems and greater responsibility for making choices, it also helps to reduce over-use of medical interventions (Murray, Burns, Tai, Lai, & Nazareth, 2004; O'Connor et al., 2009). Despite the central role of SDM in the government's new model of healthcare quality, the utilisation of SDM within the UK has been inconsistent (Coulter & Collins, 2011). Therefore, the overall aim of this thesis is to identify key factors that will facilitate the successful implementation of SDM in Scotland. This chapter will provide an overview of the thesis by initially discussing the context and background of the research area, which will then be followed by outlining the research problem, aims, questions and objectives, significance and the limitations of the research.

1.2 Background

1.2.1. Shared Decision-making (SDM)

Shared decision-making (SDM) is a practice in which patients and clinicians work in partnership to choose treatments, management packages, support packages, or tests based on the patient's informed preferences and clinical evidence. SDM involves the availability of evidence-based information concerning uncertainties, outcomes and options, together with counselling for decision support and a system for implementing and recording patients' informed preferences (Coulter & Collins, 2011). SDM is suitable for use in making decisions regarding taking medication, undergoing a diagnostic test or screening, attempting a change in lifestyle, undergoing a surgical or medical procedure, partaking in a psychological intervention or self-management education programme (Coulter & Collins, 2011).

The National Clinical Strategy for Scotland is a Scottish Government report which makes it clear that SDM is a critically important element of the new model of healthcare quality, based on the principles of realistic medicine (Scottish Government, 2016; G. Smith, 2024). Realistic medicine, the new model of healthcare (Calderwood, 2016) places the patient at the core of decisions made regarding their

social and health care (Scottish Government, 2024). It supports health care professionals to discover what means the most to individuals in relation to their condition and the treatment choices available, i.e. what their goals are (e.g. reducing opioid doses or improving their quality of life), so to ensure that the management of the patient's condition best suits their situation and needs. Realistic medicine therefore realises that "a one size fits all" approach to social and health care is not an optimum approach for the NHS or the individual (Scottish Government, 2024).

SDM supports the realistic medicine precepts of care centred on the person as an individual, based on strong relationships between patients and the relevant clinicians. By encouraging a change from the "doctor knows best" culture (i.e. clinical decision-making), realistic medicine promotes SDM in the care of patients (Scottish Government, 2024). Clinical decision-making is still common in the NHS, where healthcare professionals are regarded as the solitary competent decision-makers, and they will make decisions for patients, as opposed to with them, is a common assumption. Patients rarely challenge this, as they trust the healthcare professional's expertise and neither individual specifically acknowledges the validity of the patient's knowledge and role in their own decision-making process (Coulter & Collins, 2011). Therefore, a change is required in mind-set, attitudes and beliefs, by both patient and healthcare professional to move away from this traditional, paternalistic view of medical decision-making. This will then enable a more equal and fair approach which utilises and incorporates SDM (Coulter & Collins, 2011).

In contrast to paternalism, realistic medicine and SDM requires healthcare professionals to understand what is important to the patient and what their goals are. Patients should be encouraged to ask questions about their condition and the potential care and treatment proposed (Scottish Government, 2024). SDM therefore promotes self-management and independence of patients and gives them a full understanding of their problems and greater responsibility for making choices, also reducing over-use of medical interventions (Murray et al., 2004; O'Connor et al., 2009).

1.2.2. Decision Aids

A decision aid (DA) is a tool which assists individuals to engage in decision-making through making clear the decision which must be made, through defining personal values and supplying information concerning the outcomes and options. They are intended to complement instead of replacing counselling from a healthcare professional (The Ottawa Hospital Research Institute, 2022).

DAs vary in format and media, ranging from straightforward one-page sheets outlining the options, to more detailed pamphlets, interactive websites, computer programmes or DVDs that contain filmed

interviews with clinicians and patients, which enables the patient to research, delving into as little or as much information as they wish.

DAs are unlike traditional information materials given to patients as they do not instruct patients what to do but outline the facts and assist patients to contemplate the choices. DAs normally include: an outline of the symptoms and the condition, the probable prognosis without and with treatment, the self-management support and treatment choices and outcome probabilities, uncertainties and what is known from the evidence, illustrations to assist patients in comprehending what it would be like to experience a few of the most occurring complications or side-effects of the treatment choices (usually utilising patient interviews), a method of assisting patients to define their preferences, sources of additional information and references, the authors' declarations of conflict of interest, credentials and funding source (Coulter & Collins, 2011).

The evidence base within the Clinical Strategy (Scottish Government, 2016) is robust, and specifically gives strong support to the benefits of DAs. A systematic review (Dawn Stacey et al., 2014) on use of DAs to support screening or treatment decisions found that there is high quality evidence that DAs improve patient-practitioner communication and increase people's ability to make informed, value-based decisions. The potential for DAs to reduce over-use of services is underlined by meta-analyses (Stacey et al., 2014) showing that people supported with DAs are more likely to favour conservative options over elective surgery, less likely to choose to have prostate-specific antigen screening, and less likely to choose menopausal hormone therapy. Shared DAs can also decrease decisional conflict, while increasing knowledge and encouraging patients to be more active participants in decision-making, without increasing their anxiety (O'Connor et al., 1999).

1.2.3. Chronic Pain

Chronic pain (otherwise characterised as persistent pain) can be defined as pain which lasts longer than 12 weeks despite treatment or medication (NHS Scotland, 2023). The prevalence of severe chronic pain is not unlike that of conditions such as major depression, heart disease and diabetes. Within Europe, it is predicted that 20% of adults endure chronic pain (Breivik, Collett, Ventafridda, Cohen, & Gallacher, 2006), while 5.6% of adults suffer severe (i.e. disabling and intense) chronic pain (B. H. Smith et al., 2001). Chronic pain conditions are certainly the biggest cause of disability (determined as Years Lived with Disability (Vos et al., 2015). There are estimated to be over 4 million doctor appointments per year in the UK regarding chronic pain (equal to 793 fulltime doctors (Belsey, 2002)) and individuals with chronic pain visit a doctor 5 times more regularly compared to those without (Von Korff, Dworkin, & Le Resche, 1990).

Chronic pain as a condition would be a viable case study for a DA as there are many treatment options for patients to choose from which can either be pharmacological (e.g. painkillers, ointment and patches) or non-pharmacological (e.g. physiotherapy exercises, acupuncture and Transcutaneous Electro-Nerve Stimulator (TENS) units).

SDM has been shown to improve longer term outcomes in several studies that explored both mental and physical health conditions (Joosten et al., 2008). Joosten et al. (2008) also demonstrated patients' adherence to treatment plans, as well as satisfaction, knowledge and well-being to be positively impacted. The effects of SDM in patients with Fibromyalgia syndrome (which is an exemplary condition of chronic widespread pain) has been examined (Müller et al., 2004), where it was found that patients' readiness to enrol in physical activities, take analgesics, and participate in psychotherapeutic elements were most likely to be raised through SDM.

SDM in patients with chronic pain is important as patients need to self-manage their pain (Mann, LeFort, & VanDenKerkhof, 2013) and SDM can help them to evaluate their options and help identify the best one for them to help manage their condition, thus amongst other benefits, potentially reducing over-use of medical interventions (Murray et al., 2004; O'Connor et al., 2009).

1.3 The Research Problem

The General Medical Council's Good Medical Practice instruction for every clinician incorporates an expectation that SDM will be standard practice for the majority of medical decisions (General Medical Council, 2013). The General Medical Council also stated in their more recent guidance (General Medical Council, 2020) that SDM is crucial to good medical practice and is fundamental to good patient care. However, international surveys produced and distributed by the Commonwealth Fund found higher levels of paternalism within healthcare in the UK when compared to North American and other European countries, with lower levels of support for self-management and self-care as well as lower levels of patient engagement in healthcare decisions (Davis, Schoen, & Stremikis, 2010). Additionally, the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) were asked to provide guidance around facilitating SDM and how to implement it as standard practice, because the majority of NHS commissioners and healthcare professionals recognised that SDM is not currently standard practice (Carmona, Crutwell, Burnham, & Polak, 2021).

Therefore, the key point is that the NHS can and must do better. Efficient SDM is currently not the norm, and a lot of patients want to be more involved and to be provided with more information in decisions concerning support, treatment or care than they presently experience (Coulter & Collins, 2011). Driever, Stiggelbout & Brand (2022) also found that the majority of patients want to be included

in decision-making but believe that the healthcare professional makes the healthcare decision more frequently than they would like. However, implementing SDM into practice, such as formal processes, systems, workforce attitudes, behaviours and skills remains a difficult task (Coulter & Collins, 2011).

Therefore, whilst SDM is aimed to be standard practice in healthcare within the UK (Scottish Government, 2016; Smith, 2024) and DAs should be used to assist the SDM process, successful implementation of SDM and DA is patchy and not currently the norm within the UK and universally (Légaré, Ratté, Gravel, & Graham, 2008). The Scottish Government (2018) also concur that whilst there are numerous examples of excellent practice across NHS Scotland and despite an increasing drive towards SDM in Scotland, (Creaney, 2019) effective SDM between patients and healthcare professionals is yet to be standard practice.

1.4 Original Contribution to Knowledge

The current project aims to investigate this problem by identifying if the utilization of SDM and DAs is consistent within NHS Boards in Scotland as no previous literature exists on utilization and implementation of SDM and DAs in Scotland. Despite, research claiming to be based in the UK, no studies are based in Scotland. Despite the existence of literature on clinicians' attitudes to SDM, no literature could additionally be found on Scottish healthcare professionals' attitudes to SDM and only one study could be found on clinicians' attitudes to SDM in a chronic pain context. This study took place in America.

The current project also aims to identify what factors are important for SDM to be accepted by individuals with chronic pain and their healthcare professionals as this could aid successful implementation of SDM for the treatment of chronic pain patients. Acceptance of SDM is important because for SDM to be standard practice, SDM needs to be accepted by everyone and viewed as being beneficial and useful.

In addition, no literature could be found which investigated which factors are involved in the acceptance of SDM in a chronic pain context. There are theories and models of decision-making in Psychology and in healthcare but there are no theories or models which review or incorporate the acceptance of SDM in a chronic pain context. Therefore, investigating potential factors of acceptance in SDM in a chronic pain context from chronic pain patients can help contribute to a new psychological model or theory which outlines acceptance in SDM in a chronic pain context, thus addressing a gap in the literature.

In their guidance around facilitating SDM and how to implement it as standard practice, NICE recommends that future research focuses on how SDM differs between different groups of patients

and in different healthcare settings; how to encourage patients to engage in SDM and how SDM may be required to be adapted for remote consultations (Carmona et al., 2021). Thus, the current project also focuses on these key areas, originally contributing to knowledge in a Scottish context to aid the successful implementation of SDM in Scotland.

1.5 Research Aims

The overall aim of the project is: To identify key factors that will facilitate the successful implementation of medical SDM in Scotland.

The current research questions are:

- Is medical SDM successfully implemented in Scotland?
- What factors predict acceptance of medical SDM for individuals with chronic pain?
- What factors predict engagement in medical SDM for members of the Scottish general population?
- What are the Scottish general populations' and individuals with chronic pains' attitudes to and experiences of medical SDM?

Thus, study 1 aimed to answer the following research questions:

- Are DAs successfully implemented and used routinely as standard practice within Scottish NHS Boards?
- What features do clinicians think a successful DA should have?
- Is SDM routinely used as standard practice within Scottish NHS Boards?
- What are the potential barriers to SDM and DAs?
- What are clinicians' opinions towards a possible future DA for chronic pain and what features should this DA include?

Study 2 aimed to investigate the predictors of acceptance of SDM by individuals with chronic pain.

The purpose of study 3 was to investigate the predictors of engagement in SDM in the Scottish general population.

The final and fourth study aimed to examine the Scottish general populations and individuals with chronic pain attitudes to and experiences of SDM.

1.6 Justification

Therefore, this research will contribute to the existing knowledge on SDM by identifying key factors that will facilitate the successful implementation of medical SDM in Scotland for healthcare professionals to implement with Scottish patients, both with and without chronic pain. This will help to close the current gap in this area and provide key, practical value to healthcare by aiding the successful implementation of SDM across Scottish healthcare.

1.7 Structure

The first chapter introduced the context and provided some background for the research. The research aims and questions were also outlined. The significance of the research was also addressed. Additionally, the limitations of the research were discussed.

The second chapter will review the existing literature to identify key factors in implementing SDM within the context of healthcare, focusing on both patients with chronic pain and on members of the general population.

The third chapter will present the research methodology that was used. The adoption of a multi-phase mixed methods research approach will be justified, and the wider research design of each study will be discussed, including the strengths of these approaches and designs.

Chapters 4-7 present studies 1 - 4. Each of these chapters contain an introduction, methods, results and conclusion section discussing each study.

By using semi-structured interviews with members of different Scottish NHS boards, study 1 (the fourth chapter) preliminarily answered the research questions, specified previously. Through answering these exploratory research questions, a more precise and relevant basis was formed for the subsequent research studies (studies 2, 3 and 4) by focusing more on how to successfully implement SDM into healthcare than DAs.

Based on the findings of study 1, study 2 (the fifth chapter) investigated the predictors of acceptance of SDM by individuals with chronic pain by using an online quantitative survey answered by individuals with chronic pain. Through addressing the aim of study 2, a basis was formed for the following research studies (studies 3 and 4) by highlighting what factors are important for engaging in SDM by members of the Scottish general population and for individuals with chronic pain.

Building on the findings of study 2, study 3 (the sixth chapter) then investigated the predictors of engagement in SDM in the Scottish general population by using an online quantitative survey answered by members of the Scottish general population. Through addressing the aims of studies 2 and 3, a basis was formed for study 4 by highlighting what are the attitudes towards and experiences of both individuals with chronic pain and of members of the Scottish general population towards SDM.

The findings of Studies 2 and 3 provided a base for Study 4 (the seventh chapter), examining the Scottish general populations and individuals with chronic pains' attitudes to and experiences of SDM by using semi-structured interviews with both members of the Scottish general population and individuals with chronic pain.

Finally, Chapter 8 entails the Discussion and Conclusion. The researcher presents the findings of each study in relation to each of the study aims. The researcher also examines the link between findings from individual studies, and then surmises the original contribution to knowledge, research impact, suggestions for future research and concludes the thesis.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

This chapter provides an overview of the literature relevant to this thesis, namely on topics such as shared decision-making (including key issues, models and theories, and DAs) as well as chronic pain. The chapter will also highlight gaps in the literature for these topics.

2.1 Shared Decision-making

Shared decision-making (SDM) is a practice in which patients and clinicians work in partnership to choose treatments, management packages, support packages, or tests based on the patient's informed preferences and clinical evidence. SDM involves readily available evidence-based information on uncertainties, outcomes and options, together with counselling for decision support and a system for implementing and recording patients' informed preferences (Coulter & Collins, 2011). Taking medication, undergoing a diagnostic test or screening, attempting a change in lifestyle, undergoing a surgical or medical procedure, partaking in a psychological intervention or self-management education programmes are all examples of healthcare decisions where SDM would be suitable (Coulter & Collins, 2011).

SDM can include compromise and negotiation, despite this, at its centre is the acknowledgement that patients and healthcare professionals contribute separate yet equally valuable types of knowledge to the decision-making process (Coulter & Collins, 2011). The healthcare professional has knowledge concerning probable prognosis, diagnosis, the extent of likely outcomes taken from population data and support and treatment choices. Whereas the patient is an expert concerning the impact of their condition on their everyday life and their individual preferences, values and attitude to risk (Coulter & Collins, 2011).

The national clinical strategy for Scotland is a Scottish Government report (2016) which makes clear that SDM is a critically important element of the new model of healthcare quality, based on the principles of realistic medicine. Realistic medicine, the new model of healthcare (Calderwood, 2016), places the patient at the core of decisions made regarding their social and health care (Scottish Government, 2024). It supports health care professionals to provide healthcare in a manner that is the most suitable for the patient and their family, so that they receive healthcare which factors in the priorities of the patient receiving the healthcare (Fleck, 2017), i.e., what their goals are (e.g. reducing opioid doses or improving their quality of life), so to ensure that the management of the patient's condition best suits their situation and needs. Realistic medicine therefore views SDM as a central

feature and considers that “a one size fits all” approach to social and health care is not an optimum approach for the NHS or the individual (Scottish Government, 2024).

SDM supports the realistic medicine precepts of care centred on the person as an individual, based on strong relationships between patients and the relevant healthcare professionals. Realistic medicine promotes SDM in the care of patients and concerns changing from a “doctor knows best” culture i.e., clinical decision-making (Scottish Government, 2024). The traditional method of clinical decision-making, which is still common in the NHS, places the healthcare professionals as the solitary competent decision-makers, and assumes that they will make decisions for the patient, rather than with them. Patients rarely question this expectation, as the healthcare professional’s expertise is to be trusted, yet neither recognises the validity of the patient’s knowledge and role in the decision-making process (Coulter & Collins, 2011). Therefore, a change is required in mind-set, attitudes and beliefs, by both patient and healthcare professional to move away from this traditional, paternalistic view of medical decision-making. This will then enable a more equal and fair approach which utilises and incorporates SDM (Coulter & Collins, 2011).

As described in the Introduction chapter (Chapter 1), the Commonwealth Fund produced and administered international surveys demonstrating the UK healthcare has higher levels of paternalism when compared to North American and other European countries, lower levels of support for self-management and self-care, and lower levels of patient engagement in decisions (Davis et al., 2010). Additionally, less than 1 in 5 British individuals with chronic health conditions had been distributed a self-management plan. The UK was also found to score lowest for SDM compared to North American and other European countries with most of these SDM scores being significantly different (Coulter & Ellins, 2006). However, these surveys only took into account 9 countries, therefore the UK may have performed better in SDM compared to other countries, not included in this study.

Over recent years, there has been increasing interest in improving SDM in standard healthcare and in expanding the incorporation of SDM in health policies in numerous countries. Researchers (Härter, Moumjid, Cornuz, Elwyn, & van der Weijden, 2017) outlined that out of 22 countries that attempted to develop activities to advance SDM, 19 countries had health policies which promote or request the implementation of SDM (Härter et al., 2017). The majority of the depicted countries were in America or Europe. Highlighting that SDM between healthcare professionals and patients is increasingly becoming standard practice in Western societies (Bomhof-Roordink, Gärtner, Stiggelbout, & Pieterse, 2019).

However, regardless of many countries health policies commitment to carrying out SDM and its incorporation in a variety of medical guidelines, studies from other countries depict poor

implementation in standard medical practice (Bomhof-Roordink et al., 2019). Amongst some of these countries were Canada (Charles, Gafni, & Whelan, 2004), Germany (Vogel, Helmes, & Hasenburg, 2008) and the UK (Coulter, Edwards, Elwyn, & Thomson, 2011). Despite increasing evidence base for SDM, work has also demonstrated its implementation has been slow in Australia too (Dimopoulos-Bick, Osten, Shipway, Trevena, & Hoffmann, 2019). However, it is anticipated that the requirement for SDM will exponentially increase in Australia.

An international comparison in 2000 aimed to determine features of general practice which are typically evaluated positively by patients and to compare beliefs of patients in different European countries on care provision (Grol et al., 2000). Patients in ten European countries were given and completed an internationally validated questionnaire. A stratified sample of 36 general practices per country with a minimum of 1080 patients per country, was encompassed. Questions on frequency of visiting the GP, age, overall health status, sex and a set of 23 validated questions on evaluations of various aspects of care was utilised. The patient sample consisted of 17,391 patients in 10 different countries. Variations in overall assessment were observed between countries. An inclination for more positive evaluations were found in Belgium, Switzerland and Germany, yet suggested fewer positive evaluations were found for Scandinavian countries and the UK.

These results, although not explicitly stated or investigated by Grol and colleagues (2000) could perhaps be due to differences in SDM between these countries as in later work (Coulter & Ellins, 2006), Germany was found to score higher in all but one aspect of SDM than the UK with two significant differences. Therefore, a possible, unexplored reason for more positive healthcare evaluations in countries such as Belgium, Switzerland and Germany could be because they are more involved in SDM compared to the UK which scored the least in SDM scores and had fewer positive evaluations of their healthcare. However, Grol et al.'s (2000) study looked only at European countries and Coulter and Ellin's (2006) work focused more on North American countries, therefore a direct comparison of positive evaluations of care and involvement in SDM could not be concluded for Belgium, Switzerland and Scandinavian countries.

Realistic medicine and SDM contrasts paternalistic medicine, involving healthcare professionals to understand what is important to the patient and what their goals are. Patients should be encouraged to ask questions concerning their health condition and the potential care proposed (Scottish Government, 2024). SDM promotes self-management and independence, and by giving patients a full understanding of their problems and greater responsibility for making choices, it also helps to reduce over-use of medical interventions (Murray et al., 2004; O'Connor et al., 2009).

The General Medical Council's Good Medical Practice (2013) is a document which looks like a report but is described as an "ethical guidance", divided into four sections that describe the professional behaviours and values that the General Medical Council expects from any doctor that is registered with them.

The General Medical Council's (2013) Good Medical Practice instruction for every clinician incorporates an expectation that SDM will be standard practice for the majority of medical decisions. The instruction incorporates the following declaration: "Whatever the context in which medical decisions are made, you must work in partnership with your patients to ensure good care. In so doing, you must listen to patients and respect their views about their health, discuss with patients what their diagnosis, prognosis, treatment and care involve; share with patients the information they want or need in order to make decisions; maximise patients' opportunities, and their ability, to make decisions for themselves; respect patients' decisions." (General Medical Council, 2013).

A systematic review examined health care professionals' attitudes to SDM in an effort to comprehend why SDM is not currently standard practice universally (Légaré et al., 2008). The most frequently used arguments included:

- "No time to do it"
- "We already do it"
- "Patients don't want it"
- "It's irrelevant and ineffective"
- "Patients will want inappropriate/expensive treatments"
- "There's no incentive to do it"
- "Not appropriate for those with low health literacy"

2.1.1. "No Time to Do It"

A frequent belief is that SDM appointments use more time than appointments in which healthcare professionals alone decide (Coulter & Collins, 2011). Whilst the appointments themselves might perhaps use a bit more time, the time used involving the patient in the decision might decrease the overall time used working with a patient who is unhappy or uncertain regarding a decision they were not included in (Bekker, Hewison, & Thornton, 2004).

Therefore, SDM might include reconsidering clinical pathway design in order to include time for coaching and information provision.

2.1.2. “We Already Do It”

Healthcare professionals often believe they are sharing decisions to a greater extent than their patients do (Stevenson, Barry, Britten, Barber, & Bradley, 2000). Whilst nearly everybody agrees that patients should be requested to provide their informed consent prior to receiving invasive treatment, this does not indicate that they are consistently given comprehensive information regarding the alternatives and encouraged to articulate their preferences (Coulter & Collins, 2011).

Informed consent frequently includes the supply of just basic information regarding a single treatment, prior to acquiring the patient’s signature on a form to signify their agreement. Some individuals have testified that the entire idea of informed consent is greatly passive and should be discarded, instead substituted with SDM or the principle of informed choice (Veatch, 2008).

Surveys issued in 2010 reported that few patients experience important medical decisions while fully informed regarding the key facts, which may influence their treatment choices, and efforts to obtain their informed preferences are uncommon (Coulter, 2010; Fagerlin et al., 2010; Zikmund-Fisher et al., 2010). This is generally because healthcare professionals have traditionally assumed the task of decision-maker, stepping in as the patient’s representative to decide the most suitable course of action (Coulter & Collins, 2011).

2.1.3. “Patients Don’t Want It”

Most people want healthcare professionals to listen, answer their questions and explain (Coulter & Magee, 2003). Additionally, there is powerful evidence that patients wish to be considered as a whole person and that they wish to work alongside healthcare professional that they trust (Ridd, Shaw, Lewis, & Salisbury, 2009). There is a large desire for information concerning treatments and diseases and the majority of patients desire more of this information than is often received. This entails truthful assessments of treatment risks, benefits and side-effects. A lot of people articulate disappointment regarding the limited opportunities to engage in decisions concerning their care (Coulter & Collins, 2011). Whilst not everybody desires active engagement, the majority of surveys find that most people do (Flynn, Smith, & Vanness, 2006).

The want for inclusion tends to differ between social groups, as more educated and younger individuals are more inclined to say they desire an active role (Coulter & Collins, 2011). Although, a lot of individuals from disadvantaged groups and elderly individuals do wish to have an active role in

decisions concerning their care, and healthcare professionals should encourage individuals to engage (Coulter & Collins, 2011). Individuals who have not been encouraged might believe that their feelings are not important or relevant and might not attempt to share their concerns or feelings in the future.

2.1.4. “It’s Irrelevant and Ineffective”

Evaluations of different forms of SDM demonstrate that it can contribute to the subsequent benefits (Murray et al., 2004; O'Connor et al., 2009):

- Greater engagement
- Better health behaviours
- Increased knowledge and understanding
- Less individuals choosing major surgery
- More suitable service use
- Increased accurate risk perceptions
- Increased coping skills and confidence
- Increased comfort with decisions
- Improved treatment adherence

The chronic care model is constructed by a bulk of evidence portraying that self-management support can make a substantial difference to health outcomes (Bodenheimer, Wagner, & Grumbach, 2002). Information is beneficial, specifically if it is personalised, although information only is not sufficient. It must be enriched by decision support, self-management education and personalised care planning from sufficiently trained health care professionals, in addition to social support from peers, family and friends (Coulter & Collins, 2011). There is proof that this can increase individual’s level of engagement and understanding, in addition to their confidence to self-manage and coping skills, leading to improved health outcomes (Coulter & Ellins, 2007; Loveman, Frampton, & Clegg, 2008).

Utilisation of evidence-based decision aids (DAs) for patients have been demonstrated to lead to increases in knowledge, improved comprehension of treatment choices and increased accurate perceptions of risks (O'Connor et al., 2009). Decision aids assist to increase engagement in decision-making and improve patients’ confidence during the process. They additionally generate a greater match between individuals’ preferences and the treatments selected, leading to higher satisfaction. There is also no proof that they increase patients’ anxiety.

'Active' patients are more equipped to make personally relevant and informed decisions regarding their care; they frequently utilise less health care; they tend to make healthier lifestyle choices; they are better at self-managing chronic conditions and are more inclined to adhere to treatment recommendations (Mosen et al., 2007). Patients with decreased levels of activation tend to yield to health care professionals as decision makers, and without active support or encouragement from health care professionals commonly stay at decreased levels of activation.

2.1.5. "Patients Will Want Inappropriate/Expensive Treatments"

It is frequently believed that patients that are well-informed regarding accessible self-management support or treatment choices will select the most costly, however DA trials have discovered that the opposite is true (Cantor, Rajan, Linder, & Volk, 2015). It appears that patients are commonly more risk-averse compared to the healthcare professionals that advise them, thus when they receive complete information regarding the risks and advantages of treatment, they are likely to choose self-management support or the least invasive treatment (Coulter & Collins, 2011). For instance, females referred to hospitals in south-west England faced with the decision of whether to undergo or not a hysterectomy to cure inordinate menstrual bleeding were a lot less inclined to choose the operation after receiving a DA and an opportunity to discuss it over with a health care professional (Kennedy et al., 2002). Additional trials including elective surgery have reported similar findings (O'Connor et al., 2009).

A meta-analysis which consisted of 8 trials included patients which faced potential surgical operations discovered that the proportions of surgery were 24% lower amongst patients that utilised DAs (O'Connor & Stacey, 2005). Studies from America have demonstrated the potentiality of telephone and community support. For instance, elderly individuals attending 2 seniors' centres in LA benefited from conversing and viewing a video about how to self-manage their health. The individuals who attended most frequently were more actively engaged in self-management, stated increases in their quality of life and carried out more exercise (Frosch, Rincon, Ochoa, & Mangione, 2010).

An American randomised trial of telephone health coaching demonstrated that it had the potential to lower the proportions of health care costs and hospital admissions amongst a vast group of individuals with conditions that may need elective surgery or chronic conditions (D. E. Wennberg, Marr, Lang, O'Malley, & Bennett, 2010). However, it has still to be discovered if it would have a similar impact within the NHS.

2.1.6. “There’s No Incentive to Do It”

Patients that are well-informed commonly favour to refrain from the highest invasive treatments, thus encouraging them to engage in decisions can aid to guarantee they are given just “the care they need and no less, the care they want, and no more” (Mulley, Trimble, & Elwyn, 2012). Within a few health systems in which healthcare professionals are paid for activity, there might be a discouragement to advocate SDM, specifically when this causes decreased proportions of intervention (Coulter & Collins, 2011). Thus, healthcare professionals within the NHS, specifically those who work in hospitals, are pressured as a consequence of the incentives hospitals encounter to boost throughput and volume, there might be a discouragement to spend time with patients in taking into account other choices, including no intervention or treatment (Coulter & Collins, 2011). The people who are accountable for clinical rewards and pay and for designing payment systems and future tariffs must guarantee they supply incentives for healthcare professionals and organisations to involve patients in SDM.

Incentivising SDM will additionally need suitable feedback and performance measures in order to monitor progress. Building on the saying that “what gets measured gets done”, what is required is a method of measuring the quality of the decision-making process (Sepucha, Fowler Jr, & Mulley Jr, 2004). Decision quality concerns the degree to which management or treatments choices indicate the contemplated preferences of well-informed patients and are carried out (Coulter & Collins, 2011). The important questions are:

- Did the healthcare professional pay crucial attention to engaging and educating the patient in the decision process?
- How knowledgeable was the patient regarding the important factors an individual should know prior to undergoing a self-management programme, specific treatment, behaviour change or screening test?
- To what measure was the decision personalised to indicate the patient’s aims? Did the chosen treatment parallel their preferences?

Particular questions have been produced for utilisation in patient surveys to measure performance regarding these subjects (Sepucha et al., 2008). These involve how sufficient the facts have been articulated (e.g. information regarding the nature of the condition, the importance of treatment, the advantages and risks of these and the treatment choices), and if the patient’s aims have been obtained (e.g. the want for symptom relief, attitudes to recovery or the treatment, and the prevention of harm as a consequence of the treatment).

An additional method to measure patient's ability to self-manage their health care and health is to utilise the patient activation measure (PAM), an instrument to measure patient's activation level (Hibbard, Stockard, Mahoney, & Tusler, 2004). Patient activation includes 4 steps:

- Accepting the patient role is valuable
- Possessing the knowledge and confidence needed to take action
- Literally taking action to increase and maintain one's health
- Maintain the course even through stress (Hibbard et al., 2004).

Patients with higher PAM scores are greater at self-managing their health compared to patients with lower scores and attain improved health outcomes (Mosen et al., 2007). The PAM survey has additionally been utilised within UK populations. In a survey of patients aged 45+, many of whom had long-term conditions, it was discovered that just 22% were certain that they could self-manage their health efficiently during periods of stress (Ellins & Coulter, 2005).

A survey of healthcare professionals located in the UK and the US discovered that many were reluctant to encourage patient activation (Hibbard, Collins, Mahoney, & Baker, 2010). Instead, they were more inclined to assert that patients should adhere to medical advice than that they should be encouraged to take independent actions or make independent judgements. However, it seems likely to intervene to increase patient's capability to self-manage their health through carefully aiming interventions to their activation level, improving the probability of improved health outcomes (Hibbard, Greene, & Tusler, 2009).

Hibbard et al. (2009) also note both activation measures and decision quality measures can be utilised to examine if an intervention to advocate SDM has been successful. A patient's capability to self-manage their health is not permanent. It is attainable to intervene to increase it through carefully aiming interventions to their activation level, improving the probability of improved health outcomes.

Local commissioners, the NHS Commissioning Board and NICE must guarantee that contracts and commissioning standards recognise decision points in care pathways and check the quality of SDM within pathways and services through utilising suitable patient-reported measures in patient surveys (Coulter & Collins, 2011).

2.1.7. “Not Appropriate for Those with Low Health Literacy”

Studies have demonstrated worries that SDM is just of benefit to more-educated middle class individuals (Say, Murtagh, & Thomson, 2006; Stiggelbout et al., 2012) but these worries are not justified. It is evidently possible to involve and educate patients from every educational background and occupation, if they receive suitable decision support from well-trained staff and are supplied with well-designed information materials (J. S. King, Eckman, & Moulton, 2011; O'Connor et al., 2009). One study examined the effect of health literacy on an educational intervention for individuals diagnosed with coronary artery disease, where 187 patients were randomised to only a booklet; or a DVD/VHS and a printed booklet before their appointment (Eckman et al., 2012). The main outcome measures entailed knowledge assessment about their health condition, health behaviours (smoking, diet and exercise) and clinical outcomes (blood pressure and weight); whilst functional health literacy was determined as a potential predictor variable. It was found that health behaviours and knowledge scores improved after utilising both interventions. Patients that were given the video and booklet additionally showed a significant increase in weight loss and exercise and a tendency for increased test scores. Individuals with lower health literacy were found to benefit from the interventions just as much as patients with higher health literacy. Therefore, patients with lower health literacy can benefit also from educational SDM interventions.

Essentially, individuals with low health literacy are likely to yield to health care professionals to decide for them (Coulter and Collins, 2011) and are inclined to have fewer good health outcomes (Berkman, Sheridan, Donahue, Halpern, & Crotty, 2011) compared to individuals that are more actively engaged in their health (Hibbard & Greene, 2013). The attraction for health care professionals confronted with a patient that does not possess much knowledge of health matters and is not confident in declaring their feelings is to decide for them, hence additionally reinforcing their passive role and the inclination towards worse health in the future (Coulter & Collins, 2011). However, individuals can be supported and encouraged to become active participants in care (Hibbard et al., 2009; Volandes et al., 2011).

The key point is that the NHS can and must do better. Efficient SDM is currently not the norm, and many patients do want to be more involved and to be provided with more information in decisions concerning support, treatment or care than they presently experience (Coulter & Collins, 2011). However, implementing SDM into practice, such as formal processes, systems, workforce attitudes, behaviours and skills remains a difficult task (Coulter & Collins, 2011).

Therefore, whilst SDM is aimed to be standard practice in healthcare within the UK (Scottish Government, 2016) and DA should be used to assist the SDM process, successful implementation of SDM and DA is patchy and not currently the norm within the UK and universally (Légaré et al., 2008).

As described previously, patients responded to surveys to reveal very few are fully informed when experiencing important medical decisions and that their preferences are rarely sought after (Fagerlin et al., 2010; Zikmund-Fisher et al., 2010), often where the healthcare professional assumes the role of decision-maker on the patients' behalf. Therefore, whilst healthcare professionals believe they are carrying out SDM and that it is standard practice for their board, perhaps reviews are needed to assess whether they are truly carrying out SDM in the proper fashion.

Faegerlin and colleagues (2010) aimed to ascertain adults' knowledge concerning information relating to common kinds of surgery, medication or screening decisions they had recently made. The study design was a cross-sectional survey carried out from November 2006 to May 2007. A total 2575 English-speaking US adults aged 40+ were selected through random-digit dialling. Participants stated having discussed the subsequent medical decisions with a clinician in the last 2 years: surgeries for lower back pain, knee/hip replacements or cataracts; prescription medications for depression, hypertension or hypercholesterolemia or screening tests for prostate, colorectal or breast cancer. Participants responded to knowledge questions and rated the significance of the media, their health care provider, and family/friends as sources of information. The study found that patient knowledge of vital facts relating to recently made medical decisions is frequently deficient and differs systematically by patient characteristics and decision type. Therefore, increasing patient knowledge concerning characteristics, risks and benefits of medical procedures is vital to aid informed decision making.

Zikmund-Fisher and colleagues (2010) carried out a similar study to Fagerlin and colleagues (2010). They aimed to identify differences and deficits in patients' experiences of making common medical decisions concerning initiation of surgeries for lower back pain, knee or hip replacements or cataracts; prescription medications for depression, hypertension or hypercholesterolemia and screening tests for prostate, colorectal or breast cancer together with determining factors associated with patient confidence with the decisions. The study design was also a cross-sectional survey carried out from November 2006 to May 2007. 2473 English-speaking US adults aged 40+ were selected again through random-digit dialling. Participants stated having undertaken one or more of the aforementioned nine medical actions or discussing doing so with a clinician in the last 2 years. Patients stated their confidence that the decision was the correct one, who made the final decisions and initiated discussions, whether they were asked about their preferences, and how much discussion of pros and cons occurred. The study found that participants stated broad differences in the proportion of conversations which included a discussion concerning reasons to not take action or a discussion concerning patients' preferences concerning what they would want to do. These factors seem directly connected with patients' confidence that their decision was "correct". However, generalisability of

results may have been limited as participants were American adults aged 40+ and data relied on participants' memory of clinical consultations within the previous 2 years by which time, some participants might have struggled to recall specific details and so might have guessed what was done or said at their consultation.

Currently, the main challenge is developing and implementing processes and tools to support SDM into standard practice, in an efficient manner. Implementing SDM into behaviours and skills, systems, workforce attitudes and processes is also difficult (Coulter & Collins, 2011). However, multiple pilot implementation projects, involving both healthcare professionals and patients, are underway. Projects such as these offer important experiences and lessons on which to build practice for the future. Making Good Decisions In Collaboration (MAGIC) is an example of such a project, investigating ways in which SDM can be implemented into standard clinical practice (Natalie Joseph-Williams et al., 2017).

2.2 MAGIC Programme

The MAGIC Programme's first phase ran from August 2010 to February 2012 which involved testing and designing the optimum methods to implement SDM into standard clinical locations. The locations used for this included: Cardiff University and Newcastle University (as the main areas), Cardiff and Vale University Health Board, Northumbria Healthcare NHS Foundation Trust and Newcastle upon Tyne Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust. The clinical areas which were incorporated included: General practices (4 each in Newcastle and Cardiff), Urology (treatment choices for prostate cancer) in Newcastle, Breast cancer (surgery choices for early stage breast cancer, Maternity (choices associated with method of delivery post caesarean, screening for Down's syndrome, and place of birth) in Newcastle, Chronic kidney disease (treatment for end stage renal failure) in Cardiff, Paediatric ears, nose and throat (surgery for recurring tonsillitis) in Cardiff and Head and neck cancer (treatment choices for head and neck cancer) in Cardiff.

The second phase ran from February 2012 to October 2013 which involved showing that SDM can become a component of standard clinical practice (broader dissemination, implementation & sustainability) and increase transferable and practical knowledge concerning the conditions for success. For this phase, in Cardiff: work was carried out alongside up to 10 clinical groups over the Cardiff and Vale University Health Board to engage more patients in SDM (extended from first phase) and the groups were able to access interventions/approaches and support created during the first phase (quality improvement support, SDM skills, patient participation and decision support tools). Meanwhile, in Newcastle: resources, materials and tools were supplied to allow clinical

implementation groups from the first phase to carry on their proposals for sustainable change, processes, materials and tools were further developed to aid the expansion of SDM and to establish sustainable change, 4 new clinical groups (2 each from primary and secondary care) were engaged with and third sector organisations were engaged with to supply forms of skills training workshops to advocated and service users.

A range of sources were used in the programme including questionnaires, facilitated shared learning events, focus groups, clinic and consultation observations, patient and public involvement panels and interviews with clinicians and patients. Progress was assessed utilising the “plan do study act” data collection tools (Lloyd, Joseph-Williams, Edwards, Rix, & Elwyn, 2013) in which core groups were asked to agree on coherent goals and measures utilising the iterative Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) cycles. These cycles are used to test an idea through testing a change on a short scale and assessing the effect, increasing the learning from prior cycles in a systematic manner prior to extensive implementation (NHS, 2019). Progress was also assessed utilising monthly project team meetings (involving patient representatives, researchers, healthcare organisations and clinical teams), and an independent evaluation report of the first phase (E. King, Taylor, Williams, & Vanson, 2013). The report exploits the learning from the 3-year programme and the following experience to outline the key challenges to implementing SDM and to propose some practical solutions.

2.2.1. Challenges Identified

The first challenge experienced by the MAGIC programme, and which was also identified as a barrier to implementing SDM earlier is: “We do it already”. A crucial obstacle in all change programmes is to alter attitudes. Both attitudinal and cultural change amongst patients and healthcare professionals and structural change within healthcare delivery and pathways, are needed for patient choice and SDM to be standard practice. Numerous healthcare professionals believe that they already include patients in decisions regarding their care, thus frequently do not realise how SDM varies from their typical practice. A few healthcare professionals perceive their position as “decision maker” for the benefit of their patients. This long-time obligation to doing what they view to be in the best interests of their patients is a crucial obstacle to attitudinal change. Whilst well intentioned, this does not acknowledge that patients’ preferences, values, or opinions are significant and may diverge from theirs.

A vital action in implementing SDM is to deepen understanding of what it involves (Lloyd et al., 2013; May & Finch, 2009). Clinical groups require support to review present practice, to form a common understanding of how SDM varies from their present practice, and to determine how they wish to

reach decisions with patients. The MAGIC programme discovered that interactive skills training workshops aided to promote positive attitudes, build coherence and improve skills (Elwyn et al., 2013). Workshop feedback suggested that role play based training that highlighted practical skills, functioned better than presentations which were theory heavy. Researchers progressively incorporated exercises which confronted embedded attitudes and encouraged discussion concerning them. The groups were typically already efficient in identifying options and conversing them with patients, although there was capacity to increase their conversation of risk and the duty of investigating what is important to patients. The training aided healthcare professionals understanding of how SDM varied from their present method of working. Some healthcare professionals stated altering their perspective from, “We do this already” to “We could do this better.”

The second challenge faced in the MAGIC programme was: “We don’t have the right tools”. Numerous healthcare professionals think that a DA alone will facilitate SDM and that decisions cannot be shared without an aid to supply their patients. A crucial learning detail from the MAGIC project was that “skills trump tools, and attitudes trump skills.” Improving understanding and attitudes is important, however healthcare professionals must consider their conversational skills to involve patients in decision making, making use of evidence-based aids when suitable. There will not be DAs for all decisions; neither will each patient perceive them as being beneficial or acceptable. The skills to have various types of discussions with patients are of the most importance, with or without an accessible aid.

Within the skills training workshops, role play was specifically efficient for displaying that aids might assist the process yet do not substitute conversational skills. Patient information sources created for utilisation out with the consultation, like websites, are expensive and take a lot of time to create and keep updated. Creating short DAs supported overcoming this problem (Elwyn et al., 2013). Healthcare professionals readily created short evidence-based aids to utilise within the consultation, like Option Grids at the Cardiff locations and short DAs at the Newcastle locations (National Institute for Health and Care Excellence, 2016). These supply brief (1-3 pages) summaries of the treatment options, the probable outcomes, and the aspects that patients may take into account when making their decision, as well as benefit and risk data.

Knowledge from the MAGIC programme proposes that in-consultation aids are frequently better at aiding conversation between healthcare professional and patient compared to those utilised out with the consultation. A few patients utilised the aids to direct their questions for the healthcare professional and it helped them to converse what was important to them - the core of SDM. Nevertheless, the risk is that healthcare professionals utilise short DAs to improve information transfer and speak at patients, instead of developing how they work with patients.

The third challenge experienced by the MAGIC programme and which was also identified as a barrier to implementing SDM earlier is: “Patients don’t want shared decision-making”. Healthcare professionals frequently state that their patients do not wish to be included in making healthcare decisions. This may be true for some patients, and a few patients desire various levels of inclusion, thus the SDM process should appreciate the patient’s preference. This preference alone should be informed, instead of being based on a healthcare professional’s belief concerning what the patient wishes. A lot of patients feel not able instead of reluctant to share in decision making (N. Joseph-Williams, Elwyn, & Edwards, 2014). Some patients believe they will irritate healthcare professionals by attempting to be more included (Frosch, Singer, & Timmermans, 2011), and their want to be a “good” patient supersedes their want for sharing decisions. Frequently this comes from traditional expectations and experience of a paternalistic approach and appears to be more frequent in elderly individuals (Say et al., 2006). This can be misread as no interest in participating in decision making.

Healthcare professionals’ misinterpretations concerning what patients desire needs to be addressed. It is not achievable and not advantageous to make each patient be more included, although more can be done to make patients feel involved and respected, and healthcare professionals can frequently make more attempts to appreciate what is valuable to the patient. Nevertheless, patients might additionally require preparation and support to partake in a different sort of consultation.

Patient preparation and activation can boost the probability of jointly beneficial discussions between patients and healthcare professionals. Patient activation campaigns concentrate on altering patient’s attitudes concerning inclusion in healthcare decisions, defining what SDM includes, how it may help, and supply interventions like question prompt lists. Interventions like the Ask 3 Questions campaign in which patients ask their healthcare professional: “What are my options? What are the benefits and harms? How likely are these?” can improve patients’ knowledge of what to anticipate and give “permission” and support to be included (Shepherd et al., 2011).

Successful implementation additionally requires broader public and patient engagement. Within the MAGIC programme, patients were involved with the appropriate circumstances in creating local interventions in addition to having a broader user panel to direct the wider implementation process. The lay panel was vital in recognising areas for enhancement within the implementation work, recognising users’ requirements, and assisting intervention testing and development.

The fourth challenge experienced in the MAGIC programme was “How can we measure it?” Healthcare professionals and managers implementing SDM wish to understand what difference it makes to clinical practice and to their patients. Within the MAGIC programme, researchers encountered difficulties in developing and identifying appropriate patient reported measures to encapsulate experience of SDM.

Patient reported measures are hindered by social desirability bias (wishing to provide high satisfaction scores), and patients might additionally not completely recognise and comprehend SDM if they have not encountered it before (Paul J Barr & Elwyn, 2016). Although, the 3 item CollaboRATE measure that evaluates the range to which each of three core SDM dimensions exist within a clinical consultation: clarification of the health problem, extraction of patient preferences and consolidation of patient preferences (utilised in 40+ studies worldwide) demonstrates potential in overcoming these challenges (Paul James Barr et al., 2014).

Tensions are present between the requirement for measuring for quality improvement and for reliable and validated measures for research. Concentrating on quality improvement aided embedding SDM quicker for some clinical groups. When measures precisely improved patient care and informed practice, researchers observed increased motivation to improve and to maintain the improvement (for example, the decision quality measure used for breast cancer that measures patient's preferences and knowledge). The breast care team utilises the tool to determine gaps in knowledge, show increases in knowledge, and obtain patients' preferences for more conversation (McGarrigle, Lloyd, Joseph-Williams, & Elwyn, 2012). Combining with local quality improvement resources and expertise, where accessible, was beneficial.

The final challenge faced by the researchers in the MAGIC programme was: "We have too many other demands and priorities". Altering behaviours and attitudes requires effort at every organisational level. Clinical groups confront numerous contending priorities and demands, some being mandatory, a few incentivised (either via targets or monetary). For instance, the Quality and Outcomes Framework rewards GPs for evidence-based behaviours though not certainly concerning what is most important to patients. Tensions are additionally escalating between SDM and referral management schemes or clinical threshold guidelines that are broadly practiced in England within commissioning. Likewise, for cancer care time targets, the present priority is on time to care however patients might prioritise time for making the decision.

Clear organisational support and buy-in are vital. Throughout the MAGIC programme, important organisational leaders demonstrated to healthcare professionals that SDM was a valuable organisational priority to push improvement, and clinical guidance was crucial to implementation. This caused increased engagement as healthcare professionals then viewed SDM as something the organisation carries out, instead of as an additional initiative being set on them and contending with different demands. Groups sometimes required help from the organisation to acclimate clinical pathways to aid productive SDM. SDM is not the singular responsibility of clinicians; it should be encouraged by every representative of the healthcare team. Responsibility can be shared-for instance,

a breast care surgeon can define the options, although the specialist nurse can evoke the patient's preferences in greater detail. It is vital to distribute learning concerning what works both between and within groups to refrain from "reinventing the wheel."

The important challenges the MAGIC programme encountered in implementing SDM in organisations traversing primary and secondary care have been summarised, however numerous additional factors also influence implementation. These include micro level and macro level factors. The micro level factors are: health/organisation board buy in displaying clear support for SDM, organisational control of SDM interventions, clinical group engagement, healthcare professionals that back SDM (and is clear to patients), patients that possess positive attitudes to SDM and wish to be involved, public and patient inclusion in intervention/development/testing/implementation. The macro factors are: national healthcare policies coordinated with SDM, education (undergraduate nursing/medical modules), training events (e.g. sustained professional development), school situated education (future patients), incentivise, help from professional groups, coordinating SDM with different targets (e.g. referrals, QOF), legal concerns e.g. informed consent. Greater detailed discussion of the obstacles and resolutions are accessible elsewhere (Joseph-Williams et al., 2014 ; Légaré et al., 2008). Identical discoveries have been recorded in the US (Andrews, Kearing, & Vidal, 2016; Tai-Seale et al., 2016; Zeballos-Palacios et al., 2016).

In reality, time, money and resources are each insufficient. Despite SDM being cited in important policy documents, like the NHS Constitution (Department of Health and Social Care, 2015) it has not any incentives and is not advocated consistently at organisational, national or regional levels. Promoting cultural change between patients and healthcare professionals is still required, and this is a significant difficulty. An amenable culture will legitimately exist solely if healthcare professionals regard SDM as common practice and as a vital part of compassionate, safe and efficient healthcare for patients. It must be embedded in the nursing and medical course of studies and interprofessional training programmes. Likewise, a lot of professional practice and health policy has caused feelings of passivity and powerlessness for numerous patients. Increasing patient health literacy, agency and activation are equivalently crucial (Hernandez, Anderson, & Chao, 2009).

Albeit these actions might aid implementation of SDM, they do not standardise the process: each discussion differs, contingent on the healthcare professional, patient, their preferences, and the nature of decision being made. SDM might not certainly depend on or result in total agreement between a patient and a healthcare professional. Rather, it is concerning brining both forms of knowledge together and evaluating the available choices in considering both of these viewpoints; it makes it more probable that the conclusive decision is informed by what healthcare professional knows (clinical

experience, medical evidence) and by what the patient knows (the consequences they are ready to accept, what is important to them).

Attitudes must change to demonstrate this, in order that patients are not viewed as “non-compliant” if they have another opinion, and healthcare professionals are not viewed as excessively paternalistic if they are heeding the patient’s preferences and taking this into account within a recommended treatment plan. Additionally, it should be stressed that SDM is not limited to one patient and one healthcare professional, during one appointment. The process is dispersed across healthcare groups, and among patients and their families, each of whom will impact the process, particularly for patients that have long-term conditions (Rapley, 2008).

Implementing SDM is difficult but attainable. One intervention will not succeed on its own. It needs interventions to help patients, organisations and healthcare professionals: an array of interventions functioning together wholly across each healthcare location.

The important lessons from the MAGIC programme were: SDM concerns more than tools: “skills trump tools, but attitudes trump skills”, successful implementation depends on an amalgamation of interventions assisting the patients, organisations and healthcare professionals, organisational backing and local ownership are crucial for involvement. A crucial finding of the MAGIC project was that “skills trump tools, and attitudes trump skills”.

The significance of embedding training in SDM into every level of education for GPs, nurses and other healthcare professionals was raised by several participants. Training offers familiarity with a range of techniques and tools, including option grids and DAs to be used in appointments with patients, and decision quality measures to aid them in testing if they are “getting it right”. However, one doctor stated whilst it was important to learn about the tools (i.e. the option grids and DAs), the most valuable thing they had acquired from training in SDM was the confidence and mindset (i.e. positive attitude) to have various conversations with their patients, and the skills and knowledge to support these conversations.

2.3 Key Models and Theories for SDM

Despite the extensive interest in SDM, the implementation of SDM within Scotland has been inconsistent (Coulter & Collins, 2011). Shared decision-making is still in its early stages and there is still uncertainty surrounding what it means and inconsistency in how it is implemented for both practitioners and patients. If it is to be successfully implemented greater clarity is required about SDM.

In trying to provide greater consistency and aiming towards a more unified view on what SDM is, Bomhof-Roordink et al. (2019) carried out a systematic review that aimed to identify key components of shared decision-making models. They found that the top components included: describe treatment options, make the decision, patient preferences, tailor information, deliberate, create choice awareness, learn about the patient and agreeing on the final decision.

In order to achieve SDM, patients need to be informed on the outcomes of different treatment options (Elwyn et al., 2012). Then the healthcare professional needs to aid patients in deliberating over the available options. Elwyn et al. (2012) suggested a model based on how to carry out SDM in medical practice, composed of 3 important stages: choice talk, option talk and decision talk but additionally considering that numerous other individuals might contribute to the SDM process. Choice talk entails healthcare professionals ensuring that patients are aware that valid options are available. The healthcare professional then gives more detailed information regarding the options i.e. option talk. Finally, the decision talk seeks to aid in the process of deliberating preferences and deciding the best course of action.

The Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) (Icek Ajzen, 1991) is among the most influential and frequently cited psychological models used to predict human behaviour as it pinpoints the control elements of decision making (Icek Ajzen, 2011). Since TPB has proven to be useful in explaining behaviour and behavioural intention regarding health outcomes, it may be useful in studying SDM. A systematic review (Godin, Bélanger-Gravel, Eccles, & Grimshaw, 2008) found that the TPB functioned better than other theories in predicting health outcomes, and studies which utilised the TPB had significantly better predictive ability. Consequently, study 3 (Chapter 6) used the TBP as the overarching theoretical framework to examine intentions and behaviour in the area of SDM.

A key element in the TPB is the person's intention to carry out a behaviour. Intentions are expected to capture the motivational elements which influence a behaviour and are signs of how much individuals are willing to try, how much of an attempt they're preparing to apply to carry out the behaviour. Intentions to engage in SDM are an important aspect of SDM. The broad model underlying the TPB theorises 3 conceptually separate predictors of behavioural intentions: attitudes, subjective norms and perceived behavioural control. The first concerns individuals' attitude to the behaviour and regards the extent to which an individual has a positive or negative evaluation of the target behaviour, in this case SDM.

The second determinant of behavioural intention concerns a social element named subjective norms, which refers to the perceived social pressure to carry out a specific behaviour. The third motive of intention is the extent of perceived behavioural control which regards the perceived difficulty or ease

of carrying out the behaviour. Perceived behavioural control is a valuable element in the TPB. The current perspective of perceived behavioural control is most consistent with Bandura's (Bandura, 1977, 1982) construct of perceived self-efficacy which concerns judgments of how efficiently an individual can carry out courses of action needed to tackle prospective situations (Bandura, 1982). Many researchers have used the TPB to understand and predict individuals' intentions to take part in different activities (Beale & Manstead, 1991; Godin & Shephard, 1990; Van Ryn, 1990). Review of these studies show that typically a large amount of variance in behavioural intentions can be explained by the 3 determinants in the TPB.

A systematic review was carried out (Thompson-Leduc, Clayman, Turcotte, & Légaré, 2015) on studies that utilised the TPB to assess SDM behaviours amongst healthcare professionals. They found that subjective norm, perceived behavioural control (sometimes replaced with/measured using self-efficacy) and attitude were the most frequently identified determinants of healthcare professionals' intention to engage in SDM-related behaviours. They also found that intention was the most predictive variable for a healthcare professional to carry out a SDM behaviour.

2.4 Decision Aids

Decision aids (DA) are tools which assist individuals to engage in decision making through making clear the decision which must be made, through defining personal values and supplying information concerning the outcomes and options. They are intended to complement instead of replacing counselling from a healthcare professional (National Institute for Health and Care Excellence, 2016).

DAs can come in various media and formats, including traditional paper sheets explaining options, greater detailed pamphlets, dynamic web pages, computer programmes or DVDs of recorded interviews with clinicians and patients, enabling the patient to research into as little or as much information as they wish and how they choose. DAs differ from typical health education materials as they make clear the decision which must be made, supplying a personalised, specific and detailed focus on outcomes and options for the aim of preparing individuals for decision making. On the other hand, health education materials assist individuals to understand their management, treatment and diagnosis in comprehensive terms, but as they are broader in perspective, they are not focused around decision points and so do not necessarily assist individuals to engage in decision-making (Stacey et al., 2017).

Over the last twenty years, enthusiasts have advocated DAs to aid SDM (D. Stacey et al., 2017). Studies (D. Stacey et al., 2011; Waljee, Rogers, & Alderman, 2007; Whelan et al., 2004); suggest that DAs aid

SDM by increasing patients' satisfaction with the decision, confidence in the decision and knowledge of treatment options. SDM is a patient-centred practice which involves patients and clinicians working in partnership to decide together on the most appropriate treatment for each patient's unique situation (Wieringa, Engebretsen, Heggen, & Greenhalgh, 2017). DAs are tools which can aid the SDM process (Wieringa et al., 2017). However, SDM can be carried out without using DAs and is described as being more than just tools i.e. DAs (Joseph-Williams et al., 2017).

U.S. English

option grid

Depression: treatment options

Use this decision aid to help you and your healthcare professional talk about different ways to treat your depression. Most people will recover from an episode of depression. However, the first treatment may not work, and depression can come back.

Frequently Asked Questions ↓	Watchful waiting	Talk therapy	Medication
How does this treatment work?	This means no active treatment. You may see your clinician more often to check your symptoms, compare options and discuss your lifestyle and coping strategies.	Talk therapy works by helping you solve problems and clarify your thoughts. Treatment usually lasts 8 to 10 weeks, but can last longer. Therapy options include: In person: Meeting with a therapist every 1 to 2 weeks for 30 to 60 minutes. You may also do homework. On the computer: Using a program on your own or with your clinician's support.	Selective Serotonin Reuptake Inhibitors (SSRIs) are medications that help with symptoms. The pills are usually taken once a day. Treatment usually lasts for 6 to 12 months.
Will this treatment work?	23 out of every 100 people (23%) recover in 3 months through watchful waiting. 53 out of every 100 people (53%) recover in 1 year through watchful waiting.	In addition to the 23 out of every 100 people (23%) who recover through watchful waiting, another 14 out of every 100 people (14%) recover in 2 months with talk therapy. Computer programs work best when you check in regularly with your clinician. Combination therapy: In addition to the 23 out of every 100 people (23%) who recover through watchful waiting, another 26 out of every 100 people (26%) recover with a combination of SSRIs and talk therapy.	In addition to the 23 out of every 100 people (23%) who recover through watchful waiting, another 17 out of every 100 people (17%) recover in 1 month with SSRIs. Combination therapy: In addition to the 23 out of every 100 people (23%) who recover through watchful waiting, another 26 out of every 100 people (26%) recover with a combination of SSRIs and talk therapy.
What are the risks?	Watchful waiting can cause your symptoms to continue or get worse.	Talk therapy can cause discomfort, anxiety, and stress.	SSRIs can cause side effects. Nausea, diarrhea and drowsiness each affect up to 17 out of every 100 people (17%). Up to 13 out of every 100 people (13%) have sexual problems. Sweating, shaking, difficulty sleeping, and dry mouth are less common.
How much does this treatment cost?	Cost will depend on how often you visit your clinician and the type of visit. Work with your clinician and insurance company to check your costs.	In person: Prices will vary. Work with your therapist and insurance company to check your costs. On a computer: Some programs are free. "Mood Gym" is an example of a free online program: https://moodgym.anu.edu.au/	Without insurance: Prices will vary. In general, fluoxetine, citalopram, and paroxetine cost less than \$5 for a 30-day supply. Sertraline usually costs less than \$40 and escitalopram less than \$130 for a 30-day supply. With insurance: Prices will vary by plan. Work with your insurance company to check your costs and coverage.
Is there anything else I can do?	Exercise, healthy eating and visiting with friends can help with symptoms. Other resources may be available at your workplace, in your community or online.	Exercise, healthy eating and visiting with friends can help with symptoms. Other resources may be available at your workplace, in your community or online.	Exercise, healthy eating and visiting with friends can help with symptoms. Other resources may be available at your workplace, in your community or online.

Figure 1. Option Grid Decision Aid: Treatment Options

Elwyn et al. (2013) set out to describe the exploratory utilisation of short DAs for patients, named Option Grids. Option grids are designed for patients to use whilst in an appointment with their healthcare professional (see Figure 1 above). They are comprised of short tables summarising each treatment choice on one side of A4 paper, allowing the quick comparison of choices, while utilising patients most frequently asked questions. The majority of patient DAs are for patients to use themselves prior to or after appointments and contain a lot of information, however the option grids are a shorter alternative to be used by both patient and clinician during an appointment. This tackles the common problem of allotted time for patient appointments. Elwyn et al. (2013) examined the utilisation of Option Grids in a quality improvement project (the MAGIC program), carrying out 52 semi-structured interviews with 7 clinical teams over 18 months. Observations were also conducted, and field notes were gathered. Feedback from healthcare professionals indicated the Option Grids made it simpler to explain the different choices available clearly and stated a 'handover' effect, in which patient inclusion in the decision-making process was increased. Therefore, the Option Grids increased visibility in treatment choices and clinicians felt it was easier to carry out SDM when the option grids were available. The Option Grids also improved patients' voice and confidence, increasing their engagement in cooperative discussions, when used in a cooperative manner. However, a concern raised from the MAGIC programme (Joseph-Williams et al., 2017) was the risk that healthcare professionals that utilise short DAs to improve information transfer and speak at patients, instead of developing how they work with patients, therefore potentially replacing SDM by only utilising these DAs.

Figure 2. Picture Option Grid

Researchers (Durand, Alam, Grande, & Elwyn, 2016) created and assessed the usability, acceptability and accessibility of a picture-based DA (see Figure 2 above) to be utilised within clinical appointments aimed at females of low socioeconomic status (SES) diagnosed with early-stage breast cancer. Durand

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et al. (2016) chose this population as females of low socioeconomic status (SES) that have been diagnosed with early-stage breast cancer encounter differences in health outcomes, decision-making and treatment (Wheeler, Reeder-Hayes, & Carey, 2013). Evidence (Durand et al., 2014) proposes that DA can benefit underserved individuals, when adapted to their requirements. Durand et al. (2016) aimed to create and assess the accessibility, usability and acceptability of a picture DA (to be utilised within clinical appointments) aimed at females of low socioeconomic status (SES) that had been diagnosed with early-stage breast cancer. The study design was community-based participatory research (CBPR) which utilised think-aloud protocols for the first 2 phases and semi-structured interviews for phase 3. The research was carried out at breast clinics and in “underserved” community settings such as senior centres, knitting groups and bingo halls. For phase 1, participants were selected via a convenience sample of academics and clinicians. For phase 2, participants consisted of low SES females aged 40+ years old despite their breast cancer history. For phase 3, participants were low SES females that had recently been diagnosed with breast cancer. The picture DA to be used in clinical appointments originated from an evidence-based option grid for breast cancer. Durand et al. (2016) tested the accessibility, usability and acceptability of the picture DA prototypes utilising the semi-structured interviews and think-aloud protocol. After primary assessment of the first prototype with eighteen clinicians and academics, additional variants were assessed and created with 53 “lay” participants in community settings. Usability was found to be high and as a response to feedback signifying that the utilisation of cartoon characters was thought to be insensitive, a picture-only variation was created and assessed with 23 “lay” individuals for phase 2, and ten target users for phase 3. Therefore, utilising iterative user testing cycles and CBPR methods increased accessibility and usability, and resulted in the creation of the Picture Option Grid, completely directed by numerous stakeholder feedback. Every female of low SES recently diagnosed with early-stage breast cancer perceived the Picture Option Grid accessible, usable and acceptable. However, a weakness of the study was the deficiency in diversity of participants in phase 3 as they were all Caucasian. Additionally, another limitation was the challenges in comparison created through the iterative method of the creation and assessment processes.

Interestingly, the creation of the Picture Option Grid being completely directed by numerous stakeholder feedback also coincides with Yamey’s (2011) findings. Yamey (2011) proposed a framework for describing success in large scale changes to global health, formed from key themes in the developing field. Factors which contributed to success for large scale changes were established from the published literature and from interviews with implementation experts. These factors included: active participation of a variety of key stakeholders (notably those delivering the change and

those impacted by the new intervention), strong governance and leadership and selecting a simplistic intervention broadly agreed to be beneficial by a majority (Yamey, 2011).

Volandes and colleagues (2011) aimed to evaluate the palliative preferences of aging patients in rural communities and if preferences are linked to level of health literacy. Elderly participants (aged 65+) took part in a randomised controlled trial of a “goals-of-care” video DA of advanced dementia at a primary care clinic in rural Louisiana. Half of the participants listened to a verbal description of advanced dementia and the goals of care. The remaining half listened to the same verbal description and then watched the video DA. End points were the favoured goal of care in advanced dementia: comfort care (symptom relief), life-prolonging care (cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR), etc.) or limited care (hospitalisation but not CPR). The most important category for analysis was the variation in ranges of participants favouring comfort care for every characteristic including health literacy level and randomisation group. The study found that rural participants with increased health literacy were more inclined to want comfort care in comparison to participants with decreased levels of health literacy. Additionally, participants who watched a video DA were more inclined to choose comfort in comparison to participants that only heard a verbal description. These results propose that video can assist in eliciting preferences and that interventions to enable such patients must be created in an approach that takes into account varying levels of health literacy. However, there were several limitations to this study. The interviewer who collected the data was not blinded to randomisation assignment, thus potentially introducing bias. Additionally, it was a smaller study that consisted of 76 participants from one rural location in Louisiana meaning that the results may not be able to be generalised to other rural locations. Finally, the video used in the study portrayed an African American healthcare professional as the narrator with white patients. The researchers did not assess the robustness of the study results utilising additional video clips which assorted the characteristics of the patient e.g. the clinical setting, ethnicity/race or gender. It is possible that the race of healthcare professionals or patients could be internalised differently for individuals from different races (Jibaja-Weiss & Volk, 2007).

Figure 3. The Diabetes Medication Choice Decision Aid Cards

Researchers (Mullan et al., 2009) created a medicinal option DA (see Figure 3 above) for patients that have type 2 diabetes. They created the DA via active collaboration with designers, patients and clinicians, observations of clinical appointments, literature review, and collaborative creation of design criteria. Observations from these methods informed the iterative development of prototypes which were field tested and reviewed in real appointments. The aim of the DA was to promote a discussion between the patient and clinician regarding diabetes medication choices. A total of 4 iterations of the DA were produced and field-tested prior to attaining issue cards which arranged the data for 5

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medications regarding glucose control, weight alterations, hypoglycaemia, side effects, daily routine and self-monitoring. These cards successfully produced discussions during appointments. The card-based DA was then named Diabetes Medication Choice and was utilised in a pilot, cluster randomised trial (Mullan et al., 2009). The aid explains 5 antihyperglycemic medications, their treatment strains (unfavourable effects, self-monitoring, and administration requirements), and effect on haemoglobin A1c (HbA1c) levels. 21 clinicians were randomised to utilise the DA during the clinical appointment and 19 to operate typical care and an information pamphlet. Researchers utilised video analysis and surveys to evaluate post-visit decisional outcomes and pharmacy and medical records to evaluate 6-month HbA1c levels and medication adherence. Compared to the 37 typical care patients, the 48 patients that received the DA found it more beneficial, had increased knowledge and were more included in making decisions regarding diabetes medications. At the six-month follow-up, the two groups had almost perfect medication utilisation with improved persistence and adherence in the typical care patients and no significant effect on HbA1c levels. Therefore, this creative DA efficiently engaged patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus in decisions regarding their medications, but it did not increase adherence or HbA1c levels.

Each of these DAs appear distinct in their own right, however whilst there are notable differences, there are also similarities between these DA. One obvious similarity is that each one is a DA. Another similarity for each of the DA except for the video DA, is that they all feature text. However, the option grid is the only DA which is solely text based. The picture option grid and the medication cards both heavily feature visual information, i.e. pictures and illustrations, and have some text to accompany the visual information. The video DA is also heavily visual but instead of pictures and illustrations, recorded film clips are used instead.

Each DA except for the video DA was created to be used in appointments. It is unclear whether the video DA is aimed to be used in or out with appointments. Two of the DA were specifically designed for use with patients with lower health literacy, the picture option grid and the video DA. However, the target population for each DA differed as the picture option grid was aimed at females of low socioeconomic status (SES) diagnosed with early-stage breast cancer and the video DA was target towards elderly participants (aged 65+) with advanced dementia in a rural community setting. The medication choice DA was aimed at patients with type 2 diabetes and the option grid DA has a range of target users as there are numerous option grids which are designed for various health conditions.

Each DA except for the video DA was tested with clinicians or had received clinician input to help create the DA. All DAs were tested with their own target population of patients. However, the medication card DA also involved work with designers of the DA and the picture option grid utilised academics,

low SES females aged 40+ years old despite their breast cancer history and “lay” individuals in addition to clinicians and target patient users. The medication card DA and the picture option grid also both utilised iterative user testing cycles of prototypes of their DA.

Outcome measures also differed for the DAs, as Option Grids found that patient inclusion in the decision-making process was increased. Option Grids also increased visibility in treatment choices, and clinicians felt it was easier to carry out SDM when the Option Grids were available. When utilised in a collaborative manner, the Option Grids improved patients’ voice and confidence, increasing their engagement in discussions. For the Picture Option Grid, every female of low SES recently diagnosed with early-stage breast cancer perceived the Picture Option Grid accessible, usable and acceptable. The video DA study found that rural participants with increased health literacy were more inclined to want comfort care in comparison to participants with decreased levels of health literacy, participants who watched a video DA were more inclined to choose comfort in comparison to participants that only heard a verbal description, therefore proposing that video can assist in eliciting preferences and that interventions to enable such patients must be created in an approach that takes into account varying levels of health literacy. For the medication cards DA compared to the 37 typical care patients, the 48 patients that received the DA found it more beneficial, had increased knowledge and were more included in making decisions regarding diabetes medications. At the six-month follow-up, the two groups had almost perfect medication utilisation with improved persistence and adherence in the typical care patients and no significant effect on HbA1c levels. Therefore, this creative DA efficiently engaged patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus in decisions regarding their medications, but it did not increase adherence or HbA1c levels. However, the option grid DA and the medication cards DA both reported increases in patients’ engagement with decisions regarding their condition.

As each DA listed above and in general is targeted towards a specific population with their own specified outcome measures, it is impossible to assess which DA is the “best”. However, the picture option grid and the video DA were examples of visual DA which were aimed at and found that they could be used to aid individuals with low health literacy, thus these DA may be more accessible for more people to use compared to other DAs. As a result, there are no studies which have compared DA and evaluated or rated which one is the “best”. Although, researchers (Elwyn et al., 2009) created inter-rater reliability and validated an instrument to measure the quality of DA.

As global interest in DAs is increasing, it is vital to have internationally accepted standards to test the quality of their creation, potential bias, process, content and method of evaluation and field testing. Thus, this scale development study was carried out which included scale, construct and item development, reliability and validation testing. 25 researcher-members of the International Patient

Decision Aid Standards Collaboration collectively worked to create the instrument (IPDASi). For the reliability study, 8 raters tested 30 randomly chosen DA. IPDASi measures quality utilising 47 items, in 10 dimensions and supplies an overall quality score for each DA (scaled from 0 to 100). Overall IPDASi scores varied from 33 to 82 over the 30 DAs tested, enabling discrimination. The inter-rater intraclass correlation for the overall quality score was 0.80. All correlations of dimension scores with the overall score were positive (0.31-0.68) Cronbach's alpha values for the eight raters varied from 0.72-0.93. Cronbach's alphas formed on the dimension means varied from 0.50-0.81, signifying that the dimensions, despite highly correlated, measure distinct features of DA. A short variation which consisted of 19 items was additionally created which had highly similar average scores to IPDASi and high correlation between overall score and short score 0.87. Thus, displaying that IPDASi has the capability to test the quality of DA. The existent IPDASi supplies an assessment of the quality of a DA's components and will be utilised as an instrument to supply formative advice to DA creators and summative assessments for individuals who desire to compare their DA against an existent benchmark. Of the 30 DA evaluated in this study, the DA which scored highest using the IPDASi was a text based (paper) DA created by (Wakefield et al., 2008) for breast and ovarian cancer screening. The remaining DA used either text, website or video, perhaps suggesting that these formats are best for DA. However, only 30 DAs were included in this study and even though Wakefield et al.'s (2008) DA performed the best, the DA had no impact on genetic testing decision, informed choice or post-decisional regret. Although, females that used the DA had increased knowledge and felt better informed regarding genetic testing than females who were given a pamphlet. The DA additionally assisted females who did not have blood taken at their initial appointment to clarify their values around genetic testing.

Additionally, Stacey et al. (2017) tested the impacts of 105 DAs targeted towards individuals facing screening or treatment decisions. Whilst collectively the DAs were found to have positive outcomes such as improved patient knowledge, increased patients' decisional readiness and decreased decisional conflict. Again, not one DA measured or achieved every outcome as different DAs only included/looked at certain outcome and therefore different DAs would perform better in regards to different outcomes. This coincides with a finding from the MAGIC (Joseph-Williams et al., 2017) programme that there will not be DAs for all decisions; neither will each patient perceive them as being beneficial or acceptable. Crucially, not one DA thus far has been able to achieve all SDM outcomes in relation to the International Patient Decision Aids Standards (IPDAS) criteria for appraising the efficiency of DAs (Elwyn et al., 2006; Sepucha et al., 2013). Therefore, currently there is no "best" DA.

The majority of DA have been created for patients to utilise alone out with the appointment, either at home or in the waiting room (Elwyn, Frosch, Volandes, Edwards, & Montori, 2010). Despite these DAs supporting understanding of the problems, they cannot assure that decisions in the appointment are

shared (Hargraves & Montori, 2014; Stiggelbout et al., 2012) and there is not enough evidence to discover how their utilisation impacts the appointment (Hargraves & Montori, 2014). Another issue is that utilisation of DAs in standard care is low (Elwyn, Légaré, Weijden, Edwards, & May, 2008), primarily due to poor design and deficiency of available access to them. Additionally, clinicians might find the form unrealistic to utilise in appointments and might be as inexperienced as their patients with risk estimations and the natural doubt accompanying probabilities (Perneger & Agoritsas, 2011).

Newer DAs such as the ones mentioned above seem to adopt a trend of being brief and to be utilised within appointments compared to traditional aids which contained more information and were to be used out with the appointment (Agoritsas et al., 2015).

DAs are unlike traditional information materials given to patients as they do not instruct patients what to do but outline the facts and assist patients to contemplate the choices. DAs normally include: an outline of the symptoms and the condition, the probable prognosis without and with treatment, the self-management support and treatment choices and outcome probabilities, uncertainties and what is known from the evidence, illustrations to assist patients in comprehending what it would be like to experience a few of the most occurring complications or side-effects of the treatment choices (usually utilising patient interviews), a method of assisting patients to define their preferences, sources of additional information and references, the authors' declarations of conflict of interest, credentials and funding source (Coulter & Collins, 2011).

Currently, there are an abundant amount of DAs available, a lot of which are indexed on 2 websites, "www.thedecisionaidcollection.nl" and "www.decisionaid.ohri.ca". A Cochrane review (O'Connor et al., 2009) has outlined the results from 55 randomised controlled trials which evaluated the utility of these DAs. This review discovered that the utilisation of DAs produced: increased participation in decision-making, greater accuracy in risk perceptions, less patients remaining undecided, increase in knowledge, less people opting for major surgery, increased ease with decisions and no additional anxiety.

The evidence base for SDM within the Clinical Strategy (Scottish Government, 2016) is robust, and specifically gives strong support to the benefits of DA. A systematic review (Stacey et al., 2014) on use of DA to support screening or treatment decisions confirmed that there is high quality evidence that DAs improve patient-practitioner communication and increase people's ability to make informed, value-based decisions. There is also strong evidence showing shared DA decrease decisional conflict, increase knowledge and encourage patients to be more involved in decision-making, while not increasing their anxiety (O'Connor et al., 1999). Meta-analyses have also demonstrated the potential for DAs to reduce over-use of services (Stacey et al., 2014), showing that people supported with DA

are more likely to favour conservative options over elective surgery. They are also less likely to choose to have prostate-specific antigen screening, and less likely to choose menopausal hormone therapy.

This reduction in over-use of services could lead to huge cost-saving significance for health-care providers (Jayadev, Khan, Coulter, Beard, & Price, 2012). Researchers (Kennedy et al., 2002) carried out a multicentre randomised controlled trial in the UK that evaluated the impact of a DA across 894 females that had heavy menstrual bleeding which was followed up for two years. Utilisation of the DA resulted in a significant decline for surgery rates and a related decline in health care spending. Waiting times for elective surgery are also a principal health policy concern for about half of the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) countries (Hurst & Siciliani, 2003). Average waiting times for elective surgical procedures are more than 3 months in numerous countries and maximum waiting times can extend into years. This creates discontent amongst the general public and for the patients. Waiting times can also cause additional costs, deterioration in health and loss of utility (Hurst, & Siciliani, 2003). Conservative treatment options have also been shown to improve quality of life and improve symptoms in patients with Primary Chronic Venous Disease (Lurie & Kistner, 2011) and to significantly improve functioning and pain in patients with clinical indications of Prearthritic, Intra-articular Hip Disorders (Hunt, Prather, Hayes, & Clohisy, 2012).

Over the last 20 years enthusiasts have promoted DAs to assist SDM and more than 500 have been created (Stacey et al., 2014). A systematic review of 105 DAs demonstrated that their utilisation caused individuals to feel more informed, better educated and more transparent regarding their values, and they possibly have a more active part in decision making and more precise risk perceptions. There is also increasing evidence the DAs might increase values-congruent decisions. There are not any unfavourable impacts on satisfaction or health outcomes. However, there is evidence signifying increased knowledge and precise risk perceptions when DAs are utilised in or prior to appointments. Although, more research is required on the impacts of adherence with the selected choice, cost-effectiveness, and utilisation with lower literacy populations (Stacey et al., 2017). Therefore, not one DA thus far has been able to achieve all SDM outcomes in relation to the International Patient Decision Aids Standards (IPDAS) criteria for appraising the efficiency of DA (Elwyn et al., 2006; Sepucha et al., 2013).

Despite, the existence of several DA for chronic pain, there appears to be a knowledge gap in which type/format of DA is more effective for patients with chronic pain. However, researchers (Fraenkel, Rabidou, Wittink, & Fried, 2007) carried out a study composed of 87 patients who compared an educational pamphlet with an interactive computer program for decision-making in knee pain. Patients that utilised the interactive computer program had increased preparedness to partake in SDM and

increased confidence than patients who utilised the pamphlet. Thus, showing that well-developed DA for patients with chronic pain can be readily accepted and increase patient engagement in SDM.

However, as each DA discussed previously and in general is targeted towards a specific population with their own specified outcome measures, it is impossible to assess which DA is the “best”. However, the picture option grid and the video DA were examples of visual DA which were aimed at and found that they could be used to aid individuals with low health literacy, thus these DA may be more accessible for more people to use compared to other DAs. Limited literacy skills are common in all ethnic groups and ages however individuals from ethnic and racial minorities and the elderly are disproportionately affected (Kindig, Panzer, & Nielsen-Bohlman, 2004).

Smith et al. (2001) aimed to describe the distribution and prevalence in the society of chronic pain defined as ‘severe’ and ‘significant’ and to investigate the effect of chronic pain on activity and health. A questionnaire survey was completed by a sample taken from the general population in the Grampian area of Scotland. Questionnaires were distributed to a random sample of 4,611 people aged 25+ years old, stratified for gender and age, chosen from the practice lists of 29 general practices. The total practice population was 136,383. The instrument used in the study included a case definition questionnaire, which identified people with ‘any chronic pain’ (pain lasting a minimum of 3 months). From this sample, 14.1% stated ‘significant chronic pain’ which was more prevalent in older age groups and females. A total of 6.3% stated ‘severe chronic pain’ which was more prevalent amongst older age groups. Factors independently associated with both ‘severe’ and ‘significant’ chronic pain were lower educational level, female gender, being retired or unable to work because of disability or sickness and living in council rented accommodation.

Therefore, the individuals who would perhaps benefit most from a DA for chronic pain i.e., that have significant or severe chronic pain are individuals with low health literacy e.g. the elderly and individuals with lower educational level. Thus, a visual DA such as a picture or video DA would perhaps be the most suitable type of DA for chronic pain as these formats have been shown to benefit individuals with low health literacy as discussed previously with the picture option grid and the video DA. Video DA can also help address the limited literacy skills that are common amongst ethnic and racial minorities who are disproportionately affected (Kindig et al., 2004).

Researchers (Weng et al., 2007) tested the effect of an educational video concerning total knee replacement (TKR) on expectations and knowledge in 102 white and black veterans. Veteran’s reactions to the video were tested via questions concerning how informative it was, usefulness in decision-making and its understandability. Both groups recommended the video and found it useful for decision-making. The study stated an increase in expectations for black participants and small

difference for white participants from baseline, proposing a removal of baseline decisional disparities. Decisional conflict increased after DA intervention with decisional conflict scores lowering from 29.4 to 25.8. Knowledge also increased with participants able to successfully describe TKA efficiency improving from 31% preintervention to 77% postintervention. However, the study was limited as there was a relatively small number of participants and the study did not include a control group. Although, the researchers did state that the study produced pilot data which proposes hypotheses for evaluation in future studies.

There are several other studies which also support using a video DA for chronic pain conditions. Researchers (Spunt et al., 1996) carried out a large-scale study composed of 239 patients that watched a video about back pain treatment which demonstrated similar shifts in decisional conflict with less patients remaining undecided concerning treatment after watching the video (17% vs 29%). The video was well accepted in concern to its amount of information, understandability, helping patients decide about treatment and keeping the interest of viewers. However, the researchers admitted that they were unsure the degree to which their participants represented all patients with low back pain that are contemplating surgery.

Phelan et al. (2001) carried out a randomised trial of 100 surgical candidates with low back pain that received an interactive video and a booklet or only a booklet about back surgery. Every patient showed an increase in knowledge regarding treatment options. Although, the combination of the booklet and video led to higher knowledge gain for patients with low baseline scores. Also, participants favoured the combination intervention and surgical preference was less in the group supplied with the video. However, this study provided support for a video DA and a booklet, not just for the video DA alone, perhaps suggesting a video DA and a booklet maybe beneficial for chronic pain patients instead of only a video DA. Similarly, Deyo et al. (2000) conducted a study of 393 elective spine surgery candidates, utilising the same study design and found that there was a 22% decreased surgery rate overall in the video group with no significant difference in patient satisfaction with the decision-making process or their care. However, the study only took place at 2 general practices and with well-educated patients which may have affected the generalisability of the results.

However, despite years of research into the effectiveness of DAs validating the benefits of their use, widespread medical implementation has yet to be achieved (Natalie Joseph-Williams et al., 2021).

2.5 Chronic Pain

Chronic pain (otherwise characterised as persistent pain) can be understood as pain which lasts longer than 12 weeks, despite treatment or medication (NHS Scotland, 2023). The prevalence of severe

chronic pain is akin to that of major depression, heart disease and diabetes, and within Europe, it is predicted that 20% of adults endure chronic pain (Breivik et al., 2006) and 5.6% of adults suffer severe (i.e. disabling and intense) chronic pain (Smith et al., 2001). Within Scotland and universally, chronic pain conditions are certainly the biggest cause of disability (determined as Years Lived with Disability) (Vos et al., 2015). Chronic pain is more severe and of greater frequency amongst elderly adults (Breivik et al., 2006; Smith et al., 2001), thus the issue is increasing as the UK population becomes older with 18% aged 65 and over, and 2.4% aged 85 and over (Randall, 2017).

Chronic pain impacts every form of wellbeing – social, physical, psychological – and is correlated with low overall quality of life (Smith et al., 2001). It is one of the most frequent comorbidities of different long-term conditions, such as diabetes, respiratory and heart disease and cancer (Barnett et al., 2012). Specifically, it is linked with depression, which is inclined to be bi-directional by pain aggravating depression and conversely.

Chronic pain has been chosen as the test case for this thesis, as in addition to having a considerable impact on the quality of life for many individuals and their families in Scotland, the condition also has a substantial impact on society, the healthcare services and on economic costs. There are approximately 4.6 million doctor appointments per year in the UK for chronic pain (equal to 793 fulltime doctors) (Belsey, 2002). Individuals with chronic pain visit a doctor 5 times more regularly compared to those without (Von Korff et al., 1990). Chronic pain makes for a worthwhile case study for a DA as the many treatment options patients may choose from can be understood as either pharmacological (e.g. painkillers, ointment and patches) or non-pharmacological (e.g. physiotherapy exercises, acupuncture and Transcutaneous Electro-Nerve Stimulator (TENS) units).

SDM has been shown to improve longer term outcomes in several studies that explored both mental and physical health conditions (Joosten et al., 2008), and positive impacts were observed on patient's adherence to plans, satisfaction, knowledge and well-being. Researchers (Müller et al., 2004) looked at the effects of SDM in patients with Fibromyalgia syndrome which is an exemplary condition of chronic widespread pain. They found that patients' readiness to enrol in physical activities, to take analgesics, and to participate in psychotherapeutic elements were most likely to be raised through SDM.

SDM in patients with chronic pain is important, as patients need to self-manage their pain effectively. (Mann et al., 2013). SDM can support patients in evaluating their options and help identify the best one for them to help manage their condition, thus amongst other benefits, potentially reducing over-use of medical interventions (Murray et al., 2004; O'Connor et al., 2009).

Researchers (Kerns, Rosenberg, Jamison, Caudill, & Haythornthwaite, 1997; Strong, Ashton, & Chant, 1992) have suggested examining whether differences in the type of pain suffered by patients with chronic pain, persistent baseline level and breakthrough levels of pain and differences in patients' readiness to change influence their attitudes to pain. Strong and colleagues (1992) compared the psychometric properties of 2 scales designed to measure the beliefs about and attitudes towards pain; the Pain Beliefs and Perceptions Inventory (PBPI) (Williams & Thorn, 1989) and the Survey of Pain Attitudes (Revised) SOPA(R) (Jensen, Karoly, & Huger, 1987) were investigated in relation to sensitivity to gender and age effects, internal consistency, construct validity, discriminant validity and factor structure. The results showed strong support for the SOPA(R) as a beneficial measurement tool for utilisation with individuals with chronic low back pain. More work is proposed for the PBPI, as the stated factor structure was not replicated. Discussion focused on the possible causes for this result, with problems such as the possible influence of length of years in pain and the possible variation in attitudes between individuals with different types of pain being considered.

Kerns and colleagues (1997) detailed the development and preliminary validation of a self-report questionnaire created to evaluate a person's readiness to undertake a self-management approach to their chronic pain condition (i.e. their readiness to change). Theory and initial empirical work led to the formation of a pool of items which were given to a sample of people reporting chronic pain. Data analysis supported a 4-factor measure which is compatible with the associated stages of change model and the transtheoretical model of change. The 4 factors (precontemplation, contemplation, action, and maintenance) were established to be stable and internally consistent over time. There was also ample support for every factor's criterion-related and discriminant validity.

Examining a person's level of motivation, i.e. their readiness to change, has transpired in adult pain research as a probable key factor for successful pain self-management (Jensen, Nielson, & Kerns, 2003).

Readiness to change is an important factor/stage in patients changing behaviour in 2 health models: The Transtheoretical Model (TTM) (Prochaska & DiClemente, 1983) and the Motivational Model of Pain Self-Management (Jensen et al., 2003).

2.5.1. Key Chronic Pain Models

The Transtheoretical Model (TTM) (Prochaska & DiClemente, 1983), also referred to as the Stages of Change Model, was developed as a result of studies investigating the experiences of smokers that chose to quit by themselves and those that needed further treatment, to comprehend why some individuals were able to quit without support. A key outcome was the realisation that individuals

stopped smoking if they felt ready to. Therefore, TTM is a model of intentional change and concentrates on the decision-making of a single person. The model functions on the assumption that individuals do not change behaviours decisively and quickly, with the “readiness to change” the third stage of the model, referred to as the “Preparation or determination” stage. In this stage, individuals feel ready to take action in the following 30 days and begin to take small steps towards the behaviour change and they feel that altering their behaviour can lead to a healthier life.

Researchers (Nielson, Jensen, Ehde, Kerns, & Molton, 2008) described further development of the Multidimensional Pain Readiness to Change Questionnaire (MPRCQ2), a measure of readiness to use a range of coping and pain management strategies frequently taught in multidisciplinary treatment programs. Participants were recruited from an Arthritis Day Program (n = 51) and a Fibromyalgia Day Program (n = 139) in addition to 2 survey samples with pain resulting from either an amputation (n = 120) or a spinal cord injury (n = 127). The results signified initial support for the validity and reliability of the MPRCQ2. It was also found that the MPRCQ2 could be useful in future research examining the relationship between adjustment to chronic pain and adoption of coping behaviours and readiness to change pain-related coping. However, a limitation of this study was that participants were self-selected causing a deficiency in random selection of study samples from each participants represented population. Therefore, their answers to the questionnaires might have been different in some aspects from the populations of individuals they portray. Despite participation rates and sample sizes being high for this study, it is possible that if the participants had been randomly selected from a wider population of patients with chronic health conditions that the findings may have differed. The generalisability of the findings might have additionally been limited by the ethnic and gender composition of participants as most arthritis and fibromyalgia patients were females and most participants were Caucasian.

The Motivational Model of Pain Self-Management (Jensen et al., 2003) is a model in which patient motivation to participate in pain self-management behaviours was assumed to be a vital predictor of adaption to pain. Established from an expectancy value approach, readiness to change is determined through the patient’s perceived importance of the coping behaviour and the patient’s perceived ability to utilise or adopt the coping response (i.e. self-efficacy). An expectancy value approach encompasses that an individual’s performance, choice and persistence can be influenced by their beliefs concerning how well they will perform on the activity and how much they value the activity (Wigfield, 1994). The essential outcomes of the model are avoidance of maladaptive and engagement in adaptive coping responses. These coping responses are then believed to aid patient function (or dysfunction).

The TTM operates on the assumption that people do not change behaviours quickly and decisively. Readiness to change is the important factor/stage in patients changing behaviour in both health models and is associated with an increase in pain coping and in multidisciplinary pain treatment (Jensen, Nielson, Turner, Romano, & Hill, 2004; Kerns & Rosenberg, 2000). Therefore, it might be a key factor for patients with chronic pain to partake in SDM which may in turn help them to engage in adaptive coping responses and to self-manage their pain efficiently.

2.6 Impact of COVID-19 on SDM

Throughout the present Coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic, there is a larger demand to promote participation in SDM. The pandemic has produced opportunities and challenges for delivering healthcare, as system changes impact the patient-healthcare professional relationship. However, whilst the reallocation of health services and social distancing can impede preference for a face-to-face appointment, these measures simultaneously present the opportunity to examine and implement virtual SDM processes (Abrams et al., 2020).

Additionally, the most recent National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) guidance (Carmona et al., 2021) on SDM made recommendations for research to fill the most notable gaps in the evidence, agreeing that research was needed into how SDM needs to be modified for remote consultations (for example, by telephone or online).

2.7 Gaps in the Literature

The current research makes an original contribution to knowledge by exploring the use of DAs and SDM in NHS Boards in Scotland. Despite the central role of SDM in the government's new model of healthcare quality, the utilisation of DAs and SDM within the UK has been inconsistent (Coulter and Collins, 2011) and no existing literature or resources were found that detailed the use of DAs and SDM in NHS Scotland. All DAs and SDM literature including the MAGIC programme (despite claiming to cover the UK) were all in relation to NHS England and Wales. Therefore, the current research described in this work seeks to fill the gap in the literature. Also, despite the existence of literature on clinicians' attitudes to SDM, no literature could additionally be found on Scottish healthcare professionals' attitudes to SDM and only one study could be found on clinicians' attitudes to SDM in a chronic pain context (conducted in the United States).

Additionally, another potential for original contribution to knowledge investigating patients' attitudes to SDM in study 2 (see Chapter 5), whereas the majority of the literature focuses mostly on healthcare professionals' attitudes to SDM and DAs. Studies such as Légaré and colleagues (2008) have examined health care professionals' attitudes to SDM in an effort to comprehend why SDM is not currently standard practice universally. Furthermore, no existing literature can be found on the relationship between readiness to change and SDM, yet there are studies discussed previously that show support for SDM and readiness to change for chronic pain patients.

No literature could be found which investigated which factors are involved in the acceptance of SDM in a chronic pain context. There are theories and models of decision-making in Psychology and in healthcare but there are no theories or models which look at/incorporate the acceptance of SDM in a chronic pain context. Therefore, investigating potential factors of acceptance in SDM in a chronic pain context from chronic pain patients can help contribute to a new psychological model or theory which outlines acceptance in SDM in a chronic pain context, thus addressing a further gap in the literature.

In their guidance around facilitating SDM and how to implement it as standard practice, the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) recommended that future research focuses on how SDM differs between different groups of patients and in different healthcare settings; how to encourage patients to engage in SDM and how SDM may be required to be adapted for remote consultations. Thus, this research also focuses on these key areas, originally contributing to knowledge in a Scottish context to aid the successful implementation of SDM in Scotland.

Chapter 3: Methodology

3.1 Introduction

Previous research on shared decision-making (SDM) in healthcare had focussed on healthcare professionals' views about SDM. Little research had been carried out looking at patients' views about SDM for health decisions. Clearly, in order for SDM to be implemented successfully, both parties need to buy into and accept the advantages of SDM. Consequently, the overall aim of this thesis was to address this gap and provide a fuller and more comprehensive picture of SDM, by exploring and identifying key factors that would facilitate the successful implementation of medical SDM amongst patients in Scotland. The main research questions are:

- Is medical SDM successfully implemented in Scotland?
- What factors predict acceptance of medical SDM for individuals with chronic pain?
- What factors predict engagement in medical SDM for members of the Scottish general population?
- What are the attitudes to and experiences of medical SDM amongst the general population in Scotland and amongst individuals with chronic pain?

3.2 Research Methods

The first study (1) was qualitative, with nine semi-structured interviews conducted with members from 7 different NHS boards. The second study (2) used a quantitative survey to investigate the predictors of acceptance of SDM by 195 individuals with chronic pain. The third study (3) also used a quantitative survey, with 210 respondents that were members of the Scottish general population. Finally, the fourth study (4) consisted of semi-structured interviews with 12 participants who were members of the Scottish general population and 12 participants that experience chronic pain who also live in Scotland. Chronic pain is pain that persists for more than 12 weeks despite treatment or medication (NHS Scotland, 2023). Although 24 interviews were carried out, 14 of the interviews (7 general population and 7 chronic pain) were transcribed and analysed as data saturation had occurred at this point.

The use of qualitative measures in studies 1 and 4 and the use of quantitative methods in studies 2 and 3 results in a mixed methods approach which combines quantitative and qualitative methods (Lund, 2012). More specifically, a multiphase mixed methods design was used. The multiphase mixed methods design consists of 3 or more phases of data collection and is a more complex design (Almeida,

2018). The complexity of the design is not solely based on the number of studies but additionally in what way the studies depend on one another (Almeida, 2018). The phases can be qualitative, quantitative or mixed methods. There are three steps in a multiphase mixed methods design:

- Examine and define the overarching aim of the issue
- Carry out a sequence of quantitative, qualitative and/or mixed methods studies
- Base each new study on what was previously learned

3.3 Justification

The reason behind using a mixed methods approach is through blending quantitative and qualitative methods, each respective methods strengths are utilised, and their respective weaknesses are avoided (Tashakkori & Teddlie, 1998). A multiphase mixed methods design was used as health research involves investigating complex systems and multilevel processes that can require both qualitative and quantitative types of data (Creswell, Fetters, & Ivankova, 2004; Curry et al., 2013). Additionally, mixed methods research aims to supply a more in-depth understanding of a phenomenon which would not have been attainable through utilising a single approach (Creswell & Clark, 2011; Morse & Niehaus, 2009).

Creswell (2014) believes that all researchers bring a philosophical view to their research. The philosophical view is a set of values or beliefs which inform how researchers carry out a study (Guba, 1990). These beliefs might relate to epistemology (the types of evidence researchers use to make claims) or ontology (whether the researcher believes that reality is singular or multiple) (Creswell, 2014). Individuals often associated philosophy with research methods, i.e. collecting qualitative data was frequently associated with a constructivist philosophical view whilst gathering quantitative data reflected a postpositivism philosophical view (Creswell, 2014).

Thus, the current researcher adheres to critical realism as this philosophy informs both qualitative and quantitative data collection using mixed methods (Creswell, 2014). Referred to as a “stance” (Maxwell & Mittapalli, 2010), critical realism supports the notion that qualitative and quantitative research can work together in order to address the other’s weaknesses. Critical realists highly value new perspectives, representing diverse voices & understanding differing viewpoints (Shannon-Baker, 2016). Critical realism also promotes including insights which are mentally based, such as collecting perception-based data (Shannon-Baker, 2016).

Study 1 used qualitative methods as the research was exploratory and study 4 also used qualitative methods as more in-depth information was sought after regarding participants' perceptions and experiences of medical SDM, therefore qualitative methods were more appropriate in this circumstance (Lund, 2012). Study 2 and study 3 used quantitative methods as hypothesis testing was involved and answers to questions in both studies were desired to be more generalisable to the participant populations, making quantitative methods more appropriate for study 2 and 3 (Lund, 2012).

Semi-structured interviews were used for study 1 as researchers (Newcomer, Hatry, & Wholey, 2015) state that they should be used if the researcher is required to carry out an evaluation of a program and they desire individual interviews with key stakeholders or members of staff. Semi-structured interviews were also used for study 4 as Newcomer et al. (2015) state that they should be used when the researcher wishes to gather the different perceptions of every individual in a group. Although focus groups and semi-structured interviews are similar in their flexible approach by asking open-ended questions that enable extensive probing, individual semi-structured interviews were more appropriate for studies 1 and 4 as Newcomer et al. (2015) state that they are more appropriate if the researcher is required to ask open-ended, probing questions on topics in which the participants may not be candid about if they were sitting alongside peers in a focus group.

3.4 Data Analysis

Semi-structured interviews were carried out in studies 1 and 4. These interviews were recorded, then transcribed and thematically analysed. For study 4, both groups of participants' interviews were thematically analysed together.

Within qualitative research, amongst the most frequently used method of analysis is thematic analysis (Guest, MacQueen, & Namey, 2011). Thematic analysis focuses on identifying, analysing and interpreting patterns of significance i.e. themes in qualitative data (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Prominent thematic analysis advocates, psychologists Virginia Braun & Victoria Clarke (Braun & Clarke, 2022) identify 3 predominant models of thematic analysis: code book approaches, coding reliability approaches and reflexive approaches. They characterize their own broadly used technique, first defined in the journal: *Qualitative Research in Psychology* in 2006 (Braun & Clarke, 2006), as reflexive thematic analysis.

Reflexive approaches focus on flexible and organic coding processes. Thus, there is no code book, coding can be carried out by a single researcher, and if numerous researchers are participating in coding, this is viewed as a cooperative process instead of one that should result in general agreement.

Singular codes are not rigid – they can develop for the duration of the coding process, the confines of the code can be altered, codes can be divided into 2 or more codes, grouped with different codes and even developed into themes (Clarke & Braun, 2013). Reflexive approaches usually include later theme development with themes developed from grouping together similar codes. Themes should convey shared significance formed around a main idea or concept (Braun, Clarke, & Rance, 2014).

The thematic analysis of the data produced in studies 1 and 4 can be described as following a reflexive approach and was carried out utilizing Braun and Clarke's Six Phases of Thematic Analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006). This 6-phase cyclical process entails to and froing between the different phases of data analysis as required until the researcher is content with the final themes (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

As outlined by (Braun & Clarke, 2006) the first phase involved reading and re-reading data to become well-known with what the data encompasses, paying particular attention to patterns that transpired. Therefore, this first step involved listening to and transcribing the interview recordings, highlighting similarities between participants and in different parts of the interviews.

For the second phase, the researcher created the initial codes by recording where patterns in the data transpired, both within and between individual interviews. This occurred via data reduction where the researcher broke data down into labels to generate categories for more effective analysis. This entailed the researcher making inferences concerning what the codes signified.

In accordance with the third phase, the researcher then examined the codes and the related data to form overarching themes and sub-themes. Related data and codes were grouped into significant themes and subthemes which accurately described the different features of the data.

The researcher progressed to examine how the themes supported the codes and the interview data, i.e. the fourth phase, making distinctions between some initial subthemes. The themes were then grouped together in a separate word document to evaluate the associations between the themes and the corresponding subthemes.

The fifth phase saw the researcher define each theme and subtheme, which aspects of the data were being conveyed, and what was interesting about the themes and subthemes. Both themes and subthemes were also assigned labels.

For the final phase, the researcher wrote up the themes and sub-themes within this chapter, choosing quotes from different participants to emphasise the importance of each sub-theme. The sub-themes were also related to previous literature and the research questions. Differences in the discussion of sub-themes between the two groups of participants in study 4 were also highlighted, thus the themes

and sub-themes were examined at both an individual level and between the two groups of participants for the final study.

Following best practice (Braun & Clarke, 2006), the thematic analysis was cyclical and iterative. Thus, the researcher moved between the 6 stages in a non-linear fashion. The grouping and refining of codes, subthemes and themes were carried out by the researcher with guidance from the supervision team. The first five phases were carried out using a software package for analysing qualitative data, NVIVO 12. An example of a coded interview transcript can be found in Appendix A. To convey the process of theme creation, a summary of the codes, subthemes and themes are highlighted in Table 1 in Chapter 4. Additionally, to demonstrate how the 6 stages of thematic analysis were applied to the data in studies 1 and 4, an example from study 1 is provided in Appendix B.

Studies 2 and 3 both used a survey design. For study 2, the outcome variables related to acceptance of SDM in patients with chronic pain. A number of different measures were used to assess acceptance of SDM amongst chronic pain patients. These were: preferred consultation style, knowledge of SDM, and attitudes to SDM.

The predictor variables, i.e. the predictors of acceptance of SDM were:

- demographic information (age, race, education level, gender, pain diagnosis, whether the participant has made a treatment decision/chosen a treatment option with their healthcare professional)
- pain variables (baseline pain intensity, locality of pain, duration of pain, pain diagnosis, breakthrough pain intensity, type of pain, frequency of pain, time for peak of pain, cause of pain, onset of pain, type of medication, interventions for pain – (what helps and makes pain worse))
- readiness to change (which were measured by their use of adaptive and maladaptive coping mechanisms): Exercise, task persistence, Relaxation, Cognitive Control – (Diverting Attention, coping Self-Statements, Reinterpreting Sensations, Avoiding Catastrophizing, Ignoring Pain), Pacing, Avoid Pain Contingent Rest, Avoid Asking for Assistance, Assertive Communication, Proper Body Mechanics
- awareness of SDM and information on participant's decisional needs (decision, decisional conflict, process used in decision-making and participants' preferred methods of receiving information about options).

Correlations, t-tests, chi-squares, one-way ANOVAs and regression analyses were carried out in IBM SPSS to examine which of these variables best predicted SDM and to test for differences between different groups e.g. age, participants who made/did not make a treatment decision etc.

Study 3 used an online survey. The dependent variables for participants who had made a medical decision in the last year were participants' engagement in SDM, and participant's satisfaction with their healthcare decision. Whereas the dependent variable for participants who had not made a medical decision in the last year was their intention to engage in SDM.

The independent variables included: participant's preferred consultation style, attitudes toward SDM, knowledge of SDM and SDM awareness; participant's subjective norms towards SDM, participants' self-efficacy in engaging in SDM; participant's intention to engage in SDM (for participants that had made a medical decision in the last year); the patient and healthcare professional relationship. Demographic information (age, gender, occupation, education level, country of origin and country of residence) was also obtained in addition to some health information (self-rated health and frequency of attending medical appointments).

Some descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, means and standard deviations) were obtained using IBM SPSS software. Cronbach's alpha reliability testing was also carried out on scale items in SPSS. Additionally, logistic regressions, chi-square tests of independence, multiple regressions, linear regressions, one-way ANOVAs, independent t-tests, point-biserial correlations and a Pearson product-moment correlation were all carried out on the data in IBM SPSS.

3.5 Materials

For study 1, an interview schedule (see appendix C) was used to ask participants semi-structured questions that were formed by carrying out a literature review into decision aids (DAs) and SDM. A Dictaphone was used to record each interview. Participant information sheets, consent forms and debrief sheets (see Appendices D-F) were all emailed to participants also. Consent forms were signed by participants and then scanned into an email which was sent back to the researcher from all participants.

For study 2, an online questionnaire was developed to collect data on the predictor and outcome variables relating to SDM. The following scales were administered to patients with chronic pain: the Chronic Pain Assessment Questionnaire (CPAQ), the Multidimensional Pain Readiness to Change Questionnaire (MPRCQ2) (Nielson et al., 2008), the Decisional Needs Assessment Questionnaire

(DNAQ) (Jacobsen, O'Connor, & Stacey, 2013) and a questionnaire to measure patients' attitudes to SDM. Despite being unable to find any questionnaires which measure patients' attitudes to SDM, a relevant study (Durand et al., 2017) assessed attitudes to SDM using a questionnaire with 250 UK medical students. Therefore, these questions were adapted for patients for this study.

The survey was administered using the online e-survey software. An e-mail with the link to the online survey (<https://www.esurveycreator.co.uk/s/chronicpainpatientsurvey> - see Appendix G for the paper version) was sent onto chronic pain charities and local community groups for individuals with chronic pain to complete in their own time. Information regarding the study including a link to the online survey was also shared on Facebook and Twitter. The first survey assesses individuals' experiences of chronic pain and consequently the questionnaire could only be completed by patients who have chronic pain.

Paper copies of the questionnaire were also made available for participants who preferred this method. The researcher emailed participant information sheets, consent forms and paper copies of the survey to the relevant chronic pain charity and community group sites in Scotland for staff to pass onto their members. The researcher emailed a debrief sheet to the one participant that completed a paper copy of the survey. When participants clicked onto the online survey, the participant information sheet was the first thing they were presented and read. Participants could not complete the survey without first saying yes to the online consent form questions and providing a memorable word or phrase to show they provide consent to complete the survey. At the end of the online survey, the debrief sheet was the last page participants seen.

For study 3, an online survey including 5 scales was administered to participants: a questionnaire (Yen et al., 2019) assessed participant's preferred consultation style, attitudes toward SDM, knowledge of SDM & SDM awareness; subjective norm scales (Légaré et al., 2013) measured participant's subjective norms towards SDM; decision self-efficacy scale (DSS) (Bunn & O'Connor, 1996) measured participants' self-efficacy in engaging in SDM; Légaré et al.'s (2013) intention scales measured participant's intention to engage in SDM; and the Patient-Doctor Relationship Questionnaire (PDRQ-9) (Van der Feltz-Cornelis, Van Oppen, Van Marwijk, De Beurs, & Van Dyck, 2004) measured the patient and healthcare professional relationship. Demographic information was also obtained in addition to 3 questions relating to the health of participants.

One of the health questions asked participants if they had made a medical or treatment decision in the last year. If participants responded "yes" they then also were administered the 9-item Shared Decision-Making Questionnaire (SDM-Q-9) (Kriston et al., 2010), which measured individual's

engagement in SDM, and The Satisfaction with Decision Scale (Holmes-Rovner et al., 1996) which measured participant's satisfaction with their healthcare decision.

The survey was administered using the online "surveyhero" software (formerly known as "esurvey"). Information regarding the study including a link to the online survey was shared on social media platforms Facebook and Twitter (now known as "X"). When participants clicked onto the online survey, the participant information sheet was the first thing they were presented to read. Participants could not complete the survey without saying "yes" to the online consent form questions and providing a memorable word or phrase to show they provide consent to complete the survey. At the end of the online survey, the debrief sheet was the last page participants seen.

For study 4, an interview schedule was used which contained semi-structured questions. Questions for the interview schedule were drawn both from previous literature and from the results of studies 2 and 3. Other questions used in the interview were drawn from Bomhof-Roordink, et al.'s (2019) study which found that the top components of SDM included: Describe treatment options, Make the decision, Patient preferences, Tailor information, Deliberate, Create choice awareness, Learn about the patient, and Agreeing on the final decision. There were also questions on how SDM might need to be modified for remote consultations by asking participants the potential impact of COVID-19 on SDM.

The same core questions were asked to both groups of participants. There were also a series of prompts and further questions that were asked to participants if they were uncertain of how to answer the question or did not fully understand the question and for participants to elaborate on their answers. Most of the prompts or further questions were the same for both groups of participants also except for one. This prompt read: "How does your chronic pain impact on your ability to take part in SDM?" for participants with chronic pain, while general population were asked: "How does your *health condition* (if mentioned) impact on your ability to take part in SDM?" to see whether chronic pain impacts on individuals' ability to take part in SDM differently than other health conditions.

To recruit individuals with chronic pain for study 4, all of the charities listed on the Pain UK website were emailed a summary of the study, participant information sheets, consent forms and a copy of the letter from the researchers' school ethics committee confirming permission to carry out the study (participants from study 2 were also recruited via this method).

To recruit members of the general population and some individuals with chronic pain, information about the study was shared on Facebook and Twitter (participants from studies 2 and 3 were also recruited using this method). Participants recruited through Facebook and Twitter were also sent emails containing a summary of the study, participant information sheets, consent forms and a copy

of the letter from the researchers' school ethics committee confirming permission to carry out the study.

Participants were asked to confirm that they lived in Scotland and if they experienced chronic pain prior to the interviews being carried out. All participants were also emailed debrief sheets after the interviews.

3.6 Ethical Considerations

Ethics applications were made and approved by the University of the West of Scotland's (UWS) School of Education and Social Science's (formerly School of Media, Culture and Society's) ethics committee for all four studies before each of phase of data collection began. NHS ethics did not need to be obtained as participants were not recruited as patients via healthcare professionals. Every participant was provided with an information sheet and consent form for them to read and complete prior to taking part in the studies, thus consent was obtained, and this allowed participants to make an informed choice about whether or not to participate in the research.

All participants were also debriefed after their participation in each study by either emailing each participant or through participants reading the debrief sheet at the end of the online surveys which re-states the aim of the study, contains contact information for the researcher and supervision team if participants had any further questions regarding the research, references which are relevant to the study if they were interested in finding more out about the research and contact details for participants if the research caused them any distress or discomfort and they would like to speak to someone or if they had any complaints or feel that they had been affected by the study in any way. For studies 1 and 4, the researcher also set aside time for participants to ask any questions they may have had after the interview.

To ensure the confidentiality of personal data obtained during each study, only the researcher and the research team have access to the data. The data was not accessed by anyone other than the researchers and the data will be kept strictly confidential in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation, 2018. Each study was anonymous meaning that participants could not be identified on the basis of their responses and any publication resulting from the studies would only report data that did not identify participants. The data collected will be stored securely at UWS for up to 10 years after the studies completion.

For studies 2, 3 and 4, there were some questions which may have caused participants to reflect on potentially upsetting or sensitive experiences e.g. reflecting on their healthcare experiences and their relationship with their healthcare professional. This may have been upsetting for participants if they

did not have a pleasant or positive healthcare experience or if they did not have a positive relationship with their healthcare professional. There were also questions which may have been sensitive for participants with chronic pain as they asked participants to reflect on their chronic pain.

As a result, on the participant information sheet for members of the general population it explained that: "There are no disadvantages of taking part, however there are some questions which ask you to reflect on your healthcare experiences. Due to the nature of the topic, reflecting on your health and healthcare experiences may be difficult and upsetting. If the study raises any concerns for you about your health, you should contact your health care provider or speak to a family member or friend. Alternatively, you may wish to contact a helpline: The Samaritans (116 123) or NHS 24 (111) for urgent support."

At the end of the debrief sheet it also stated: "If this research has caused you any distress or discomfort and you would like to speak to someone please contact the following sources of support and advice: The Samaritans (116 123) or NHS 24 (111) for urgent support."

On the participant information sheet for individuals with chronic pain it explained that "There are no disadvantages of taking part, however there are some questions which ask you to report on your chronic pain. Due to the nature of the topic, reflecting on your chronic pain and healthcare experiences may be difficult and upsetting. If the study raises any concerns for you about your chronic pain, you should contact your health care provider or speak to a family member or friend. Alternatively, you may wish to contact a chronic pain helpline. See: www.painconcern.org.uk for helplines in the UK. You will also find chronic pain support and advice contact information at the end of the study on the debrief sheet." At the end of the debrief sheet it also stated: "If this research has caused you any distress or discomfort and you would like to speak to someone please contact the following sources of support and advice: Pain Concern (0300 123 0789); The Samaritans (116 123) or NHS 24 (111) for urgent support".

For study 4, the researcher ensured that end-to-end encryption was enabled on Zoom. Participants were allowed to rename themselves so they did not wish to use their real names, recordings of meetings were saved to a file on the researcher's university password protected laptop and "lock meeting" was enabled shortly after interview calls began so that no-one else could join or access the interview call. All meetings on Zoom were passcode protected, which were encrypted and included in the invite link to allow participants to join with just one click without having to enter the passcode.

For study 1, the interviews were either conducted over the phone or in person depending on the participant's preference but for study 4 these interviews had to be done over Zoom due to COVID-19 lockdowns and restrictions. For study 2, an online survey and paper copies of the survey was used to

gather as many responses from as many individuals with chronic pain as possible but for study 3 an online survey had to be implemented, again due to COVID-19 restrictions. The focus of study 4 also changed due to the impact of COVID-19 as the researcher was originally going to recruit healthcare professionals instead of members of the general population and individuals with chronic pain but due to the high demand and pressures upon healthcare professionals during the COVID-19 pandemic, the focus for study 4 changed.

The original aim of the thesis also changed due to the findings of study 1. Originally the project was going to focus on DAs but the findings of study 1 indicated more interest and importance on SDM instead. The test case for the thesis additionally changed, as the original focus was the insertion of grommets for otitis media, but the focus shifted to chronic pain as the research team discovered that there was already work being carried out into making a DA for grommets. In the context of chronic pain, there are more options for people to consider for treatment, thus allowing more room for SDM and opportunity for this research.

Chapter 4: Investigating the Implementation of Shared Decision-making and Decision Aids in NHS Scotland

4.1 Introduction

As described earlier, shared decision-making (SDM) is a practice in which patients and clinicians work in partnership to choose treatments, management packages, support packages, or tests based on the patient's informed preferences and clinical evidence. Decision aids (DAs) are tools which assist individuals to engage in decision-making through making clear the decision which must be made, through defining personal values and supplying information concerning the outcomes and options. The primary purpose of study 1 was to identify existing good practice in the development DAs by gathering examples of current practice in the use, design and implementation of DAs in Scotland's NHS Boards.

Despite the central role of SDM in the government's new model of healthcare quality, the utilisation of DAs and SDM within the UK has been inconsistent (Coulter and Collins, 2011), not being used routinely in every healthcare setting. Légaré et al. (2008) examined health care professionals' attitudes to SDM in an effort to comprehend why SDM is not currently standard practice. The most frequently

used arguments included: No time to do it; We already do it; Patients don't want it; It's irrelevant and ineffective; Patients will want inappropriate/expensive treatments; There's no incentive to do it; and Not appropriate for those with low health literacy. Although, the greatest difficulty currently is to formulate efficient methods to aid SDM and guarantee that these are implemented in standard clinical practice.

Multiple pilot implementation projects, which incorporate both healthcare professionals and patients, are currently in progress and they will offer important experience on which to build practice for the future. One such project was Making Good Decisions In Collaboration (MAGIC), which investigated how SDM can be implemented into standard clinical practice (Joseph-Williams et al., 2017) (further discussed in Chapter 2). Although, no existing literature or resources were found (at the time of conducting the research) that detailed the use of DAs in NHS Scotland, all DAs and literature (despite claiming to cover the UK) were all in relation to NHS England and Wales. Therefore, this work seeks to address a gap in the literature.

Another aim of study 1 was to gather healthcare professionals' views on various characteristics of SDM and DAs such as potential challenges/barriers to the implementation of SDM and DAs, which formats should DAs be made available in and whether DAs should be used in consultations or out with consultations. Again, literature did exist which looked at healthcare professionals' attitudes to SDM and their views on various characteristics of SDM and DAs, in an effort to comprehend why SDM is not currently standard practice universally (Légaré et al., 2008). However, despite some research claiming to be from the UK, again no literature was found on Scottish healthcare professionals' attitudes, thus identifying another gap in the literature to be addressed.

Additionally, some questions were asked concerning opinions towards a future DA for chronic pain and what features this DA should include as a DA for chronic pain was initially intended to be created for study 3 and these interview responses would have informed the DA design as the healthcare professionals would have been the key stakeholders.

Therefore, the first study sought to address the first aim of the thesis. Additionally, study 1 aimed to identify existing good practice in the development of DAs by gathering examples of current practice in the use, design and implementation of DAs in Scotland's NHS Boards. Thus, the research questions for the first study were:

- Are DAs successfully implemented and used routinely as standard practice within Scottish NHS Boards?
- What features do healthcare professionals' think a successful DA should have?
- Is SDM routinely used as standard practice within Scottish NHS Boards?

- What are the potential barriers to SDM and DAs?
- What are healthcare professionals' opinions towards a possible future DA for chronic pain and what features should this DA include?

4.2 Methods

4.2.1. Design

As the study was exploratory in nature and to address the aims of the study as outlined above, the study design was qualitative as semi-structured interviews were carried out and these interviews were then thematically analysed.

4.2.2. Participants

The stakeholders were 9 various members of Scotland's NHS Boards as these individuals were able to provide information about whether DAs are currently used and to see if there were any differences between different areas in their use and design. Out of a possible 14 NHS boards, 8 were able to provide an interview (5 participants were females and 4 participants were males). All participants varied in their job roles: Unscheduled care programme manager; Head of evidence; Professional lead consultant psychologist; Realistic medicine clinician lead and General practitioner; Clinical director and National lead clinician for chronic pain; Clinical service lead pain management service; Acute pain nurse; Clinical specialist physiotherapist and Consultant anaesthetist and pain management.

4.2.3. Materials

See Appendix C for the interview schedule given to participants. The questions in the interview schedule were split into 5 topics: Use of DAs; Best practice DAs; Features of DAs; SDM; and Chronic pain DA. The gaps in the literature in relation to DAs and SDM in Scotland and the variation in the use, design, healthcare focuses and features of existing DAs and SDM in other countries led to this choice of topics to examine how Scotland compares and differs in these various aspects.

The use of DAs concerned questions regarding how a best DA should be used i.e. in consultations or at home and who by i.e. clinicians, patients or both. Best practice DAs questions aimed to identify existing good practice in the development of shared DAs by gathering examples of "best" current

practice in the use, design and implementation of SDM aids in Scotland's NHS Boards. Features of DAs questions aimed to identify which features a best practice DA should have, such as which format should the DA be made available in. SDM asked questions regarding potential challenges or barriers to the implementation of SDM. Chronic pain DA questions concerned healthcare professionals' attitudes towards a future DA for chronic pain and what features this DA should include.

As can be seen in the interview schedule (see Appendix C), a series of prompts were provided for each question. Although these prompts were provided, they were not always used or required, and they were only used when participants wanted reassurance that they were on the right path when answering questions.

Participant information sheets, consent forms and debrief sheets (see Appendices D-F) were all sent to participants also and consent forms were signed and scanned into an email sent back to the researcher from all participants. A Dictaphone was used for recording the interviews.

4.2.4. Procedure

An email was sent to a lead member (chief executive, board headquarters etc.) of each NHS regional board in Scotland (found by visiting each health boards own website) which outlined the study and had the participant information sheet and consent form attached. By emailing the listed contact detail for each NHS board, it was hoped that one individual from each board who was knowledgeable in the use of DAs and SDM in their board would be interviewed. Interviewing different regional boards would give a broader indication into the DAs and SDM practices used in Scotland and to also compare similarities and differences between each region in these respects.

An additional email was also sent to a Chronic Pain Implementation Group mailing list which consisted of 37 NHS contacts from each health board who frequently meet in Glasgow to discuss each board's current plans and strategies for treating and improving the treatment of chronic pain patients. It was thought that having some healthcare professionals who were experienced in chronic pain would also be useful to answer the questions on ideas for a future DA for chronic pain.

From emailing each board and the Chronic Pain Implementation Group, nine interviews were conducted, most of which were over the telephone with one being face to face. A Dictaphone was used to record each interview. There are a total of 14 regional boards and 9 healthcare professionals/board leads from 7 different NHS Boards were interviewed. All NHS boards had been contacted but due to various difficulties (including staff shortages and time constraints) only 7 NHS boards were able to provide an interview. Each interview was transcribed and thematically analysed.

4.2.5. Data Analysis

Within qualitative research, amongst the most frequently used method of analysis is thematic analysis (Guest et al., 2011). Thematic analysis focuses on identifying, analysing and interpreting patterns of significance i.e. themes in qualitative data (Braun & Clarke, 2006, 2022; Clarke & Braun, 2013). Prominent thematic analysis advocates, psychologists Virginia Braun & Victoria Clarke (Braun & Clarke, 2022) identify 3 predominant models of thematic analysis: code book approaches, coding reliability approaches and reflexive approaches. They characterise their own broadly used technique, first defined in the journal: *Qualitative Research in Psychology* in 2006 (Braun & Clarke, 2006), as reflexive thematic analysis.

Reflexive approaches focus on flexible and organic coding processes. Thus, there is no code book, coding can be carried out by a single researcher, and if numerous researchers are participating in coding, this is viewed as a cooperative process instead of one that should result in general agreement. Singular codes are not rigid – they can develop for the duration of the coding process, the confines of the code can be altered, codes can be divided into 2 or more codes, grouped with different codes and even developed into themes (Clarke & Braun, 2013). Reflexive approaches usually include later theme development with themes developed from grouping together similar codes. Themes should convey shared significance formed around a main idea or concept (Braun et al., 2014).

The thematic analysis of the data produced in study 1 can be described as following a reflexive approach and was carried out utilising Braun and Clarke's Six Phases of Thematic Analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006, 2022; Clarke & Braun, 2013). This 6-phase cyclical process entails to and froing between the different phases of data analysis as required until the researcher is content with the final themes (Braun & Clarke, 2006, 2022; Clarke & Braun, 2013). The 6 phases are outlined below with examples using quotes taken from participants' transcripts to convey how the first theme was formed. The 6 phases have been used to form all themes and an example of this can be found in Appendix B.

Phase 1 involves reading and re-reading data to become well-known with what the data encompasses, paying particular attention to patterns that transpire: "Anything that's basically, we think something is a good idea and we're, we've spoken to our patients, we can actually facilitate work, then we actually go ahead and do it but we've not actually used any tools to-, to start a service like that."; "The approach is a person-centred approach and not a financial or performance gain." and I: "...are there audits or reviews carried out on shared decision-making? P: "Yeah, em, no and I'm not sure how you would do that either..."

Phase 2, the researcher creates the initial codes by recording how and where patterns transpire. This occurs via data reduction where the researcher breaks data down into labels to generate categories for more effective analysis. Data complication is also concluded here. This entails the researcher making inferences concerning what the codes signify:

“Anything that's basically, we think something is a good idea and we're, we've spoken to our patients, we can actually facilitate work, then we actually go ahead and do it but we've not actually used any tools to-, to start a service like that.” - healthcare professionals prefer/favour shared SDM to DAs.

“The approach is a person-centred approach and not a financial or performance gain.” – there are no financial or performance-based incentives for partaking in SDM.

I: “...are there audits or reviews carried out on shared decision-making?”

P: “Yeah, em, no and I'm not sure how you would do that either...” – most participants stated that no audits or reviews were carried out on SDM or DAs.

Phase 3, the researcher groups codes into overarching themes which accurately describe the data. It is vital in developing themes that the researcher depicts exactly what the themes signify, even if the theme does not appear to "fit". The researcher should also depict what is missing from the analysis:

Theme: Priority

Sub-themes: Favour existing practice, incentive and lack of review

Phase 4, in this stage, the researcher examines how the themes support the overarching theoretical perspective and the data. If the analysis appears unfinished, the researcher must go back and find what is missing:

Theme: Priority

Sub-themes: Favour existing practice and incentive (removed lack of review as does not fit)

Phase 5, the researcher must define what each theme is, which aspects of data are being conveyed, and what is interesting about the themes:

Priority (now changed to Shared decision-making is the top priority), Favour existing practice (now changed to Favour shared decision-making) & Incentive (now changed to Personal & Professional Incentive).

Phase 6, when the researcher creates the report, decision must be made to which themes make significant contributions to understanding what is occurring within the data. Researchers should also

carry out "member checking". This is where the researcher goes back to the sample to see if their depiction is an accurate representation:

The theme “Shared decision-making is the top priority” is composed of 2 sub-themes: Favour shared decision-making and Personal & Professional Incentive. The 2 sub-themes both convey how important SDM was across the different health boards, being the top priority for participants... (see Findings section below for the full report).

4.3 Findings

4.3.1. Summary of Findings

A total of 4 hours and 47 minutes of recordings were gathered from the interviews with participants. The interviews ranged in length from 19.46 minutes to 47.56 minutes. The average time for the interviews was 31.50 minutes.

A total of 6 themes emerged from the data: Shared Decision-making is the Top Priority; Implementation of Decision Aids; Listed Barriers in Implementing Decision Aids & Shared Decision-making; Crucial Factors in Designing A Decision Aid; A Decision Aid for Chronic Pain; Common Features in Existing Decision Aids.

A total of 19 sub-themes also emerged from the data: Favour Shared Decision-making; Personal & Professional Incentive; Decision Aids were New; Variation in the Use of Decision Aids; Time Pressures; Increased Awareness of Decision Aids & Shared Decision-making is Needed; Lack of Review of Decision Aids & Shared Decision-making; Incorporating Visual Elements; Consulting Key Stakeholders; Ensuring Accessibility; Considering Health Literacy Levels; Include Localised Information; Signpost Information & Resources; Unfamiliarity; Suitability of a Decision Aid for Chronic Conditions; Outlining All Options; Utilisation of Decision Aids; Shared Use of Decision Aids; Decision Aid Guidelines.

Table 1

Summary of Themes & Sub-themes

Themes	Sub-themes	Codes
1) Shared Decision-making is the Top Priority	a) Favour Shared Decision-making;	a) Healthcare professionals prefer/favour shared decision-making to decision aids

	<p>b) Personal & Professional Incentive</p>	<p>b) There were no financial or performance-based incentives for partaking in shared decision-making</p>
<p>2) Implementation of Decision Aids</p>	<p>a) Decision Aids were New;</p> <p>b) Variation in the Use of Decision Aids</p>	<p>a) Decision aids were new to most healthcare professionals</p> <p>b) There were differences between NHS boards in whether they used decision aids or not</p>
<p>3) Listed Barriers in Implementing Decision Aids & Shared Decision-making</p>	<p>a) Time Pressures;</p> <p>b) Increased Awareness of Decision Aids & Shared Decision-making is Needed;</p> <p>c) Lack of Review of Decision Aids & Shared Decision-making</p>	<p>a) Most participants listed time as being a barrier for using decision aids and for carrying out shared decision-making</p> <p>b) Another listed barrier for implementing decision aids and shared decision-making was a lack of awareness regarding decision aids and shared decision-making</p> <p>c) Most participants stated that no audits or reviews were carried out on shared decision-making or on decision aids</p>
<p>4) Crucial Factors in Designing A Decision Aid</p>	<p>a) Incorporating Visual Elements;</p>	<p>a) Most of the healthcare professionals agreed that a decision aid should be more visual rather than having lots of text</p>

	<p>b) Consulting Key Stakeholders;</p> <p>c) Ensuring Accessibility;</p> <p>d) Considering Health Literacy Levels;</p> <p>e) Include Localised Information;</p> <p>f) Signpost Information & Resources</p>	<p>b) As many key stakeholders as possible should have a say in/ be included in the development of a decision aid or for any medical intervention</p> <p>c) Another agreed aspect for a decision aid is that it needs to be accessible for anyone who uses it</p> <p>d) The information contained in a decision aid needs to be kept simple and understandable for people of all reading abilities/health literacy levels</p> <p>e) Another consistently cited attribute for a best practice decision aid was that it should contain localised information/guidelines</p> <p>f) Another commonly suggested feature of a best practice decision aid was that it should include signposting</p>
<p>5) A Decision Aid for Chronic Pain</p>	<p>a) Unfamiliarity;</p> <p>b) Suitability of a Decision Aid for Chronic Conditions;</p> <p>c) Outlining All Options</p>	<p>a) Most of the healthcare professionals were not aware of any decision aids for chronic pain.; Most decision aids were for the same health conditions</p> <p>b) The healthcare professionals believed a decision aid for chronic pain would be useful.; It was believed that decision aids would be most suited to long-term conditions like chronic pain</p>

		c) Healthcare professionals believed that decision aids for chronic pain should list all possible options for patients
6) Common Features in Existing Decision Aids	<p>a) Utilisation of Decision Aids;</p> <p>b) Shared Use of Decision Aids;</p> <p>c) Decision Aid Guidelines</p>	<p>a) Most decision aids could be used both in and outwith consultations/appointments</p> <p>b) Most decision aids could also be used by patient's family members</p> <p>c) Most decision aids followed the same SIGN and NICE guidelines</p>

As shown in Table 1 above, the sub-themes below led to formations of the overarching themes:

1. "Favour shared decision-making" and "Personal & Professional Incentive" formed the theme **"Shared Decision-making is the Top Priority"**
2. "Decision Aids were New" and "Variation in the Use of Decision Aids" formed the theme **"Implementation of Decision Aids"**
3. "Time Pressures", "Increased Awareness of Decision Aids & Shared Decision-making is Needed" and "Lack of Review of Decision Aids & Shared Decision-making" formed the theme **"Listed Barriers in Implementing Decision Aids & Shared Decision-making"**
4. "Incorporating Visual Elements", "Consulting Key Stakeholders", "Ensuring Accessibility", "Considering Health Literacy Levels", "Include Localised Information" and "Signpost Information & Resources" formed the theme **"Crucial Factors in Designing A Decision Aid"**
5. "Unfamiliarity", "Suitability of a Decision Aid for Chronic Conditions" and "Outlining All Options" formed the theme **"A Decision Aid for Chronic Pain"**
6. "Utilisation of Decision Aids", "Shared Use of Decision Aids" and "Decision Aid Guidelines" formed the theme **"Common Features in Existing Decision Aids"**

4.3.2. Theme 1: Shared Decision-making is the Top Priority

Summary

The theme “Shared Decision-making is the Top Priority” is composed of 2 sub-themes: “Favour Shared Decision-making” and “Personal & Professional Incentive”. The 2 sub-themes both convey how important SDM was across the different health boards, being the top priority for participants.

Sub-theme 1a) Favour Shared Decision-making

SDM (the process and practice of patients and clinicians working in partnership to choose treatments) seemed to be the priority for all healthcare professionals instead of using DAs (physical “tools” such as an app on a tablet or an information leaflet) to facilitate SDM with most boards reported SDM being carried out routinely as part of standard practice.

I: ...Is shared decision-making used routinely as part of standard practice in your board?

P: Y-yes, yes, o-, openly and intentionally, it would be a-, the approach that we would, eh, choose to adopt...” (P008, Healthboard 7)

Thus, the third research question has been addressed: Is SDM routinely used as standard practice within Scottish NHS Boards? The answer being that SDM is reported as being routinely used as standard practice within most of the interviewed Scottish NHS Boards.

“I think that's a cultural thing...that's definitely started and people that I speak to and you know, talk to in realistic medicine, people are on board with that, they really do believe in it and they believe that that's absolutely the future of where the NHS needs to go...” (P002, Healthboard 1)

SDM was viewed as standard practice and as a priority in most of the NHS Boards, therefore aligning with the Scottish Government’s (*A National Clinical Strategy For Scotland, 2016*) aim for SDM to be standard practice in healthcare within the UK and the General Medical Council’s *Good Medical Practice (Good Medical Practice, 2013)* instruction for every clinician which incorporates an expectation that SDM will be standard practice for the majority of medical decisions. This finding then conflicts with Légaré et al.’s (2008) suggestion that successful implementation of SDM is patchy and not currently the norm within the UK or at least for Scotland. Although, this view also matched healthcare professionals’ views from Légaré et. al.’s (2008) study that they believe that they “already do it”. However, studies suggest that healthcare professionals frequently believe they are sharing decisions to a greater extent than their patients do (Stevenson et al., 2000). Therefore, whilst the healthcare professionals believe that SDM is being used and carried out routinely as standard practice, perhaps patients do not believe this to be the case.

SDM involves the availability of evidence-based information concerning uncertainties, outcomes and options, together with counselling for decision support and a system for implementing and recording patients' informed preferences (Coulter & Collins, 2011). Therefore, SDM can be carried out by the healthcare professional telling the patient evidence-based information concerning uncertainties, outcomes and options, provide counselling for decision support and implement and record patients' informed preferences through researching information before the patient arrives, discussing this information with the patient and then taking note of the patient's choice on their computer. DAs can aid SDM by presenting this information in a simple format to the patient, but DAs are not always needed for SDM to be carried out as the healthcare professional can carry out SDM through skilled conversation with the patient.

"Well, I would say shared decision-making is used but not a specific tool." (P005, Healthboard 4)

As found from participants' responses, SDM seemed to be the priority for all healthcare professionals instead of using DAs to facilitate SDM. This reflects the finding of the MAGIC project (Joseph-Williams et al., 2017) that "skills trump tools, attitudes trump all", numerous healthcare professionals had said that whilst the tools (the option grids and DAs) were useful, the most important thing for them was their/clinicians attitudes to SDM and carrying out SDM i.e. having various conversations with their patients, and the skills and knowledge to aid these conversations.

"Anything that's basically, we think something is a good idea and we're, we've spoken to our patients, we can actually facilitate work, then we actually go ahead and do it but we've not actually used any tools to-, to start a service like that." (P007, Healthboard 6)

Sub-theme 1b) Personal & Professional Incentive

Every board had stated that there were no financial incentives or company targets surrounding carrying out SDM. Many participants believed that it was a crucial part of their job to carry out SDM and that improving patient care through SDM was the real incentive as opposed to monetary rewards or performance targets.

"The approach is a person-centred approach and not a financial or performance gain." (P001, Healthboard 1)

"Well, I think the main incentive is, if it improves your (coughs) your patient care and your management then, you know, that's incentive enough, I would say." (P005, Healthboard 4)

Therefore, SDM was viewed as being a routine part of the healthcare professionals' job and as a priority in most of the NHS Boards, thus aligning with the Scottish Government's (*A National Clinical Strategy For Scotland, 2016*) aim for SDM to be standard practice in healthcare within the UK and the General Medical Council's Good Medical Practice (2013) instruction for every clinician which incorporates an expectation that SDM will be standard practice for the majority of medical decisions.

I: Ok, eh, are there any staff incentives for partaking in or carrying out shared decision-making and using decision aids?

P: Eh, no, it's just part of the job... it's part of the, eh, being a good clinician actually. It's ensuring that what they're doing is working." (P006, Healthboard 5)

4.3.3. Theme 2: Implementation of Decision Aids

Summary

The theme "Implementation of Decision Aids" is composed of 2 sub-themes: "Decision Aids were New" and "Variation in the Use of Decision Aids". Both sub-themes relate to the inconsistent implementation of DAs which were consistently found across the different health boards.

Sub-theme 2a) Decision Aids were New

From the boards who were using DAs (6 out of 9 boards), it was found that they were all relatively new (at the time that the interviews took place in January-March 2019) and had only started being used with patients and/or healthcare professionals. Other boards had finished designing the DA but "were in a program to roll it out" i.e. were just about to start testing the DA for use in initial clinical trials with patients.

"Shared decision and decision aid tools... it's still relatively new to the organisation and therefore, in a program to roll it out." (P001, Healthboard 1)

Thus, the first research question for the current study was addressed (are DAs successfully implemented and used routinely as standard practice within Scottish NHS Boards?), as found from participants' responses, the implementation of DAs was "patchy" and varied across the different health boards. Some NHS Boards that were interviewed for this study did not use or have any DAs and the ones that did, either had not used the DAs yet or the DAs were just being rolled out for use as and were new.

Sub-theme 2b) Variation in the Use of Decision Aids

Whilst most boards had heard of DAs and stated that some health services and professionals used them, not all health services and professionals used them.

“...they're all aware of them, I suspect they don't all use them, but they are aware that they exist.” (P004, Healthboard 3)

This aligns with Legare et al.'s (2008) finding that the successful implementation of DAs is patchy and not currently the norm within the UK or at least for Scotland in this case. The variation in DA use between the boards also aligns with Coulter and Collins (2011) observation that despite the central role of SDM in the government's new model of healthcare quality, the utilisation of DAs and SDM within the UK has been inconsistent.

Some boards had stated that they use SDM in place of a DA, for others there was a variation in reasons ranging from: not having the right IT equipment, accessibility issues, some healthcare professionals may not see them as being of any use and that they might take a lot of time to use.

“...anything that's basically, we think something is a good idea and we're, we've spoken to our patients, we can actually facilitate work, then we actually go ahead and do it but we've not actually used any tools to-, to start a service like that. We've actually just spoken to-, to our patients to find out what they think would be a good idea and then actually trialled it and if it's a good idea we go with it and if-, and if it's not, we change it and then try again, so but I've never used a tool to do that.” (P007, Healthboard 6)

“...I mean access, time, training, awareness, you know, they're not aware that they should use them. If they are aware that they should use them, they don't have any time to use them. If they do have the time to use them and they are aware that they should use them, do they have the technology to use them? All of those things.” (P002, Healthboard 1)

It was argued by the boards that did not yet have DAs that their primary focus was to carry out SDM and that they did not feel that they necessarily needed tools to do this. This coincides with the finding from the MAGIC programme (Joseph-Williams et al., 2017) that numerous healthcare professionals had said that whilst the tools (the option grids and DAs) were useful, the most important thing for them was attitudes to SDM and carrying out SDM i.e. having various conversations with their patients, and the skills and knowledge to aid these conversations. Therefore, from the interviews with the Scottish NHS Boards and from the literature, it is clear that DAs are not successfully implemented and used routinely as standard practice within the majority of Scottish NHS Boards.

4.3.4. Theme 3: Listed Barriers in Implementing Decision Aids & Shared Decision-making

Summary

The theme “Listed Barriers in Implementing Decision Aids & Shared Decision-making” is composed of 3 sub-themes: “Time Pressures”, “Increased Awareness of Decision Aids & Shared Decision-making is Needed” and “Lack of Review of Decision Aids & Shared Decision-making”. All 3 sub-themes relate to the reported challenges that need to be addressed for the successful implementation of SDM and DAs which were consistently found across the different health boards.

Sub-theme 3a) Time Pressures

When asked about challenges or barriers to using DAs nearly every healthcare professional stated that time was a worry for them as they were unsure if they would have sufficient time to use the DAs in consultations, a lot of time would need to be spent on constructing a DA, installing the aid, the time for professionals and the patients in taking to input the data into the DA and how much time it would take to train staff in how to use the DA.

“Time, I think is the biggest constraint. If you were to ask any clinician about the biggest constraints on anything, any aspect of clinical care, it's always going to be time.” (P006, Healthboard 5)

Therefore, participants’ responses addressed the current study’s fourth research question: “what are the potential barriers to SDM and DAs?”, with time pressures being one of the barriers. This sub-theme coincides with a theme found in Légaré et al.’s (2008) study which also asked healthcare professionals’ attitudes to SDM in which they felt there was “no time to do it”. This frequent belief amongst healthcare professionals is that SDM appointments use more time than appointments in which healthcare professionals alone decide (Coulter & Collins, 2011). Whilst the appointments themselves might require more time, the time used involving the patient in the decision might decrease the overall time used working with a patient who is unhappy or uncertain regarding a decision they were not included in (Bekker et al., 2004).

There was also concern that the time taken to train in the use of a DA and SDM would be significant and to use a DA in an appointment would impact on time.

“So firstly, it's massively time-consuming to put together these decision aids, yeah and-, and the supportive materials around them, yeah, so, we had someone employed that spent quite a few months

doing this and liaising with teams, getting people around the table to get those who have to-, to, um, express their opinions. It takes multiple meetings in order to be able to do this, people often don't have the time, so getting people around the table, this is all hugely complicated, hugely difficult, yeah, so, there's real logistics issues around this..." (P003, Healthboard 2)

However, Elwyn et al. (2013) produced a specific, short DA for patients to use whilst in an appointment with their clinician, named Option Grids (see Chapter 2). Therefore, it can also be argued that whilst, the appointments themselves require a bit more time, this additional time used to involve the patient in the decision might decrease the overall time used working with a patient who is unhappy or uncertain regarding a decision they were not included in (Bekker et al., 2004), where only one slightly longer appointment is necessary compared to potential further appointments for a patient in future. Therefore, SDM might include reconsidering clinical pathway design in order to include time for coaching and information provision.

"...negative outcomes in using the decision aids has been resource time to support patients and staff, em, in understanding the use of the tools. Em, what I mean by that, [researcher], is you can't just "here it is" without any, em, supported guidance etcetera, to it." (P002, Healthboard 1)

Sub-theme 3b) Increased Awareness of Decision Aids & Shared Decision-making is Needed

Another commonly stated challenge which needs to be addressed for the successful implementation of SDM and DAs was to increase healthcare professional and patients' awareness of SDM, DAs, the need to use SDM and DAs and their benefits.

"I think it is raising awareness for public and staff." (P001, Healthboard 1)

Again, participants' responses addressed the current study's fourth research question, highlight the lack of awareness of DAs and SDM as another one of the potential barriers to SDM and DAs. Stiggelbout et al. (2012) discuss in their paper why SDM is vital and focus on a few best practices. They explain that SDM is a complex intervention and for it to be implemented in healthcare, multifaceted strategies are required along with culture change amongst patients, healthcare professionals and their organisations. They also outline that this culture change begins with increasing awareness of SDM at every level of society, which was not only echoed by the current study findings but was also articulated in the Salzburg statement on SDM (Seminar, 2011). Additionally, they comment that the fundamental aim for SDM is that it is not viewed as a tiresome additional extra but as the centre of good clinical practice, placing patients completely at the core of every decision which reflects the current study's finding of increasing awareness of the need to use SDM. Furthermore, Stiggelbout and colleagues

(2012) state that numerous patients do not anticipate being included in decision-making and therefore should be made aware that their choices, when well informed, could decide the most suitable treatment option, thus echoing the current study's findings of increasing the awareness of the benefits of SDM.

In the study (Brace et al., 2010), the researchers set out to determine clinicians' utilisation and awareness of DAs, their views on the main barriers to the utilisation of DAs, and clinician characteristics predictive of utilisation of DAs in clinical practice. A population-based survey was mailed to a total of 878 clinicians composed of radiation oncologists, general surgeons and medical oncologists. The complete response rate for the survey was 64.5%. Most of the clinicians were males and had worked in community hospital for over a decade. From the total participants, 69% were aware of DAs and 46% were aware of DAs appropriate to their practice. Although, only 24% were presently utilising DAs. One of the fundamental barriers to the utilisation of DAs was stated as a lack of awareness and the researchers agreed with the finding of the current study that increasing awareness of DAs and to implement them into clinical practice is vital.

Sub-theme 3c) Lack of Review of Decision Aids & Shared Decision-making

Most participants had stated that no audits or reviews were carried out on SDM or DAs for their board. For the DAs, most of them were relatively new and this was the main reason for no audits or reviews to have occurred.

"The-, they're ongoing most of them at the moment so why-, whenever a project is still new, the amputation was still ongoing and that sort of, I think that's 4 years in now so, um, yeah, we still audit it, any changes that we still make, we still audit those changes, so yeah it's an ongoing process." (P007, Healthboard 6)

However, for SDM, most boards stated there were no audits or reviews but did not elaborate why this was the case except for one board who again stated that SDM was relatively new for them.

"...the work is still relatively new... so that process is ongoing." (P001, Healthboard 1)

Also one board commented that they had no audits or reviews carried out on SDM and they were not sure how an audit or review on SDM could be carried out.

I: "...are there audits or reviews carried out on shared decision-making?"

P: "Yeah, em, no and I'm not sure how you would do that either..." (P008, Healthboard 7)

Since most boards stated that there were no audits or reviews carried out on SDM, healthcare professionals may believe that they are consistently carrying out SDM or that it is routinely being used as standard practice within Scottish NHS Boards, but without any audits or reviews being carried out on SDM, there is no way to officially confirm that this is the case.

I: Ok, are there audits or reviews carried out on the decision aids and on shared decision-making?

P: Eh, no, we don't do any." (P004, Healthboard 3)

Consistent with this point, surveys also found that just a few patients experiencing important medical decisions are fully informed regarding the key facts which may influence their treatment choices, and efforts to obtain their informed preferences are almost rare (Fagerlin et al 2010; Zikmund-Fisher et al 2010). This is generally because clinicians have traditionally assumed the task of decision-maker, substituting as the patient's representative to decide the most suitable course of action.

Therefore, whilst healthcare professionals believe they are carrying out SDM and that it is standard practice for their board, (relating back to the third research question for the current study: "is SDM routinely used as standard practice within Scottish NHS Boards?") perhaps reviews are needed to assess whether they are carrying out SDM in the proper fashion i.e. fully informing patients, and eliciting their preferences and if SDM really is being routinely used as standard practice within Scottish NHS Boards.

4.3.5. Theme 4: Crucial Factors in Designing A Decision Aid

Summary

The theme "Crucial Factors in Designing A Decision Aid" is composed of 6 sub-themes: "Visual Elements", "Consulting Key Stakeholders", "Ensuring Accessibility", "Considering Health Literacy Levels", "Include Localised Information" and "Signpost Information & Resources". All sub-themes relate to the stated vital elements that need to be incorporated when designing a DA which were consistently found across the different health boards.

Sub-theme 4a) Visual Elements

Most of the healthcare professionals agreed that a DA should contain more visual elements rather than having lots of text. This was particularly true for DAs intended for patients, and images and animated videos are favoured over lots of text in a DA.

"I supposed the format's important because I-, I get the impression that people just get switched off with a lot of text, so I think visual stuff, in terms of patients accessing them, would probably be something that would be much more positive than just big PDF or Word documents and animation I think is always very good to have in there, em, to make things simple while people are looking at them and to keep their interest but they've obviously got to be comprehensive as well, so that they cover all the different areas that a-, you know a single patient might be interested in." (P004, Healthboard 3)

Therefore, the second research question for the current study was addressed: "what features do healthcare professionals think a successful DA should have?", where it was stated DAs should have a lot of visual aspects (animated videos, images, etc.) instead of relying on text, especially DAs aimed for patient use.

(Weng et al., 2007) tested the effect of an educational video concerning total knee replacement (TKR) on expectations and knowledge in 102 white and black veterans. Veterans' reactions to the video were tested via questions concerning how informative it was, usefulness in decision-making and its understandability. Both groups recommended the video and found it useful for decision-making. The study stated an increase in expectations for black participants and small difference for white participants from baseline, proposing a removal of baseline decisional disparities. Decisional conflict (an individual's personal uncertainty regarding what option to select) (Légaré, LeBlanc, Robitaille, & Turcotte, 2012) decreased after DA intervention with decisional conflict scores lowering from 29.4 to 25.8. Knowledge also increased with participants able to successfully describe TKR efficiency improving from 31% preintervention to 77% postintervention. However, the study was limited as there was a relatively small number of participants and the study did not include a control group. Although, the researchers did state that the study produced pilot data which proposes hypotheses for evaluation in future studies.

Researchers (Tait, Zikmund-Fisher, Fagerlin, & Voepel-Lewis, 2010) also investigated the impact of graphical and tabular presentation of benefits and risks on parents' comprehension of a research study. Parents of 408 children due to have an elective surgical procedure were randomly selected to be given information concerning the benefits and risks of a fictitious study of postoperative pain control utilising pictographs, text or tables. Participants then filled out a questionnaire to investigate their actual and essential comprehension of the information. Participant demographics were documented, and their numeracy and literacy skills measured. Parents that were given information utilising pictographs or tables had significantly greater essential and actual comprehension compared to parents that were given information utilising standard text. Pictographs and tables were additionally greater than text in promoting comprehension amongst parents with low literacy and numeracy skills.

Sub-theme 4b) Consulting Key Stakeholders

It was also agreed that key stakeholders should have a say in the development of a DA or for any medical intervention. Therefore, patients and as many various healthcare professionals which are involved in the specific health condition should all be consulted for their opinions in creating a DA. Many health boards additionally have patient representatives to consult when developing a new medical intervention to incorporate this belief. When asked about who should provide feedback or conduct an evaluation of how effective DAs are the following response was given:

“I suppose you would need the-, the users, so, em, you know, you might want to, em, a patient group or a, a group of users to give their feedback, in terms of self-reported outcomes and you might want to also look at that against any-, any clinical measures that have been taken as well. So I guess both, both the users and the clinicians.” (P005, Healthboard 4)

Thus, the second research question for the current study was also addressed (i.e. what features do healthcare professionals think a successful DA should have?). For the successful implementation of anything that is new, not just for the implementation of DAs, healthcare professionals believed that involving as many relevant individuals in the planning process is key (e.g., pharmacists, GPs, nurses, patients, etc.).

This finding corresponds with literature such as Yamey (2011) who proposed a framework for describing success in large scale changes to global health, formed from key themes in the developing field. Factors which contributed to success for large scale changes were established from the published literature and from interviews with implementation experts. These factors included: active participation of a variety of key stakeholders (notably those delivering the change and those impacted by the new intervention), strong governance and leadership and selecting a simplistic intervention broadly agreed to be beneficial by a majority.

Most boards stated that they have patient representatives that sit on their board who give their input towards the planning of implementing anything new. The greatest difficulty currently for successful implementation of SDM and DAs is to formulate efficient development and implementation processes and tools to aid SDM, and guarantee that it is implemented in standard clinical practice. Implementing SDM into behaviours and skills, systems, workforce attitudes and processes is a difficulty (Coulter & Collins, 2011). However, involving as many key stakeholders in the design and implementation process could be the answer to successful implementation of DAs as it will then be more likely to be accepted and used by everyone, which was found for the Picture Option Grid created by Durand et al. (2016). The creation of the Picture Option Grid being completely directed by numerous stakeholder feedback,

and which resulted in participants perceiving the Picture Option Grid to be accessible, usable and acceptable.

Sub-theme 4c) Ensuring Accessibility

Another agreed aspect for a DA is that it needs to be accessible for anyone who uses it. For a patient, they could use it at home or in their appointment. For a healthcare professional, they can access it where they are working when needed. Also, being able to have immediate access to the information contained in the DA, so not needing to have multiple platforms to sign into to access the information or rely on a Wi-Fi connection. Additionally, the DA having multiple formats or versions i.e. online, paper copies, braille versions, different language versions etc., enables that it is accessible for more people to use.

“So I believe having aids...that are accessible for you at a convenient time, wherever you are, supports management of that condition.” (P001, Healthboard 1)

Researchers (Rapport et al., 2006) aimed to investigate participant responses and opinions to 3 DAs aimed at genetic testing for breast cancer via focus groups. Participants consisted of 39 females, older than 18 years old, that had been referred to a regional cancer genetics service within the UK and had received a risk assessment for genetic breast cancer. The females included in the focus groups were at moderate, high and population risk. One paper-based DA and two CD-ROMs were evaluated for greater informed choice, clarity of presentation, increased knowledge, ease of handling and emotive response. There was variation in preferences for different formats of DAs and mixed emotions, a lack of agreement in the most suitable aid and no differences between risk groups. The participants reported that the DAs increased their knowledge, specifically in regard to risk and breast cancer genes and they wanted a DA created in the context of the NHS in both CD-ROM and paper-based formats. Mixed beliefs about presentation styles propose DAs would be more efficient with a user-selected range of formats. Rapport et al. (2006) also found from their focus groups that a commonly cited subject was that information should be highly accessible which corresponds with findings from the current study in addition to having a wide variety in formats for the DA.

Researchers (O'Connor, Llewellyn-Thomas, & Flood, 2004) reviewed and defined the evidence base for SDM and DAs. They found that although extensive distribution is assisted through free and easily accessible DAs, the internet cannot guarantee the appropriateness and timeliness of their supply to patients. Additionally, the internet is not equally accessible to every individual and so is not specifically appropriate for addressing differences in unwarranted variation in preference-sensitive care. This

finding corresponds with the current study's finding that it's important for patients to be able to access the information stored within the DA immediately without needing a reliable Wi-Fi connection.

Sub-theme 4d) Considering Health Literacy Levels

Additionally, a frequently mentioned requirement for developing a DA was that the information contained in the DA needs to be kept simple and understandable for people of all reading abilities and health literacy levels. As there will be variation in individuals' health literacy/reading age with a majority being of lower level, the text within the DA needs to be kept concise, clear and to avoid medical jargon so that it is suitable and more comprehensive for a wider audience.

"...they have some information there but they don't really think about what patients and carers need...given the population that we have which is a poor reading age...the average reading age in Scotland is between 11 and 12. Do most decision aids take that into consideration? No, I don't think they do...so, we need to make sure that that is all correct and I think if they did a lot of that, in my opinion, that's just as useful as, you know, making sure that it has the best information in it." (P002, Healthboard 1)

This may help combat the argument founded by healthcare professional's attitudes that DAs and SDM is "Not appropriate for those with low health literacy" (Légaré et al., 2008).

Volandes and colleagues (2011) aimed to evaluate the palliative preferences of aging patients in rural communities and if preferences are linked to level of health literacy. Elderly participants (aged 65+) took part in a randomised controlled trial of a "goals-of-care" video DA of advanced dementia at a primary care clinic in rural Louisiana. Half of the participants listened to a verbal description of advanced dementia and the goals of care. The remaining half listened to the same verbal description and then watched the video DA. End points were the favoured goal of care in advanced dementia: comfort care (symptom relief), life-prolonging care (cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR), etc.) or limited care (hospitalisation, but not CPR). The most important category for analysis was the variation in ranges of participants favouring comfort care for every characteristic including health literacy level and randomisation group. The study found that rural participants with increased health literacy were more inclined to want comfort care in comparison to participants with decreased levels of health literacy. Additionally, participants who watched a video DA were more inclined to choose comfort in comparison to participants that only heard a verbal description. These results propose that video can assist in eliciting preferences and that interventions to enable such patients must be created in an approach that takes into account varying levels of health literacy.

Another example of a DA which can help patients with low health literacy was Durand et al.'s (2016) picture option grid. They created and assessed the usability, acceptability and accessibility of a picture-based DA (to be utilised within clinical appointments) aimed at females of low socioeconomic status (SES) diagnosed with early-stage breast cancer. Every female who took part in the study that was of low SES and recently diagnosed with early-stage breast cancer perceived the Picture Option Grid accessible, usable and acceptable (however it cannot be assumed that a visual DA will also benefit males of low health literacy or SES). Therefore, it can be concluded from both studies that perhaps SDM and DAs can be "appropriate for those with low health literacy" if the DA or information is presented in a visual format such as using pictures or videos instead of predominately text-based.

Video DA can also help address the limited literacy skills that are common amongst ethnic and racial minorities who are disproportionately affected (Kindig et al., 2004).

Additionally, researchers (Peters, Dieckmann, Dixon, Hibbard, & Mertz, 2007) examined if the way in which information is presented differently impact users which vary in numeric skills. The results of their three studies supported the concept that "less is more" when presenting users with comparative performance information to make hospital decisions. This result was especially true for participants with lower numeracy skills who had increased understanding and made better decisions when the format in which information was presented was created to highlight the meaning of essential information and to alleviate the cognitive burden.

These studies tie into the current study's findings that information contained within a DA, specifically text-based information, must be kept concise and simple due to the variation in individuals' health literacy and reading abilities so that more people can understand the information being conveyed to them.

Sub-theme 4e) Include Localised Information

Another consistently cited attribute for a best practice DA was that it should contain localised information and guidelines. For example, some DAs use American-based information and guidelines which differ from those provided in Scotland. For others, their DAs are specifically region-based as opposed to national information, as their region does not have specific medical equipment (such as MRI scanners, etc.). Therefore, the information in their DA reflects their health board or region-specific circumstances, so the information is tailored to them and is more accurate as a result.

I: "Ok, em, in your opinion, what features should a best practice decision aid have?"

P: "...It should be Scotland wide as well, so it should be ones for Scotland that should be designed specifically for us. It should include national, em, and local guidelines, SIGN guidelines, NICE guidelines..." (P002, Healthboard 1)

In O'Connor et al.'s (2004) paper, they review and define the evidence base for SDM and DAs. They reflect the current study's finding that there can be vast differences in regional practice in the utilisation of preference-sensitive options e.g. the probability of having a hysterectomy or prostatectomy differs two- to fivefold between regions (J. E. Wennberg & Cooper, 1999).

The need for localised information in DAs is further highlighted by researchers (O'Connor, Légaré, & Stacey, 2003). They propose essential strategies to increase decision quality and for guaranteeing that differences in practice are consistent with the dispersion of preferences of informed patients. One of the strategies suggests expanding existing information to accommodate preference sensitive choices e.g. regional education programmes for patients.

Sub-theme 4f) Signpost Information & Resources

Another commonly suggested feature of a best practice DA was that it should include signposting. The DA needs to clearly outline all of the different options or choices for the patient's treatment of their condition or at least inform patients where they can find further information and resources on their health condition (i.e. list any local support groups, provide hyperlinks to health or charity websites, etc.).

I: "Yeah, eh, in your opinion, what features should a best practice decision aid have?"

P: "...it needs to have very clear signposting...so that people know exactly what to do with the problem that's in front of them... needs to signpost all the various options." - Another commonly suggested feature of a best practice DA was that it should include signposting. (P004, Healthboard 3)

Research (Joyce, Lord, Matlock, McComb, & Thomson, 2013) has previously examined how clinical practice guidelines (CPGs) include the patient viewpoint into aiding decision-making concerning implantable cardioverter defibrillators (ICDs). CPGs on ICD implantation were deliberately chosen from professional and national bodies in Australasia, Europe and North America. CPGs were then evaluated in accordance with 3 essential domains of SDM: engagement of patient (and significant others/family if wanted) in decision-making, personalising benefits and risks and informing patients about the consequences, and risks and benefits known to be valuable to patients. Evaluation of 6 CPGs found large inconsistencies or deficiencies in guidance and focused on evidence of device efficiency with poor consideration of other outcomes vital to patients like psychosocial well-being and effects of

quality of life. Particular recommendations for CPG development involved the requirement for signposting to preference sensitive decision points in addition to inclusion of a wider variation of outcomes that are known to be vital to patients when choosing whether or not to fit a device.

Therefore, Joyce et al.'s (2013) study also highlights the need for signposting not only in DAs but in clinical practice guidelines too.

4.3.6. Theme 5: A Decision Aid for Chronic Pain

Summary

The theme: "A Decision Aid for Chronic Pain" is composed of 3 sub-themes: "Unfamiliarity", "Suitability of a Decision Aid for Chronic Conditions" and "Outlining All Options". All sub-themes relate to various aspects of a DA for chronic pain which were consistently found across the different health boards.

Sub-theme 5a) Unfamiliarity

Most participants had stated that they did not know of a DA for chronic pain. However, this was most likely because the participants which had said this did not specifically work in/with chronic pain. Therefore, it is probably likely that DAs for chronic pain exist but that these particular healthcare professionals were not aware of them as they perhaps did not need to use them.

"I'm not aware of it because we haven't looked into them for chronic pain..." (P003, Healthboard 2)

Others, who did work in chronic pain had heard of or knew of DAs for chronic pain.

"Yeah, well, the one that, em, the one that I use, em and it's something that's, that we've developed, sort of, within our department, is the patient activation measure. So that's a standard, eh, tool that's used in chronic conditions, em, and it was developed by King's Fund and we have modified it, em, you know, there's a list of questions but we've modified them to be specific to chronic pain and so then we, em, identify what, em, level the patient's at and then we can target their treatment according to that." (P005, Healthboard 4)

The health conditions which the DAs were used for were all the same or similar. The most cited DAs were targeted towards cancer, tonsillitis, throat, and orthopaedics. There was a DA listed for Gastroenterology and some for chronic pain too however.

“I have been involved in developing shared decision-making aids in...there’s a few specialties we're working on, pancreatic cancer...tonsillitis and in...orthopaedics, particularly knee surgery.” (P003, Healthboard 2)

Therefore, the first research question for the current study was addressed: “Are DAs successfully implemented and used routinely as standard practice within Scottish NHS Boards?”, as whilst some boards did use DAs, most healthcare professionals were not familiar with a DA for chronic pain. There were some DAs for some healthcare conditions, but not for all health conditions. This aligns with Légaré et al.’s (2008) earlier finding that the successful implementation of DAs is patchy and not currently the norm within the UK and Scotland. The variation in DA use between the boards also aligns with Coulter and Collins (2011) observation that despite the central role of SDM in the government’s new model of healthcare quality, the utilisation of DAs and SDM within the UK has been inconsistent.

In Brace et al.’s (2010) study, they set out to determine clinicians’ utilisation and awareness of DAs, their views on the main barriers to the utilisation of DAs, and clinician characteristics predictive of utilisation of DAs in clinical practice. Multivariate analysis displayed specialty to be the singular clinician characteristic which influenced the utilisation of DAs. This explains why most clinicians in the current study stated that they did not know of a DA for chronic pain because the participants which had noted this did not specifically work in or with a chronic pain context and chronic pain was not their speciality. Others, who did work in chronic pain contexts, had heard of or knew of a DA for chronic pain however, as this was their specialised domain.

Sub-theme 5b) Suitability of a Decision Aid for Chronic Conditions

A vast majority believed that a DA for chronic pain would be beneficial for patients to help support self-management of their condition.

“Yes...it empowers the patient and re-iterates the information, em, that can be forgotten if it's just given to you in a leaflet. You can I-use, lose the- the leaflet or you can forget, em, what information you were given at the time of a consultation. So I believe having aids in different formats that are accessible for you at a convenient time, wherever you are, supports management of that condition.” (P001, Healthboard 1)

Another common belief was that DAs are best suited for chronic conditions. Acute conditions are normally treated quickly whereas chronic conditions are longer-term. Therefore, patients with a chronic condition will need a DA potentially at various and multiple time points to help them decide how best to self-manage their condition.

“I should imagine long-standing chronic health conditions would be better because obviously it's people who are gonna be within the service for a long space of time with a condition that's not going to go away.” (P007, Healthboard 6)

Therefore, participants' responses addressed the final research question (what are clinicians' opinions towards a possible future DA for chronic pain and what features should this DA include?). There are several studies which also support the viewpoint that a DA for chronic pain would be beneficial for patients. Spunt et al. (1996) carried out a large-scale study composed of 239 patients that watched a video about back pain treatment which demonstrated similar shifts in decisional conflict with less patients remaining undecided concerning treatment after watching the video (17% vs 29%). The video was well accepted in concern to its amount of information, understandability, helping patients decide about treatment and keeping the interest of viewers. However, the researchers admitted that they were unsure the degree to which their participants represented all patients with low back pain that are contemplating surgery.

Phelan et al. (2001) carried out a randomised trial of 100 surgical candidates with low back pain that received an interactive video and a booklet or only a booklet about back surgery. Every patient showed an increase in knowledge regarding treatment options, and the combination of the booklet and video led to higher knowledge gain for patients with low baseline scores. Also, participants favoured the combination intervention and surgical preference was less in the group supplied with the video. However, the study only took place at 2 general practices and with well-educated patients which may have affected the generalisability of the results.

In O'Connor et al.'s (2004) paper, they review and define the evidence base for SDM and DAs. They also believe that individuals with chronic conditions are the most probable to encounter preference-sensitive choices and decision points can frequently be expected, so allowing the supply of DAs in a prompt order without needing the patient to begin the request. Therefore, they agree with the current study's finding that DAs are best suited for individuals with chronic conditions and that they will need a DA potentially at various and multiple time points to help them decide how best to self-manage their condition.

Sub-theme 5c) Outlining All Options

Every healthcare professional agreed that a chronic pain DA should list all available treatment options for patients.

“...if it's a decision aid, it's got to look at all-, everything right? What would be the point otherwise...the available treatments for chronic pain are huge, yeah. There's a massive number of different, both pharmacological and nonpharmacological approaches...there's also surgical interventions of course, as well, not just pharmacological...” (P003, Healthboard 2)

Thus, the DA should not just specifically focus on medication options such as painkillers and ointments but outline interventional options such as epidural injections and facet injections and non-pharmacological options such as physiotherapy exercises and acupuncture also.

“They should include all options, pharmacological and non-pharmacological and also...interventional treatments as well.” (P009, Healthboard 8)

Thus, the final research question was again addressed by participants' responses: “What are clinicians' opinions towards a possible future DA for chronic pain and what features should this DA include?”. From responses discussed in the previous sub-theme, healthcare professionals had positive opinions towards a possible future DA for chronic pain. The main feature that they believed a chronic pain DA should have been to include information on all possible treatment options.

In their paper (Lenz et al., 2012) provide an overview of SDM, DAs and evidence-based information. They believe that evidence-based patient information (EBPI) is a crucial part of DAs and internationally determined quality criteria is ready for use. They explain that ethical guidelines define what meta-information and content for patients is appropriate and involve an inclusive record of every option which takes into account the possibility of originally avoiding intervention. Thus, they also believe in addition to the current study's findings that a DA should provide information on all available options not just specifically options relating solely to medication, non-pharmacological options or on interventional options.

4.3.7. Theme 6: Common Features in Existing Decision Aids

Summary

The theme: “Common Features in Existing Decision Aids” is composed of 3 sub-themes: “Utilisation of Decision Aids”, “Shared Use of Decision Aids” and “Decision Aid Guidelines”. All sub-themes relate to commonly stated aspects found between the different DAs that health boards used which were consistently found across the different health boards.

Sub-theme 6a) Utilisation of Decision Aids

Most healthcare professionals had said that their DAs could be used both in and out with consultations. Therefore, the patient could use the DA at home in their own time or in an appointment with their clinician.

“In both, in both. So, depending on the type of decision aid. If it’s an information leaflet, it can be discussed in consultation or provided as supplementary information...a couple of different information decision aid tools we’ve developed in the past year has been...animated video, so therefore it can be used at the consultation but also provide an alternative...decision aid tool that can be accessed at home in the patient’s own time.” (P001, Healthboard 1)

This was an interesting finding as the majority of existing DA (outwith the current study) have been created for patients to utilise alone outwith the appointment, either at home or in the waiting room (Elywn et al., 2010).

DAs are unlike traditional information materials given to patients as they do not instruct patients what to do but outline the facts and assist patients to contemplate the choices. DAs normally include (Coulter & Collins, 2011):

- an outline of the symptoms and the condition
- the probable prognosis without and with treatment
- the self-management support and treatment choices and outcome probabilities, uncertainties and what is known from the evidence
- illustrations to assist patients in comprehending what it would be like to experience a few of the most occurring complications or side-effects of the treatment choices (usually utilising patient interviews)
- a method of assisting patients to define their preferences
- sources of additional information and references
- and the authors’ declarations of conflict of interest, credentials and funding source

Thus, providing the patient with sufficient information to help make a healthcare decision or to discuss the options with the healthcare professional fully.

However, despite the DAs that can be used outwith the appointment supporting understanding of the problems, they cannot assure that decisions in the appointment are shared (Stiggelbout et al., 2012; Hargraves & Montori, 2014) and there is not enough evidence to discover how their utilisation impacts the appointment (Hargraves & Montori, 2014).

Thus, newer DAs seem to adopt a trend of being brief and to be utilised within appointments compared to traditional aids which contained more information and were to be used out with the appointment (Agoritsas et al., 2015).

Sub-theme 6b) Shared Use of Decision Aids

Another commonly stated aspect was that most of the DAs could be used by a patient's relative, guardian or caregiver. So, in addition to the patient and the clinician being able to use the DA, a patient's relative, guardian, family member or caregiver could also use the DA.

"Well, people are encouraged to use this with, I mean in typically, certainly, when people come from pancreatic cancer consultations, they will be taking their family with them, there very rarely would people be coming on their own and so for sure this would be something that they would be discussing together." (P003, Healthboard 2)

Whilst information provided by a DA is beneficial, specifically if it is personalised, information alone is not sufficient. It must be enriched by decision support, self-management education and personalised care planning from sufficiently trained health care professionals, in addition to social support from peers, family and friends (Coulter & Collins, 2011). There is proof that this can increase individual's level of engagement and understanding, in addition to their confidence to self-manage and coping skills, leading to improved health outcomes (Coulter & Ellins, 2007; Loveman et al., 2008). Thus, highlighting the importance of including peers, family and friends when making healthcare decisions.

Researchers (Sleath et al., 2011) also found in their study that caregivers asked more questions than children regarding their child's medication and management of their health condition. They also found that caregivers provided input into their child's treatment plan more frequently than their children. Therefore, it was concluded that healthcare professionals must take into consideration including and requesting for both child and their caregiver's input into treatment plans in order for SDM to be carried out more often.

Sub-theme 6c) Decision Aid Guidelines

Additionally, most DAs seemed to follow SIGN and NICE guidelines. The Scottish Intercollegiate Guidelines Network (SIGN) develops evidence based clinical practice guidelines for the National Health Service (NHS) in Scotland (J. Miller, 2002), while guidelines produced by the National Institute for Clinical Excellence (NICE) concentrate on health conditions which have a significant impact on public

health. NICE guidelines also aim to decrease variations in provision and increase standards of care (Middleton, Shaw, Hull, & Feder, 2005).

“...the guidelines would be around the SIGN guideline 136 and the NICE guidelines...”. (P006, Healthboard 5)

The utilisation of these clinical practice guidelines has demonstrated positive change in clinical practice and improvement in the quality of patient care (Pallari, Fox, & Lewison, 2018).

4.4 Conclusion

4.4.1. Limitations

There are a few limitations to the study which relate to how generalisable the results are: only 8 out of 14 health boards responded and gave interviews; the interviewees all had various job roles within the NHS and only Scottish NHS boards were contacted for the study, therefore generalisability of the results may be limited by these factors.

There was also the potential for bias in the way that participants were recruited for the study. By emailing the listed contact detail for each NHS board, it was hoped that one individual from each board who was knowledgeable in the use of DAs and SDM in their board would be interviewed. Thus, most participants were knowledgeable about or had heard about DAs and/or SDM. Therefore, there was the potential for bias in that there perhaps could have been more effort to recruit participants who were not knowledgeable about or had not heard about DAs and/or SDM in order to gain a more balanced understanding of the implementation of DAs and SDM in Scottish NHS Boards.

However, efforts were made to contact and recruit members of all Scottish health boards. Only Scottish NHS boards were contacted for this study as the thesis specifically is focused on the implementation of SDM in Scotland. Additionally, whilst most participants were knowledgeable about or had heard about SDM, there were some participants that had not heard of DAs, thus slightly reducing the potential bias in the recruitment of participants.

4.4.2 Future Research

Taking into account the limitations of this study, future research could look at differences in implementation of SDM and DAs between different parts of the UK (i.e. Scotland vs England or between nationalities, such as UK vs USA.) Also, this study only asked healthcare professionals

generally (regardless of job role) about implementation of SDM and DAs, thus it may be worthwhile to look at potential differences in the implementation of SDM and DAs between different healthcare professional job roles (i.e. general practitioners, speciality doctors, nurses, physiotherapists etc.).

Additionally, since only some health boards used DAs, it seems logical for future studies in this thesis to focus on SDM instead as all health boards knew about SDM and most implemented SDM. A key finding from the current study was that healthcare professionals felt that SDM was more important than DAs. Thus, this is another crucial reason for future research to focus on SDM rather than DAs.

This study focused on healthcare professionals' views on DAs and SDM. Thus, future studies and particularly for this thesis should perhaps focus on patients' views on SDM to get a fuller picture of SDM and investigate if patients also believe that SDM is beneficial and standard practice when making healthcare decisions.

Finally, as participants believed that a DA and SDM is beneficial for patients with chronic pain, perhaps future research could also focus on patients with chronic pain's views on SDM and whether they believe SDM is successfully implemented in the NHS too.

4.4.3 Chapter Conclusions

The current study aimed to answer the following research questions:

1. Are DAs successfully implemented and used routinely as standard practice within Scottish NHS Boards?
2. What features do clinicians think a successful DA should have?
3. Is SDM routinely used as standard practice within Scottish NHS Boards?
4. What are the potential barriers to SDM and DAs?
5. What are healthcare professionals' opinions towards a possible future DA for chronic pain and what features should this DA include?

It was found from healthcare professionals' responses that DAs are not successfully implemented and used routinely as standard practice within most Scottish NHS Boards. Clinicians believed that a successful DA should be more visual than relying on lots of text, favouring images and animated videos. It was also agreed that key stakeholders should have a say in the development of a DA or for any medical intervention, so patients and as many various healthcare professionals which are involved in the health condition should all be consulted for their opinions and expertise in creating a DA. Information needs to be accessible, so information in a DA needs to be kept simple and understandable

for all reading and health literacy levels. They need to contain relevant localised information and signpost to additional resources.

SDM appeared to be routinely used as standard practice within Scottish NHS Boards. Time, lack of awareness and lack of reviews were identified as barriers to implementing SDM and DAs. Clinicians believed that a possible future DA for chronic pain would be useful for patients to self-manage their condition and that the DA should include and list all available treatment options for patients.

Chapter 5: A Quantitative Study of Predictors of Attitudes To, Knowledge of and Preferences for Shared Decision-Making in Patients with Chronic Pain

5.1 Introduction

The interviews in study 1 with healthcare professionals showed that decision aids (DAs) are not used routinely as standard practice within most Scottish NHS Boards. This finding led to a change in focus in the thesis in subsequent studies. The original aim was to look at patient satisfaction with DAs, but if decision aids are not widely used in health care, patients would have little experience of them and there was not much point in looking at patients' perceptions and acceptance of decision aids. Consequently, the emphasis of subsequent studies changed from looking at patients' perceptions of DAs to looking at attitudes to and acceptance of Shared Decision Making (SDM) generally since a key finding from study 1 was that healthcare professionals believed that SDM was routinely used as standard practice.

5.1.1. Aims

Study 2 adopted a quantitative approach to investigating the acceptance of SDM in individuals with chronic pain. The researcher looked at how SDM has been studied, looking at attitudes towards, knowledge of and preferences for shared decision-making as reflecting acceptance of SDM. This study also examines the possible predictors of acceptance of SDM by looking at potential factors that influence SDM, resulting in the acceptance or rejection of SDM.

5.1.2. Background

As discussed in Chapter 1, chronic pain was chosen as the test case in exploring SDM, due to the considerable impact on the quality of life of an individual and their family as well as substantial impact on society, the healthcare services and on economic costs. SDM may also be more useful for healthcare decisions where there are varied treatment options and possible decisions for patients to make.

Chronic pain poses an opportunity to practice SDM, as there are many treatment options for patients to choose from.

In a systematic review of the effects of SDM, Joosten et al. (2008) found that SDM improved longer term outcomes in several studies that explored both mental and physical health conditions. Positive impacts were observed on patients' adherence to plans, satisfaction, knowledge and well-being. Müller et al. (2004) looked at the effects of SDM in patients with Fibromyalgia syndrome which is an exemplary condition of chronic widespread pain. They found that patients' readiness to enrol in physical activities, to take analgesics, and to participate in psychotherapeutic elements were most likely to be raised through SDM.

Acceptance of SDM by patients is important because for SDM to be standard practice, SDM needs to be accepted by everyone and viewed as being beneficial and useful. Acceptance of SDM specifically by patients with chronic pain is important as patients need to self-manage their pain (Mann et al., 2013) and SDM can help them to evaluate their options and help identify the best one for them to help manage their condition.

5.2 Literature

5.2.1. How has Acceptance of SDM been Assessed?

Preferred Consultation Style

An important measure that has been widely reported in looking at acceptance of SDM is a single-item measure developed by Yen et al. (2019) to assess patients' preferred consultation style. The measure asks patients: "How do you think healthcare decisions should be made?". There are five possible response options that reflect patients' views of the balance of responsibility in terms of making health decisions with respect to the extent of the patient's involvement in the decision, ranging from 1 that they the patient make the final decision about which treatment they should receive themselves to 5, that the healthcare professional should make the final decision about which treatment the patient should receive. Lower scores were linked to more favourable attitudes towards SDM. "Active" patients, i.e. patients who engage in healthcare decisions and discussions with their healthcare professional, are more equipped to make personally relevant and informed decisions regarding their care; they frequently utilise less health care; they tend to make healthier lifestyle choices; they are better at self-managing chronic conditions, and they are more inclined to adhere to treatment recommendations

(Mosen et al., 2007). In contrast “passive” patients tend to yield to the health care professionals as decision makers, and without active support or encouragement from health care professionals commonly stay at decreased levels of activation (Mosen et al., 2007).

Attitudes towards SDM

Attitudes is another construct that could be useful in looking at acceptance of SDM. Having a positive attitude to an issue is generally important in determining our acceptance. In order for patients to buy into or adopt SDM in healthcare decisions, they need to have positive attitudes towards it. There is surprisingly little research looking at attitudes towards SDM in healthcare. While research exists on practitioners’ attitudes, there is less research looking at other stakeholders. Durand et al. (2017) found that “Research into the knowledge and attitudes of medical students with regard to SDM is scarce”, p2. These authors developed a number of measures of attitudes that were used in this study.

Knowledge of Shared Decision-Making

Knowledge is also a construct which could be useful in looking at acceptance of SDM. The knowledge scale was also developed by Durand et al. (2017) but was originally made to measure medical students’ knowledge of SDM. This measure assesses participants’ (in this case patients with chronic pain) understanding of the ideas behind SDM. Joseph-Williams et al. (2014) found that patients require knowledge of SDM to engage in SDM. Similarly, other researchers (Hawley & Morris, 2017) stated that for SDM to be achieved, patients need to have increased knowledge of SDM.

5.2.2. Possible Predictors of Acceptance of SDM

Baseline Pain Intensity

Strong et al. (1992) and Kerns et al. (1997) suggest a number of variables that should be examined in looking at patients’ attitudes to chronic pain. These include differences in the type of pain suffered, persistent baseline level and breakthrough levels of pain and differences in patients’ readiness to change influence their attitudes to pain. Persistent baseline pain is defined as pain that spans a period of 6 months or more (Payne, 2007). Contrary to persistent pain is breakthrough pain which has a quick onset, is temporary and intense. It “breaks through” the medication utilised to treat persistent baseline pain (Payne, 2007). Strong and colleagues (1992) compared the psychometric properties of 2 scales designed to measure beliefs about and attitudes towards pain. The Pain Beliefs and Perceptions

Inventory (PBPI) (Williams & Thorn, 1989) and the Survey of Pain Attitudes (Revised) SOPA(R) (Jensen et al., 1987) were investigated in relation to sensitivity to gender and age effects, internal consistency, construct validity, discriminant validity and factor structure. The results showed strong support for the SOPA(R) as a beneficial measurement tool for utilization with individuals with chronic low back pain. More work is proposed for the PBPI, as the stated factor structure was not replicated. Discussion focused on the possible causes for this result, with problems such as the possible influence of length of years in pain and the possible variation in attitudes between individuals with different types of pain being considered.

Kerns and colleagues (1997) detailed the development and preliminary validation of a self-report questionnaire created to evaluate a person's readiness to undertake a self-management approach to their chronic pain condition (i.e. their readiness to change). Theory and initial empirical work led to the formation of a pool of items which were given to a sample of people reporting chronic pain. Data analysis supported a 4-factor measure which is compatible with the associated stages of change model and the transtheoretical model of change. Each of the 4 factors: precontemplation, contemplation, action, and maintenance were established to be stable and internally consistent over time. There was also ample support for every factor's criterion-related and discriminant validity.

An important finding from the MAGIC programme (Joseph-Williams et al., 2017) was that skills and attitudes were viewed as more important than tools and that positive attitudes were found to be more important than skills in SDM by healthcare professionals. However, this has yet to be investigated from the patient's perspective. Therefore, instead of "communication skills" which is an important factor for clinicians, "skills" will be measured by the patient's readiness to change as this is a crucial skill for managing their pain.

Readiness to Change

Examining a person's level of motivation, i.e. their readiness to change, has emerged in adult pain research as a probable key factor for successful pain self-management (Jensen et al., 2003). Readiness to change is an important factor or stage in patients changing their behaviour in 2 health models: The Transtheoretical Model (TTM) (Prochaska & DiClemente, 1983) and the Motivational Model of Pain Self-Management (Jensen et al., 2003).

The Transtheoretical Model (Prochaska & DiClemente, 1983), also referred to as the Stages of Change Model, developed as a result of studies investigating the experiences of smokers who chose to quit by themselves and those who needed further treatment to comprehend why some individuals were able to quit without help. It was found that individuals stopped smoking if they felt ready to. Therefore, TTM is a model of intentional change and concentrates on the decision-making of a single person. The

model functions on the assumption that individuals do not change behaviours decisively and quickly. The readiness to change stage of the TTM is the third stage of the model and is referred to as the “Preparation or determination” stage. In this stage, individuals feel ready to take action in the following 30 days and begin to take small steps towards the behaviour change and they feel that altering their behaviour can lead to a healthier life.

The Motivational Model of Pain Self-Management (Jensen et al., 2003) is a model in which patient motivation to participate in pain self-management behaviours was assumed to be a vital predictor of adaption to pain. Established from an expectancy value approach, readiness to change is determined through the patient’s perceived importance of the coping behaviour and the patient’s perceived ability to utilise or adopt the coping response (i.e. self-efficacy). An expectancy value approach encompasses that an individual’s performance, choice and persistence can be influenced by their beliefs concerning how well they will perform on the activity and how much they value the activity (Wigfield, 1994). The essential outcomes of the model are avoidance of maladaptive and engagement in adaptive coping responses. These coping responses are then believed to aid patient function (or dysfunction).

TTM operates on the assumption that people do not change behaviours quickly and decisively. Readiness to change is the important factor or stage in patients changing behaviour in both health models. Therefore, it might be a key factor for patients with chronic pain to partake in SDM which may help them to engage in adaptive coping responses and to self-manage their pain efficiently.

Decisional Needs

If they are to successfully engage in SDM, patients have specific needs. Decisional needs assessments, such as The Ottawa Decision Support Framework (ODSF) (Jacobsen et al., 2013) focus on recognising what patients require to make better decisions and what healthcare professionals require to enhance the support they supply to patients during decision-making. The assessment gathers information regarding the preferences, opinions and attitudes of groups and individuals. A decisional needs assessment can aid in determining what individuals or groups need. The spotlight is on both the healthcare professional and the patient to discover the problems they encounter with decision-making. Possible needs involve: resources and support, deficits in expectations and knowledge, clarity of values, feeling prepared to make a decision and decisional conflict. Decisional needs might additionally be specific to the characteristics of the healthcare professionals and patients and the type of decision.

5.3 Hypotheses

As the current study is a preliminary and exploratory study of variables that could potentially impact on acceptance of SDM and given the complexity of the variables that might impact on acceptance of SDM, a number of hypotheses were tested in the current study. Whilst, the researcher is aware of the problems associated with multiple testing, mainly that through doing this, it is more likely for the researcher to have a false-positive finding (Ranganathan, Pramesh, & Buyse, 2016), the researcher still felt it was necessary to test multiple different variables in order to identify which variables impact on the acceptance of SDM in individuals with chronic pain to address the aims of the research, further knowledge and potentially facilitate the successful implementation of SDM. Also, whilst the researchers are additionally aware that the p-values would normally be adjusted for multiple comparisons using the methods outlined in (Chen, Feng, & Yi, 2017), instead the researchers have decided to split the analyses and hypotheses into primary and secondary analyses and hypotheses.

To help address the potential problem of multiple hypotheses testing without reducing the number of variables tested, the researcher will identify a few primary hypotheses that highlight the most important and interesting variables that might impact on acceptance of SDM as well as some secondary hypotheses which will explore other variables that might have a significant impact on acceptance of SDM by individuals with chronic pain. However, any significant results which are greater than .001 should be interpreted with caution.

5.3.1. Primary Hypotheses

The researcher identified primary hypotheses that highlight the impact of the most important and interesting variables on acceptance of SDM. First of all, it was useful to examine the links between the measures of acceptance of SDM that were used in the current study: attitudes towards SDM, preferred consultation style and knowledge of SDM. The remaining primary hypotheses focused on variables that had been identified in the literature as most relevant to the current study: baseline pain intensity, readiness to change, decisional conflict and preparation for decision-making.

Outcome Variables

A number of measures of SDM have been proposed in the literature and the first set of primary hypotheses concerned the relationships between the outcome variables used to measure acceptance of SDM in the current study: patients' attitudes towards SDM, their preferred consultation style and their knowledge of SDM. Measures of attitude seem to be most relevant in studying acceptance of SDM as positive attitudes seem to underlie acceptance of SDM. Yen et al.'s (2019) single-item measure

to assess patients' preferred consultation style: "How do you think healthcare decisions should be made?" is also useful in tapping into acceptance of SDM and is possibly the most widely used measure reported in the literature. Measures of knowledge of SDM could also be important for the acceptance of SDM. As there were not many validated measures of SDM which could be found by the researcher when carrying out the current study, and because the measures used in the current study had not been examined in relation to patients with chronic pain before, it was a priority to examine the relationships between these measures.

Consequently, the measures used in the current study were: participants' preferred consultation style, participants' attitudes towards SDM & participants' knowledge of SDM. Charles, Gafni & Whelan (1997) found that the association between patients' preferences for participation in healthcare decisions and their actual participation was weak, suggesting that whilst some patients have positive attitudes towards SDM, they may not be given the chance to be actively involved in their healthcare. Additionally, other researchers (Carlsen & Aakvik, 2006) stated that whilst some patients prefer to be passive in their healthcare decisions, it is key to encourage positive attitudes towards SDM. Therefore, it is expected that:

P H1 OV: Participants' attitudes towards SDM will be associated with their preferred consultation style.

Mathijssen, van den Bemt, Wielsma, van den Hoogen, & Vriezolk (2020) found that, whilst healthcare professionals had decreased knowledge of SDM, they still had positive attitudes towards SDM. Pollard, Bansback, & Bryan (2015) additionally found that patients' knowledge and a positive attitude towards SDM were frequently cited facilitators for carrying out SDM. Therefore, it is expected that:

P H2 OV: Participants' knowledge of SDM will be associated with their attitudes towards SDM.

Whilst there is no previous literature which could be found that addresses whether patients who have more knowledge of SDM will prefer to be more active or passive in their medical decision-making, it seems reasonable to predict that knowledge of SDM may be associated with their preferred consultation style. Therefore, it is expected that:

P H3 OV: Participants' knowledge of SDM will be associated with their preferred consultation style.

Predictor Variables

The remaining primary hypotheses focus on the impact of the key predictor variables for this study: participants' baseline pain intensity, readiness to change, preparation for decision-making and decisional conflict. Additionally, all primary hypotheses focused on attitudes towards SDM as the outcome variable to be examined, since the researcher believes that attitudes is the most important measure of acceptance of SDM and was the only SDM measure to have an acceptable internal consistency and reliability.

Baseline Pain Intensity

Since the participants are all chronic pain patients, it made sense to look at the impact of pain related variables on attitudes to SDM, particularly participants' baseline pain as all participants' experienced baseline pain. Previous studies by Strong et al. (1992) and Kerns et al. (1997) had also suggested that persistent baseline levels of pain should be examined in looking at patients' attitudes to chronic pain. Consequently, the primary hypothesis concerning participants' baseline pain intensity was proposed as follows:

P H4 PAIN: Participants' attitudes towards SDM will differ based on their baseline pain intensity.

Readiness to Change

Examining a person's level of motivation, i.e. their readiness to change, has emerged in adult pain research as a probable key factor for successful pain self-management (Jensen et al., 2003). Readiness to change is an important factor or stage in patients changing their behaviour in 2 health models: The Transtheoretical Model (TTM) (Prochaska & DiClemente, 1983) and the Motivational Model of Pain Self-Management (Jensen et al., 2003). Therefore, readiness to change might be a key factor for patients with chronic pain to partake in SDM which may help them to engage in adaptive coping responses and to self-manage their pain efficiently. A patient's acceptance that they may need to make some modifications to their current lifestyle to cope better with pain suggested that readiness to change might also impact on their attitudes towards SDM. Keij, van Duijn-Bakker, Stiggelbout, & Pieterse (2021) identified five components of patient readiness in their study and the first component was patients' attitudes towards SDM. Therefore, it is expected that:

P H5 READINESS: Participants' readiness to change will be associated with their attitudes towards SDM.

Decisional Needs: Decisional Conflict

If they are to successfully engage in SDM, patients have specific needs. Decisional needs assessments, such as The Ottawa Decision Support Framework (ODSF) (Jacobsen et al., 2013) focus on recognising what patients require to make better decisions and what healthcare professionals require to enhance the support they supply to patients during decision making. The assessment gathers information regarding the preferences, opinions and attitudes of groups and individuals. A decisional needs assessment can aid in determining what individuals or groups need. The spotlight is on both the healthcare professional and the patient to discover the problems they encounter with decision-making. One of these problems that patients can encounter is decisional conflict. Kremer, Ironson, Schneiderman, & Hautzinger (2007) suggested that healthcare professionals could decrease patients' decisional conflict through meeting patients' desire for SDM. Therefore, it is expected that:

P H6 DECISION: Participants who experience less decisional conflict will have more positive attitudes towards SDM.

Decisional Needs: Preparation for Decision-making

Another important decisional need for patients is that they feel prepared to make a healthcare decision by having access to resources and support, addressing deficits in expectations and knowledge and by clarifying values. Keij et al. (2021) identified five components of patient readiness in their study and the first component was patients' attitudes towards SDM. Therefore, it is expected that:

P H7 DECISION: Participants' preparation for decision-making will be associated with their attitudes towards SDM.

5.3.2. Secondary Hypotheses

As the literature review suggested, there are many other variables that could potentially impact on acceptance of SDM and so this section focuses on these secondary hypotheses. Since the primary hypotheses focused on participants' attitudes towards SDM as an outcome variable, the first set of secondary hypotheses considered the impact of predictor variables considered under the primary

hypotheses (baseline pain intensity, readiness to change and decisional needs) on the other two outcome variables: participants' preferred consultation style and their knowledge of SDM. The researcher then considered the impact of a range of demographic variables (age, gender, education level and employment status), health related variables and additional pain and readiness to change variables on all three outcome variables: attitudes towards SDM, preferred consultation style and knowledge of SDM.

Hypotheses Related to the Primary Variables

In this section, the hypotheses focus on the impact of the "primary" variables on knowledge of SDM and preferred consultation style.

Baseline Pain Intensity

The impact of the baseline pain intensity variable on participants' attitudes to SDM was examined as a primary hypothesis. To complete our understanding of the effects of this variable on acceptance of SDM, the researcher also examined the impact of baseline pain intensity on participants' preferred consultation style and knowledge of SDM.

Whilst no previous literature was found that addresses whether patients who experience different levels of baseline pain intensity will be more active or passive in their medical decision-making or have more knowledge of SDM, the following hypotheses were proposed:

S H1 PAIN Participants' baseline pain intensity will predict their preferred consultation style.

S H2 PAIN: Participants' knowledge of SDM will differ based on their baseline pain intensity.

Readiness to Change

While the researcher also examined the impact of participants' readiness to change on their attitudes to SDM as a primary hypothesis, the researcher will also examine the impact of readiness to change on participants' knowledge and preferred consultation style.

Campbell and Crawford (2000) identified numerous approaches employed by dietitians in carrying out weight management. Two of these approaches included assessing the patients' readiness to change and assessing their preferred style of consultation. This suggests a possible link between patients' readiness to change and their preferred consultation style. Additionally, Miller, Marolen, and Beech (2010) suggested that patients who prefer to be more passive in their consultation style may prefer being given advice regarding different types of exercise that they can take part in when they are ready to make changes. This may suggest a possible association between patients' readiness to change and their preferred consultation style. Therefore, it is expected that:

S H3 READINESS: Participants' readiness to change will be associated with their preferred consultation style.

Keij et al. (2021) also identified understanding of SDM as a component of patient readiness in their study. Participants in the study stated that patients must have knowledge of SDM to be ready. Therefore, it is expected that:

S H4 READINESS: Participants who have higher readiness to change scores will have more knowledge of SDM.

Decisional Needs

The impact of participants' decisional conflict and their preparation for decision-making on their attitudes towards SDM were additionally proposed as primary hypotheses. However, it is also useful to explore the impact of participants' decisional conflict and their preparation for decision-making as secondary hypotheses in looking at the impact of these variables on participants' preferred consultation style and their knowledge of SDM.

Decisional Needs: Decisional Conflict

Previous research (Links et al., 2020) found that a higher level of decisional conflict was linked to a more passive consultation style. Therefore, it is expected that:

S H5 DECISION: Participants who experience more decisional conflict will prefer a passive consultation style.

Previous research (Kaplan et al., 2014) suggests that patients who experience less decisional conflict might feel more confident in their decision-making ability. These patients are referred to as being “activated”. Patient activation is assessed by their confidence, skill and knowledge in managing their healthcare. Therefore, it is expected that:

S H6 DECISION: Participants who experience less decisional conflict will have more knowledge of SDM.

Decisional Needs: Preparation for Decision-making

Kiesler and Auerbach (2006) found in their study that there were different levels of support for the positive impacts of providing patients with their preferred amount of information and their preferred involvement in healthcare decisions. Therefore, it is expected that:

S H7 DECISION: Participants’ preparation for decision-making will be associated with their preferred consultation style.

Keij et al. (2021) also identified understanding of SDM as a component of patient readiness in their study. Participants in the study stated that patients must have knowledge of SDM to be ready. Therefore, it is expected that:

S H8 DECISION: Participants who have higher preparation for decision-making scores will have more knowledge of SDM.

Additional Secondary Hypotheses

Based on the literature, a number of additional secondary hypotheses were proposed. The impact of additional pain variables, additional readiness to change variables and a range of demographic variables and health related variables on participants’ attitudes towards SDM, their preferred consultation style and their knowledge of SDM were considered.

Additional Pain Variables

The impact of three further pain related variables: participants' breakthrough pain intensity, their type of pain and their duration of pain on all three outcome variables were also examined as secondary hypotheses. Whilst no previous literature was also found that addresses the impact of these pain predictor variables on the outcome variables, the following hypotheses were proposed:

Breakthrough Pain Intensity

S H9 PAIN: Participants' attitudes towards SDM will differ based on their breakthrough pain intensity.

S H10 PAIN: Participants' breakthrough pain intensity will predict their preferred consultation style.

S H11 PAIN: Participants' knowledge of SDM will differ based on their breakthrough pain intensity.

Type of Pain

S H12 PAIN: Participants' attitudes towards SDM will differ based on their type of pain.

S H13 PAIN: Type of pain will predict participants' preferred consultation style.

S H14 PAIN: Participants' knowledge of SDM will differ based on their type of pain.

Pain Duration

S H15 PAIN: Participants' duration of pain will be associated with their attitudes towards SDM.

S H16 PAIN: Participants' duration of pain will be associated with their preferred consultation style.

S H17 PAIN: Participants' duration of pain will be associated with their knowledge of SDM.

Additional Readiness to Change Variables

Although the impact of participants' overall readiness to change was a primary variable, there are also 9 subscales associated with participant's readiness to change: Exercise, Task Persistence, Relaxation,

Cognitive Control, Pacing, Avoid Pain Contingent Rest, Avoid Asking for Assistance, Assertive Communication and Proper Body Mechanics. The impact of these further 9 readiness to change variables on all three outcome variables were additionally examined as secondary hypotheses.

Exercise

Hu et al. (2023) found in their study that patients who exercised often were more inclined to use SDM, suggesting that patients who exercise frequently will have more positive attitudes towards SDM. Therefore, it is expected that:

S H18 READINESS: Participants that have higher exercise scores will have positive attitudes towards SDM.

Researchers (Hu et al., 2023) also found in their study that patients who did not exercise often were more inclined to prefer a passive consultation style. Therefore, it is expected that:

S H19 READINESS: Participants that have lower exercise scores will prefer a passive consultation style.

As Hu et al. (2023) found that patients who exercised often were more inclined to use SDM, this suggests that patients who exercise frequently will have more knowledge of SDM.

S H20 READINESS: Participants that have higher exercise scores will have more knowledge of SDM.

Avoiding Pain Contingent Rest

Bekkering et al. (2003) believes that patients that do not avoid pain contingent rest have more passive attitudes, depending on other people to help control their pain (Jensen, Turner, Romano, & Karoly, 1991). Thus, it is likely they will have more negative attitudes towards SDM. Therefore, it is expected that:

S H21 READINESS: Participants that do not avoid pain contingent rest will have negative attitudes towards SDM.

Researchers (Bekkering et al., 2003) also believe that patients that do not avoid pain contingent rest prefer a passive consultation style. Therefore, it is expected that:

S H22 READINESS Participants that do not avoid pain contingent rest will prefer a passive consultation style.

As Bekkering et al. (2003) believed that patients that do not avoid pain contingent rest have more passive attitudes, depending on other people to help control their pain (Jensen et al, 1991). It is likely they will have less experience and so also less knowledge of SDM. Therefore, it is expected that:

S H23 READINESS: Participants that do not avoid pain contingent rest will have less knowledge of SDM.

Assertive Communication

Researchers (Street Jr, Gordon, Ward, Krupat, & Kravitz, 2005) believed that assertive communication represented patient preference for an active consultation style. Therefore, it is expected that:

S H24 READINESS: Participants that use assertive communication will prefer an active consultation style.

Whilst no previous literature was found that addresses the impact of assertive communication on participants' attitudes towards SDM and their knowledge of SDM, the following hypotheses were proposed:

S H25 READINESS: Participants assertive communication will be associated with their attitudes towards SDM.

S H26 READINESS: Participants assertive communication will be associated with their knowledge of SDM.

Task Persistence

Whilst no previous literature was also found that addresses the impact of participants': task persistence, relaxation, cognitive control, pacing, asking for assistance and proper body mechanics on the outcome variables, the following hypotheses were proposed:

S H27 READINESS: Participants' task persistence will be associated with their attitudes towards SDM.

S H28 READINESS: Participants' task persistence will be associated with their preferred consultation style.

S H29 READINESS: Participants' task persistence will be associated with their knowledge of SDM.

Relaxation

S H30 READINESS: Participants' relaxation will be associated with their attitudes towards SDM.

S H31 READINESS: Participants' relaxation will be associated with their preferred consultation style.

S H32 READINESS: Participants' relaxation will be associated with their knowledge of SDM.

Cognitive Control

S H33 READINESS: Participants' cognitive control will be associated with their attitudes towards SDM.

S H34 READINESS: Participants' cognitive control will be associated with their preferred consultation style.

S H35 READINESS: Participants' cognitive control will be associated with their knowledge of SDM.

Pacing

S H36 READINESS: Participants' pacing will be associated with their attitudes towards SDM.

S H37 READINESS: Participants' pacing will be associated with their preferred consultation style.

S H38 READINESS: Participants' pacing will be associated with their knowledge of SDM.

Avoiding Asking for Assistance

S H39 READINESS: Participants' avoiding asking for assistance will be associated with their attitudes towards SDM.

S H40 READINESS: Participants' avoiding asking for assistance will be associated with their preferred consultation style.

S H41 READINESS: Participants' avoiding asking for assistance will be associated with their knowledge of SDM.

Proper Body Mechanics

S H42 READINESS: Participants' proper body mechanics will be associated with their attitudes towards SDM.

S H43 READINESS: Participants' proper body mechanics will be associated with their preferred consultation style.

S H44 READINESS: Participants' proper body mechanics will be associated with their knowledge of SDM.

Demographic Variables

Demographic variables that might influence acceptance of SDM include age, gender, education level and employment status. In this section, previous research addressing these demographic variables is examined and the secondary hypotheses concerning these demographic variables are proposed.

Age

Mah, Muthupalaniappen, & Chong (2016) found that younger participants had increased preferences for SDM. Other research (Keij et al., 2021) also found that age had both positive and negative impacts on participants' attitudes towards SDM. Therefore, it is expected that:

S H45 AGE: Participants' attitudes towards SDM will differ based on their age group.

Hamann et al. (2012) also found that younger participants preferred a more active consultation style. Therefore, it is expected that:

S H46 AGE: Participants under the age of 50 will prefer a more active consultation style than those over 50.

Keij et al. (2021) additionally found that age had both positive and negative impacts on participants' knowledge of SDM. Other researchers (Holm, Berland, & Severinsson, 2016) also found that patients aged 50 years or older needed more knowledge to help them in making healthcare decisions. Therefore, it is expected that:

S H47 AGE: Participants' knowledge of SDM will differ based on their age group.

Gender

There is some evidence that females are more likely to engage in SDM (Shepherd et al. 2011) than males. Therefore, it is expected that:

S H48 GENDER: Participants' attitudes towards SDM will differ based on their gender.

Similarly, Hamann et al. (2012), Flynn et al. (2006) and Levinson, Kao, Kuby & Thisted (2005) also found that women were more likely than males to prefer an active consultation style. Therefore, it is expected that:

S H49 GENDER: Female participants will prefer an active consultation style.

Torrente-Jimenez et al. (2022) found that women had less knowledge than men of their health condition and of possible treatment options for their health condition. Therefore, it is expected that:

S H50 GENDER: Female participants will have less knowledge of SDM.

Education Level

There is some evidence in the literature that education level might influence acceptance of SDM with more educated people being more accepting of SDM. Zeuner, Frosch, Kuzemchak, & Politi (2015) found that numerous healthcare professionals believed that patients with lower levels of education may have more negative attitudes towards SDM. Therefore, it is expected that:

S H51 EDLEVEL: Participants with a lower education level will have more negative attitudes towards SDM.

Flynn et al. (2006) and Arora and McHorney (2000) also found that more highly educated patients (college degree, university degree or postgraduate degree) prefer an active consultation style compared to less educated patients (high school or some college or university). Therefore, it is expected that:

S H52 EDLEVEL: Participants with a higher education level will prefer an active consultation style.

Chang, Li, & Lin (2019) found that education level influences SDM. Therefore, it is expected that:

S H53 EDLEVEL: Participants' knowledge of SDM will differ based on their highest education level.

Employment Status

There is also some evidence that unemployed people might prefer SDM. Bot et al. (2014) found that patients who were unemployed provided more favourable ratings to SDM. Therefore, it is expected that:

S H54 EMPLOY: Participants who are unemployed will have more positive attitudes towards SDM.

In contrast, Hill and Laugharne (2006) found that participants in employment preferred an active consultation style compared to participants who were unemployed. Therefore, it is expected that:

S H55 EMPLOY: Participants who are employed will prefer an active consultation style.

Meneer et al. (2018) found that increased SDM behaviours in healthcare professionals were influenced by patients being employed. A possible reason given by the researchers for this was that perhaps healthcare professionals assumed which patients might benefit from or prefer SDM, leading to the healthcare professional deciding that SDM was not as applicable for patients what were unemployed. Thus, patients who are unemployed may have less experience and so less knowledge of SDM. Therefore, it is expected that:

S H56 EMPLOY: Participants who are unemployed will have less knowledge of SDM.

Health Related Variables

In addition to demographic variables, a number of health-related variables that might also impact on the acceptance of SDM were considered. These include awareness of SDM, whether participants had made a treatment decision or not regarding their chronic pain and attendance at medical appointments.

Awareness of SDM

While there is no previous literature that addresses whether patients who had previously heard of SDM before completing the study would be more or less accepting of SDM, it seems reasonable to make the following predictions:

S H57 AWARE: Participants' attitudes towards SDM will differ based on their awareness of SDM.

S H58 AWARE: Participants' awareness of SDM will predict their preferred consultation style.

S H59 AWARE: Participants' knowledge of SDM will differ based on their awareness of SDM.

Made a Treatment Decision

No previous literature could also be found that addresses whether patients who had previously made a treatment decision will be more or less accepting of SDM. However, it seems reasonable to predict that:

S H60 TREATMENT: Participants' attitudes towards SDM will differ based on whether they have made a treatment decision.

S H61 TREATMENT: Participants' preferred consultation style will differ based on whether they have made a treatment decision.

S H62 TREATMENT: Participants' knowledge of SDM will differ based on whether they have made a treatment decision.

Attendance at a Medical Appointment

Little et al. (2001) found that patients who had a high attendance at medical appointments were more likely to prefer an active consultation style. Therefore, it is expected that:

S H63 ATT: Participants' attitudes towards SDM will differ based on whether they have attended a medical appointment.

S H64 ATT: Participants who attend a medical appointment will prefer an active consultation style.

Scherr et al. (2022) stated that in order for patients to completely take part in SDM, they must have knowledge regarding their treatment options and their health condition, and they must possess the skills needed to take part in the medical appointment. Thus, suggesting that patients can only experience SDM and so have knowledge of SDM from taking part in SDM in a medical appointment. Therefore, it is expected that:

S H65 ATT: Participants who have attended a medical appointment will have more knowledge of SDM.

5.4 Methods

5.4.1. Design

The study used an online survey design to investigate the predictors of acceptance of SDM by individuals with chronic pain. The study adopted a correlational and regression design, looking at the impact of varied demographic and health related variables on acceptance of SDM. Several aspects of acceptance of shared decision making were of interest in the current study, including participants' preferred consultation style, participants' attitudes towards SDM and participants' knowledge of SDM.

5.4.2. Participants

The intended sample size was 110 participants. This is based on similar studies such as Nielson et al. (2008) which implemented the Multidimensional Pain Readiness to Change Questionnaire (MPRCQ2) for clinical samples which were recruited from a Fibromyalgia Day Program (n = 139) and an Arthritis Day Program (n = 51), as well as 2 survey samples with pain resulting from either a spinal cord injury (n = 127) or an amputation (n = 120). The average from this sample size results in 109 participants for each health condition. As the current sample consisted only of chronic pain patients, 100 to 110 participants would have sufficed for the current study.

The final sample size was 195 participants. A total of 454 participants clicked onto or began the survey, although 195 participants completed the full survey (42.95% completion rate). Most participants were female n=169 (86.7%) with fewer male participants, n=26 (13.3%). All participants experienced chronic pain.

5.4.3. Materials

The online survey was created and administered using the online esurvey software. The online survey was composed of the following scales: the Chronic Pain Assessment Questionnaire (CPAQ) (Portenoy et al., 2006); readiness to change was assessed by the Multidimensional Pain Readiness to Change Questionnaire (MPRCQ2) (Nielson et al., 2008); decisional needs were assessed by the Decisional Needs Assessment Questionnaire (DNAQ) (Jacobsen et al., 2013).

5.4.4. Procedure

An e-mail with the link to the online survey (see Appendix G) was sent to various chronic pain charities/local community groups for individuals with chronic pain to complete in their own time. Information regarding the study, including a link to the online survey, was also shared on Facebook and Twitter. The first section of the survey assesses individuals' experiences of chronic pain and consequently the questionnaire could only be completed by patients who have chronic pain. When participants clicked onto the survey, they were presented with an information sheet (see Appendix H) and a consent form (see Appendix I) before they could complete the survey. After participants completed the survey, they were presented with a debrief sheet (see Appendix J). The survey was open from 13/09/2019 to 16/03/2020.

Paper copies of the questionnaire were also made available for participants who preferred this format (see Appendix G). Participant information sheets (see Appendix H), consent forms (see Appendix I), details of the study and paper copies of the survey were sent on to the relevant chronic pain charities and community group sites for staff to send onto individuals with chronic pain via newsletters, email, in person at community events and by sharing on online chronic pain pages and groups. Only one participant completed a paper copy of the survey, and they were emailed a debrief sheet (see Appendix J) upon completion.

5.4.5. Outcome Variables

SDM was measured in a number of ways in the current study including: participants' preferred consultation style, participants' attitudes towards SDM and participants' knowledge of SDM. Participants' attitudes towards SDM was identified as being the primary outcome variable for the current study. However, examining the relationships between each of the outcome variables were also primary hypotheses for the current study. Durand et al., (2017) developed a number of measures that were adapted for use in this study: attitudes towards SDM, knowledge of SDM and preferred consultation style. The main adaptation for use in this study was to change the wording of items from the healthcare professional's views to the patients' views as the original items were developed for medical students whereas the items have been adapted for use with patients in the current study. For example, when asked "How do you think healthcare decisions should be made?", one of the original responses was "The patient should make the final decision about which treatment she/he would receive" but for the current study, this response was adapted to read "The healthcare professional should make the final decision about which treatment I receive". Details of the original measures can

be found in the supplementary materials attached to Durand et al.'s paper. More details of how the original measures were adapted for use in the current study are outlined below.

Preferred Consultation Style

Preferred consultation style was assessed using a single-item measure that was also developed by Durand et al. (2017) and used by Yen et al. (2019). This asks: "How do you think healthcare decisions should be made?". There are five possible responses: 1) As the patient, I should make the final decision about which treatment I should receive; 2) As the patient, I should make the final decision about which treatment I should receive after seriously considering my healthcare professional's opinion; 3) The healthcare professional should share responsibility with me for making the final decision about the treatment I should receive; 4) The healthcare professional should make the final decision about which treatment I should receive after seriously considering my opinion; 5) The healthcare professional should make the final decision about which treatment I should receive. Higher scores were linked to less favourable attitudes towards SDM.

Active or passive style

For the purposes of the current study, this single-item measure was also converted to a binary variable, active or passive, where participants who responded 1, 2 or 3 were considered as preferring an active consultation style, while participants responding 4 or 5 were considered as preferring a passive consultation style.

Attitudes towards SDM

In order for patients to buy into/adopt shared decision making, they need to have positive attitudes towards it. Durand et al. (2017) developed a measure of attitudes for medical students, but due to concerns about the reliabilities of some items, this was adapted for the participants in the current study.

Cronbach's alpha reliability score for the original 6-item version of the attitudes scale was 0.384 indicating that the attitudes scale items had unacceptable internal consistency. However, when the 1st, 4th and 5th items are removed from the attitudes scale, the Cronbach's alpha reliability score using items 2, 3, & 6 are increased to .617 which was acceptable. Therefore, only responses to these 3 items were included in the attitudes towards SDM analyses (see Table 2 below).

Three out of the original six items were used for the analysis for this study (see Table 2 below). Responses were presented on a 4-point scale where 1 meant strongly agree and 4 meant strongly disagree. Participants gained a point if they responded either disagree or strongly disagree to the three items listed in Table 2 below. Positive responses to the items i.e. agree or strongly agree were awarded 0 points. Thus, possible scores ranged from 0 to 3 with a higher attitudes score indicating a more favourable attitude towards shared decision-making.

Table 2

Items on Attitude scale

2	Doing shared decision-making is unrealistic because it takes too much time.
3	Doing shared decision-making is low on my priority list.
6	Patients should trust clinicians to make all decisions on their behalf.

Knowledge of SDM

The knowledge scale was also developed by Durand et al., (2017) to assess participants' knowledge of SDM. This assesses participants' understanding of the ideas behind SDM. There were 16 items in the original scale. An additional item (item 16 in the current study) was added to the knowledge scores to give a more balanced and unbiased framing to the knowledge items as in the original study only "A majority of patients do not want to engage in shared decision making with their clinician." was included. 3 items were also not included in this study as in the original study (Yen et al., 2019) these are described as risk communication items instead of knowledge items.

As Table 3 shows below, the Cronbach's alpha reliability score for the 14-item knowledge scale was 0.302 indicating that the knowledge scale items also had unacceptable internal consistency. However, when the 1st, 5th, 6th, 7th, 8th, 9th, 11th, 12th, 13th, 15th and 17th items are removed from the knowledge scale, the Cronbach's alpha reliability score increases to 0.455. Although this still indicates an unacceptable internal consistency, it is the highest internal consistency score, therefore these 6 items were included in the analyses for knowledge of SDM. Response options were true or false. The total possible scores range from 0 to 6 with 6 reflecting very good knowledge of the principles of shared decision making.

Table 3

Items on Knowledge Scale

	6 item Knowledge Scale
2	Shared decision-making causes patients to feel uncertain about their decisions.
3	Shared decision-making increases patient decision regret.
4	Shared decision-making results in fewer patients choosing major surgery.
10	There is no need for the clinician to check the patient's understanding.
14	A majority of patients do not want to engage in shared decision-making with their clinician.
16	A majority of clinicians do not want to engage in shared decision-making with their patients.

5.4.6. Predictor Variables

Predictor Variables in the current study were measured using the Chronic Pain Assessment Questionnaire, Multidimensional Pain Readiness to Change Questionnaire (MPRCQ2) and the Decisional Needs Assessment Questionnaire (DNAQ).

Chronic Pain Assessment Questionnaire

The Chronic Pain Assessment Questionnaire (Portenoy et al., 2006) was used to measure varied aspects of patient health and chronic pain. The first set of questions in the Chronic Pain Assessment Questionnaire asked basic questions about patient information including demographic question and health questions such as age; gender; occupation; highest level of education and if the participant had attended a medical appointment for chronic pain. The Chronic Pain Assessment Questionnaire also asked if the participant had made a treatment decision for their pain.

The next series of questions asked participants if they had experienced pain during the past week or would they have had pain if it was not for the treatment they were receiving and if the pain is present continuously on most days or would the pain persist if not for the treatment they were receiving. Participants who answered “yes” to these items were identified as having baseline pain.

Specific items evaluated location of pain and the duration of pain experienced in weeks since onset. Participants were then asked if they experienced temporary flares of uncontrolled pain as well as baseline pain. Participants that answered “yes” to this item were identified as having breakthrough pain and were asked to identify where they felt this pain. Participants were also asked to rate their pain (baseline and breakthrough pain) on a scale of 0-10 which was divided into three categories (mild,

moderate or severe). Participants who gave a score of 0-3 were classed as experiencing mild severity of pain, 4-6 was moderate and 7-10 was severe. Participants’ baseline pain intensity was identified as being a primary predictor variable.

Employment Status

Participants were asked their occupation. Participants stated their occupation in an open text box (e.g. “Nurse”) for the current study. The responses were then categorised into two groups: Employed or Not in employment to create an employment status variable.

SDM Awareness

SDM awareness was assessed by a one item measure that asked: “Had you heard of shared decision making before completing this survey?”. Responses were either yes or no.

Multidimensional Pain Readiness to Change Questionnaire (MPCRCQ2)

Readiness to change was assessed by the Multidimensional Pain Readiness to Change Questionnaire (MPCRCQ2) (Nielson et al., 2008) which assesses patients’ readiness to adopt various strategies to cope with their pain management. The questionnaire is made up of two sections with the first section addressing the use of adaptive coping behaviours, while the second addressing stopping maladaptive coping behaviours. Participants’ readiness to change was also identified as being a primary predictor variable.

The MPCRCQ2 questionnaire has 69 items across nine scales: exercise, task persistence, relaxation, cognitive control – (diverting attention, coping self-statements, reinterpreting sensations, avoiding catastrophizing, ignoring pain subscales), pacing, avoid pain contingent rest, avoid asking for assistance, assertive communication and proper body mechanics. The subscales, examples of items from each subscale and Cronbach’s reliability scores are shown below in Table 4.

Table 4

The Multidimensional Pain Readiness to Change Questionnaire (MPCRCQ2)

Scale	Example Item	Reliability Score
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Exercise	Walk fast, jog, swim (or use an exercise machine) at least 20 minutes 3 times a week or more.	0.862
Task Persistence	Keep on doing what I want to do despite pain.	0.819
Relaxation	Use imagery to decrease pain.	0.831
Cognitive Control	Distract myself from my pain.	0.925
Pacing	Break up tasks into smaller pieces to get more done.	0.863
Avoid Pain Contingent Rest	Rest when I hurt.	0.912
Avoid Asking for Assistance	Ask for help with chores when I hurt.	0.891
Assertive Communication	Tell people I am close to what is on my mind.	0.920
Proper Body Mechanics	Stand straight when I carry something heavy.	0.835
Total Readiness to Change		0.930

Participants respond to each item on 1-7 scale indicating their intention to use each of the different methods of coping with or managing their pain. The responses for items 1-52 mean:

1 = I am not doing this now, and am not interested in ever doing it.

2 = I might do this someday but I have made no plans to do it.

3 = I will probably start doing this sometime (in the next 6 months).

4 = I have made plans to start doing this soon (within the next month).

5 = I have recently started doing this (within the past month).

6 = I have been doing this for a while (more than 1 month but less than 6 months).

7 = I have been doing this for a long time (at least 6 months).

Participants respond to each item on 1-7 scale indicating their intention to not use each of the different methods of coping with or managing their pain. The responses for items 53-69 mean:

- 1 = I am doing this now and am not interested in ever stopping.
- 2 = I might stop this someday, but I have made no plans to stop doing it.
- 3 = I will probably stop doing this sometime (in the next 6 months).
- 4 = I have made plans to stop doing this soon (within the next month).
- 5 = I have recently stopped doing this (sometime in the past month).
- 6 = I have not done this for a while (more than 1 month but less than 6 months).
- 7 = I have not done this for a long time (at least 6 months).

Mean scores for each of the 9 sub-scales were calculated by summing the scores for each statement in that sub-scale and dividing by the number of items. Sub-scale scores ranged from 1-7. As Table 4 shows above, the Cronbach's alpha reliability score for the readiness to change items was 0.930 indicating that the readiness to change items have very high internal consistency. Alphas for subscales ranged from .819 to .920, indicating good reliability for all subscales.

Decisional Needs Assessment Questionnaire (DNAQ)

Decisional needs were assessed by the Decisional Needs Assessment Questionnaire (DNAQ) (Jacobsen et al., 2013) who worked on assessing patients' and practitioners' decision-making needs. The decisional needs questionnaire measured participants' preparation for decision-making and their decisional conflict. Both participants' preparation for decision-making and decisional conflict were additionally identified as being primary predictor variables for the current study.

Preparation for Decision-making

Table 5

Preparation for Decision-making Items

1	Did you know which options were available to you?
2	Did you know the benefits and risks of each option?
3	Did you know how likely (the chances of) each of the benefits and harms were?
4	Were you clear about which benefits and harms matter most to you?

5	Did you choose without pressure from others?
6	Did you have enough support and advice to make a choice?
7	Did you feel motivated or ready to make the decision?
8	Did you feel you had the ability or skill to make this type of decision?
9	Did you feel sure about the best choice for you?
10	Did you have information on the options, and their benefits and harms?
11	Did you have information on how likely each of the benefits and harms were to occur?
12	Did you get information on what others decide or recommend?

In order to successfully take part in SDM, patients need to feel that they are adequately prepared to make the decision. Jacobsen et al. (2013) also asked patients about this in the Preparation for decision-making questions. Table 5 above shows the original 9 items in the preparation for decision-making scale plus the added 3 items taken from the Steps in Decision-Making section in the original questionnaire as these also seemed like items which measured participants' preparation for decision-making.

“When considering this same treatment decision about your chronic pain (i.e. decided to start, stop, switch, or not use a specific treatment)”:

Response options were yes, unsure or no to all items apart from the first item: “Did you know which options were available to you?” where response options were yes or no. Assuming scoring of 0 for no, 1 for unsure and 2 for yes, possible scores on the preparation for decision-making scale were 0 to 24. Higher scores indicated participants were more prepared to make a healthcare decision.

The Cronbach's alpha reliability score for the preparation for decision-making items when respondents were considering their options scale was 0.91, indicating that the scale items have high internal consistency.

Decisional Conflict

Jacobsen et al. (2013) were interested in the extent to which patients experienced conflict in making difficult health decisions and they developed a set of questions addressing varied behavioural manifestations of decisional Conflict. Table 6 below shows 7 out of the 8 items from the Decisional

Needs Assessment Questionnaire that addressed decisional conflict and that were used for analysis in the current study. The eighth item: “Were you able to play the role you wanted in the decision?” was not included for analysis in the current study as the item didn’t seem to relate to decisional conflict. Participants were asked “When you were thinking about your options for this recent decision.....”. Possible responses were yes or no, if participants answered yes to any item, they scored a point so total responses on the decisional conflict scale varied from 0 to 7. Higher scores indicated participants experience more decisional conflict.

The Cronbach’s alpha reliability score for the reported manifestations of decisional conflict when respondents were considering their options scale was 0.72, indicating that the scale items have acceptable internal consistency.

Table 6

The Decisional Conflict Scale

1	Did you feel worried about what could go wrong?
2	Did you feel distressed or upset?
3	Did you feel like you couldn’t get the decision off your mind?
4	Did you waiver (or keep changing your mind) between the choices that you faced?
5	Did you want to delay the decision?
6	Did you question what was important to you?
7	Did you feel physically or mentally stressed (have tense muscles, a racing heartbeat or difficulty sleeping) about making this decision?

5.5 Results

5.5.1. Descriptive Data

Making Healthcare Decisions

The graph below (Figure 4) shows the number of participants who gave each of the 5 possible responses when asked about how they think healthcare decision should be made. The most popular response was: “As the patient, I should make the final decision about which treatment I should receive

after seriously considering my healthcare professional's opinion" (50.8%), followed by: "The healthcare professional should share responsibility with me for making the final decision about the treatment I should receive" (37.4%). The option with the fewest responses were: "The healthcare professional should make the final decision about which treatment I should receive" (0.5%).

Figure 4. Bar Chart of "How do you think decisions should be made?"

Preferred Consultation Style

The five response options from the "How do you think healthcare decision should be made" question were recoded into a binary variable to reflect patients' preference for active or passive consultation style. The following responses: "As the patient, I should make the final decision about which treatment I should receive"; "As the patient, I should make the final decision about which treatment I should receive after seriously considering my healthcare professional's opinion" and "The healthcare professional should share responsibility with me for making the final decision about the treatment I should receive" were recoded as participants preferring an "active" consultation style, whereas "The healthcare professional should make the final treatment decision after seriously considering my opinion" and "The healthcare professional should make the final decision about which treatment I should receive." were recoded as participants preferring a "passive" consultation style. The vast majority of participants preferred an active consultation style (183; 94%) with relatively few (12; 6%)

preferring a passive consultation style. Responses to this measure therefore suggests that most patients with chronic pain have bought into and are quite accepting of SDM in healthcare.

Attitudes towards SDM

As is shown in table 7 below, the mean score for participants attitudes towards SDM was 2.66 indicating typically positive attitudes towards SDM as the maximum score participants could receive was 4 and higher scores indicated more positive attitudes towards SDM. The standard deviation was 0.64 indicating some variability between attitude scores.

Table 7

Attitudes Descriptive Data

Mean	Standard Deviation
2.66	0.64

Knowledge of SDM

As is shown in table 8 below, the average score for participants' knowledge about SDM was 4.50. Since the maximum score was 6, this suggests that participants had good levels of knowledge about SDM. The standard deviation was 0.99 indicating that there was not much variation between participants' knowledge scores.

Table 8

Knowledge Descriptive Data

Mean	Standard Deviation
4.50	0.99

Readiness to Change

Table 9 below shows the mean scores and standard deviations for each readiness to change subscale along with the total score. The mean score for participants overall readiness to change was 38.12 (7.94). This score indicates on average, each participant employs a greater use of adaptive coping behaviours (or less use of maladaptive ones). Possible mean scores for coping strategy subscales ranged from 1 to 7, with lower scores indicating very little intention of using that coping strategy and higher scores indicating more intention of using that coping strategy. As we can see from the means, participants intended or recently started using most of the adaptive coping behaviours whilst for the maladaptive coping behaviours, avoiding pain contingent rest and avoiding asking for assistance, participants intended to stop using these coping behaviours. Pacing and using proper body mechanics seemed to be the most popular coping strategies employed by participants for managing their chronic pain. Standard deviations highlighted some variability in scores, with highest variability in scores being present for Avoid Pain Contingent Rest, Avoid Asking for Assistance and Assertive Communication. A total coping strategies score was calculated by summing scores from all of the 9 sub-scales.

Table 9

The Multidimensional Pain Readiness to Change Questionnaire (MPRCQ2)

Scale	Example Item	Mean	Standard Deviation
Exercise	Walk fast, jog, swim (or use an exercise machine) at least 20 minutes 3 times a week or more.	4	1.67
Avoid Pain Contingent Rest	Rest when I hurt.	2.70	2.01
Assertive Communication	Tell people I am close to what is on my mind.	4.73	2.09
Task Persistence	Keep on doing what I want to do despite pain.	4.69	1.73
Relaxation	Use imagery to decrease pain.	3.94	1.65

Cognitive Control	Distract myself from my pain.	4.74	1.34
Pacing	Break up tasks into smaller pieces to get more done.	5.27	1.56
Avoid Asking for Assistance	Ask for help with chores when I hurt.	3.22	2.15
Proper Body Mechanics	Stand straight when I carry something heavy.	4.83	1.77
Total Readiness to Change		38.12	7.94

Decisional Conflict

Table 10 below shows the means and standard deviations for participants' decisional conflict. The average score for participants' decisional conflict was 2.78. Since the scores varied from 0 to 7, this score indicates that on average, participants did not experience a lot of decisional conflict when making healthcare decisions.

Table 10

Participants' Decisional Conflict Descriptive Data

	Mean	Standard Deviation
Decisional Conflict	2.78	1.97

Preparation for Decision-making

Table 11 below shows the means and standard deviations for participants' preparation for decision-making. The average score for participants' preparation for decision-making was 17.36. Since possible scores on the preparation for decision-making scale were 0 to 24, this score indicates that on average, participants were well prepared for making healthcare decisions.

Table 11

Participants' Preparation for Decision-making Descriptive Data

	Mean	Standard Deviation
Preparation for Decision-making	17.36	6.78

Pain Duration

Table 12 below shows that the mean score for participants' pain duration was 893.01 weeks indicating that on average, participants had experienced over 17 years of chronic pain. The standard deviation was 4616.18 indicating a lot of variability between participants' pain duration scores.

Table 12

Mean and Standard Deviation for Participants' Pain Duration

	Mean	Standard Deviation
Pain Duration (Weeks)	893.01	4616.18

5.6 Analyses

5.6.1. Primary Hypotheses

In this section, the analyses for the primary hypotheses are presented. Firstly, the relationship between the primary outcome variables: attitudes towards SDM, knowledge of SDM and preferred consultation style, are presented. This is followed by the analyses of the impact of the primary predictor variables that were identified for study 2: baseline pain intensity, readiness to change, decisional conflict and preparation for decision-making, on participants' attitudes towards SDM.

Outcome Variables

The results of the correlational analyses conducted to examine the relationship between the 3 outcome variables are shown in Table 13 below. The strongest correlation was between attitudes towards SDM and knowledge of SDM, although this correlation was weak. Preferred consultation style was significantly but weakly negatively correlated with attitudes towards SDM, but the correlation between preferred consultation style and knowledge of SDM was not significant.

Table 13

Correlations between the Outcome Variables

	Preferred Consultation Style	Attitudes Towards SDM	Knowledge of SDM
Preferred Consultation Style	1	-.163*	-.109
Attitudes Towards SDM	-.163*	1	.193**
Knowledge of SDM	-.109	.193**	1

To explore the relationships between the significant outcome variables further, a series of regressions were also carried out.

P H1 OV. Preferred Consultation Style & Attitudes Towards SDM

A point biserial correlation showed that there was a weak, negative correlation between attitudes and participants' preferred consultation style, which was statistically significant ($r_{pb} = -.163$, $n = 195$, $p = .023$). This suggests that individuals who are more positive about SDM prefer to be more active when making healthcare decisions. A logistic regression was also carried out to further investigate whether participants' attitudes towards SDM could significantly predict their preference for an active or passive consultation style. The logistic regression model was statistically significant, $\chi^2(1) = 3.869$, $p = .049$. The model explained 5.3% (Nagelkerke R^2) of the variance in preferred consultation style and correctly classified 93.8% of cases. Scores for attitudes towards SDM was a significant predictor of preferred consultation style ($p = .033$).

P H2 OV. The Impact of Attitudes Towards SDM & Knowledge of SDM

A Pearson correlation showed that there was a weak, positive correlation was found between participants' attitudes of SDM and their knowledge, which was statistically significant ($r = .193$, $n = 195$, $p = .007$). This suggests that individuals who have more knowledge of SDM tend to have more positive attitudes to SDM. A linear regression was also carried out to further investigate whether participants' knowledge of SDM could significantly predict participants' attitudes towards SDM. The results of the regression indicated that the model explained 3.7% of the variance and that the model was a significant predictor of attitudes towards SDM, $F(1,194) = 7.440$, $p = .007$. Participants' knowledge of SDM statistically significantly predicted their attitudes towards SDM ($B = .193$, $p = .007$).

P H3 OV. The Impact of Preferred Consultation Style & Knowledge of SDM

The point biserial correlation between knowledge and participants' preferred consultation style was not statistically significant ($r_{pb} = -.109$, $n = 195$, $p = .129$). This result was unexpected as it suggests that having an active or passive consultation style is unrelated to knowledge of SDM.

Predictor Variables

In this section, the analyses of the impact of the primary predictor variables (Baseline pain intensity, readiness to change, decisional conflict and preparation for decision-making) on the primary outcome variable, attitudes towards SDM, is presented.

Baseline Pain Intensity

P H4 PAIN. The Impact of Participants' Baseline Pain Intensity on Attitudes towards SDM

As is shown in Table 14 below, the mean scores for attitudes towards SDM was 2.65 (SD=0.69) for participants who had mild baseline pain, 2.71 (SD=0.55) for participants who had moderate baseline pain and 2.61 (SD=0.71) for participants who had severe baseline pain.

Table 14

Participants' Attitudes towards SDM by Participants' Baseline Pain Intensity

	No. of Participants	Mean	Standard Deviation
Mild	26 (13.3%)	2.65	0.69
Moderate	85 (43.6%)	2.71	0.55
Severe	84 (43.1%)	2.61	0.71

To assess whether there were differences in attitudes towards SDM between the different baseline pain intensity groups, a one-way ANOVA was performed. No statistically significant differences were found between the pain groups for attitude scores ($F(2,192) = .497$, $p = .609$), indicating that the intensity of baseline pain experienced by the participant (mild, moderate or severe) did not impact on their attitudes towards SDM.

Readiness to Change

P H5 READINESS. The Impact of Participants' Readiness to Change on Attitude towards SDM

A Pearson correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between readiness to change and attitudes towards SDM, but this was not statistically significant ($r = -.005$, $n = 195$, $p = .940$). Therefore, participants' readiness to change was not significantly associated with their attitudes towards SDM.

Decisional Needs: Decisional Conflict

P H6 DECISION. The Impact of Participants' Decisional Conflict on Attitude towards SDM

A Pearson correlation was carried out to examine the relationship between decisional conflict and attitude towards SDM, but this was not statistically significant ($r = .002$, $n = 195$, $p = .488$). Therefore, decisional conflict was not significantly associated with participants' attitudes towards SDM.

Decisional Needs: Preparation for Decision-making

P H7 DECISION. The Impact of Participants' Preparation for Decision-making on Attitude towards SDM

A Pearson correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between participants' preparation for decision-making and attitude towards SDM. The correlation between participants' preparation for decision-making and attitude towards SDM, was not statistically significant ($r = .048$, $n = 195$, $p = .507$). Therefore, participants' preparation for decision-making was not significantly associated with participants' attitudes towards SDM.

Summary of Primary Hypotheses

To summarise the results of the primary hypotheses, attitudes towards SDM were weakly linked to knowledge of SDM and preferred consultation style, but the correlation between knowledge of SDM and preferred consultation style was not significant. None of the primary hypotheses concerning the impact of the predictor variables on attitudes towards SDM was significant.

5.6.2. Secondary Hypotheses

Numerous secondary hypotheses were also tested and to help keep the findings concise, only the significant results for the tests performed on the secondary variables will be reported in this chapter.

The non-significant results of the analyses involving the secondary variables can be viewed in Appendix K.

Hypotheses Related to the Primary Variables

This section presents analyses which examined the impact of the key predictor variables (baseline pain intensity, readiness to change, decisional conflict and preparation for decision-making) on knowledge of SDM and preferred consultation style.

Baseline Pain Intensity

The only analysis of the impact of baseline pain intensity that was significant was the analysis of baseline pain intensity on knowledge of SDM.

S H2 PAIN. The Impact of Participants' Baseline Pain Intensity on Knowledge of SDM

As is shown in Table 15 below, the mean scores for knowledge of SDM was 4.46 (SD=1.21) for participants who had mild baseline pain, 4.69 (SD=0.89) for participants who had moderate baseline pain and 4.32 (SD=0.98) for participants who had severe baseline pain.

Table 15

Participants' Knowledge of SDM by Participants' Baseline Pain Intensity

	No. of Participants	Mean	Standard Deviation
Mild	26 (13.3%)	4.46	1.21
Moderate	85 (43.6%)	4.69	0.89
Severe	84 (43.1%)	4.32	0.98

To assess whether there were differences in knowledge of SDM between the different baseline pain intensity groups, a one-way ANOVA was performed. There was a statistically significant difference found between the baseline pain intensity groups for knowledge scores ($F(2,192) = 3.108, p = .047$). A Tukey post hoc test revealed that knowledge of SDM was statistically significantly higher for participants who experienced moderate baseline pain intensity ($4.69 \pm 0.9, p = .037$) compared to participants who experienced severe baseline pain intensity (4.32 ± 1.0). There was no statistically significant difference between the mild and moderate groups ($p = .538$) or between the mild and

severe groups ($p = .798$). This indicates that participants with moderate baseline pain intensity had significantly more knowledge of SDM than participants with severe baseline pain intensity. It may be that patients with mild levels of pain do not see the need to find out about SDM, while those with moderate levels do try to find out about SDM. Those with higher levels of pain maybe feel helpless since any knowledge they have has not helped them deal with the pain.

Readiness to Change

Analysis of the primary hypothesis showed that readiness to change did not impact on attitudes to SDM, but a significant correlation was found between participants' overall readiness to change and knowledge of SDM.

S H4 READINESS. The Impact of Participants' Readiness to Change on Knowledge of SDM

A Pearson correlation showed that there was a weak, positive correlation between participants' readiness to change and their knowledge of SDM, which was statistically significant ($r = .171$, $n = 195$, $p = .009$). This suggests that individuals who employ a greater use of adaptive coping behaviours (or less use of maladaptive ones) have more knowledge of SDM. A linear regression was also carried out to further investigate whether readiness to change could significantly predict participants' knowledge of SDM. The results of the regression indicated that the model explained 2.9% of the variance and that the model was a significant predictor of knowledge of SDM, $F(1,194) = 5.791$, $p = .009$. Participants' readiness to change statistically significantly predicted their knowledge of SDM ($B = .171$, $p = .009$). Therefore, it seems that patients who want to change their behaviours have greater knowledge of SDM.

Decisional Needs

Decisional Needs: Decisional Conflict

The analysis of the impact of decisional conflict on knowledge of SDM was significant.

S H6 DECISION. The Impact of Participants' Decisional Conflict on Knowledge of SDM

A Pearson correlation found a weak, negative correlation between participants' decisional conflict and their knowledge of SDM, which was statistically significant ($r = -.176$, $n = 195$, $p = .007$).

A linear regression was also carried out to further investigate whether decisional conflict could significantly predict participants' knowledge of SDM. The results of the regression indicated that the model explained 3.1% of the variance and that the model was a significant predictor of knowledge of SDM, $F(1,194) = 6.196, p = .007$. Decisional conflict statistically significantly predicted participants' knowledge of SDM ($B = -.176, p = .007$), showing that individuals who experienced less decisional conflict had more knowledge of SDM.

Decisional Needs: Preparation for Decision-making

Preparation for decision-making was unrelated to knowledge of SDM, but did predict preferred consultation style.

S H7 DECISION. The Impact of Participants' Preparation for Decision-making on Preferred Consultation Style

There was a weak, positive correlation between participants' preparation for decision-making and their preferred consultation style, which was statistically significant ($rpb = .178, n = 195, p = .013$). This suggests that individuals who were more prepared to make a healthcare decision preferred to be passive when making healthcare decisions.

A logistic regression was also performed to further investigate whether participants' preparation for decision-making could significantly predict participants' preference for an active or passive consultation style. The logistic regression model was statistically significant, $\chi^2(1) = 8.502, p = .004$. The model explained 11.5% (Nagelkerke R^2) of the variance in preferred consultation style and correctly classified 93.8% of cases. Participants' preparation for decision-making was a significant predictor of their preferred consultation style ($p = .030$) confirming that individuals who were more prepared to make a healthcare decision preferred to be passive when making healthcare decisions.

Summary of Hypotheses Related to the Primary Variables

To summarise, baseline pain intensity, readiness to change and decisional conflict impacted knowledge of SDM, while preparation for decision-making was linked to preferred consultation style.

Additional Secondary Hypotheses

In this section, additional secondary analyses were carried out looking at the impact of additional pain variables, demographic variables and health related variables on all three outcome variables: attitudes

towards SDM, knowledge of SDM and preferred consultation style. The pain variables were breakthrough pain intensity, type of pain and duration of pain. The demographic variables were age, gender and education level and the health-related variables were awareness of SDM, whether participants had made a treatment decision and attendance at medical appointments.

Additional Pain Variables

The only analysis of pain-related variables that was significant was the impact of breakthrough pain intensity on knowledge of SDM.

Breakthrough Pain Intensity

S H11 PAIN. The Impact of Participants' Breakthrough Pain Intensity on Knowledge of SDM

As is shown in Table 16 below, the mean scores for knowledge of SDM was 3.63 (SD=1.30) for participants who had mild to moderate breakthrough pain and 4.51 (SD=0.93) for participants who had severe breakthrough pain.

Table 16

Participants' Knowledge of SDM by Participants' Breakthrough Pain Intensity

	No. of Participants	Mean	Standard Deviation
Mild to Moderate	8 (4.1%)	3.63	1.30
Severe	149 (76.4%)	4.51	0.93

To assess if this difference was significant, independent t-tests were performed with breakthrough pain intensity as the IV and knowledge of SDM as the DV. Knowledge scores were found to be significantly higher in the group who had severe breakthrough pain intensity (4.51) than those who had mild to moderate breakthrough pain intensity (3.63) [$T(155) = -2.574, p = .011$], indicating that participants who had severe breakthrough pain intensity had significantly more knowledge of SDM compared to participants who had mild to moderate breakthrough pain intensity. It should be pointed out however that the number of participants in the group with mild to moderate pain was low.

Additional Readiness to Change Variables

To explore the relationships between the individual subscales of readiness to change and knowledge of SDM in more detail, correlations and regressions were carried out between all readiness to change subscales and knowledge of SDM. As discussed below, significant correlations were found between the exercise, cognitive control and pacing sub-scales and knowledge of SDM, but no other correlations were significant.

Exercise

S H20 READINESS. The Impact of Participants' Exercise on Knowledge of SDM

A Pearson correlation found that there was a statistically significant, but weak, positive correlation between participants' exercise and their knowledge of SDM ($r = .190$, $n = 195$, $p = .004$). A linear regression was also carried out to further investigate whether exercise could significantly predict participants' knowledge of SDM. The results of the regression indicated that the model explained 3.6% of the variance and that the model was a significant predictor of knowledge of SDM, $F(1,194) = 7.211$, $p = .004$. Exercise statistically significantly predicted participants' knowledge of SDM ($B = .190$, $p = .004$). This suggests that individuals who exercise more to cope with their chronic pain have more knowledge of SDM.

Cognitive Control

S H35 READINESS. The Impact of Participants' Cognitive Control on Knowledge of SDM

A Pearson correlation found a statistically significant but weak, positive correlation between participants' cognitive control and their knowledge of SDM ($r = .152$, $n = 195$, $p = .034$). A linear regression was also carried out to further investigate whether cognitive control could significantly predict participants' knowledge of SDM. The results of the regression indicated that the model explained 2.3% of the variance and that the model was a significant predictor of knowledge of SDM, $F(1,194) = 4.561$, $p = .034$. Cognitive control statistically significantly predicted participants' knowledge of SDM ($B = .152$, $p = .034$). This suggests that individuals who use more cognitive control strategies, such as diverting their attention, using coping self-statements, re-interpreting sensations, avoiding catastrophising and ignoring pain, to cope with their chronic pain have more knowledge of SDM.

Pacing

S H38 READINESS. The Impact of Participants' Pacing on Knowledge of SDM

A Pearson correlation found a weak, positive correlation between participants' pacing and their knowledge of SDM, which was statistically significant ($r = .254, n = 195, p < .001$). A linear regression was also carried out to further investigate whether pacing could significantly predict participants' knowledge of SDM. The results of the regression indicated that the model explained 6.5% of the variance and that the model was a significant predictor of knowledge of SDM, $F(1,194) = 13.326, p < .001$. Pacing statistically significantly predicted participants' knowledge of SDM ($B = .254, p < .001$). This suggests that individuals who pace themselves more to cope with their chronic pain have more knowledge of SDM.

Demographic Variables

Two analyses concerning the impact of demographic variables showed significant results. The first was the impact of participants' age on preferred consultation style and the second was the impact of education level on attitudes towards SDM.

Age

S H46 AGE. The Impact of Participants' Age on Preferred Consultation Style

Table 17 below shows participants' active or passive preference for involvement as a function of their age group.

Table 17

Preference for Involvement by Participants Age Group

	Active	Passive	Total
Under 50 years old	97	10	107
50+ years old	86	2	88
Total	183	12	195

A chi-square test of independence was performed to examine the relation between participant's age groups and preference for involvement. The relation between these variables was significant, $\chi^2(1, N = 195) = 4.183, p = .021$, indicating that participants who were under 50 years of age preferred a more

passive role in health decision-making. This shows that younger people prefer their GP to make healthcare decisions for them.

Education Level

S H51 EDLEVEL. The Impact of Education Level on Attitudes towards SDM

Table 18 below shows that scores for attitudes towards SDM was higher for participants with a higher education level (2.76; SD=0.50) than for participants with a lower education level (2.50; SD=0.79).

Table 18

Participants' Attitudes towards SDM by Participants' Highest Education Level

	No. of Participants	Mean	Standard Deviation
Lower education level	78 (40.0%)	2.50	0.79
Higher education level	117 (60.0%)	2.76	0.50

To find out if this difference in attitudes was significant, an independent t-test was performed. Attitude scores were found to be significantly higher for participants who had a higher education level than participants who had a lower education level, [$T(193) = -2.827, p = .003$], indicating that more educated participants (university level and above) had significantly more positive attitudes towards SDM than those who were less educated (college level and below).

Health Related Variables

In addition to demographic variables, a number of health-related variables that might also impact on the acceptance of SDM were considered. These include awareness of SDM, whether participants had made a treatment decision or not regarding their chronic pain and attendance at medical appointments.

Awareness of SDM

S H57 AWARE. The Impact of Participants' Awareness of SDM on Attitudes towards SDM

As Table 19 below shows, the vast majority of participants (70.8%) were aware of SDM before taking the survey.

Table 19

Participants' Awareness of Shared Decision-making

	No. of Participants	Mean Attitude score	Standard Deviation
Previous Awareness of SDM	138 (70.8%)	2.72	0.53
No Previous Awareness of SDM	57 (29.2%)	2.51	0.85

Table 19 also shows mean attitude scores for those who had or had not heard of SDM. To assess if there was a difference in participants' attitudes towards SDM as a result of their previous awareness of SDM, an independent t-test was performed. Attitude scores were found to be significantly higher for participants who had previously heard about SDM (2.72) than participants who had not heard of SDM before taking the survey (2.51), [$T(193) = 2.081, p = .039$], indicating that participants who had previously heard about SDM before taking the survey had significantly more positive attitudes towards SDM than participants who had not heard of SDM before taking the survey.

S H59 AWARE. The Impact of Participants' Awareness of SDM on Knowledge of SDM

As Table 20 below shows, the mean scores for participants' knowledge of SDM was 4.61 (SD=0.88) for those with a previous awareness of SDM and 4.25 (SD=1.17) for those with no previous awareness of SDM.

Table 20

Participants' Knowledge of SDM by Awareness of Shared Decision-making

	No. of Participants	Mean Knowledge Score	Standard Deviation
Previous Awareness of SDM	138 (70.8%)	4.61	0.88
No Previous Awareness of SDM	57 (29.2%)	4.25	1.17

To assess if there was a difference in participants' knowledge of SDM as a result of previous awareness of SDM, an independent t-test was performed. Knowledge scores were found to be significantly higher for participants that had previously heard about SDM before taking the survey (4.61) than participants who had not heard of SDM before taking the survey (4.25). [$T(193) = 2.365, p = .019$], indicating that participants that had previously heard about SDM before taking the survey had significantly more knowledge of SDM than participants who had not heard of SDM before taking the survey.

Made a Treatment Decision

S H60 TREATMENT. The Impact of Whether Participants Had Made a Treatment Decision on Attitudes towards SDM

As is shown in Table 21 below, the mean scores for attitudes towards SDM was 2.71 (SD=0.55) for participants who had made a treatment decision and 2.49 (SD=0.84) for participants who had not made a treatment decision.

Table 21

Participants' Attitudes towards SDM by Whether Participants Had Made a Treatment Decision

	No. of Participants	Mean	Standard Deviation
Made a treatment decision	146 (74.9%)	2.71	0.55
Not made a treatment decision	49 (25.1%)	2.49	0.84

To assess if there was a difference in attitudes towards SDM for the participants who made a treatment decision and who had not made a treatment decision, independent t-tests were performed. Attitude scores were found to be significantly higher for participants who had made a treatment decision (2.71) than participants who had not made a treatment decision (2.49), [$T(193) = 2.118, p = .035$], indicating that participants who had made a treatment decision had significantly more positive attitudes towards SDM than participants who had not made a treatment decision.

S H62 TREATMENT. The Impact of Whether Participants Had Made a Treatment Decision on Knowledge of SDM

As is shown in Table 22 below, the mean scores for knowledge of SDM was 4.59 (SD=0.94) for participants who had made a treatment decision and 4.24 (SD=1.07) for participants who had not made a treatment decision.

Table 22

Participants' Knowledge of SDM by Whether Participants Had Made a Treatment Decision

	No. of Participants	Mean	Standard Deviation
Made a treatment decision	146 (74.9%)	4.59	0.94
Not made a treatment decision	49 (25.1%)	4.24	1.07

To assess if there was a difference in knowledge of SDM for the participants who made a treatment decision and who had not made a treatment decision, independent t-tests were performed. Knowledge scores were found to be significantly higher in the group who had made a treatment decision (4.59) than those who had not made a treatment decision (4.24), [$T(193) = 2.133, p = .034$], indicating that participants who made a treatment decision had significantly more knowledge of SDM compared to participants who had not made a treatment decision.

Attendance at a Medical Appointment

S H65 ATT. The Impact of Attendance at a Medical Appointment on Knowledge of SDM

Table 23 below shows mean scores for knowledge for participants who attended a medical appointment for their chronic pain compared with those who did not.

Table 23

Participants' Knowledge of SDM by Attendance of a Medical Appointment

	No. of Participants	Mean	Standard Deviation
Attended a medical appointment	181 (53.4%)	4.46	0.99
Did not attend a medical appointment	14 (46.6%)	5.00	0.78

To assess if there was a difference in knowledge of SDM for the participants who attended medical appointments and who did not attend medical appointments, independent t-tests were performed. Knowledge scores were found to be significantly higher in the group who had not attended a medical

appointment (5.00) than those who had attended a medical appointment (4.46), [$T(193) = -1.973, p = .025$], indicating that, contrary to our prediction, participants who had not attended a medical appointment had significantly more knowledge of SDM compared to participants who had attended a medical appointment. This may suggest that those who had not attended a medical appointment referred to other sources of information to acquire knowledge about SDM to control their pain.

Summary of Additional Secondary Hypotheses

To summarise the results from the additional secondary hypotheses, education level, awareness of SDM, and having made a treatment decision all had a significant impact on attitudes towards SDM.

Breakthrough pain intensity, exercise, cognitive control, pacing, awareness of SDM, having made a treatment decision and attendance at a medical appointment had a significant impact on knowledge of SDM. Age had a significant impact on preferred consultation style.

5.7 Discussion

The current study aimed to investigate factors that impact on acceptance of SDM in individuals with chronic pain. Acceptance of SDM was assessed using 3 measures that had previously been reported in the literature: preferred consultation style, attitudes towards SDM and knowledge of SDM.

5.7.1. Primary Hypotheses

Relationships Between the Measures of Acceptance of Shared Decision-making

The first set of primary analyses looked at the relationships between the three outcome variables to try and get a better understanding of constructs that impact on the acceptance or rejection of SDM. Correlational and regression analysis showed that the strongest relationship was a positive correlation between attitudes towards SDM and knowledge of SDM, although this was still a relatively weak correlation. This suggests that individuals who have more knowledge of SDM, such as the benefits of taking part in SDM, will feel more positively about SDM. This result reflected the findings of Pollard et al. (2015) who found that patients' knowledge and a positive attitude towards SDM were frequently cited facilitators for carrying out SDM. However, this result was not in line with Mathijssen et al.'s (2020) finding that whilst healthcare professionals had decreased knowledge of SDM, they still had

positive attitudes towards SDM as the current study's finding was that participants (patients) that had decreased knowledge of SDM had negative attitudes towards SDM.

Participants' attitudes towards SDM were also significantly, but negatively, associated with their preferred consultation style. This suggests that individuals who have more positive attitudes to SDM will also prefer to play a more active role when making healthcare decisions. This result is in line with Charles et al. (1997) and Carlsen and Aakvik's (2006) findings that also found that there was an association between preferred consultation style and attitudes towards SDM.

Thus, attitudes towards SDM were linked to knowledge of SDM and preferred consultation style, suggesting that attitudes did provide a reasonable measure of acceptance of SDM as initially proposed. However, as noted previously, whilst the analyses between attitudes towards SDM and knowledge of SDM and attitudes towards SDM and preferred consultation style were referred to as being significant results, this may not have been the case had adjustments been made for multiple comparisons. Knowledge of SDM and preferred consultation style were not related. This finding was unexpected and contrary to predictions as it was predicted that there would be a significant association between all of the outcome variables but perhaps this result was to be expected as there was no previous literature which could be found that cited an association between knowledge of SDM and preferred consultation style

Impact of Predictor Variables on Attitudes towards Shared Decision-making

In addition to examining the relationships between the measures of acceptance of SDM, a further set of primary hypotheses was considered that focused on key variables identified in the literature as the most important and interesting variables for patients making decisions about coping with pain. These were: baseline pain intensity, readiness to change, decisional conflict and preparation for decision-making. Since attitudes towards SDM was viewed as a key outcome variable, the next set of primary hypotheses focused on the impact of these variables on attitudes to SDM.

Despite our view that attitudes towards SDM was a useful outcome variable in looking at SDM, the analyses revealed that none of the predictor variables was significantly related to attitudes towards SDM. Although previous studies by Strong et al. (1992) and Kerns et al. (1997) had suggested that persistent baseline levels of pain should be examined in looking at patients' attitudes to chronic pain, in the current study, the intensity of baseline pain did not impact on attitudes towards SDM. Also contrary to predictions and to Keij et al. (2021), the primary hypothesis that readiness to change would be associated with attitudes towards shared decision-making was not supported.

Similarly, the two primary variables based on participants' decisional needs, decisional conflict and preparation for decision-making were not significantly linked to attitudes. These results were unexpected and not in line with Kremer et al.'s (2007) suggestion that healthcare professionals could decrease patients' decisional conflict through meeting patients' want for SDM and Keij et al.'s (2021) finding which identified five components of patient readiness in their study and the first component was patients' attitudes towards SDM.

To summarise, none of the primary hypotheses, testing the impact of key variables relating to patients' baseline pain intensity, their readiness to change and their decisional needs, on attitudes towards SDM was supported.

5.7.2. Secondary Hypotheses

Secondary Hypotheses Relating to the Primary Variables

In testing the impact of the key predictor variables on knowledge of SDM and preferred consultation style, the outcome variable that was related to more of the predictors was knowledge of shared decision-making. Baseline pain intensity, readiness to change and decisional conflict all predicted knowledge of SDM.

Baseline Pain Intensity

Knowledge of SDM was significantly higher for participants who experienced moderate baseline pain intensity compared to those who experienced severe baseline pain intensity. This suggests that participants with moderate baseline pain intensity had significantly more knowledge of SDM than participants with severe baseline pain intensity. Although there was no previous literature on this topic, this finding makes sense as individuals with moderate baseline pain intensity will likely have participated in SDM to help find ways to reduce or manage their pain, thus these individuals have more knowledge of SDM, whereas individuals with severe baseline pain intensity will likely just prefer the doctor to make healthcare decisions because they are in too much pain to participate in SDM, thus these individuals will have less knowledge of SDM. Therefore, this result was consistent with the hypothesis that participants' knowledge of SDM will differ based on their baseline pain intensity.

However, contrary to predictions, baseline pain intensity did not predict preferred consultation style. Although perhaps this result was to be expected as there was no previous literature which could be found that cited a link between baseline pain intensity and preferred consultation style.

Readiness to Change

Readiness to change was also a significant predictor of knowledge of SDM. This suggests that individuals who employ a greater use of adaptive coping strategies (or less use of maladaptive ones) have more knowledge of SDM. This finding makes sense as individuals who use more adaptive coping behaviours have probably learned about using these adaptive coping behaviours through participating in SDM, thus these individuals would have more knowledge of SDM. This result was also in line with Keij et al.'s (2021) finding where they identified understanding of SDM as a component of patient readiness in their study and participants in the study stated that patients must have knowledge of SDM to be ready.

However, contrary to predictions, the correlation between readiness to change and preferred consultation style was not significant, and this contrasted with Campbell & Crawford's (2000) and Miller et al.'s (2010) findings which suggested a possible link between patients' readiness to change and their preferred consultation style.

Decision Needs: Decisional Conflict

With respect to the impact of decisional needs variables, a weak, negative correlation was found between participants' decisional conflict and their knowledge of SDM, and the regression analysis confirmed that decisional conflict was a predictor of knowledge of SDM. This suggests that individuals who experience more conflict in making their health-related decision had less knowledge of SDM. Knowledge of shared decision-making helps to ensure that participants are more aware of the implications of their decisions. This result was in line with Kaplan et al.'s (2014) suggestion that patients who experience less decisional conflict might feel more confident in their decision-making ability. These patients are referred to as being "activated". Patient activation is assessed by their confidence, skill and knowledge in managing their healthcare. Thus, patients who have more knowledge in managing their healthcare (of SDM) will experience less decisional conflict, which is also what the current study found too.

However, contrary to predictions and in contrast with Links et al.'s (2020) finding that higher levels of decisional conflict was linked to a passive consultation style, the correlation between decisional conflict and preferred consultation style was not statistically significant.

Decisional Needs: Preparation for Decision-making

There was a weak, positive correlation between participants' preparation for decision-making and their preferred consultation style, which was statistically significant. The regression analysis also confirmed that preparation for decision-making was a significant predictor of participants' preferred consultation style. This suggests that individuals who were more prepared to make a healthcare decision preferred to be passive when making healthcare decisions. This finding seems unexpected as individuals who were more prepared to make a healthcare decision, one would expect to prefer to be more active in their healthcare decisions because they are prepared to make a healthcare decision, but this was not the case for the current study's findings. Perhaps participants that preferred a passive consultation style felt more prepared to make a healthcare decision because they felt confident in the healthcare professionals' opinion and decisions. However, this result was consistent with the hypothesis that participants preparation for decision-making will be associated with their preferred consultation style. This result was also in line with Kiesler & Auerbach's (2006) finding that there were different levels of support for the positive impacts of providing patients with their preferred amount of information and their preferred involvement in healthcare decisions.

The correlation between participants' preparation for decision-making and knowledge of SDM, was not statistically significant. This result was unexpected and not consistent with the hypothesis that participants that have higher preparation for decision-making scores will have more knowledge of SDM. This finding was also not in line with Keij et al.'s (2021) finding which also identified understanding of SDM as a component of patient readiness in their study.

Summary of the Secondary Hypotheses Relating to the Primary Variables

To summarise, baseline pain intensity, readiness to change and decisional conflict all predicted knowledge of SDM, while participants' preparation for decision-making predicted their preferred consultation style.

Additional Secondary Hypotheses

To summarise the results from the additional secondary hypotheses, education level, awareness of SDM, and having made a treatment decision all had a significant impact on attitudes towards SDM. Breakthrough pain intensity, exercise, cognitive control, pacing, awareness of SDM, having made a treatment decision and attendance at a medical appointment had a significant impact on knowledge of SDM, while age had an impact on preferred consultation style.

Predictors of Attitudes towards SDM

Education level, awareness of SDM, and having made a treatment decision all had a significant impact on attitudes towards SDM.

Education Level

While analysis of the primary variables showed no effects on attitudes towards SDM, education level did impact on attitudes: scores were found to be significantly higher for participants who had a higher education level than participants who had a lower education level. This suggests that participants who had taken part in higher education (university level and above) had significantly more positive attitudes towards SDM and would be more receptive towards SDM than individuals with lower levels of education. This result was in line with the hypothesis and Zeuner et al.'s (2015) finding that numerous healthcare professionals believed that patients with lower levels of education would perhaps have more negative attitudes towards SDM.

Awareness of SDM

Attitude scores were found to be significantly higher for participants who had previously heard about SDM before taking the survey than for participants who hadn't, indicating that participants who had previously heard about SDM had significantly more positive attitudes towards SDM and those participants who hadn't previously heard about SDM before taking the survey had more negative attitudes towards SDM. This finding makes sense as individuals who had heard about SDM before taking the survey will have more awareness of SDM and its benefits, thus these individuals would be more receptive towards SDM, whilst individuals that hadn't previously heard about SDM before taking the survey will have less awareness of SDM and its benefits, thus these individuals would be less receptive towards SDM. Although there was no previous literature on this topic, it seemed reasonable to predict that participants' attitudes towards SDM may differ depending on their awareness of SDM.

Therefore, this result was consistent with the hypothesis that participants' attitudes towards SDM will differ based on their awareness of SDM.

Made a Treatment Decision

Attitude scores were found to be significantly higher for participants who had made a treatment decision than participants who had not made a treatment decision, indicating that participants that had made a treatment decision had significantly more positive attitudes towards SDM than participants who had not made a treatment decision. This finding makes sense as individuals who had made a treatment decision regarding their chronic pain will have more experience of SDM and its benefits, thus these individuals would be more receptive towards SDM, whilst individuals who hadn't made a treatment decision about their chronic pain will have less experience of SDM and its benefits, thus these individuals would be less receptive towards SDM. Although there was additionally no previous literature on this topic, it seemed reasonable to predict that participants' attitudes towards SDM may differ by whether they have made a treatment decision for their chronic pain. Therefore, this result was consistent with the hypothesis that participants' attitudes towards SDM will differ based on whether they have made a treatment decision.

Predictors of Knowledge of SDM

Breakthrough pain intensity, exercise, cognitive control, pacing, awareness of SDM, whether participants made a treatment decision for their chronic pain and whether they had attended a medical appointment, all impacted on knowledge of SDM.

Breakthrough Pain Intensity

Although there was no previous literature which could be found on the topic, knowledge scores were found to be significantly higher in the group who had severe breakthrough pain intensity compared to those who had mild to moderate breakthrough pain intensity, indicating that participants who had severe breakthrough pain intensity had significantly more knowledge of SDM compared to those who had mild to moderate breakthrough pain intensity. This suggest that patients with severe breakthrough pain intensity will probably want to find out more about shared decision-making in order to manage it effectively, compared to those with mild to moderate breakthrough pain intensity. Therefore, this result was consistent with the hypothesis that participants' knowledge of SDM will differ based on their breakthrough pain intensity.

Exercise

Exercise, one of the readiness to change subscales, was a significant predictor of participants' knowledge of SDM, suggesting that individuals who exercise more to cope with their chronic pain have more knowledge of SDM. This finding makes sense as individuals who exercise more to cope with their pain have probably learned about using exercise to manage their pain through participating in SDM, thus these individuals would have more knowledge of SDM. This result was also in line with the hypothesis and Hu et al.'s (2023) finding that patients who exercised often were more inclined to use SDM, suggesting that patients who exercise frequently will have more knowledge of SDM.

Cognitive Control

Cognitive control, another readiness to change subscale, was also a significant predictor of participants' knowledge of SDM. This suggests that individuals who use more cognitive control (i.e. divert their attention, use coping self-statements, re-interpret sensations, avoid catastrophising and ignore pain) to cope with their chronic pain have more knowledge of SDM. This finding also makes sense as individuals that use more cognitive control (i.e. strategies such as redirecting their attention, using coping affirmations, re-interpreting sensations, avoiding catastrophising and ignoring pain) to cope with their pain have probably also learned about using these cognitive control strategies to manage their pain through participating in SDM, thus these individuals would have more knowledge of SDM. Although there was no previous literature on this topic, it seemed reasonable to predict that participants' cognitive control may be associated with their knowledge of SDM. Therefore, this result was consistent with the hypothesis that participants' cognitive control will be associated with their knowledge of SDM.

Pacing

Pacing, also a readiness to change subscale, was a significant predictor of participants' knowledge of SDM. This suggests that individuals who pace themselves more to cope with their chronic pain have more knowledge of SDM. This finding makes sense as individuals that pace themselves more to cope with their pain have probably also learned about using pacing to manage their pain through participating in SDM, thus these individuals would have more knowledge of SDM too. Although there was also no previous literature on this topic, it seemed reasonable to predict that participants' pacing

scores may be associated with their knowledge of SDM. Therefore, this result was also consistent with the hypothesis that participants' pacing will be associated with their knowledge of SDM.

Awareness of SDM

Awareness of SDM had a significant impact on knowledge, with knowledge scores significantly higher for participants who had previously heard about SDM before taking the survey than participants who had not, indicating that participants that had previously heard about SDM before taking the survey had significantly more knowledge of SDM and participants that had not previously heard about SDM before taking the survey had less knowledge of SDM. This finding makes sense as individuals who had heard about SDM before taking the survey will have more awareness of SDM, thus these individuals would have more knowledge about SDM, whilst individuals that had not previously heard about SDM before taking the survey will have less awareness of SDM, thus these individuals would have less knowledge about SDM. Although there was also no previous literature on this topic, it seemed reasonable to predict that participants' knowledge of SDM may differ by their awareness of SDM. Therefore, this result was consistent with the hypothesis that participants' knowledge of SDM will differ based on their awareness of SDM.

Made a Treatment Decision

Knowledge scores were found to be significantly higher in the group who had made a treatment decision than those who had not made a treatment decision, indicating that participants who made a treatment decision had significantly more knowledge of SDM compared to participants who had not made a treatment decision. This finding makes sense as individuals who had made a treatment decision regarding their chronic pain will have more experience of SDM and consequently more knowledge of SDM, whilst individuals who hadn't made a treatment decision about their chronic pain will have less experience of SDM and less knowledge of SDM. Although there was also no previous literature on this topic, it seemed reasonable to predict that participants' knowledge of SDM may differ by whether they have made a treatment decision for their chronic pain. Therefore, this result was consistent with the hypothesis that participants knowledge of SDM will differ based on whether they have made a treatment decision.

Attendance at a Medical Appointment

Knowledge scores were found to be significantly higher in the group who had not attended a medical appointment than those who had attended a medical appointment, indicating that participants who had not attended a medical appointment had significantly more knowledge of SDM compared to participants who had attended a medical appointment. This finding was unexpected and not consistent with the hypothesis that participants that attend a medical appointment will have more knowledge of SDM. This result was also not in line with Scherr et al.'s (2022) statement that in order for patients to completely take part in SDM, they must have knowledge regarding their treatment options and their health condition, and they must possess the skills needed to take part in the medical appointment. Thus, suggesting that patients can only experience SDM and so have knowledge of SDM from taking part in SDM in a medical appointment. However, perhaps a possible reason for participants who had not attended a medical appointment having more knowledge of SDM is that the participants who had not attended a medical appointment perhaps referred to other sources of information (such as Google) to acquire knowledge about SDM to control their pain or perhaps the participants that had attended a medical appointment did not experience/participate in SDM in their appointment thus they didn't have knowledge of SDM.

Predictors of Preferred Consultation Style

Age had a significant impact on preferred consultation style, while other variables were found to be non-significant.

Age

The relationship between participants' age and their preferred consultation style was significant, showing that participants under the age of 50 years old had a preference for a passive consultation style, that is they prefer the healthcare professional to make healthcare decisions for them. This finding was unexpected and not consistent with the hypothesis that participants under the age of 50 will prefer an active consultation style. This result was also not in line with Hamann et al.'s (2012) finding that younger people preferred a more active consultation style. However, it is possible that participants under the age of 50 years old preferring the healthcare professional to make healthcare decisions is that because they are younger, perhaps they do not have as much experience in making healthcare decisions as individuals over the age of 50 years old, thus they prefer to turn to the healthcare professionals' medical knowledge and expertise for making the healthcare decision.

Non-significant Additional Pain Variables

Participants' breakthrough pain intensity did not predict their preferred consultation style nor did their attitudes towards SDM differ by their breakthrough pain intensity. Additionally, neither type of pain nor duration of pain predicted any of the SDM acceptance measures. These results were unexpected and contrary to predictions but there was also no previous literature on these topics which could perhaps explain why these results were not significant.

Non-significant Readiness to Change Subscales

Participants' exercise, cognitive control and pacing were not significantly associated with their attitudes towards SDM nor with their preferred consultation style. These results were unexpected and were also not in line with predictions and Hu et al.'s (2023) findings that patients who didn't exercise often were more inclined to prefer a passive consultation style and patients who exercised often were more inclined to use SDM, suggesting that patients who exercise frequently will have more positive attitudes towards SDM, but this was not the case for the current study's findings. However, for participants' cognitive control and pacing, there was no previous literature on these topics which could perhaps explain why these results were not significant.

Additionally, no other readiness to change subscale i.e., avoiding pain contingent rest, assertive communication, task persistence, relaxation, avoiding asking for assistance nor proper body mechanics were significantly associated with any of the SDM acceptance measures. These results were also unexpected and were also not in line with predictions and Bekkering et al.'s (2003) beliefs that patients that do not avoid pain contingent rest prefer a passive consultation style and patients that do not avoid pain contingent rest have more passive attitudes, depending on other people to help control their pain (Jensen et al, 1991). Thus, it is likely they will have more negative attitudes towards SDM, and they will have less experience and so also less knowledge of SDM, but this was not the case for the current study's findings. These results were also not in line with Street Jr et al.'s (2005) belief that assertive communication represented patient preference for an active consultation style. However, for the other non-significant readiness to change subscales, there was no previous literature on these topics which could perhaps explain why these results were not significant.

Non-significant Demographic Variables

Contrary to predictions and to Mah et al. (2016), Keij et al. (2021) and Holm et al. (2016) age unexpectedly did not impact on attitudes towards SDM or knowledge of SDM. Additionally, no significant differences of participants' education level were found on preferred consultation style or knowledge of SDM. These results were also unexpected and contrary to predictions and to Flynn et al (2006) and Arora & McHorney (2000) who found that more highly educated patients, preferred a more active consultation style compared to less educated patients. However, perhaps the latter result was to be expected as there was no previous literature which could be found that addresses whether patients' knowledge of SDM differ based on their education level. Although it seemed reasonable to predict that there would be a difference in participants' knowledge of SDM based on their education level as Chang et al. (2019) found that education level influences SDM, thus it would make sense for education level to influence differences in knowledge of SDM, but this was not the case for the current study's findings.

Furthermore, no significant gender differences were found for attitudes towards SDM, knowledge of SDM or preferred consultation style. These findings were unexpected and contrasted predictions and with Hamann et al. (2012) who found that being female predicted preference for an active consultation style and Levinson et al.'s (2005) and Flynn et al.'s (2006) findings that women were more likely than males to prefer an active consultation style. These findings also contrast with those of Shepherd et al. (2011) who found that female participants were more likely to engage in SDM, thus it would make sense for female participants to also have positive attitudes towards SDM, but this was not the case for the current study's findings. Additionally, these findings contrast with Torrente-Jimenez et al.'s (2022) finding that women had less knowledge than men of their health condition and for a possible treatment option for their health condition. A possible listed reason for this given by the researchers was that knowledge of SDM could have been decreased for female patients but this was also not the case for the current study's findings.

Finally, participants' employment status was also unrelated to their attitudes towards SDM, their preferred consultation style or their knowledge of SDM. These findings were unexpected and contradicted predictions and Hill and Laugharne's (2006) finding that participants in employment preferred an active consultation style compared to participants who were unemployed and Bot et al. (2014) who found that patients who were unemployed provided a better rating of SDM. These findings are also inconsistent with Menear et al. (2018) who found that increased SDM behaviours in healthcare professionals was influenced by patients being employed. A possible reason given by the researchers for this was that perhaps healthcare professionals assumed which patients might benefit from or prefer SDM, leading to the healthcare professional deciding that SDM was not as applicable

for patients what were unemployed. Thus, patients who are unemployed may have less experience and so less knowledge of SDM, but this was not the case for the current study's findings.

Non-significant Health-related Variables

Participants' awareness of SDM and their attendance at a medical appointment did not predict their preferred consultation style nor did their preferred consultation style differ by whether they had made a treatment decision for their chronic pain. Additionally, participants' attitudes towards SDM did not differ based on whether they attended a medical appointment. These results were unexpected and not in line with predictions and with Little et al.'s (2001) finding that patients that had a high attendance of medical appointments were more likely to prefer an active consultation style and Scherr et al.'s (2022) statement that in order for patients to completely take part in SDM, they must have knowledge regarding their treatment options and their health condition and they must possess the skills needed to take part in the medical appointment. Thus, suggesting that patients can only experience SDM and so have knowledge of SDM from taking part in SDM in a medical appointment. However, for the other non-significant health-related variables, there was no previous literature on these topics which could perhaps explain why these results were not significant.

5.7.3. Limitations & Ideas for Future Research

There were a few limitations surrounding the current study in relation to distribution of certain demographic characteristics. There were a lot more females than males who took part in the current study. Most participants experienced both baseline and breakthrough pain. There also were not a lot of participants who had preference for a passive consultation style. Additionally, the knowledge items did not have an acceptable reliability, but these were included as these were the only knowledge items that could be found in relation to SDM. Also, despite the knowledge items having an unacceptable reliability, most of the significant associations that were found for the current study were between knowledge of SDM and some predictor variables for the current study. Additionally, in retrospect, if the analyses were to be carried out again, then the p-values should be adjusted as discussed previously since multiple testing was carried out. Finally, this study was exploratory in nature which could explain why there was not a lot of significant results but there still were some significant results found regardless.

Ideas for future research include examining a different population such as members of the general population to see if some of the same variables also predict acceptance of SDM. Another area to explore would be other theories and variables which could influence acceptance of SDM and which measure acceptance of SDM as this study was aimed towards individuals with chronic pain and was exploratory in nature. One further suggestion for future research would be to develop and validate a knowledge scale for SDM which has an acceptable reliability score.

5.8 Conclusion

Acceptance of SDM by patients is essential for SDM to be standard practice, as SDM needs to be accepted by everyone involved and viewed as being beneficial and useful. Acceptance of SDM specifically by patients with chronic pain is vital as patients need to self-manage their condition (Mann et al., 2013), and SDM can enable effective evaluation of options and help identify the best one for a patient to help manage their condition.

The purpose of the current study was to use a quantitative approach to investigate the acceptance of SDM in individuals with chronic pain. The results of the study have indicated which factors are important in supporting individuals with chronic pain to accept SDM.

Attitudes towards SDM were linked to knowledge of SDM and preferred consultation style, suggesting that attitudes did provide a reasonable measure of acceptance of SDM as initially proposed. However, none of the other primary hypotheses concerning predictors of attitudes towards SDM was supported. With respect to the secondary hypotheses, three variables: participants' highest education level, awareness of SDM and whether they had made a treatment decision for their chronic pain predicted participants' attitudes towards shared decision-making.

With respect to predictors of preferred consultation style: participants' age and preparation for decision-making were important predictors. The outcome variable that was related to the most predictor variables was knowledge of SDM, with 10 predictors: participants' awareness of SDM, attending a medical appointment, whether participants had made a treatment decision, participants' baseline pain intensity, participants' breakthrough pain intensity, readiness to change (with subscales: exercise, cognitive control, pacing) and decisional conflict.

The identification of these important factors will be crucial to the successful implementation of SDM as this will increase both healthcare professional and patient's knowledge and understanding of what is key in order for patients with chronic pain to prefer an active consultation style, to have positive

attitudes towards SDM and to have more knowledge of SDM. However, as there were a lot of non-significant results, the findings also demonstrate that these were perhaps poor measures of acceptance of SDM and highlight the need for better measures of acceptance of SDM. This is addressed in the subsequent chapter (Chapter 6, Study 3) where the Theory of Planned Behaviour is utilised.

Chapter 6: Investigating the Predictors of SDM behaviour, Preferred Consultation Style and Satisfaction with the Healthcare Decision in the Scottish General Population

6.1 Introduction

6.1.1. Background

Shared Decision-Making (SDM), where patients take more of a role in making decisions about their health care, is an important goal in many modern healthcare systems (Scottish Government, 2016; Smith, 2024). The purpose of study 3 is to investigate the predictors of engaging in SDM in patients in Scotland. The results are of interest as they will indicate which factors are important in supporting members of the general population to engage in SDM. An understanding of this will be crucial to the successful implementation of SDM in Scotland.

The literature review showed that most studies looking at SDM focus only on healthcare professionals (Chung, Juang, & Li, 2019; Hernández-Leal, Pérez-Lacasta, Feijoo-Cid, Ramos-García, & Carles-Lavila, 2021), or on a specific health condition, or a specific population, e.g. Swiss adults aged 65–80 years old (Sak, Rothenfluh, & Schulz, 2017). There was a relative absence of literature on patients' acceptance of SDM compared to healthcare professionals' acceptance of SDM and no studies were identified that looked at predictors of engagement in SDM in members of the general population in Scotland.

Study 2 looked at acceptance of SDM for individuals with a specific health condition, chronic pain. The SDM variables that were examined in Study 2 were preferred consultation style, attitudes, knowledge and awareness of SDM, in addition to pain related variables and demographic variables. The results showed that participants' preferred consultation style, knowledge of SDM and education level, as well as their awareness of SDM and whether they had made a treatment decision predicted attitudes to SDM, while age and preparation for decision-making predicted preferred consultation style. The results also showed that participants' awareness of SDM, attendance at a medical appointment, whether participants had made a treatment decision, participants' baseline pain intensity, participants' breakthrough pain intensity, readiness to change (with subscales: exercise, cognitive control, pacing) and decisional conflict predicted knowledge of SDM.

While study 2 looked at acceptance of SDM for individuals with a specific health condition, study 3 aimed to broaden out the scope of our investigation by looking at predictors of engagement in SDM amongst the general public living in Scotland. Members of the general public may differ from chronic pain patients in their acceptance of and attitudes to SDM. Fenning, Smith and Calderwood (2019) proposed that “a one size fits all” approach to social and health care is not the best route for the NHS or for the individual. Additionally, in their guidance around facilitating SDM and how to implement it as standard practice, the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (2021) recommended that future research should focus on how engagement in SDM may differ between different groups of patients. Consequently study 3 has a specific focus on the general public in Scotland, aiming to identify which factors impact on their engagement in SDM. For SDM to be successfully implemented, both healthcare professionals and patients need to accept and engage in SDM. Thus, the results of this study will aid in the future implementation of SDM with the general population.

Limitations of Study 2 Outcome Measures in Measuring Patients’ Acceptance of SDM

Study 2 suggested that there were limitations in the measures used in assessing acceptance of shared decision-making: preferred consultation style, attitudes towards and knowledge of SDM. Consequently, for study 3, further measures of patients’ engagement in shared decision-making were introduced. An important theory that emerged from the literature review that was of potential interest was the theory of planned behaviour (TPB) (Godin et al., 2008).

6.1.2. The Theory of Planned Behaviour

The theory of planned behaviour (TPB) (Ajzen, 1991) is among the most influential and frequently cited psychological models in predicting human behaviour and pinpoints the controlled elements of decision making (Ajzen, 2011). Socio-cognitive theories such as the TPB have proven to be useful in explaining behaviour and behavioural intention regarding health outcomes. A systematic review carried out by Godin et al. (2008) determined the TBP as the most frequently utilised socio-cognitive theory in the prediction of healthcare behaviours amongst healthcare professionals. The study found that the TPB functioned better and had significantly better predictive utility than other theories such as the Theory of Reasoned Action (Millstein, 1996), the Social Cognitive Theory (I. Ajzen & Fishbein, 1980) and the Protection Motivation Theory (Rogers, 1975). Consequently, the TBP was used as the overarching theoretical framework to examine intentions and behaviour in the area of SDM in study 3. The TPB was not used in study 2, as it did not appear at the time of the initial literature review of relevant theories of SDM in relation to chronic pain. Rather, models that were more specific to the management of chronic pain were relevant instead.

A key element in the TPB is the person's intention to carry out a behaviour (Sheeran, 2002). Intentions capture the motivational elements which influence a behaviour and are signs of how much individuals are willing to try, how much of an attempt they're preparing to apply to carry out the behaviour. The TPB theorizes 3 conceptually separate predictors of intention (see Figure 5 below).

Figure 5. The Theory of Planned Behaviour Conceptual Diagram (Ajzen, 1991)

The first variable concerns attitudes to the target behaviour, which refers to the extent to which an individual approves or disapproves of that behaviour. The second factor concerns the social element, subjective norms, which refers to the perceived social pressure to carry out or not to carry out the target behaviour. The third TPB variable is the extent of an individual's perceived behavioural control. This refers to the individual's perception of their ability to carry out the target behaviour. Perceived behavioural control is most consistent with Bandura's (1977, 1982) construct of perceived self-efficacy, which concerns an individual's judgments of how effectively they can carry out courses of action needed to tackle prospective situations (Bandura, 1982) and perceived behavioural control is sometimes replaced with the term "self-efficacy". Many researchers have used the TPB to understand and predict individuals' intentions to take part in different health-related activities, such as limiting sugar intake (Beale & Manstead, 1991) and exercise promotion (Godin & Shephard, 1990). Ajzen's (1991) review of these studies showed that a large amount of variance in intentions can be explained by these 3 determinants in the TPB.

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Thompson-Leduc et al. (2015) carried out a systematic review of studies that utilised the TPB to assess SDM behaviours amongst healthcare professionals and they confirmed that subjective norms, perceived behavioural control and attitudes were the most frequently identified determinants of healthcare professionals' intention to engage in SDM-related behaviours. They also found that intention was the strongest predictor variable for a healthcare professional to carry out a SDM behaviour.

Engagement in Shared Decision-making

Given the success of TPB with healthcare professionals in these previous studies by Godin et al. (2008) and Thompson-Leduc et al. (2015), the TBP was chosen in the current study to examine whether it would also provide a useful model for understanding SDM in the general population/with patients. Engagement in SDM is what would be considered the target behaviour in the TPB for the current study. Therefore, engagement in SDM is a primary outcome variable for the current study.

Intention to Engage in Shared Decision-making

Since intention in the TPB has three separate predictors: attitudes, social norms and perceived behavioural control (also sometimes referred to as self-efficacy) and Thompson-Leduc et al.'s (2015) systematic review on studies that utilised the TPB to assess SDM behaviours amongst healthcare professionals found that subjective norms, perceived behavioural control and attitude were the most frequently identified determinants of healthcare professionals' intention to engage in SDM-related behaviours, intention was also used as a primary outcome variable in the current study to examine whether participants' attitudes, subjective norms and self-efficacy were also determinants of patients/the general population's intention to engage in SDM.

Thompson-Leduc et al.'s (2015) also found in their study that intention was the most predictive variable for a healthcare professional to carry out a SDM behaviour, therefore participant's intention to engage in SDM was also examined as a predictor variable in the current study to examine whether intention was a predictive variable for patients/the Scottish general population to engage in SDM.

Satisfaction with the Healthcare Decision

An important aspect of patients' views of SDM concerns whether they are happy with the outcomes of taking part in SDM, i.e., how satisfied patients are with their healthcare decision. If shared decision

making is successful, we would expect that patients who advocate and engage in SDM would be happier with the health decisions that they make than those who adopt a more passive style of health decision making. Support for this view comes from Glass et al. (2012) who found that SDM was positively associated with satisfaction with an individual's healthcare decision and Shay and Lafata (2015) who also found that patients who have engaged in SDM are more likely to have higher levels of satisfaction. Consequently, in the current study we chose to look at satisfaction with an individual's healthcare decision as another outcome variable. Following Glass et al.'s (2012) findings, the current study used The Satisfaction with Decision Scale (Holmes-Rovner et al., 1996) to measure participant's satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

Summary of Outcome Variables

Thus, the four outcome variables for the current study are: intention to engage in SDM and engagement in SDM from the TPB, preferred consultation style and satisfaction with the healthcare decision. Intention to engage in SDM, engagement in SDM, and satisfaction with the healthcare decision were new measures of SDM introduced in the current study, while preferred consultation style was one of the measures of SDM that was also used in study 2. We have seen that intention to engage in SDM, engagement in SDM, preferred consultation style and satisfaction with the healthcare decision have all been examined in studies looking at SDM. We will now review studies that have looked at factors that influence participants' shared decision-making.

6.2 Hypotheses

In study 2 multiple factors were found influence participants' acceptance of SDM, such as age, level of and health-related variables. Thus, numerous hypotheses were tested for this current study also. The researcher has already discussed and acknowledged the problems associated with multiple testing in chapter 5. However, the researcher still believed that testing numerous variables was required to identify the predictors of engagement in SDM by members of the Scottish general population in order to address the aims of the research, advance knowledge and to aid the successful implementation of SDM.

To help overcome the potential issue of multiple testing without decreasing the number of variables tested or adjusting the p-values using the methods outlined in Chen et al. (2017), the researcher identified primary hypotheses that convey the impact of key variables on engagement in SDM as well as numerous secondary hypotheses that tested other variables that may also impact on engagement

in SDM, which may also be significant for members of the Scottish general population. However, any significant results which are greater than .001 should be interpreted with caution.

6.2.1. Primary Hypotheses

Given the key role of the theory of planned behaviour in the current study, the six primary hypotheses focused on the TPB variables. The first four hypotheses focused on intention as an outcome variable, looking at the impact of attitudes towards SDM, subjective norms and self-efficacy on intention and two further hypotheses focused on engagement in SDM behaviours, looking at the relationship between intention and engagement in SDM, as well as the impact of all 4 variables: attitudes towards SDM, subjective norms, self-efficacy and intention on engagement in SDM behaviours.

Intention (Outcome Variable)

The first outcome variable to be analysed was participants' intention to engage in shared decision-making. Based on previous research (Godin & Shephard, 1990; Van Ryn, 1990; Beale & Manstead, 1991; & Thompson-Leduc et al., 2015), and consistent with the TPB, it is expected that the traditional TPB variables: attitudes, subjective norms and self-efficacy, will significantly predict intention to engage in SDM. Consequently, each of these variables: attitudes, subjective norms and self-efficacy was examined individually as a predictor of intention to engage in SDM with the following hypotheses.

- **P H1 INT:** Attitudes towards SDM will predict intention to engage in SDM.
- **P H2 INT:** Subjective norms will predict intention to engage in SDM.
- **P H3 INT:** Self-efficacy will predict intention to engage in SDM.

Additionally looking at these 3 variables together, it is predicted that:

- **P H4 INT:** Attitudes towards SDM, subjective norms & self-efficacy will predict intention to engage in SDM.

Predictors of Engagement in SDM

As well as being an outcome variable, intention to engage in SDM may also influence participants' engagement in SDM. Ajzen (1991) also believed that the stronger the intention to perform a behaviour, the more likely it is that the behaviour will be engaged in. Therefore, it is expected that:

- **P H5 ENGAGE:** Participants who have higher scores for intention will have higher scores for engagement in SDM behaviour.

The TPB variables: attitudes, subjective norms and self-efficacy, as well as intention to engage in SDM may also influence participants' engagement in SDM behaviour. Thompson-Leduc et al.'s (2015) systematic review on studies that utilised the TPB to assess SDM behaviours amongst healthcare professionals found that subjective norms, perceived behavioural control (also sometimes referred to as self-efficacy) and attitudes were the most frequently identified determinants of healthcare professionals' intention to engage in SDM-related behaviours. They additionally found that intention was the most predictive variable for a healthcare professional to carry out a SDM behaviour. Therefore, it is expected that:

- **PH6 ENGAGE:** Attitudes, subjective norms, self-efficacy and intention will predict engagement in SDM

6.2.2. Secondary Hypotheses

The researcher also identified further secondary hypotheses relevant to participants' engagement in SDM. These will be discussed in the following order:

1. Relationships between the outcome variables
2. The TPB variables as predictors of engagement in SDM behaviours, preferred consultation style and satisfaction with the healthcare decision
3. Demographic variables
4. Health-related variables
5. Variables from study 2

Relationships Between the Outcome Variables

The TPB was introduced into this study in the hope that intention to engage and engagement in SDM behaviour would provide better measures of SDM than other measures used to assess engagement in SDM. However, two further outcome variables, preferred consultation style and satisfaction with the healthcare decision, were also included as outcome variables in study 3. Preferred consultation style was used as a key measure of SDM in study 2 (Yen et al., 2019), while satisfaction with the healthcare decision was a new variable introduced for study 3 (Glass et al., 2012). Consequently, links between the four outcome variables: intention to engage in SDM, engagement in SDM, preferred consultation style and satisfaction with shared decision-making, were examined in the current study. Since the relationship between intention to engage in SDM and engagement in SDM was discussed as a primary hypothesis, the remaining hypotheses relating to the four outcome variables are:

Preferred Consultation Style

- **S H1 OV:** Participants' intention to engage in SDM will predict their preferred consultation style.

Charles et al. (1997) produced a framework of the SDM process and identified 5 basic characteristics of SDM. An important aspect was the active participation of the patient and the healthcare professional. This suggests that an active consultation style is needed for engagement in SDM. Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H2 OV:** Participants who are more engaged in SDM behaviour will prefer an active consultation style.

Satisfaction with the Healthcare Decision

It seems reasonable to predict that patients who have stronger intention to engage in SDM will be more likely to engage in SDM behaviour (Ajzen, 1991; Thompson-Leduc et al., 2015) which in turn, increases patient satisfaction with the healthcare decision (Glass et al., 2012; Shay & Lafata, 2015). Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H3 OV:** Participants who have stronger intentions to carry out SDM will also be more satisfied with the healthcare decision.

Glass et al. (2012) found that SDM was positively associated with satisfaction with an individual's healthcare decision, Shay and Lafata (2015) also found that patients who have engaged in SDM are more likely to have higher levels of satisfaction. Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H4 OV:** Participants who have higher scores for engagement in SDM behaviour will also have higher scores for satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

Golin, DiMatteo, & Gelberg (1996), Guadagnoli and Ward (1998) and Frosch and Kaplan (1999) all found that patient satisfaction is associated with an active consultation style. Therefore, it is predicted that:

- **S H5 OV:** Participants who prefer an active consultation style will have higher scores for satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

The TPB Variables as Predictors of Engagement in SDM Behaviours, Preferred Consultation Style and Satisfaction with the Healthcare Decision

In addition to looking at the links between the outcome variables, it was also of interest to look at how well the TPB predictor variables: attitudes, subjective norms and self-efficacy, predicted the other outcome measures, i.e. engagement in SDM, preferred consultation style and satisfaction with the healthcare decision. The individual contributions of the TPB predictor variables will now be examined.

Attitudes towards SDM

Based on the TPB (Ajzen, 1991), it seems reasonable to predict that patients' attitude towards SDM will predict their engagement in SDM behaviour and possibly their preferred consultation style. Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H6 ENGAGE:** Attitudes towards SDM will predict engagement in SDM behaviour.
- **S H7 PCS:** Attitudes towards SDM will predict preferred consultation style.

It also seems reasonable to predict that patients' attitudes towards SDM predict their engagement in SDM (Ajzen, 1991) which in turn, predicts patient's satisfaction with the healthcare decision (Glass et al.'s 2012; Shay & Lafata, 2015). Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H8 SAT:** Attitudes towards SDM will predict satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

Subjective Norms

Subjective norms might also influence participants' engagement in SDM. Researchers (Glanz, Rimer, & Viswanath, 2008) state that subjective norms are a key construct in the TPB to carry out particular actions and that the theory of planned behaviour has had a significant impact on practice and research in health behaviours. Joseph-Williams, et al. (2014) also believe that subjective norms is a key "entry level" factor to SDM. Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H9 ENGAGE:** Subjective norms will predict engagement in SDM.

In the context of healthcare, subjective norms influence patients to behave in a manner they think is expected of them by people who are important to them (Brabers, van Dijk, Groenewegen, & de Jong, 2016; Doekhie, Buljac-Samardzic, Strating, & Paauwe, 2020). Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H10 PCS:** Participants who have higher subjective norms scores will prefer an active consultation style.

It seems reasonable to predict that patients' subjective norms will predict their engagement in SDM (Joseph-Williams et al., 2014) which in turn, will also predict their satisfaction with the healthcare decision (Shay & Lafata, 2015). Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H11 SAT:** Subjective norms will predict satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

Self-efficacy

Another factor that may influence participants' engagement in SDM is self-efficacy. Durand et al. (2014) state that engagement in SDM requires self-efficacy and found that SDM interventions significantly increased self-efficacy in disadvantaged groups. Previous research (Coulter, 2012) also states that self-efficacy is required for patient engagement in their healthcare. Additionally, researchers (McCaffery, Smith, & Wolf, 2010) say that the implementation of a behaviour (i.e. engagement in SDM) requires self-efficacy. Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H12 ENGAGE:** Participants who have stronger self-efficacy will be more engaged in SDM behaviour.

Previous research (Chawla & Arora, 2013) found that patients who prefer a passive consultation style had significantly lower self-efficacy compared to patients that prefer an active consultation style. Similarly, previous research (Arora, Ayanian, & Guadagnoli, 2005) also found that patients who had high self-efficacy preferred an active consultation style. Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H13 PCS:** Participants who have higher self-efficacy scores will prefer an active consultation style.

Self-efficacy is also a factor which can influence participants satisfaction with a healthcare decision. Researchers (Molina, Kim, Berrios, & Calhoun, 2015) found that patients who had increased self-

efficacy reported increased patient satisfaction. Other researchers (Zhong et al., 2013) also found that patients reported increased satisfaction when they had increased self-efficacy. Additionally, previous researchers (Kaya et al., 2018) found that COPD patients had decreased healthcare satisfaction and decreased self-efficacy. Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H14 SAT:** Participants who have higher self-efficacy scores will have higher satisfaction with the healthcare decision scores.

Demographic Variables

In this section, previous research addressing demographic variables that might impact on the outcome variables: engagement in SDM, preferred consultation style and satisfaction with the healthcare decision will be examined.

Age

An important factor that might influence participants' engagement in SDM is their age. Previous research (Elwyn et al., 2003) found that participants' engagement in SDM declined as their age increased. Shepherd et al. (2011) also found that younger participants were more likely to engage in SDM, while Singh, Butow, Charles & Tattersall (2010) also found that younger participants had higher SDM scores in consultations. Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H15 ENGAGE:** Younger participants will have higher scores for engagement in shared decision-making behaviour.

Previous research (Schneider et al., 2006) also found that participants are less likely to prefer an active consultation style as they get older and Hamann et al. (2012) found that younger participants preferred an active consultation style. Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H16 PCS:** Younger participants will prefer an active consultation style.

Just as age impacts preferred consultation style, it can also influence participants' satisfaction with the healthcare decision. Jaipaul and Rosenthal (2003) found that patients' age is a factor that tends to yield the strongest relationship with satisfaction. It has also been portrayed that patients who are older are more satisfied with their healthcare (DeVoe, Wallace, & Fryer Jr, 2009) than middle-aged and younger

patients (Quintana et al., 2006; Rahmqvist, 2001; Thi, Briancon, Empereur, & Guillemin, 2002). Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H17 SAT:** Older participants will have higher scores for satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

Gender

Gender is another factor that might impact on engagement in SDM, since females have more experience of making decisions about health-related matters relating to contraception and pregnancy. Researchers (Spies et al., 2006) found that females had higher scores for SDM compared to males. Shepherd et al. (2011) and Fallowfield (2008) also found that women tended to be more engaged in SDM than men. Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H18 ENGAGE:** Female participants will have higher scores for engagement in SDM.

Gender might also predict preferred consultation style. Hamann et al. (2012) found that being female predicted preference for an active consultation style, while Levinson et al. (2005) and Flynn et al. (2006) also found that women were more likely than males to prefer an active consultation style. Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H19 PCS:** Female participants will prefer an active consultation style.

Gender has also been found to impact on participant's satisfaction with their healthcare decision, but men seem to be more satisfied than women. For example, Thi et al. (2002), Quintana et al. (2006), Foss (2002) and (Bener & Ghuloum, 2013) found that males were more likely to be satisfied with numerous aspects of healthcare compared to females (Wessels et al., 2010). Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H20 SAT:** Male participants will have higher scores for satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

Education Level

We might predict that those with a higher level of education will be more likely to engage in SDM. Research by Spies et al. (2006) supported this, finding that participants who had higher levels of education were more likely to have increased SDM scores. Similarly, (Légaré et al., 2011) found that participants who lacked a post-secondary education were less inclined to engage in SDM compared to participants who had a post-secondary education. Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H21 ENGAGE:** Participants with higher levels of education will have higher scores for engagement in SDM.

Education level might also influence participants' preferred consultation style. Flynn et al. (2006) and Arora & McHorney (2000) found that more highly educated patients (college degree, university degree or postgraduate degree) preferred an active consultation style compared to less educated patients (high school or some college/university). Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H22 PCS:** Participants with higher levels of education will prefer an active consultation style.

Additionally, education level can also impact on participant's satisfaction with the healthcare decision. In their systematic review, (Crow et al., 2002) found contradictory evidence relating to this: in five studies higher levels of education were significantly associated with higher levels of satisfaction, but 11 studies found that higher levels of education were significantly associated with lower levels of satisfaction. Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H23 SAT:** Participants with a higher education level will have lower scores for satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

Employment Status

Employment status is another factor which can impact on patients' engagement in SDM. Milky and Thomas III (2020) found that employment status (employed or not in employment) was associated with shared decision-making. Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H24 ENGAGE:** Employment status will be associated with engagement in shared decision-making.

Employment status might also influence participants preferred consultation style. Hill and Laugharne (2006) found that participants in employment preferred an active consultation style compared to participants who were unemployed. Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H25 PCS:** Participants who are employed will prefer an active consultation style.

Whilst there is no previous literature which could be found that addresses satisfaction with the healthcare decision by participants' employment status. However, it seems reasonable to predict that patients' employment status will be associated with engagement in SDM (Milky & Thomas III, 2020) which in turn, will also be associated with satisfaction with the healthcare decision (Shay & Lafata, 2015). Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H26 SAT:** Employment status will be associated with satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

Health-related Variables

In addition to demographic variables, there are also a number of health-related variables that might impact on perspectives on and engagement in SDM. These include frequency of attending medical appointments, self-rated health and the patient's relationship with their healthcare professional.

Frequency of Attending Medical Appointments

Patients' frequency of attending medical appointments/seeing a medical consultant is a variable that might additionally impact on patients' engagement in SDM. It seems reasonable to predict that patients who attend their GP more frequently will have been more exposed to the philosophy of SDM and thus we might predict that engagement in SDM will differ based on frequency of attending medical appointments. Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H27 ENGAGE:** Engagement in SDM will differ based on the frequency of attending medical appointments.

Similarly, we might predict that patients who attend their GP more frequently will have been more exposed to the philosophy of SDM and thus we might predict that frequency of attending medical appointments will predict preferred consultation style. Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H28 PCS:** Participants' frequency of attending medical appointments will predict their preferred consultation style.

With respect to satisfaction with the healthcare decision, Kimman, Dellaert, Boersma, Lambin & Dirksen (2010) state that for patients with breast cancer, especially during the first-year post-treatment when follow-up appointments are more frequent, a more flexible follow-up & SDM process could increase their satisfaction. Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H29 SAT:** Participants who attend medical appointments more frequently will have higher scores for satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

Self-rated Health

Self-rated health is another factor which can influence engagement in SDM. Researchers (Janssen, Ommen, Pfaff, Lefering, & Neugebauer, 2009) found that SDM is associated with better self-rated health and that poor self-rated health is significantly associated with less SDM behaviour. Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H30 ENGAGE:** Participants who have better self-rated health will have higher scores for engagement in SDM.

Levinson et al. (2005) and Flynn et al. (2006) also found that participants who self-rated their health as better (good, very good or excellent) prefer an active consultation style compared to participants in poorer self-rated health (poor or fair). Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H31 PCS:** Participants who have better self-rated health will prefer an active consultation style.

Zhang, Rohrer, Borders & Farrell (2007) found that participants who had lower self-rated health were less inclined to be satisfied with their health care. Similarly, Gupta, Patel & Lis (2015) found that patients with better self-rated health experienced increased satisfaction in relation to their healthcare. Geitona, Kyriopoulos, Zavras, Theodoratou & Alexopoulos (2008) too found a positive association between self-rated health and participants' satisfaction with treatment, again indicating that patients with better self-rated health experienced more satisfaction with their treatment. Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H32 SAT:** Participants who have better self-rated health will have higher scores for satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

Relationship with the Healthcare Professional

As a result of research suggesting that the patient's relationships with their healthcare professional is an important factor in making healthcare decisions, the participant's relationship with their healthcare professional was introduced as a predictor variable in study 3. Deniz, Akbolat, Çimen & Ünal (2021) found that the patients' relationship with the healthcare professional positively impacts SDM, while Eliacin, Salyers, Kukla & Matthias (2015) also characterised the healthcare professional-patient relationship as the basis of shared decision-making. Consequently, it is expected that:

- **S H33 ENGAGE:** Participants who have a more effective relationship with their healthcare professional will also be more engaged in SDM.

The relationship a patient has with their healthcare professional might also influence their preferred consultation style. Eliacin et al. (2015) found that patients who had a better and longer relationship with their healthcare professional preferred a passive consultation style. Previous research (Wrede-Sach et al., 2013) also found that patients who experienced a good relationship with their healthcare professional relied on the healthcare professional for decision-making. Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H34 PCS:** Participants who have a better relationship with their healthcare professional will prefer a passive consultation style.

Prip et al. (2018) found that the patient-healthcare professional relationship can impact patients' satisfaction with their healthcare, while (Qudah & Luetsch, 2019) also report that increased patient satisfaction was associated with positive patient-healthcare professional relationships. Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H35 SAT:** Participants who have a better relationship with their healthcare professional will also have higher scores for satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

Variables from Study 2

Two variables that were found to impact on SDM in study 2 were knowledge of SDM and awareness of SDM.

Knowledge of SDM

Joseph-Williams et al. (2014) found that patients need to know about SDM to engage in it. Similarly, Hawley and Morris (2017) stated that for SDM to be achieved, patients need to have good knowledge. Additionally, Smith, Dixon, Trevena, Nutbeam & McCaffery (2009) found that participants with low health literacy wanted to participate in medical decisions but frequently lacked the knowledge to engage in SDM. Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H36 ENGAGE:** Participants with less knowledge of SDM will be less engaged in SDM behaviours.

Participants' knowledge of SDM might also influence their preferred consultation style. Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H37 PCS:** Knowledge of SDM will predict preferred consultation style.

Stacey et al. (2017) found that decision aids (DAs) increased patients' knowledge of SDM and satisfaction with the healthcare decision (Elwyn, Frosch, & Kobrin, 2015). Other researchers (Makarov et al., 2016) also found that patients who had engaged in SDM had increased knowledge and satisfaction. Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H38 SAT:** Participants who have more knowledge about SDM will also have higher scores for satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

Awareness of SDM

With respect to participants' engagement in SDM, Joseph-Williams et al. (2017) provided a table of suggested solutions to challenges around carrying out SDM and listed increasing patients' awareness of SDM as a recommended solution for carrying out SDM. Previous research (Gravel, Légaré, & Graham, 2006) also found that decreased familiarity with SDM was listed as a barrier to carrying out SDM in five studies. Researchers (DeMeester, Lopez, Moore, Cook, & Chin, 2016) additionally cited

that training and education in SDM which aided healthcare professionals to increase their familiarity with shared decision-making was an organisational driver for SDM. Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H39 ENGAGE:** Participants who have previous awareness of SDM will engage more in shared decision-making.

Since awareness of SDM may also influence participants' preferred consultation style, it is expected that:

- **S H40 PCS:** Awareness of SDM will predict preferred consultation style.

It seems reasonable to predict that patients who have previous awareness of SDM will be more likely to engage in SDM (Gravel et al., 2006; DeMeester et al., 2016 & Joseph-Williams et al., 2017) and this in turn, will increase patient satisfaction with the healthcare decision (Glass et al., 2012; Shay & Lafata, 2015). Therefore, it is expected that:

- **S H41 SAT:** Participants who have previous awareness of SDM will be more satisfied with the healthcare decision.

6.3 Method

6.3.1. Design

The design of the study is a correlational and regression design examining the impact of a range of predictor variables including demographic, TPB and health related variables on the 2 TPB variables: Intention to engage in SDM and Engagement in Shared Decision-making as well as the additional outcome variables: Preferred Consultation Style, and Satisfaction with the Healthcare Decision.

6.3.2. Participants

Overall, 210 participants took part in Study 3. Participants' mean age was 34.19 years ($SD=13.32$). The age ranged from 19 years old to 71 years old. The vast majority of participants, 164 (78.1%), were female, with 46 (21.9%) males. Most participants had a university level education at the undergraduate

level (36.7%), followed by postgraduate level (32.4%). 32 participants (15.2%) had taken part in further education, 13.8% of participants had high school as their highest level of education and 4 participants selected “other”. Responses in the “other” category included: “Not sure”, “None”, “Na” and “Yearly”. The majority of participants (53.3%) were not in employment whilst nearly half (46.7%) were employed.

6.3.3. Procedure and Measures

An online questionnaire was developed using Surveyhero software (formerly known as esurvey). Information regarding the study including a link to the online survey (<https://www.surveyhero.com/s/c5c167f>) was shared on Facebook and Twitter (see Appendix L). When participants clicked onto the online survey, the participant information sheet (see Appendix M) was the first thing they read. Participants could not complete the survey without saying yes to the online consent form (see Appendix N) questions and providing a memorable word/phrase to show they provide consent to complete the survey. At the end of the online survey, participants were presented with a debrief sheet (see Appendix O) telling them further details about the study. Ethical Approval was obtained by the Education and Social Sciences School Ethics Committee at the researchers’ institution (the University of the West of Scotland). Measures used in the online survey to assess the outcome variables and predictor variables are described below.

6.3.4. Outcome Variables

Intention to Engage in SDM

Participants’ intention to engage in SDM is the first outcome variable to be examined from the TPB and was measured in the current study using the same three items that were used in Légaré et al.’s (2013) study. The items were: “I intend to engage in shared decision-making” with possible responses on a seven-point scale ranging from -3 to +3 (strongly disagree to strongly agree); “To me, to engage in shared decision-making would be...” with possible responses on a seven-point scale ranging from -3 to +3 (very unlikely to very likely); and “I believe that my chances to engage in shared decision-making are...” with possible responses on a seven-point scale ranging from -3 to +3 (very low to very high). Possible scores ranged from -9 to 9. A higher score for these items (intention) indicates an increased intention to engage in SDM. Cronbach’s alpha reliability score for the intention to engage in SDM scale was 0.806, indicating that the intention to engage in SDM scale items have very good

internal consistency. Intention to engage in SDM was a primary outcome and predictor variable for the current study.

Engagement in SDM Behaviour

Engagement in SDM behaviour is the second outcome variable to be examined in this study. It is important to note that this variable assesses SDM behaviour in the TBP and was measured in the current study using the 9-item Shared Decision-Making Questionnaire (SDM-Q-9) (Kriston et al., 2010) (see Appendix L). Example items are: “My doctor wanted to know exactly how I want to be involved in making the decision” and “My doctor and I selected a treatment option together”. Each item was rated on a six-point scale which ranged from 1= “Completely Disagree” to 6= “Completely Agree”. Possible overall scores ranged from 9 to 54, with a higher score indicating more engagement in SDM behaviours. Only participants who had made a treatment decision in the past year could complete this scale as only patients who engaged in decision-making behaviour regarding their healthcare could answer these questions. Cronbach’s alpha reliability score for the SDM behaviour scale was 0.944 showing that these items have excellent internal consistency. Engagement in SDM behaviour was also a primary outcome variable for the current study.

Preferred Consultation Style

As in study 2 patients’ preferred consultation style was assessed using a single-item measure (Yen et al., 2019) which asked: “How do you think healthcare decisions should be made?”. There are five possible responses: 1) As the patient, I should make the final decision about which treatment I should receive; 2) As the patient, I should make the final decision about which treatment I should receive after seriously considering my healthcare professional's opinion; 3) The healthcare professional should share responsibility with me for making the final decision about the treatment I should receive; 4) The healthcare professional should make the final decision about which treatment I should receive after seriously considering my opinion; 5) The healthcare professional should make the final decision about which treatment I should receive. Higher scores were linked to less favourable attitudes towards SDM.

Active or Passive Consultation Style

For the purposes of the current study, participants were considered as preferring an active consultation style if they responded 1, 2 or 3 to Yen et al.’s (2019) single item measure and as preferring a passive consultation style if they answered 4 or 5. Consequently preferred consultation style was recoded as active or passive.

Satisfaction with the Healthcare Decision

The current study used the 6 item Satisfaction with Decision Scale (Holmes-Rovner et al., 1996) (see Appendix L) to measure participants' satisfaction with the healthcare decision, another outcome variable. An example item is: "I am satisfied that I was adequately informed about the issues important to the decision." Decisions were made on a 5-point scale from "Strongly disagree" to "Strongly agree". Possible scores were 6 to 30. Higher scores indicate greater satisfaction with the participants' healthcare decision. As with engagement in SDM behaviours, only participants who had made a treatment decision in the past year could answer these items.

6.3.5. Predictor Variables

Many variables were identified in the literature as having an impact on these varied aspects of shared decision-making. These predictor variables were split into (a) demographic variables, (b) the theory of planned behaviour variables, (c) health-related variables and (d) variables used in study 2.

Demographic Variables

Age

Participants were asked "what is your age (years)?". Participants' age was collected numerically (e.g. "27") via an open text box.

Gender

Participants were asked to "Please select your sex" with response options being either "male" or "female".

Education Level

Participants were asked "what is your highest level of education?". The responses were inserted into an open text box. The responses were then categorised into the following groups: High school; Further; Higher (undergraduate); Postgraduate and Other. Responses in the "other" category included: "none", "NA", "yearly" and "not sure".

From this, these responses were then categorised further into: Post-secondary education level (Further; Higher (undergraduate); Postgraduate and Other) & No post-secondary education level (High School & “none” and “NA” from the “other” category) for the engagement analysis based on the previous literature (see hypotheses section above). The responses were also then categorised into patients who had taken part in higher education (higher (undergraduate) & postgraduate) & less educated patients (high school, further & other) for the preferred consultation style and satisfaction with the healthcare decision analyses based on the previous literature (see hypotheses section above).

Employment Status

Participants were asked “what is your occupation?”. Participants stated their occupation in an open text box (e.g., “Nurse”) for the current study. The responses were then categorised into two groups: Employed or Not in employment to create an employment status variable. Responses in the “not in employment” category included: “Student”, “Retired”, “None”, “Unemployed”, “Na”, “Not working due to ill health”, “Medically retired” and “Stay at home mum”.

The Theory of Planned Behaviour Variables

Attitudes Towards SDM

Attitudes towards SDM for the current study and for study 2 was measured using 4 out of 6 items, taken from Yen et al.’s (2019) study (see Table 24 below). Responses to these items were presented on a 4-point scale, where 1 meant strongly agree and 4 meant strongly disagree, with possible scores ranging from 0 to 4 (if participants chose either disagree or strongly disagree for an item, they would have a score of 1 for that item) with higher attitudes scores indicating a more favourable attitude towards shared decision-making. Possible overall scores ranged from 0 to 16. Cronbach’s alpha reliability score for the 4-item measure was 0.603 which indicates an acceptable internal consistency.

As discussed in Chapter 5, only 4 out of the original 6 attitude items were used for analysis (see Table 24 below) for this study as the internal consistency was unacceptable when all 6 items were used. This could be because the original 6 items were developed and used with medical students instead of patients with chronic pain and members of the Scottish general population (similar to study 2 and the current study). Attitudes towards SDM was also a primary predictor variable for the current study.

Table 24

Attitudes Towards SDM items

1	Shared decision-making can only be done with patients who are sufficiently educated and confident to discuss treatment or screening options with their clinician.
2	Doing shared decision making is unrealistic because it takes too much time.
3	Doing shared decision making is low on my priority list.
4	Patients should trust clinicians to make all decisions on their behalf.

Subjective Norms

Subjective norms were measured in the current study using three items that were used in Légaré et al.'s (2013) study, rated on a seven-point scale which ranged from -3 (strongly disagree) to +3 (strongly agree). Possible scores ranged from -9 to +9. Thus, a higher score for these items (subjective norms) indicated that participants believe that others want them to engage in SDM. The items were: "Most people who are important to me would recommend that I engage in shared decision-making"; "Most people who are important to me would think it preferable for me to engage in shared decision-making"; and "Most people who are important to me are in favour of me engaging in shared decision-making". Cronbach's alpha reliability score was .952, indicating very good acceptable internal consistency. Participants' subjective norms was additionally a primary predictor variable for the current study.

Self-efficacy

Bunn & O'Connor's (1996) 11 item decision self-efficacy scale (DSS) was used to measure self-efficacy for the current study (see appendix L). An example item was "I feel confident that I can: Get the facts about the healthcare choices available to me". Participants were asked to reflect on how confident they felt in making an informed medical decision on a 5-point scale that ranged from "Not at all confident" to "Very Confident". These scales are then converted to give scores of 0-100 by summing items, dividing them by 11 and multiplying by 25. A score of 0 indicates no confidence (or extremely low self-efficacy) and a score of 100 indicates very confident (or extremely high self-efficacy). Cronbach's alpha reliability score for the self-efficacy scale was 0.924 indicating that the self-efficacy scale items have excellent internal consistency. Participants' self-efficacy was also a primary predictor variable for the current study.

Health-Related Variables

Frequency of Attending a Medical Appointment

Frequency of attending a medical appointment was measured using a single question: “How frequently do you attend medical appointments/see a medical consultant?” Participants could select one of the following answers: “Daily; Weekly; Fortnightly; Monthly; Every few months; Every six months; Yearly; Every few years or Other”. If participants selected “other”, they were then asked to “please specify” in an open text box. Responses in the “other” open text box included: “Infrequently; as required; only when needed; whenever I require a GP appointment & Every few months prior to COVID. Currently awaiting various appointments.” From this, these responses were then categorised further into: frequently attended medical appointments (daily, weekly, fortnightly, monthly or every few months) and who infrequently attended medical appointments (every six months, yearly, every few years or other) for the satisfaction analysis based on the previous literature (see hypotheses section above).

Self-rated Health

The current study used a global 5-point measure for participants to self-rate their health (Stewart & Ware, 1992). Participants were asked: “How would you rate your health?”, where possible response options were 1=excellent, 2=very good, 3=good, 4=fair and 5=poor. These categories were then grouped into 2 categories: better self-rated health (good, very good or excellent) & poorer self-rated health (poor or fair), as previous studies had also grouped the responses this way.

Relationship with the Healthcare Professional

For the current study, the Patient-Doctor Relationship Questionnaire (PDRQ-9) (Van der Feltz-Cornelis et al., 2004) was used to measure the patient-healthcare professional relationship. The PDRQ-9 includes 9 items (see appendix L) that a person can make about his/her Health Care Professional (HCP). An example item was: “My HCP has enough time for me”. Responses were measured on a 5-point scale that ranges from 1 (not at all appropriate) to 5 (totally appropriate), resulting in overall scores of 9-45. Higher scores indicate a better patient-healthcare professional relationship. Cronbach’s alpha reliability score for the patient-healthcare professional relationship scale was 0.958 indicating that the patient-healthcare professional relationship scale items have excellent internal consistency.

Attendance at a Medical Appointment

After answering all other questions, participants were asked “Have you attended a medical appointment and made a medical/treatment decision in the last year?” if they responded “yes” then they also completed the engagement in SDM and the satisfaction with the healthcare decision questions at the end of the survey, if participants responded “no” they were directed to the end of the survey. Therefore, 146 participants also completed these 2 questionnaires as they answered “yes” they had made a treatment decision in the past year, whilst 64 participants did not answer questions about their engagement in SDM and their satisfaction with the healthcare decision as they did not make a treatment decision in the past year. Cronbach’s alpha reliability score for the satisfaction with the healthcare decision scale was 0.948 indicating that the satisfaction with the healthcare decision scale items have excellent internal consistency.

Variables Used in Study 2

In addition to these variables, knowledge of SDM and awareness of SDM were also used for comparison with study 2.

Knowledge of SDM

Participants’ knowledge of SDM for the current study and for study 2 was measured using 13 items, taken from Yen et al.’s (2019) study and an additional original item that the researcher added to the scale. This assesses participants’ understanding of the ideas behind shared decision making. Whilst there were originally 16 items in Yen et al.’s knowledge scale, only 13 of these items were used for the current study as in the original study (Yen et al., 2019) 3 of these items are described as risk communication items instead of knowledge items. An additional original item was also added to the knowledge scale: “A majority of clinicians do not want to engage in shared decision making with their patients” to give a more balanced and unbiased framing to the knowledge items as in the original study only “A majority of patients do not want to engage in shared decision making with their clinician” was included. Response options were: “true” or “false”.

Therefore, 14 items were used to assess participant’s knowledge of SDM. However, only 6 of these items (see Table 25 below) were used for analysis in study 2 and for the current study as the reliability for all 14 items were not acceptable, so the items with the highest internal consistency were used for analysis. The total possible scores range from 0 to 6, with 6 reflecting very good knowledge of the principles of SDM. The Cronbach’s alpha reliability score for the 6-item knowledge scale was 0.517,

indicating an unacceptable internal consistency but improved reliability than when all 14 items are used. The reason for the poor reliability again could be because the original knowledge items were developed and used with medical students instead of patients with chronic pain and members of the Scottish general population (like in study 2 and the current study).

Table 25

Knowledge of SDM Items

1	Shared decision-making causes patients to feel uncertain about their decisions.
2	Shared decision-making increases patient decision regret.
3	Shared decision-making results in fewer patients choosing major surgery.
4	There is no need for the clinician to check the patient's understanding.
5	A majority of patients do not want to engage in shared decision making with their clinician.
6	A majority of clinicians do not want to engage in shared decision making with their patients.

Awareness of SDM

Participants' awareness of SDM was measured by asking participants: "Had you heard of shared decision-making before completing this survey?". The responses were "Yes" or "No".

6.4 Results

6.4.1. Descriptive Data

Table 26 below shows the descriptive data for the TPB variables: attitudes, subjective norms, and self-efficacy as well as for three of the outcome variables: intention, engagement & satisfaction with the healthcare decision and for 2 of the predictor variables: relationship with the healthcare professional, and knowledge.

Table 26

Descriptive Data

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Attitude towards SDM	2.92	1.04	0	4
Subjective norms	5.02	3.55	-9	9
Self-efficacy	72.69	19.13	0	100
Intention to engage in SDM	5.06	3.27	-8	9
Engagement in SDM Behaviour	37.88	11.09	9	54
Satisfaction with the healthcare decision	24.23	5.42	6	30
Relationship with the Healthcare Professional	32.97	8.74	9	45
Knowledge of SDM	4.28	1.07	0	6

As we can see from Table 26 above, the mean score for the 4-item measure of participants' attitudes towards SDM was 2.92 (SD =1.04). This suggests that participants have a positive attitude towards SDM, since the maximum score was 4 and higher scores indicated more positive attitudes towards SDM. The mean score for participants' subjective norms was 5.02 (SD=3.55). This suggests that individuals who are close to participants believe that engaging in SDM is a good thing, since the maximum score was 9 and higher scores indicated higher levels of subjective norms.

Mean score for participants' self-efficacy was 72.69 (SD=19.13). This suggests that participants have relatively high self-efficacy in making a medical decision, since the maximum score was 100 and higher scores indicated higher levels of self-efficacy. Mean score for participants' intention to engage in SDM was 5.06 (SD=3.27), suggesting that participants intend to engage in SDM, since the maximum score was 9 and higher scores indicated higher levels of intention to engage in SDM. The mean score for participants' engagement in SDM was 37.88 (SD=11.09). This suggests that participants engaged in SDM, since the maximum score was 54 and higher scores indicated higher levels of engagement in SDM. Mean score for participants' satisfaction with the healthcare decision was 24.23 (SD=5.42). This suggests that participants were satisfied with their healthcare decision, since the maximum score was 30 and higher scores indicated greater satisfaction with their healthcare decision.

Mean score for participants' patient-healthcare professional relationship was 32.97 (SD=8.74). This suggests that participants generally had a good relationship with their healthcare professional, since the maximum score was 45 and higher scores indicated better patient-healthcare professional relationships. The average score for participants' knowledge about SDM was 4.28. Since the maximum score was 6, this suggests that participants had fair levels of knowledge about SDM. The standard deviation was 1.07 indicating that there was some variation between participants' knowledge scores.

6.4.2. Frequencies

Preferred Consultation Style

Preferred consultation style was assessed by asking participants: "How do you think healthcare decisions should be made?". Figure 6 below shows the frequencies of the five possible responses in answer to this question. Most participants believed that they themselves should make the final decision about their treatment after seriously considering their healthcare professional's opinion, with 126 participants giving this response. 58 participants also believed that the healthcare professional should share responsibility with them for making the final treatment decision. Only 10 patients opted for the most extreme response "As the patient, I should make the final decision about which treatment I should receive" and relatively few participants selected the passive options with 14 participants selecting the response: "The healthcare professional should make the final decision about which treatment I should receive after seriously considering my opinion" and only 2 participants selecting the response: "The healthcare professional should make the final decision about which treatment I receive."

Figure 6. Bar Chart of Number of Participants' Preferred Consultation Style

Active or Passive Consultation Style

Yen et al. (2019) indicated that the first three responses indicate a preference for an active consultation style whilst the last two responses indicate a preference for a passive consultation style. Thus, from Table 27 shown below, most participants preferred an active consultation style (194), wanting to engage in their healthcare decisions, with only 16 opting for a passive style.

Table 27

Frequency of Preferred Consultation Style

	Frequency	Percent (%)
Active	194	92.4
Passive	16	7.6
Total	210	100

As Table 27 above depicts, an overwhelming majority of participants preferred a more active consultation style (92.4%), thus believing that either they should make the final decision about their healthcare or that the healthcare professional should share responsibility with them for making the

final decision about their healthcare (engaging in SDM) with only 7.6% preferring a passive style, where the healthcare professional makes the final decision. This is an important result, and it reflects the results of study 2 in showing that the majority of patients in these studies accept that they have an important role to play in making their healthcare decisions. For these patients, the balance of responsibility in making the health-related decision lies more towards them than the professional, although very few patients agreed that they should make the decision entirely on their own.

Frequency of Attending Medical Appointments

Table 28

Frequency of Attending Medical Appointments

	Frequency	Percent (%)
Weekly	4	1.9
Fortnightly	6	2.9
Monthly	8	3.8
Every Few Months	78	37.1
Every Six Months	31	14.8
Yearly	51	24.3
Every Few Years	24	11.4
Other	8	3.8
Total	210	100

Table 28 above shows how frequently participants attended a medical appointment. The most frequent response was “every few months” (37.1%), followed by yearly (24.3%). Very few of the 210 participants were regular attenders at medical appointments with only 4 attending weekly and 6 attending fortnightly.

Self-rated Health

Most participants (163) fell into the better self-rated health category (77.6%), self-rating their health as being very good or excellent, with only 47 (22.4%) rating themselves as being in poorer health. These percentages reflect a similar trend in percentages as the ones that were reported in Scotland's Census (2022) where most members (91.9%) of the Scottish general population self-rated their health as being good or very good and only 8.1% of the general population self-rated their health as being bad or very bad.

Awareness of SDM

In response to the question: "Had you heard of shared decision-making before completing this survey?", 93 (44.3%) of participants said yes and 117 (55.7%) said no, suggesting that the majority of participants had not previously heard of SDM.

Made Healthcare Decision in the Past Year

In response to the question "Have you made a healthcare decision in the past year?" 146 (69.5%) said yes and 64 (30.5%) said no, showing that over two thirds of participants had made a healthcare decision in the past year. As it was only these participants who could complete the engagement in SDM and the satisfaction with the healthcare decision questionnaires, 146 participants completed these 2 questionnaires.

6.5 Analyses

6.5.1. Primary Hypotheses

Intention (Outcome Variable)

The first set of analyses focused on the primary hypotheses, looking at links between the 3 key predictor variables from the TPB: attitudes, subjective norms & self-efficacy, and intention to engage in SDM. As Table 29 below shows, all of the theory of planned behaviour predictor variables were significantly, positively correlated with intention. Subjective norms showed the highest correlation and attitudes the weakest correlation with intention to engage in SDM.

Table 29

Correlations between the TPB Variables

	Attitude	Subjective norm	Self-efficacy	Intention
Attitude	1			
Subjective norm	.295**	1		
Self-efficacy	.137*	.404**	1	
Intention	.280**	.609**	.522**	1

To examine these relationships further a series of regressions were carried out, firstly with each variable individually and then with all three together.

- **P H1 INT:** Attitudes towards SDM will predict intention to engage in SDM.

A linear regression was carried out to test whether participants' attitudes could significantly predict their intentions to engage in SDM. The results of the regression indicated that the model explained 7.8% of the variance and that the model was a significant predictor of intention to engage in SDM, $F(1,208) = 17.651, p < .001$. Participants' attitudes significantly predicted their intention to engage in shared decision-making ($B = .280, p < .001$).

- **P H2 INT:** Subjective norms will predict intention to engage in SDM.

A linear regression was carried out to investigate whether participants' subjective norms could significantly predict participants' intention to engage in SDM. The results of the regression indicated that the model explained 37% of the variance and that the model was a significant predictor of intention to engage in SDM, $F(1,208) = 122.378, p < .001$. Participants' subjective norms significantly predicted their intention to engage in SDM ($B = .609, p < .001$).

- **P H3 INT:** Self-efficacy will predict intention to engage in SDM.

A linear regression was carried out to investigate whether participants' self-efficacy could significantly predict their intention to engage in SDM. The results of the regression indicated that the model explained 27.3% of the variance and that the model was a significant predictor of intention to engage in SDM, $F(1,208) = 77.944, p < .001$. Participants' self-efficacy significantly predicted their intention to engage in SDM ($B = .522, p < .001$).

- **P H4 INT:** Attitudes towards SDM, subjective norms & self-efficacy will predict intention to engage in SDM.

To explore the relationships further, and to investigate which TPB variables: subjective norms, self-efficacy and attitudes, were the strongest predictors of intention to engage in SDM, a multiple regression was carried out looking at all 3 predictor variables together. The results of the regression indicated that the model explained 47.1% of the variance and that the model was a significant predictor of intention to engage in SDM, $F(3,206) = 61.195, p < .001$. Subjective norms were the strongest predictor ($B = .446, p < .001$), followed by self-efficacy ($B = .328, p < .001$), while attitudes was a nearly significant predictor of intention to engage in SDM ($B = .103, p = .053$).

Predictors of Engagement in SDM

To further examine the predictions of the TPB, the impact of subjective norms, self-efficacy, attitudes & intention on engagement in SDM behaviour was examined.

- **P H5 ENGAGE:** Participants who have higher scores for intention will have higher scores for engagement in SDM.

First of all, intention was examined on its own as a predictor of engagement in SDM behaviour. As table 30 below shows, a positive, moderate correlation of .448 ($r = .448, n = 146, p < .001$) was found between intention and engagement in SDM behaviour, indicating that participants who had higher scores for intention also had higher scores for engagement in SDM. A linear regression was also carried out to further investigate whether participants' intention to engage in SDM could significantly predict participants' engagement in SDM. The results of the regression indicated that the model explained

20.0% of the variance and that the model was a significant predictor of engagement in SDM, $F(1,144) = 36.111, p < .001$. Participants' intention statistically significantly predicted their engagement in SDM ($B = .448, p < .001$).

As Table 30 below also shows, subjective norms and self-efficacy were positively and significantly correlated with SDM behaviour, with intention the strongest correlate and subjective norms the weakest. The only TBP predictor variable that was not significantly correlated with engagement in SDM behaviour was attitudes towards SDM.

Table 30

Correlations between All TPB Variables

	Attitude	Subjective norm	Self-efficacy	Intention	Engagement
Attitude	1				
Subjective norm	.295**	1			
Self-efficacy	.137*	.404**	1		
Intention	.280**	.609**	.522**	1	
Engagement	.154	.251**	.331**	.448**	1

- **P H6 ENGAGE:** Attitudes, subjective norms, self-efficacy and intention will predict engagement in SDM

To further explore the relationship between the TPB variables and to investigate which of the 4 predictor variables had the strongest impact on engagement in SDM behaviour, a regression was carried out, looking at attitudes, subjective norms, self-efficacy and intention on engagement in SDM behaviour. The results of the regression indicated that the model explained 22.5% of the variance and that the model was a significant predictor of engagement in SDM, $F(4,141) = 10.205, p < .001$. Intention ($B = .380, p < .001$) was the strongest predictor, self-efficacy ($B = .173, p = .040$) also contributed to the model, statistically significantly predicting engagement in SDM, while attitudes ($B = .006, p = .937$) and subjective norms ($B = -.014, p = .877$) did not.

6.5.2. Secondary Hypotheses

Numerous secondary hypotheses were tested, and these will be reported in the following order:

1. Relationships between the outcome variables
2. The TPB variables as predictors of engagement in SDM behaviours, preferred consultation style and satisfaction with the healthcare decision
3. Demographic variables
4. Health-related variables
5. Variables from study 2

In order to keep the findings concise, only the significant results for the tests performed on the secondary hypotheses are reported in this chapter. The non-significant results of the analyses including the secondary variables can be viewed in Appendix P.

Relationships Between the Outcome Variables

The TPB was introduced into this study in the hope that the theory would provide a useful and informative framework for thinking about SDM. It was hoped that intention to engage and engagement in SDM behaviour would provide better measures of SDM than other measures used to assess engagement in SDM. We have already seen that, consistent with the predictions of TPB, intention was a moderate predictor of engagement in SDM behaviour. However, it was also useful to examine the relationship between all four outcome variables used in the study: intention to engage in SDM, engagement in SDM behaviour, preferred consultation style and satisfaction with the healthcare decision, to establish how good they are as measures of engagement in SDM. Correlations between the four outcome variables are shown in Table 31 below.

Table 31

Correlations between All Outcome Variables

	Preferred Consultation Style	Intention	Engagement in SDM behaviour	Satisfaction
Preferred Consultation Style	1			
Intention	-.242**	1		

Engagement in SDM behaviour	-.087	.448**	1	
Satisfaction	.026	.440**	.729**	1

Preferred Consultation Style

- **S H1 OV:** Participants' intention to engage in SDM will predict their preferred consultation style.

As Table 31 above shows, the only significant correlation between preferred consultation style and the other outcome variables was a significant, negative correlation between intention to engage and preferred consultation style ($r_{pb} = -.242, n = 210, p < .001$). This suggests that participants who had more intention to engage in SDM preferred to take a more active role in their healthcare decisions.

A logistic regression was also performed to ascertain the effects of participants' intention to engage in SDM on the likelihood that participants prefer an active or passive consultation style. The logistic regression model was statistically significant, $\chi^2(1) = 10.755, p = .001$. The model explained 12% (Nagelkerke R^2) of the variance in preferred consultation style and correctly classified 92.4% of cases. Score for intention to engage in SDM was a significant predictor of consultation style ($p = .001$). As displayed in Table 31 above, intention to engage in SDM was linked to preference for an active consultation style.

Satisfaction with the Healthcare Decision

If SDM is successful, we would expect that patients who advocate and engage in SDM would be more satisfied with the healthcare decisions that they make. In this section we report on the relationship between the other outcome variables and satisfaction with the healthcare decision. The first hypothesis is:

- **S H3 OV:** Participants who have higher scores for intention to carry out SDM will also have higher scores for satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

A Pearson product-moment correlation was run to determine the relationship between participants' intention to engage and their satisfaction with the healthcare decision. As Table 31 above shows, there

was a moderate, positive correlation between intention to engage and satisfaction with the healthcare decision, which was statistically significant ($r = .440, n = 146, p < .001$). This suggests that individuals who intend to engage in SDM tend to be more positive about the decisions that they make.

A linear regression was also carried out to further investigate whether participants' intention to engage in SDM could significantly predict their satisfaction with the healthcare decision. The results of the regression indicated that the model explained 19.3% of the variance and that the model was a significant predictor of satisfaction with the healthcare decision, $F(1,144) = 34.543, p < .001$. Participants' intention to engage in SDM significantly predicted their satisfaction with the healthcare decision ($B = .440, p < .001$).

- **S H4 OV:** Participants with higher scores for engagement in SDM will have higher scores for satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

A Pearson product-moment correlation was run to determine the relationship between participants' engagement in SDM and their satisfaction with the healthcare decision. As Table 31 above shows, there was a strong, positive correlation between engagement in SDM and satisfaction with the healthcare decision, which was statistically significant ($r = .729, n = 146, p < .001$). This suggests that individuals who engage in SDM tend to be more positive about the decisions that they make. Table 31 above also shows that preferred consultation style was not related to satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

A linear regression was also carried out to further investigate whether participants' engagement in SDM behaviour could significantly predict their satisfaction with the healthcare decision. The results of the regression indicated that the model explained 53.1% of the variance and that the model was a significant predictor of satisfaction with the healthcare decision, $F(1,144) = 162.970, p < .001$. Participants' engagement in SDM behaviour significantly predicted their satisfaction with the healthcare decision ($B = .729, p < .001$).

To summarise, intention and engagement in SDM behaviours were significantly linked to satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

The TPB Variables as Predictors of Engagement in SDM Behaviours, Preferred Consultation Style and Satisfaction with the Healthcare Decision

While the correlation between the TPB predictor variables (attitudes, subjective norms and self-efficacy) and engagement in SDM behaviours was examined as a primary hypothesis, it is also useful to also explore these relationships individually. It was also useful to examine the relationship between the TPB predictor variables and preferred consultation style and satisfaction with the healthcare decision. Consequently, the next set of secondary analyses looked at the links between the TPB predictor variables and the three main outcome variables: engagement in SDM, preferred consultation style and satisfaction with the healthcare decision. Table 32 below shows the correlations between these variables.

Table 32

Correlations between the TBP Variables and Key Outcome Variables

	Attitude	Subjective norm	Self-efficacy	Engagement in SDM behaviour	Preferr ed consultation style	Satisfaction
Attitude	1					
Subjective norm	.295**	1				
Self-efficacy	.137*	.404**	1			
Engagement in SDM behaviour	.154	.251**	.331**	1		
Preferred consultation style	-.238**	-.250**	-.061	-.087	1	
Satisfaction	.010	.219**	.226**	.729**	.026	1

Attitudes Towards SDM

As Table 32 above shows, attitudes towards SDM had no significant relationship with engagement in SDM or with satisfaction with the healthcare decision. The lack of correlation between attitudes and engagement in SDM behaviour was contrary to the predictions of the TPB. However, attitudes towards

SDM were negatively correlated with preferred consultation style, indicating that positive attitudes towards SDM were linked to preference for an active consultation style.

- **S H7 PCS:** Attitudes towards SDM will predict preferred consultation style.

To further explore the relationship between attitudes and preferred consultation style, a logistic regression was performed to ascertain the effects of participants' attitudes towards SDM on the likelihood that participants prefer an active or passive consultation style. The logistic regression model was statistically significant, $\chi^2(1) = 10.339, p = .001$. The model explained 11.5% (Nagelkerke R^2) of the variance in preferred consultation style and correctly classified 92.4% of cases. Score for attitudes towards SDM was a significant predictor of consultation style ($p = .001$). As displayed in Table 32 above, positive attitudes towards SDM were linked to preference for an active consultation style.

Subjective Norms

As shown in table 32 above, subjective norms was significantly correlated with all three outcome variables: engagement in SDM, preferred consultation style and satisfaction with the healthcare decision. The correlations between subjective norms and engagement in SDM and between subjective norms and satisfaction with the healthcare decision were positive, while the correlation between subjective norms and preferred consultation style was negative.

- **S H9 ENGAGE:** Subjective norms will predict engagement in SDM.

A linear regression was carried out to further investigate the significant correlation between subjective norms and engagement in SDM. The results of the regression indicated that the model explained 6.3% of the variance and that the model was a significant predictor of engagement in SDM, $F(1,144) = 9.708, p = .002$. Participants' subjective norms statistically significantly predicted their engagement in SDM ($B = .251, p = .002$).

- **S H10 PCS:** Participants who have higher subjective norms scores will prefer an active consultation style.

A point-biserial correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between participants' subjective norms and preferred consultation style. As shown in table 32 above, there was a weak,

negative correlation between subjective norms and preferred consultation style, which was statistically significant ($r = -.250, n = 210, p < .001$). Therefore, participants with higher subjective norms scores preferred an active consultation style.

A logistic regression was also performed to further ascertain whether participants' subjective norms predict preference for an active or passive consultation style. The logistic regression model was statistically significant, $\chi^2(1) = 11.467, p < .001$. The model explained 12.8% (Nagelkerke R^2) of the variance in preferred consultation style and correctly classified 91.9% of cases. Score for subjective norms was a significant predictor of consultation style ($p < .001$). Therefore, participants who are more influenced by what others think preferred an active consultation style.

- **S H11 SAT:** Subjective norms will predict satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

A linear regression was carried out to test the hypothesis that participants' subjective norms could significantly predict their satisfaction with the healthcare decision. The results of the regression indicated that the model explained 4.8% of the variance and that the model was a significant predictor of satisfaction with the healthcare decision, $F(1,144) = 7.287, p = .008$. Participants' subjective norms statistically significantly predicted their satisfaction with the healthcare decision ($B = .219, p = .008$). These results indicate that participants who are more influenced by what others think also tend to be more satisfied with their healthcare decision.

Self-efficacy

As Table 32 above shows, self-efficacy was not significantly linked to preferred consultation style, but was significantly, positively linked to engagement in SDM and satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

- **S H12 ENGAGE:** Participants who have higher self-efficacy scores will have higher scores for engagement in SDM.

As shown in Table 32 above, a significant, moderate, positive correlation was found between self-efficacy and engagement in SDM behaviours ($r = .331, n = 146, p < .001$). This suggests that participants who had higher self-efficacy scores also had higher scores for engagement in SDM behaviour.

A linear regression was also carried out to further investigate whether participants' self-efficacy could significantly predict participants' engagement in SDM. The results of the regression indicated that the

model explained 10.9% of the variance and that the model was a significant predictor of engagement in SDM, $F(1,144) = 17.662, p < .001$. Participants' self-efficacy significantly predicted their engagement in SDM ($B = .331, p < .001$).

- **S H14 SAT:** Participants who have higher self-efficacy scores will have higher satisfaction with the healthcare decision scores.

As shown in Table 32 above, a significant, moderate, positive correlation was found between self-efficacy and satisfaction with the healthcare decision ($r = .226, n = 146, p = .003$), suggesting that participants who had higher self-efficacy scores also had higher satisfaction with the healthcare decision scores.

A linear regression was also carried out to further investigate whether participants' self-efficacy could significantly predict participants' satisfaction with the healthcare decision. The results of the regression indicated that the model explained 5.1% of the variance and that the model was a significant predictor of patients' satisfaction with their healthcare decision, $F(1,144) = 7.783, p = .006$. Participants' self-efficacy statistically significantly predicted their satisfaction with the healthcare decision ($B = .226, p = .006$), suggesting that those who feel that they are able to engage in SDM will be more satisfied with the outcome.

To summarise, attitudes towards SDM significantly predicted preferred consultation style whilst subjective norms significantly predicted all of the outcome variables and self-efficacy was significantly associated with engagement in SDM behaviours and satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

Health-related Variables

The only health-related variable that had a significant impact on any of the outcome variables in the current study was the participant's relationship with their healthcare professional.

Relationship with the Healthcare Professional

Table 33 below shows correlations between relationship with the healthcare professional and the 3 main outcome variables: engagement in SDM behaviour, preferred consultation style and satisfaction with the healthcare decision. As Table 33 shows, relationship with the healthcare professional was

significantly correlated with all 3 variables, with higher correlations for engagement with SDM and satisfaction with the healthcare decision

Table 33

Correlations between Relationship with the Healthcare Professional & the Outcome Variables

	Relationship with the Healthcare Professional	Engagement in SDM behaviour	Preferred Consultation Style	Satisfaction with the Healthcare Decision
Relationship with the Healthcare Professional	1			
Engagement in SDM behaviour	.445**	1		
Preferred Consultation Style	.139*	-.087	1	
Satisfaction with the Healthcare Decision	.437**	.729**	.026	1

- **S H33 ENGAGE:** Participants who have a more effective relationship with their healthcare professional will also be more engaged in SDM.

As Table 33 above shows, there was a moderate, positive correlation between the relationship with the healthcare professional and engagement with SDM, which was statistically significant ($r = .445$, $n = 146$, $p < .001$). Therefore, participants who have a more effective relationship with their healthcare professional also engaged more in SDM behaviours. To further explore the links between relationship with the healthcare professional and the outcome variables, a series of regressions were also carried out.

A linear regression was also carried out to further investigate whether participants' relationship with their healthcare professional could significantly predict their engagement in SDM behaviour. The results indicated that the model explained 19.8% of the variance and that the model was a significant

predictor of engagement in SDM, $F(1,144) = 35.584, p < .001$. Participants' relationship with their healthcare professional significantly predicted their engagement in SDM ($B = .445, p < .001$).

- **S H34 PCS:** Participants who have a better relationship with their healthcare professional will prefer a passive consultation style.

As Table 33 above also shows, there was a weak, positive correlation between relationship with the healthcare professional and preferred consultation style, which was statistically significant ($r = .139, n = 210, p = .022$). Therefore, participants who had a better relationship with the healthcare professional preferred a passive consultation style.

A logistic regression was also performed to further ascertain whether participants' relationship with their healthcare professional predict that participants prefer an active or passive consultation style. The logistic regression model was statistically significant, $\chi^2(1) = 4.460, p = .035$. The model explained 5.0% (Nagelkerke R^2) of the variance in preferred consultation style and correctly classified 92.4% of cases. Score for the patient-healthcare relationship was a significant predictor of preferred consultation style ($p = .050$).

- **S H35 SAT:** Participants who have a better relationship with their healthcare professional will also have higher scores for satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

As Table 33 above additionally shows, there was a moderate, positive correlation between relationship with the healthcare professional and satisfaction with the healthcare decision ($r = .437, n = 146, p < .001$), showing that participants who had a better relationship with their healthcare professional were more satisfied with their healthcare decision.

A linear regression was also carried out to further investigate whether participants' relationship with their healthcare professional could significantly predict their satisfaction with the healthcare decision. The results of the regression indicated that the model explained 19.1% of the variance and that the model was a significant predictor of satisfaction with the healthcare decision, $F(1,144) = 34.018, p < .001$. Participants' relationship with their healthcare professional statistically significantly predicted their satisfaction with the healthcare decision ($B = .437, p < .001$).

To summarise, the relationship an individual has with their healthcare professional had an important impact on all 3 main outcome variables: engagement in SDM behaviour, preferred consultation style and satisfaction with the healthcare decision, confirming the importance of an individual's relationship with their healthcare professional in SDM.

Variables from Study 2

Knowledge of SDM

Correlations were carried out to examine how participants' knowledge of SDM was related to the outcome variables. As Table 34 below shows, knowledge of SDM was significantly correlated with both engagement in SDM behaviour and satisfaction with the healthcare decision, with satisfaction with the healthcare decision showing a slightly higher correlation.

Table 34

Correlations between Knowledge of SDM & Outcome Variables

	Knowledge of SDM	Engagement in SDM Behaviour	Satisfaction with the Healthcare Decision
Knowledge of SDM	1		
Engagement in SDM Behaviour	.228*	1	
Satisfaction with the Healthcare Decision	.272**	.729**	1

To further explore the significant relationships between knowledge of SDM and the outcome variables, a series of regressions were also carried out.

- **S H36 ENGAGE:** Participants who have lower scores for knowledge of SDM will also have lower scores for engagement in SDM behaviour.

As Table 34 above shows, there was a weak, positive correlation between knowledge of shared decision-making and engagement in SDM behaviour, which was statistically significant ($r = .228, n = 146, p = .003$). This shows that participants who had less knowledge of SDM also engaged less in SDM behaviours.

A linear regression was carried out to further investigate whether participants' knowledge of shared decision-making could significantly predict their SDM behaviour. The results of the regression indicated that the model explained 5.2% of the variance and that the model was a significant predictor of SDM behaviour, $F(1,144) = 7.927, p = .006$. Participants' knowledge of SDM statistically significantly predicted their engagement in SDM behaviour ($B = .228, p = .006$).

- **S H38 SAT:** Participants who have more knowledge about SDM will also have higher scores for satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

As Table 34 above shows, there was a weak, positive correlation between knowledge of SDM and satisfaction with the healthcare decision ($r = .272, n = 146, p < .001$). Therefore, participants who had more knowledge of SDM were more satisfied with the healthcare decision.

A linear regression was also carried out to investigate whether participants' knowledge of SDM could significantly predict participants' satisfaction with the healthcare decision. The results of the regression indicated that the model explained 7.4% of the variance and that the model was significant, $F(1,144) = 11.501, p < .001$. Participants' knowledge of SDM statistically significantly predicted their satisfaction with the healthcare decision ($B = 0.272, p < .001$).

To summarise, knowledge of SDM was not related to preferred consultation style but was significantly linked to both engagement in SDM behaviour and satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

Regression of All Significant Predictors on Engagement in SDM Behaviour

The TPB variables: subjective norms, self-efficacy, and intention to engage in SDM predicted engagement in SDM behaviours suggesting that the TPB was useful in understanding engagement in SDM behaviours. However, the additional variables, relationship with healthcare professional and knowledge of SDM were also related to engagement in SDM behaviours. To further examine the predictors of engagement in SDM behaviour, correlations and multiple regression analyses were

carried out with all the variables that were significant predictors of engagement in SDM behaviour together.

The correlation table shown in Table 35 below confirms that all of these variables were significantly, positively correlated with engagement in SDM behaviour. Intention to engage in SDM behaviour was the highest correlated predictor variable, whilst knowledge of SDM was the lowest correlated predictor variable for engagement in SDM behaviour.

Table 35

Correlations Between All Significant Predictor Variables on Engagement in SDM Behaviour

	Intention	Relationship with HCP	Engagement in SDM Behaviour	Subjective Norm	Self-efficacy	Knowledge
Intention	1					
Relationship with HCP	.406**	1				
Engagement in SDM Behaviour	.448**	.445**	1			
Subjective Norm	.609**	.142*	.251**	1		
Self-efficacy	.522**	.515**	.331**	.404**	1	
Knowledge	.359**	.163*	.228**	.325**	.206**	1

To further explore this relationship between all of the significant predictor variables with engagement in SDM behaviour, a multiple regression was carried out using the enter method with all 5 variables inserted simultaneously. The results of the regression analysis indicated that the model explained 28.3% of the variance and that the model was a significant predictor of SDM behaviour, $F(5,140) = 11.043, p < .001$. Participants' relationship with their healthcare professional ($B = .279, p = .002$) was the strongest predictor of engagement in SDM behaviour, intention ($B = .257, p = .008$) also contributed to the model, statistically significantly predicting engagement in SDM behaviour, whilst self-efficacy ($B = .075, p = .390$), knowledge ($B = .053, p = .499$) and subjective norms ($B = .027, p = .762$) were not significant predictors.

To summarise, relationship with the healthcare professional and intention are the best predictors of engagement in SDM behaviour. This was interesting in confirming the importance of the TBP variable, intention, in predicting engagement in SDM behaviours but also identifies the patients' relationship with their healthcare professional as an important predictor.

Regression of All Significant Predictor Variables on Preferred Consultation Style

To further examine the predictors of preferred consultation style, correlations and a logistic regression analysis were carried out with the variables that were significant predictors of preferred consultation style. As shown in Table 36 below, these were intention to engage in SDM, subjective norms, attitudes towards SDM, and relationship with the healthcare professional.

Table 36

Correlations between All Significant Predictor Variables on Preferred Consultation Style

	Intention	Attitude	Subjective Norms	Relationship with the Healthcare Professional	Preferred Consultation Style
Intention	1				
Attitude	.280**	1			
Subjective norms	.609**	.295**	1		
Relationship with the Healthcare Professional	.406**	-.106	.142*	1	
Preferred Consultation Style	-.242**	-.238**	-.250**	.139*	1

As the correlation matrix shown in Table 36 above confirms: attitudes, subjective norms, intention and relationship with the healthcare professional were all significantly correlated with preferred consultation style. The only predictor variable to be positively correlated with preferred consultation style was relationship with the healthcare professional. Subjective norms was the highest correlated predictor variable whilst relationship with the healthcare professional was the lowest correlated predictor variable for preferred consultation style.

To further explore the relationship between all of the significant predictor variables with preferred consultation style, a logistic regression was performed to ascertain the effects of participants' attitudes towards SDM, subjective norms, intention to engage in SDM & their relationship with the healthcare professional on the likelihood that participants prefer an active or passive consultation style. The logistic regression model was statistically significant, $\chi^2(4) = 30.911, p < .001$. The model explained 32.9% (Nagelkerke R^2) of the variance in preferred consultation style and correctly classified 93.3% of cases. Intention to engage in SDM ($p = .017$) and relationship with the healthcare professional ($p = .002$) were significant predictors of preferred consultation style. Attitudes towards SDM ($p = .186$) and subjective norms ($p = .097$) were not significant predictors of preferred consultation style. Those with higher intentions to engage in SDM preferred an active consultation style whilst participants who had a better relationship with their healthcare professional preferred to be more passive when making healthcare decisions. Once again both intention to engage in SDM and relationship with the healthcare professional were identified as important predictors of preferred consultation style.

Regression of All Significant Predictors on Satisfaction with the Healthcare Decision

To further examine the predictors of satisfaction with the healthcare decision, correlations and a multiple regression analysis was carried out with the variables that were significant predictors of satisfaction with the healthcare decision: subjective norms, self-efficacy, intention to engage in SDM, relationship with healthcare professional and knowledge of SDM.

Table 37

Correlations Between All Significant Predictor Variables and Satisfaction with the Healthcare Decision

	Subjective norms	Self-efficacy	Intention	Relationship with the Healthcare Professional	Satisfaction
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					Knowledge	
Subjective norms	1					
Self-efficacy	.404**	1				
Intention	.609**	.522**	1			
Relationship with the Healthcare professional	.142*	.515**	.406**	1		
Knowledge	.325**	.206**	.359**	.163*	1	
Satisfaction	.219**	.226**	.440**	.437**	.272**	1

As Table 37 above confirms, subjective norms, self-efficacy, intention, relationship with the healthcare professional and knowledge were all positively and significantly correlated with participants' satisfaction with their healthcare decision. Intention to engage in SDM was the highest correlated predictor variable, whilst subjective norms had the lowest correlation with satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

To further explore the relationship between all of the significant predictor variables with satisfaction with the healthcare decision, a multiple regression was carried out, using the enter method looking at all 5 variables: subjective norms, self-efficacy, intention, relationship with the healthcare professional and knowledge of SDM as predictors of satisfaction with the healthcare decision. The results of the regression analysis indicated that the model explained 27.8% of the variance and that the model was a significant predictor of SDM behaviour, $F(5,145) = 10.763$, $p = <.001$. In this model, participants' relationship with their healthcare professional ($\beta=.312$, $p<.001$) was the strongest predictor of their satisfaction with the healthcare decision, intention to engage in SDM ($\beta=.281$, $p=.004$) also contributed to the model, statistically significantly predicting satisfaction with the healthcare decision, whilst subjective norms ($\beta=.008$, $p=.925$), self-efficacy ($\beta=-.056$, $p=.522$) and knowledge of SDM ($\beta=.105$, $p=.182$) did not. Once again a patient's relationship with their healthcare professional and their intention to engage in SDM both turned out to be important predictors, this time of satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

6.6 Discussion

There is a dearth of research on patients' engagement with SDM and an important aim of the current study was to address this by adopting the TPB as a model to explain factors that might influence engagement in SDM amongst general Scottish patients. The main focus of the study was to test the predictions of the TPB model in relation to SDM, by examining the impact of the key TPB variables (attitudes towards SDM, subjective norms and self-efficacy), on intention to engage in SDM and to examine the impact of these 4 variables (attitudes towards SDM, subjective norms and self-efficacy and intention) on engagement in SDM.

6.6.1. Primary Hypotheses

Intention to Engage in Shared Decision-Making (Outcome Variable)

The first set of results concerned the primary hypotheses relating to participants' intention to engage in SDM where this was viewed as an outcome variable for the TPB analyses. When analysed individually, attitudes, subjective norms and self-efficacy all predicted participants' intention to engage in SDM, but when the three predictors were all entered into a multiple regression simultaneously, only subjective norms and self-efficacy were significant, with attitudes towards SDM found to be a nearly significant predictor of intention. These results are therefore mostly consistent with the predictions of the TPB and largely correspond with Thompson-Leduc et al.'s (2015) finding that subjective norms, perceived behavioural control and attitude were the most frequently identified determinants of healthcare professionals' intention to engage in SDM-related behaviours. In the current study, patients' intentions were influenced by what other people close to them think about SDM and by how effectively individuals believe they can engage in SDM.

Predictors of Engagement in Shared Decision-Making

The next step in testing the primary hypotheses relating to the TPB was to test the predictors of engagement in SDM behaviour. When looked at individually, intention was found to be a good predictor of engagement in SDM behaviour. This reflects Ajzen's (1991) belief that the greater the intention to perform a behaviour, the increased likelihood that the behaviour is engaged in. Also consistent with this belief and the current hypothesis, the analyses of engagement in SDM behaviour showed that participants' who had higher scores for intention also had higher scores for engagement

in SDM behaviour. Thus, the stronger an individual's intention to engage in SDM behaviour, the increased likelihood that they will engage in SDM behaviour.

When all four TPB variables (attitudes, subjective norms, self-efficacy and intention) were entered simultaneously as predictors of engagement in SDM behaviour, intention was the strongest predictor, with self-efficacy also significant, but neither attitudes nor subjective norms were significant. This is consistent with the model of the TPB in Figure 5 above and also with Thompson-Leduc et al. (2015) who found that intention was the strongest predictor variable for a healthcare professional to carry out a SDM behaviour. While subjective norms and self-efficacy both predicted intention, only self-efficacy also had a direct impact on engagement in SDM behaviour. However, as noted previously, whilst self-efficacy was referred to as being a significant predictor of engagement in SDM behaviour, this may not have been the case had adjustments been made for multiple comparisons.

Overall, these results indicate that the TPB can play an important role in understanding engagement in SDM in Scottish patients' engagement in SDM.

6.6.2. Secondary Hypotheses

Relationships Between the Outcome Variables

Study 2 had suggested that it was difficult to find useful and reliable measures of SDM. While preferred consultation style is widely used in the literature, as we saw in study 2 it has limitations, and this was one reason for the introduction of the TPB model in study 3. A further important aim of the current study, but secondary to testing the predictions of the TPB, was to examine the links between the four outcome variables used in the current study: intention to engage in SDM, engagement in SDM behaviour, preferred consultation style, and satisfaction with the healthcare decision, another new variable introduced in study 3.

The TPB variables, intention and engagement in SDM behaviour, were both strongly related to patients' satisfaction with their healthcare decision, suggesting that these are all useful measures of engagement in SDM. Individuals with stronger intentions to engage in SDM and who actively engage in SDM behaviours are more satisfied with the healthcare decisions that they make. These results are consistent with Glass et al. (2012) who also found that SDM was positively associated with satisfaction with an individual's healthcare decision and with Shay and Lafata (2015) who found that patients who have engaged in SDM are more likely to have higher levels of satisfaction with their decision.

In contrast, preferred consultation style seemed to be less useful as a measure of SDM. It was only weakly linked to intention but was unrelated to engagement in SDM behaviour and satisfaction with

the healthcare decision. These results were unexpected as it was anticipated that all of the outcome variables would correlate with each other. These results also contrast with Charles et al.'s (1997) who found that an active consultation style is needed for engagement in SDM and with Golin et al. (1996), Guadagnoli & Ward (1998) and Frosch & Kaplan (1999) who reported that patient satisfaction is often associated with an active consultation style.

The TPB Variables as Predictors of Engagement in SDM Behaviours, Preferred Consultation Style and Satisfaction with the Healthcare Decision

As well as looking at the TPB predictor variables in relation to the TPB outcomes variables, intention and engagement, it was interesting to look at how well the TPB predictor variables: attitudes, subjective norms and self-efficacy, predicted the other outcome measures: preferred consultation style and satisfaction with the healthcare decision and individually on engagement in SDM.

Attitudes Towards Shared Decision-Making

The only outcome variable that attitudes was related to was preferred consultation style. This suggests that those who have more positive attitudes towards SDM are more likely to be active in their healthcare decisions. However, contrary to the current hypothesis, and to Ajzen (1991), Glass et al. (2012) and Shay & Lafata's (2015) previously discussed findings, participants' attitudes towards SDM did not predict their engagement in SDM behaviour, or satisfaction with the healthcare decision. Since attitudes is a key variable in the TPB (Ajzen, 1991), this result was unexpected, but it may be that the measure of attitudes used in the current study was not very good.

Subjective Norms

The finding that subjective norms was a significant predictor of all 3 outcome variables: engagement in SDM, satisfaction with the healthcare decision and preferred consultation style underlines the importance of what other people think in SDM. Glanz et al. (2008) view subjective norms as a key construct in the theory of planned behaviour and Joseph-Williams et al. (2014) regard what other people think as an "entry level" factor to taking part in SDM. The link between subjective norms and satisfaction with the healthcare decision shows that participants tend to be more satisfied with their healthcare decision when others who are close to them also endorse SDM. The link between subjective norms and participants' preference for an active consultation style was consistent with Brabers et al.'s (2016) and Doekhie et al.'s (2020) findings.

Self-efficacy

Consistent with Durand et al. (2014), Coulter (2012) and McCaffery et al (2010), participants who had higher self-efficacy scores in the current study were more engaged in SDM and were more satisfied with their healthcare decision (Molina et al., 2015; Zhong et al., 2013 and Kaya et al., 2018). This suggests that those who feel that they have more confidence and competence in making health-related decisions jointly with their health-care provider are better able to engage in SDM and will be more satisfied with the outcome of their healthcare decision. However, in contrast with Chawla and Arora (2013) and Arora et al. (2005), self-efficacy was not significantly associated with participants' preferred consultation style.

Demographic, Health-related and Study 2 Variables

None of the demographic variables impacted on the outcome variables. The only health-related and study 2 variables that impacted on the outcome variables in study 3 were the participant's relationship with their healthcare professional and knowledge of SDM. Relationship with their healthcare professional was an important predictor of all 3 main outcome variables: engagement with SDM behaviour, satisfaction with the healthcare decision and preferred consultation style. These findings are consistent with a substantial research base that suggests that a patient's relationship with their healthcare professional is very important in SDM. Deniz et al. (2021) found that the patient's relationship with the healthcare professional positively impacts SDM, while Eliacin et al., (2015) characterised the healthcare professional-patient relationship as the basis of SDM. This is also consistent with Eliacin et al. (2015) who found that patients who had a better and longer relationship with their healthcare professional preferred a passive consultation style, and Wrede-Sach et al. (2013) who also found that patients who experienced a good relationship with their healthcare professional relied on the healthcare professional for decision-making. Additionally, this is consistent with Prip et al. (2018) who found that the patient-healthcare professional relationship can impact patients' satisfaction with their healthcare, and Qudah & Luetsch (2019) who also report that increased patient satisfaction was associated with positive patient-healthcare professional relationships.

The regression analyses of the impact of all significant variables on the 3 outcome variables showed just how important this variable was, as the relationship with the healthcare professional was the strongest predictor of engagement in SDM behaviour, satisfaction with the healthcare decision, and preferred consultation style.

Knowledge of SDM was a predictor of both engagement in SDM behaviour and satisfaction with the healthcare decision, but did not predict preferred consultation style. These results are consistent with the findings of Stacey et al. (2017) who found that DAs increased patients' knowledge of SDM and satisfaction with the healthcare decision (Elwyn et al., 2015) and with Makarov et al. (2016) who found that patients who engaged in SDM had increased knowledge and satisfaction. These results are also consistent with Joseph-Williams et al. (2014) who found that patients require knowledge to engage in SDM. Similarly, Hawley and Morris, (2017) stated that for SDM to be achieved, patients need to have more knowledge about SDM and their condition. Additionally, Smith et al., (2009) found that participants with low health literacy wanted to participate in medical decisions but frequently lacked the knowledge to engage in SDM.

Although study 1 showed that DAs were not widely used at that time, the findings of study 3 suggest that knowledge is important to patients' engagement in SDM behaviour and satisfaction with their healthcare decision. These results suggest that patients would find it useful to have the relevant knowledge to assist them in making their healthcare decision and thus indicate that it could be useful to reconsider the role of decision aids to provide patients with this knowledge as DAs provide relevant information concerning the different possible outcomes and treatment options for different healthcare decisions which can be used to assist individuals in making their healthcare decisions. Other studies (Whelan et al., 2004; Stacey et al., 2011) have also suggested that DAs aid SDM by increasing patients' satisfaction with the decision and their knowledge of treatment options.

Contrary to the predictions and literature discussed in the hypotheses section, none of the demographic variables (age, gender, education level or employment status) were linked to any of the shared decision-making outcome variables and, apart from relationship with the healthcare professional, none of the health-related variables, self-rated health and frequency of attending medical appointments, were either. The only "study 2" variable that had a significant impact on the outcome variables was knowledge of SDM, with non-significant effects found for awareness of SDM.

6.6.3. Limitations & Ideas for Future Research

There were a few limitations surrounding the current study in relation to certain demographic characteristics. A lot more females than males took part in the current study and the vast majority of participants were educated to quite a high level of education. Similarly, there were not many unemployed participants. These demographic features possibly explain the non-significant effects for these variables. There also were not many participants who had preference for a passive consultation

style. Additionally, the knowledge items did not have an acceptable reliability, but these were included as these were the only knowledge items that could be found in relation to SDM and previous literature did find knowledge to be an important predictor for engagement in SDM and for satisfaction with the healthcare decision. Also, in retrospect, if the analyses were to be carried out again, then the p-values should be adjusted as discussed previously since multiple testing was carried out.

Ideas for future research include examining a different population such as healthcare professionals; patients with a specific health condition (such as chronic pain) or members of the general population for a different country for comparison to see if the same predictors significantly predict their engagement in SDM, preferred consultation style, intention to engage in SDM and satisfaction with the healthcare decision too. Also, a suggestion for future research would be to develop and validate a knowledge scale for SDM which has an acceptable reliability score.

6.7 Conclusion

A key conclusion from study 3 was that the theory of planned behaviour (Ajzen, 1991) provided a useful model in explaining SDM in patients and identified factors that predicted intention to engage and engagement in SDM behaviours. Thus, the TPB can help to identify variables that are key for engaging patients in SDM, so that they are more involved in making decisions about their healthcare, as this is an important aim in many modern healthcare systems (Scottish Government, 2016; Smith, 2024). Therefore, the purpose of this study was to investigate the variables that impact on engagement in SDM in patients in Scotland.

The results of the study have indicated that the following variables were important in supporting members of the Scottish general population to engage in SDM behaviours: participants' intention i.e. how much participants' plan to engage in SDM; subjective norms i.e. what other people close to participants think or feel about SDM; participants' self-efficacy i.e. how confidently participants believe that they can effectively engaging in SDM; participants' relationship with their healthcare professional & participants' knowledge of SDM.

Thus, two of the primary hypotheses were supported: participants' that had more intention to engage in SDM also engaged in more SDM behaviours and participants' intention to engage in SDM was the strongest predictor of engagement in SDM behaviours. However, one of these primary hypotheses was partially contradicted as self-efficacy was also a significant predictor of engagement in SDM when analysed simultaneously with attitudes towards SDM, subjective norms and intention to engage in SDM, but attitudes towards SDM and subjective norms were not found to be significant predictors of

engagement when analysed simultaneously. Additionally, consistent with the TPB and with three other primary hypotheses, participants' attitudes; subjective norms and self-efficacy were all significant predictors of their intention to engage in SDM when examined individually. However, mostly consistent with the TPB and with another primary hypothesis, participants' subjective norms and self-efficacy significantly predicted their intention to engage in SDM but participants' attitudes towards SDM marginally did not significantly predict their intention to engage in SDM when examined simultaneously.

Also, participants' relationship with their healthcare professional; participants' attitudes towards SDM, participants' subjective norms & participants' intention to engage in SDM were all significant predictors of participants' preferred consultation style. Participants' relationship with their healthcare professional; participants' subjective norms; participants' self-efficacy; participants' intention to engage in SDM, participants' engagement in SDM and participants' knowledge of SDM were all additionally found to be significant predictors of participant's satisfaction with their healthcare decision.

The identification of these important factors will be crucial to the successful implementation of SDM as this will increase both healthcare professionals' and patients' knowledge and understanding of what is key in order for patients to engage in SDM, to be more actively involved in healthcare decisions and to be happier with their healthcare decisions.

Chapter 7: A Qualitative Study of Attitudes to and Experiences of Shared Decision-Making in Individuals Experiencing Chronic Pain and in the General Population

7.1 Introduction

The fourth study of this work is a qualitative study of the attitudes to and experiences of shared decision-making (SDM) in individuals with chronic pain and individuals in the Scottish general population who have made a treatment decision regarding their healthcare. Study 4 follows on from studies 1, 2 and 3. Study 1 was a qualitative study which aimed to gather healthcare professionals' views on shared decision-making. Studies 2 and 3 were quantitative studies that aimed to identify factors that influence patients' engagement in SDM. Study 2, focused on chronic pain patients while study 3 focused on the general population and was grounded in the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB).

The current study aims to follow up on the findings from these studies in a more detailed qualitative exploration of patients' perceptions of SDM in healthcare decisions. The research question was: "What are the Scottish general populations and individuals with chronic pain attitudes to and experiences of SDM process?"

It is hoped that the findings of the study will provide a more detailed understanding of patients' views of SDM to help achieve a common understanding between patients and healthcare professionals which will contribute to more successful implementation of SDM.

7.1.1. Justification

The Scottish Government (2016) makes it clear that SDM is a critically important element of the new model of healthcare quality. SDM promotes self-management and independence and by giving patients a full understanding of their problems and greater responsibility for making choices, and it also helps to reduce over-use of medical interventions (Murray et al., 2004; O'Connor et al., 2009).

However, despite the extensive interest in SDM, the implementation of SDM within Scotland has been inconsistent (Coulter & Collins, 2011). SDM is still in its early stages and there is still uncertainty surrounding what it means and inconsistency in how it is implemented for both practitioners and patients. If it is to be successfully implemented, greater clarity is required about SDM.

In trying to provide greater consistency and aiming towards a more unified view on what SDM is, Bomhof-Roordink et al. (2019) carried out a systematic review that aimed to identify key components of SDM models. They found that the top components included: (1) describing treatment options, (2) making the decision, (3) patient preferences, (4) tailoring information, (5) deliberating, (6) creating choice awareness, (7) learning about the patient and (8) agreeing on the final decision. The current study will include questions about patients' experiences of these processes.

7.1.2. Why Chronic Pain and Members of the General Population?

Chronic pain has been chosen as one of the test cases as, in addition to having a considerable impact on the quality of life for many individuals and their families in Scotland, the condition also has a substantial impact on society and healthcare services. A systematic review of the effects of SDM on patient satisfaction, treatment adherence and health status by Joosten et al. (2008) found that SDM improved longer term outcomes in several studies that explored chronic health conditions.

Another reason for looking at both members of the Scottish general population and individuals with chronic pain is to examine if there are any differences or similarities in both populations in respect to their views on SDM as this has not been done before. This will also be important to the successful implementation of SDM as this will indicate if there are different needs for different populations for SDM to be beneficial to everyone. The most recent National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) guidance (Carmona et al., 2021) on SDM made recommendations for research to fill the most notable gaps in the evidence, agreeing that research was needed into how SDM differs in effectiveness between different populations (i.e., for this study, individuals with chronic pain and members of the general population).

Another NICE recommendation for research was how SDM needs to be modified for remote consultations (for example, by telephone or online) which the current study also asks participants in relation to the potential impact of COVID-19 on SDM.

Most research focus only on healthcare professionals' views of SDM (Forcino et al., 2018; Pollard et al., 2015). By focusing the current study on patients' views of SDM, this will help provide a rounder picture of SDM.

7.2 Methods

7.2.1. Participants

Purposive sampling (Etikan, Musa, & Alkassim, 2016) was used to recruit 12 participants who were members of the Scottish general population and 12 participants that experience chronic pain who also live in Scotland. Chronic pain was defined as pain that persists for more than 12 weeks despite treatment or medication (NHS Scotland, 2023). All participants were aged 18 years or older.

Purposive sampling was used for the current study as this form of sampling better matches participants with the objectives and aims of the study, hence increasing the reliability of the results and data and the rigour of the study (S. Campbell et al., 2020). Although 24 interviews were carried out as the researcher believed that 24 interviews would be required for the current study, only 14 of the interviews (7 general population & 7 chronic pain) were transcribed and analysed as data saturation had occurred at this point.

A light touch review was carried out on the remaining 10 transcripts to better inform the decision-making around saturation. Through doing this light touch review, it was apparent that no new themes or ideas were transpiring from the remaining 10 transcripts but rather just more quotes to support existing themes and sub-themes. Discussion concerning the consideration of the ethical issues of not analysing the data that participants have provided in the remaining 10 transcripts and some example quotes from these transcripts to further demonstrate that data saturation had occurred with the 14 transcripts can be found in the Limitations section later in this chapter.

Braun and Clarke (2021) state: "The recommended sample sizes to achieve data saturation within Thematic Analysis range from 6 to 16 interviews, depending on the specific characteristics of the research and the degree of data saturation required" (Braun & Clarke, 2021). Braun and Clarke (2021) also report that: "Using data from an interview study, (Guest, Bunce, & Johnson, 2006) found that 94% of what they call high frequency codes, codes applied to many interview transcripts, were identified within the first 6 interviews and 97% after 12 interviews. Thus, 'data saturation had for the most part occurred by the time we had analysed twelve interviews' (p. 74)."

Similar work has also utilised smaller participant numbers. Waterworth and Luker (1990) carried out interviews with a convenience sample of 12 patients to examine their perceptions of involvement in decisions about their care and treatment (Waterworth & Luker, 1990), and Friedberg, Van Busum, Wexler, Bowen, & Schneider (2013) carried out interviews with 10 patients to examine their

perceptions on implementing SDM (Friedberg et al., 2013). Thus 14 participants were sufficient for carrying out this study.

Out of the 14 participants' interviews that were used for this study, 12 were female and 2 were male. Both the general population and individuals with chronic pain participant groups consisted of 6 females and 1 male in each group. A summary of participants' demographics is presented in Table 38 below.

Table 38

Summary of Participant Demographics

Participant	Population Group	Gender
Participant 1	General Population	Female
Participant 2	Chronic Pain	Female
Participant 3	Chronic Pain	Female
Participant 4	General Population	Female
Participant 5	General Population	Female
Participant 6	General Population	Male
Participant 7	General Population	Female
Participant 8	General Population	Female
Participant 9	General Population	Female
Participant 10	Chronic Pain	Female
Participant 11	Chronic Pain	Female
Participant 12	Chronic Pain	Male
Participant 13	Chronic Pain	Female
Participant 14	Chronic Pain	Female

7.2.2. Data Collection

To recruit individuals with chronic pain for the current study, all of the charities listed on the Pain UK website were emailed a summary of the study, participant information sheets (see Appendices S and T), consent forms (see Appendix U) and a copy of the letter from the researchers' school ethics committee confirming permission to carry out the study.

To recruit members of the general population and some individuals with chronic pain, information about the study was shared on Facebook and Twitter (participants from studies 2 and 3 were also recruited using this method). Participants recruited through Facebook and Twitter were also sent emails containing a summary of the study, participant information sheets (see Appendices S and T), consent forms (see Appendix U) and a copy of the letter from the researchers' school ethics committee confirming permission to carry out the study.

Participants were asked to confirm that they lived in Scotland and if they experienced chronic pain prior to the interviews being carried out. Participants then took part in a Zoom call after reading the participant information sheet and signing a consent form. Data collection totalled 10 hours, 51 minutes and 32 seconds. Individual interviews ranged from 37.01 to 53.23 (average: 46.32) minutes in length.

The purpose of the study and the definition of SDM was explained to participants before questions were asked in the interviews. The definition used was: "Shared decision-making (SDM) is a practice in which patients and clinicians work in partnership to choose treatments, management packages, support packages, or tests based on the patient's informed preferences and clinical evidence" (Coulter & Collins, 2011). Each participant was also given the opportunity to ask questions before the interview questions were asked. After each interview, participants were emailed debrief sheets (see Appendices V and W).

The questions asked in the interviews focused on understanding patients' experiences SDM in relation to a healthcare decision that they had to make. Questions for the interview schedule (see Appendices Q & R) were drawn both from previous literature and from the results of studies 2 and 3 and assessed participants' views of factors that have helped and that have hindered their participation in SDM, such as knowledge of SDM, the amount of conflict linked to the decision made as well as other people's views or involvement, their attitudes towards SDM and their relationship with the healthcare professional. Other questions used in the interview were drawn from Bomhof-Roordink, et al.'s (2019) study which found that the top components of SDM included: (1) describing treatment options, (2) making the decision, (3) patient preferences, (4) tailoring information, (5) deliberating, (6) creating choice awareness, (7) learning about the patient and (8) agreeing on the final decision. The final set of

questions in the interview draw on participants' satisfaction with decisions due to SDM, how confident they feel in taking part in SDM and how SDM might need to be modified for remote consultations by asking participants the potential impact of COVID-19 on SDM.

The same core questions were asked to both groups of participants. There were also a series of prompts and further questions that were asked to participants if they were uncertain of how to answer the question or did not fully understand the question and for participants to elaborate on their answers. The prompts and further questions were the same for both groups of participants except for one. This prompt and further question read: "How does your chronic pain impact on your ability to take part in SDM?" for participants with chronic pain and read: "How does your *health condition* (if mentioned) impact on your ability to take part in SDM?" for members of the general population to determine whether chronic pain impacts on individuals' ability to take part in SDM differently than other health conditions.

7.2.3. Data Analysis

The study design was qualitative as semi-structured interviews were carried out. These interviews were recorded, then transcribed and thematically analysed. Both groups of participants' interviews were thematically analysed together.

Within qualitative research, amongst the most frequently used method of analysis is thematic analysis (Guest et al., 2011). Thematic analysis focuses on identifying, analysing and interpreting patterns of significance i.e. themes in qualitative data (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Prominent thematic analysis advocates, psychologists Virginia Braun and Victoria Clarke (Braun & Clarke, 2022) identify 3 predominant models of thematic analysis: code book approaches, coding reliability approaches and reflexive approaches. They characterise their own broadly used technique, first defined in the journal of Qualitative Research in Psychology in 2006 (Braun & Clarke, 2006), as reflexive thematic analysis.

Reflexive approaches focus on flexible and organic coding processes. Thus, there is no code book, and coding can be carried out by a single researcher. If numerous researchers are participating in coding, this is viewed as a cooperative process instead of one that should result in general agreement. Singular codes are not rigid – they can develop for the duration of the coding process, the confines of the code can be altered, codes can be divided into 2 or more codes, grouped with different codes and even developed into themes (Clarke & Braun, 2013). Reflexive approaches usually include later theme development with themes developed from grouping together similar codes. Themes should convey shared significance formed around a main idea or concept (Braun et al., 2014).

The thematic analysis of the data produced in study 4 can be described as following a reflexive approach and was carried out utilising Braun and Clarke's Six Phases of Thematic Analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006). This 6-phase cyclical process entails to and froing between the different phases of data analysis as required until the researcher is content with the final themes (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

As outlined by Braun and Clarke, phase 1 involved reading and re-reading data to become well-known with what the data encompasses, paying particular attention to patterns that transpired. Therefore, this first step involved listening to and transcribing the interview recordings, highlighting similarities between participants and in different parts of the interviews.

For the second phase, the researcher created the initial codes by recording where patterns in the data transpired, both within and between individual interviews. This occurred via data reduction where the researcher broke data down into labels to generate categories for more effective analysis. This entailed the researcher making inferences concerning what the codes signified.

In accordance with the third phase, the researcher examined the codes and the related data to form overarching themes and sub-themes. Related data and codes were grouped into significant themes and sub-themes which accurately described the different features of the data.

For the fourth phase, the researcher examined how the themes supported the codes and the interview data, making distinctions between some initial sub-themes. The themes were then grouped together in a separate word document to evaluate the associations between the themes and the corresponding subthemes.

During the fifth phase, the researcher defined each theme and sub-theme, which aspects of the data were being conveyed, and what was interesting about the themes and sub-themes. Both themes and sub-themes were also assigned labels.

For the final and sixth phase, the researcher wrote up the themes and sub-themes in this chapter, choosing quotes from different participants to emphasise the importance of each sub-theme. The sub-themes were also related to previous literature and the research questions. Differences in the discussion of sub-themes between the two groups of participants were also highlighted, thus the themes and sub-themes were examined at both an individual level and between the two groups of participants.

In accordance with best practice (Braun & Clarke, 2006), the thematic analysis was cyclical and iterative. Thus, the researcher moved between the 6 stages in a non-linear fashion. The grouping and refining of codes, sub-themes and themes were carried out by the researcher with guidance from the supervision team. The first five phases were carried out using a software package for analysing

qualitative data, NVIVO 12. To convey the process of theme creation, a summary of the codes, subthemes and themes are highlighted in Table 39 below.

7.3. Findings

Using the previously discussed procedure of thematic analysis, themes were identified from the interviews with participants, and these were then further categorised into sub-themes. The themes and sub-themes will be outlined and discussed in relation to previous literature. The themes and sub-themes will also be discussed in relation to the two participant groups (members of the Scottish General Population and individuals with chronic pain who live in Scotland) in terms of similarities or differences in themes and sub-themes between the two groups. A summary of the representativeness of themes and sub-themes across each participant and group of participants are presented in Table 40 below.

Table 39

Summary of Themes, Sub-themes and Codes

Themes	Sub-themes	Codes
1) Support from Others	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Relationship with the Healthcare Professional; b) Advice from Other People; c) Agreement on Decision; d) Impact on Others 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Relationship with the healthcare professional; Trust b) Advice or involvement of family or friends; Advice from others with same condition c) Agreement on decision; Conflict d) Consider impact on others
2) Healthcare	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Participants' Health*; b) Frequency of Attending Appointments*; c) Treatment Options; d) Health Conditions; e) Private Healthcare* 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Health or well-being; Participant knows themselves b) Has a lot of health issues or goes to doctors a lot; Rarely at doctors or make big healthcare decisions c) Medication; Injection; Non-pharmacological treatment options; Surgery; Self-management d) Pregnancy; Pain; Depression; Mental health e) Private healthcare
3) Engagement in Health Decisions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Active Involvement*: b) Paternalism, c) The Final Decision; d) Engaging in Shared Decision-making. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Active in healthcare; Passive; Ownership or accountability; Carry out own research b) Paternalism; Found it harder to take part in SDM when younger; Generational differences; Not involved in making a decision

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> c) Healthcare professional make final decision; Patient make the final decision; Make decisions on behalf of someone else d) Take part in SDM; Take part in SDM in the future; Take part in SDM now because of a bad experience; Shared decision-making
4) COVID-19 on Shared Decision-making	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Impact of COVID-19; b) Remote Consultations; c) Face-to-face Consultations* 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Impact of COVID-19; Negative impacts of COVID-19 b) Remote Consultations; Privacy c) Face-to-face consultation; Non-verbal communication or body language
5) Participants' Feelings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Uncertainty; b) Happy with the Decision; c) Unhappy with the Decision; d) Shared Decision-Making is a Positive Thing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Uncertain; Worried or anxious b) Happy with the decision; Comfortable or reassured c) Unhappy; Rubbish experience d) SDM is a good thing; SDM is important
6) Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Access*; b) Hardships and Moving Locations; c) Healthcare Professional's Attitude*; d) Time 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Access b) A lot of changes, hardships or moving location c) Attitude or willingness of healthcare professional to engage; Skills; Tool d) Time
7) Facilitators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Awareness*; b) Occupation; c) Prepared; d) Tailored*; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Aware of SDM b) Participant or family member is an academic; Participant or their family is a healthcare professional c) Prepared

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> e) Knowledge; f) Confidence; g) Communication; h) Control 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> d) Tailor; Visual e) Knowledge; Healthcare professional's experience and knowledge; Informed consent f) Confidence g) Communication h) Control
8) Important Considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Quality of life; b) Culture; c) Differences between Healthcare Professionals; d) Shared Decision-making Can Be Situational 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Quality of life; Outcomes b) Culture c) Differences between different healthcare professionals d) SDM can be situational; SDM suitable in all scenarios
9) Areas for Improvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Concerns around Shared Decision-making; b) Finance; c) Pressures in the NHS; d) Healthcare Needs Improved 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Concerns about SDM; Power dynamics b) Finance c) Pressures in the NHS; Long waiting list; NHS understaffed d) SDM or healthcare needs improved

Table 40

Representativeness of Themes and Sub-themes Across Each Participant/Group of Participants

		General Population group	Chronic Pain group	Participant													
				G1	G2	G3	G4	G5	G6	G7	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7
Themes and Sub-themes	1a	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
	1b	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
	1c	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
	1d	Y	Y	N	N	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y
	2a*	Y	Y	N	N	N	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
	2b*	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	N	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
	2c	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
	2d	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
	2e*	Y	Y	Y	N	N	N	Y	N	Y	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y
	3a*	Y	Y	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y

	General Population group	Chronic Pain group	Participant													
			G1	G2	G3	G4	G5	G6	G7	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7
3b	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
3c	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
3d	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
4a	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
4b	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
4c*	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
5a	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
5b	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
5c	Y	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
5d	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
6a*	Y	Y	N	N	N	Y	Y	N	N	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
6b	Y	Y	N	N	Y	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	N	N	N	Y	Y

	General Population group	Chronic Pain group	Participant													
			G1	G2	G3	G4	G5	G6	G7	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7
6c*	Y	Y	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
6d	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
7a*	Y	Y	N	N	N	N	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	N	N
7b	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
7c	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y
7d*	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	Y	Y	N	N	N	Y
7e	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
7f	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
7g	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
7h	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	N
8a	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
8b	Y	Y	N	Y	N	Y	Y	N	N	Y	N	N	Y	N	Y	N

	General Population group	Chronic Pain group	Participant														
			G1	G2	G3	G4	G5	G6	G7	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	
8c	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	
8d	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	
9a	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	N
9b	Y	Y	N	N	N	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	N	N	Y	Y	N	
9c	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	
9d	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	

7.3.1 Support from Others

This theme highlights the importance of the participants' relationships with their healthcare professional, family and other individuals and the amount of support they received from these people. Participants felt happier with treatment decisions when they had a good relationship with their healthcare professional. Participants also valued receiving advice from family, partners and other people with the same health condition as them on healthcare decisions. Additionally, participants spoke about the extent to which the healthcare professional agreed with them on the healthcare decision. Finally, participants considered the impact that different aspects of SDM and that similar health conditions have on other people. Therefore, this theme was composed of the following sub-themes: "relationship with the healthcare professional", "advice from other people", "agreement on decision" and "impact on others".

Relationship with the Healthcare Professional

Both groups of participants frequently cited that their relationship with the healthcare professional was an important aspect of their healthcare and for taking part in SDM. Slightly more members of the general population highlighted that trust in the healthcare professional was also a crucial part of their relationship with the healthcare professional. Participants who stated that they had a good relationship with their healthcare professional spoke about their healthcare experience and decision much more positively and one participant even went as far to say that her decision was "life-changing".

"...having a positive relationship always helps because I was confident that I had been given all the information that I needed and I trusted the information that I was given and I felt comfortable saying what I thought which isn't always the case. I know that I've seen some people where they either don't believe the doctor or they're not confident in the doctor but no, my GP has always been absolutely lovely and the heart guy I couldn't fault."

(P008, Member of the General Population, Female)

Participants who had a good relationship with their healthcare professional also frequently mentioned feeling comfortable, at ease, attended to and reassured with decisions because of their relationship with the healthcare professional. Whereas participants who did not have a good relationship with their healthcare professional spoke about their healthcare experience and decision in a more negative manner with one participant describing their experience as being "traumatic". Participants who had a negative relationship with their healthcare professional did not feel listened to, felt unhappy understood and felt that they were being dismissed.

“They just didn't listen. They didn't have an interest. They didn't understand my pain. They didn't understand what I was saying. They didn't seem to care... if I questioned them or asked for further information, they didn't provide it. They didn't like being questioned and I just found the whole process very, very negative.”

(P010, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Participants also discussed how building a relationship with the healthcare professional could be difficult if they had to move NHS Boards and geographical location, if it was their first time seeing or meeting the healthcare professional or if they do not consistently see the same healthcare professional for every appointment.

“I think it all comes down to relationships. I think having 10 minutes with somebody is fine if you know them really, really well, but I have seen a different GP every single time I've gone up to the GP practice... So I think that model of care is based on a GP who has been in the Community... serving the Community for decades and that's not the model of care that is actually being delivered... because trying to get a named GP is near impossible these days.”

(P002, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

The importance of their relationship with their medical practitioner is consistent with the results of study 3, where this was found to impact on many of the key SDM variables. For example, participants who had a better relationship with their healthcare professional reported the following: more knowledge of SDM; greater intention to engage in SDM; engaged in more SDM behaviours; preferred a more active consultation style; and were more satisfied with the outcome of their health-care decision.

The importance of having a good relationship with their healthcare practitioner is also evident in the literature. For example, Elwyn et al. (2012) found that attaining SDM is dependent upon establishing a good relationship between patients and healthcare professionals. One of the most cited components (53%) from Bomhof-Roordink et al.'s (2019) systematic review of SDM models was “Learn about the patient”. Deniz et al. (2021) also found that the relationship with the healthcare professional positively impacts SDM. Thus, highlighting the importance of a positive relationship between patients and healthcare professionals in SDM.

Advice from Other People

Both groups of participants stated that they turned to family members or partners for advice on healthcare decisions or to use them as “sounding boards” to talk through their healthcare decision.

“I do discuss these things with my family, they weren't... they wouldn't be directly involved with the decision, I just... I think I do do a bit of like sounding board with them though and I suppose they would influence my feelings about things, they wouldn't be involved directly in the healthcare interaction. My sister-in-law is a doctor in child health and I asked her opinion about taking this medication...”

(P013, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Joyce et al. (2013) believed that involving the patient's family or significant other, if the patient wanted to, in the decision-making process was a key part of SDM. Coulter and Collins (2011) also stated that when making healthcare decisions, information on its own is not enough. Information has to be complemented with support from peers, family and friends which can increase individuals' engagement in the decision-making.

Kane, Halpern, Squiers, Treiman, & McCormack (2014) additionally reported that whilst some individuals might only require a short summary of the benefits and risks to feel at ease in decision-making, others might require more support and time to discuss their options with friends, family members or other individuals that encountered a similar decision. However, most participants with chronic pain stated that whilst they would discuss their healthcare decision with others, their family members or partners would not be involved in making the final healthcare decision.

The current results provide qualitative evidence highlighting the importance of others in making health decisions. This further endorses the results of study 3 which showed that subjective norms, from the TPB behaviour predicted varied aspects of engagement in SDM. Subjective norms refer to the perceived social pressure to carry out or not to carry out the target SDM behaviour and an example item was: “most people who are important to me would recommend that I engage in shared decision-making.”. Authors, such as Glanz et al. (2008), have argued that subjective norms are a key construct in the application of the TPB to health behaviours.

Some participants from both groups noted how it was hard to have family members involved as they lived far from where they stayed or even in a different country. Also, some members of the general population mentioned how the lockdown and associated restrictions as result of the COVID-19 pandemic prevented seeing family members for advice and from their partner being able to attend appointments with them. However, one participant with chronic pain did mention that the medical facility they attended did allow families to visit and attend appointments even throughout COVID-19. A few participants with chronic pain also said that they would only discuss healthcare decisions with family members or partners if the healthcare decision directly impacted on them. One participant with chronic pain said they do not involve others in making healthcare decisions at all.

Some participants from both groups mentioned that they find it useful to receive advice and support from other people who have the same health condition as them whether that was from an in-person support group or on Facebook groups.

“...what is really helpful is talking to other people in your situation as well because you do get to know a lot through that of what treatment, other people with your same disease, what treatment they are on, in what combinations etc. and that is really, really useful and what other health boards do and what they offer, and that in terms of shared decision-making, that is a very useful, fount of knowledge as well, people with the same disease as you.”

(P011, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

One member of the general population mentioned that she would read about others' experiences and stories of the same condition. A few participants from both groups also mentioned how it was useful to consult family members who were healthcare professionals or academics for more information regarding their healthcare decision.

Agreement on Decision

Another frequently discussed topic by both groups of participants was the extent to which the healthcare professional agreed with the participant on the healthcare decision. Bomhof-Roordink et al. (2019) carried out a systematic review that aimed to identify key components of SDM models and found that the healthcare professional and the patient agreeing on the final decision was amongst one of the key components in a majority of SDM models. Researchers (Makoul & Clayman, 2006) also found that whilst SDM usually results in agreement on the healthcare decision, conflicting views between the healthcare professional and the patient can still occur after taking part in SDM. Other researcher (Dy & Purnell, 2012) additionally reported that skills in resolving conflict was a key component of SDM.

Some participants said that they and the healthcare professional both agreed on the healthcare decision. Some participants also felt that their healthcare professional would be happy to agree on any decision they made. However, some chronic pain participants mentioned that there was some conflict between them and the healthcare professional as they did not agree on the healthcare decision.

“I had said to the midwife because she was just kind of going down through the checklist and she was like "so... I'll consent you for that now" and I said "no, I'm not going to proceed to have that checked" and she said, started arguing with me about how, she would get it done... was trying to tell me exactly what to do...in terms of investigations and all the rest of it, like she was incredibly experienced and very caring but in her particular way, not in... she wasn't responding to the... like to my kind of needs

or the way I presented on that day. She was... she encountered resistance to her usual way of practice, and therefore, she wrestled rather than rolling with it... she geared up to do battle to tell me exactly what I was gonna do and how I was gonna do it.”

(P002, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

A number of participants from both groups mentioned that whilst the healthcare professional initially did not agree with a healthcare decision, the healthcare professional did still respect and go ahead with their decision. Interestingly, one participant with chronic pain mentioned how the healthcare professional did not agree with the healthcare decision and was grateful on reflection that the healthcare professional did disagree with her on the healthcare decision. A member of the general population mentioned leaving consultations and arranging appointments with other healthcare professionals due to the healthcare professional’s disagreement on the healthcare decision, whilst other participants from both groups felt that the healthcare professional forced them to agree to a healthcare decision.

“At one point, I'd seen them and they wanted me to see the psychologist and I said "I'm not really keen on seeing the psychologist because I don't see how they can help with my chronic pain" and they said, "well, if you don't see the psychologist, you'll be discharged today from the chronic pain service" and I was like "really?!" So they kind of almost bullied me into agreeing to see the psychologist, which I didn't like but I did because I accepted it and said "right, OK, fine, put me forward for the psychologist" 'cause I didn't want to lose my place within this service but I thought that was a really rubbish way of going about it.”

(P010, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Impact on Others

Both groups of participants not only spoke about how healthcare decisions and health conditions impacted on them, but they also considered the impact that their healthcare decision or health condition has on their family member and on other people with the same health condition.

Elwyn et al. (2015) highlighted that most studies aim to examine how SDM may enhance impacts for patients and others too. Previous research (Lown, Hanson, & Clark, 2009) found that it was important for patients to consider the needs of their family and partners when making healthcare decisions and that this improved SDM. Researchers (Gabe, Olumide, & Bury, 2004) suggest different scenarios where SDM includes and has an impact on others outwith or in addition to the patient and healthcare professional such as on the family and carers.

“...I'd had waves and waves of anxiety, it's horrible. People that have suffer this all their lives, I mean my heart goes out to them, it's horrific, it must be really horrible. Gave me a better understanding on that I have to say, on how it must feel to feel in that world and how they make joint decisions, God only knows...”

(P009, Member of the General Population, Female)

Two participants with chronic pain considered the impact that extending an appointment has on others waiting to be seen. One of these participants also considered the impact that not involving patients in decisions has on those patients and mentioned hesitation to make an appointment or to be referred to a service as they were considering that another individual may need the appointment or service more. A member of the general population considered the impact of capacity in taking part in SDM for young adults, individuals with mental health issues, individuals with learning disabilities and for children. Another member of the general population also mentioned that one of their biggest motivators for taking part in SDM was considering the impact it has on others.

“I think that's probably my big motivator for that kind of shared decision-making is that as many people get the best outcome as possible, and that's not only for me, but if you know. ..but if by following that recommended pathway, uhm, and understanding it, buying into it means that resource is saved on me to give to someone else who does need it more than I do, then I also... I feel better about that too.”

(P006, Member of the General Population, Male)

7.3.2. Healthcare

This theme identifies the key aspects of participants' healthcare. Participants spoke about the importance of being involved with healthcare decisions regarding their health, how much they valued their health, how having multiple health conditions can impact on their healthcare decisions and being able to tell when they need to see a healthcare professional. How often participants attended appointments and saw healthcare professionals was also highlighted. The most frequently discussed treatment options and health conditions were also identified. Additionally, participants discussed their experience of receiving private healthcare.

Therefore, this theme was composed of the following sub-themes: “participant's health”, “frequency of attending appointments”, “treatment options”, “health conditions” and “private healthcare”.

Participant's Health

Although both groups of participants did mention aspects related to their health, more participants with chronic pain felt that it was important to take part in SDM and in decisions regarding their healthcare so that it would empower them to take the best course of action for their health. Also, as participants with chronic pain felt that the decisions were being made about their health and their body, they needed to be involved in the healthcare decisions.

“It's my life, it's my health, I need to be involved. So, it's that straightforward.”

(P010, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Participants from both groups valued their health and spoke about ways in which they positively managed their health.

“I'm already very healthy, I do five exercise classes a week. I eat everything from scratch. I've got a decent diet...”

(P009, Member of the General Population, Female)

A couple of participants with chronic pain also mentioned that due to having multiple health conditions or due to the effects of taking multiple medication, that they had to take these factors into consideration when making healthcare decisions or decisions that might impact on their health.

“...especially if you've got underlying and I've got, I'm taking an immune suppressant drug. I don't want to predict when we mix with other people that may have the virus because the implications it would have on my health.”

(P012, Chronic Pain Participant, Male)

Additionally participants with chronic pain also explained that because they live with their health conditions, they can feel or know if something is not right in relation to their health and to then contact a healthcare professional as a result.

Frequency of Attending Appointments

Both groups of participants spoke about how often they attended appointments or visited their GP regarding their healthcare. Participants who experience chronic pain stated that they attended healthcare appointments frequently as they have multiple health conditions. Some of these participants mentioned attending different hospitals, GPs and being seen by different healthcare professionals such as doctors, nurses, rheumatologists and consultants.

“In the past two, three years I've been in the healthcare system a lot in different GP practices, in different hospitals and I feel like I have quite a clear picture where the NHS it works the best...”

(P003, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Whereas participants that were members of the general population reported that this was the first big healthcare decision they had to make or their first time engaging in SDM in relation to their healthcare as they rarely attend healthcare appointments or see their GP.

“I've been healthy all my life. It's not like, I've never had and maybe that's what makes it worse, 'cause I've never had anything wrong, it suddenly kind of felt like it was like a train crash, I was like "oh my God, what is happening to me?"

(P009, Member of the General Population, Female)

Treatment Options

Both groups of participants discussed the treatment options that they considered in making their healthcare decisions. Whilst the majority of the treatment options centred around pharmacological choices such as medication, injections and surgery, both groups of participants also discussed self-management and non-pharmacological treatment options.

“...there was more kind of holistic things to sort of try to take some space, go for more walks, get some fresh air, and do some exercise at those kinds of things. We talked about the possibility of... the use of counselling or CBT and that sort of thing...”

(P006, Member of the General Population, Male)

Other forms of non-pharmacological treatment options that were discussed included: physiotherapy, hypnotherapy, acupuncture, changes to diet, heat, mindfulness, reiki and pain control psychology. Participants who were members of the general population preferred using non-pharmacological treatments and felt that they worked better than pharmacological treatment options. Chronic pain participants felt they had to use non-pharmacological treatment options because there was either no other options for them to use or they had to use them to stay on their health board's pain service but stated that these options did help.

“...what I find is that heat helps reduce the pain. So one of these heat rubs that you can purchase for muscle pain, it seems to, at times, help with the nerve ending pain.”

(P012, Chronic Pain Participant, Male)

Whilst both groups of participants discussed self-management of their health condition, more participants with chronic pain mentioned the importance of self-management “just to be able to get out of bed” and carry out day-to-day tasks, highlighting how these patients become dependent on effective self-management. Slightly more participants with chronic pain also stated that their healthcare decisions focused on taking new or different medications, although one chronic pain participant said that their healthcare decision was that there were no medications that could be prescribed to help with their health condition. Participants with chronic pain also discussed that steroid injections were used to help treat their chronic pain. Whilst both groups of participants mentioned surgery, operations and c-sections when discussing their healthcare decision, slightly more members of the general population discussed surgery as a treatment option.

Health Conditions

The most talked about health conditions by participants were pregnancy, chronic pain and mental health conditions such as depression, stress, anxiety and panic attacks. Although both groups of participants spoke about pregnancy and family planning, slightly more members of the general population discussed pregnancy as being the focus point of their healthcare decision. However, it was only participants who experience chronic pain that discussed chronic pain as being the focus point of their healthcare decision and how their chronic pain can impact on their decision-making regarding their healthcare.

“...pain, so I think you just want rid of it as quickly as possible and if that means a more severe action to get rid of the pain, then sometimes it needs to be that way...”

(P014, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Whilst both groups of participants discussed having mental health conditions, slightly more chronic pain participants discussed mental health than members of the general population. Participants with chronic pain mentioned how there is a link between their chronic pain condition and mental health and how the two can impact on their healthcare experiences.

“...so I experience migraine and I'm hypermobile and... it's emerged that anxiety is quite commonly associated with hyper mobility, so I really... probably get a bit nervous before consultations and then go in, speak at 100 miles an hour and then quite often get dismissed sometimes about different concerns...”

(P002, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Another participant with chronic pain also explained how their chronic pain has a big impact on their mental health which subsequently impacts on their ability to engage in their healthcare. Participants with chronic pain and mental health conditions felt like they were not understood, being listened to by the healthcare professional or involved in healthcare decisions. A member of the general population also stated that feeling they had not been listened to by the healthcare professional or involved in decisions could also impact on mental health, causing worry and stress.

Another member of the general population voiced concerns about individuals who have limited mental capacity being able to take part in SDM and how comfortable individuals with mental health conditions feel in taking part in healthcare decisions. For example, a participant with chronic pain also explained that she felt she could not take part in SDM in her healthcare decision as she did not feel she had the mental capacity to understand everything and make decisions regarding her health at the time.

“I guess my mental health is better as well. So I'm able to think about these things a bit more and really have like, yeah, to make an informed decision. So I think... maybe that's why patients are a bit less included in this decision-making process as well when it comes to... lifesaving treatments that... how able are the patients actually to make those decisions, whether to undertake chemotherapy or surgery or anything because clearly, I at least, wasn't at the right state mentally to make those decisions.”

(P003, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Private Healthcare

Whilst the majority of participants received healthcare through the NHS, more than half of participants also mentioned receiving private healthcare. More participants with chronic pain received private healthcare than members of the general population. Participants from both groups sought private healthcare due to more treatment options and services being available via private healthcare and one chronic pain participant said they went private to avoid overwhelming the NHS. Participants from both groups also felt that private healthcare was better than the healthcare they received on the NHS as more time was allocated for appointments, less waiting times and the communication with the healthcare professional was better.

“Way better, significantly better. You've got, I mean, obviously you're paying for this expertise, but you had someone... who absolutely emphasised, listened, gave me a whole range of options, spoke me through what those options were... what factors I should consider, what else I might want to consider.

She was absolutely brilliant and then said "I'll write to your GPs practice, summarise our conversation, and highlight what we've agreed" and she did. It was brilliant."

(P009, Member of the General Population, Female)

7.3.3. Engagement in Health Decisions

This theme focuses on the level of engagement that patients and healthcare professionals demonstrated in making healthcare decisions. Half of all participants were actively involved in their healthcare and felt it was important that they were involved in healthcare decisions. Most participants encountered paternalism when making healthcare decisions and spoke about the harms associated with paternalism. Additionally, participants spoke about who made the final healthcare decision: themselves or the healthcare professional. Finally, most participants discussed taking part in SDM and most participants said they would take part in SDM in the future. Therefore, this theme was composed of the following sub-themes: "active involvement", "paternalism", "the final decision" and "engaging in shared decision-making".

Active Involvement

Whilst one member of the general population did say that they were active in their healthcare, it was mostly participants with chronic pain who were actively involved with their healthcare. Primarily participants with chronic pain believed it was important for themselves to be involved in decisions around their health as it is their body, and it gave them a sense of ownership in their healthcare. Participants with chronic pain also believed it was important for other people to take accountability and to be actively involved in their healthcare too.

"...it ultimately is their body, their health. They need to be involved in the decision-making."

(P010, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

One participant with chronic pain even described a campaign called the "it's ok to ask" campaign created by the Scottish Government, intended to encourage patients to ask questions about the benefits, risks and alternatives of treatment options (NHS 24, 2023). However, some participants with chronic pain did consider that it may be difficult to be actively involved in healthcare decisions due to pain, mental health, "having a bad day", not being given encouragement or the opportunity to engage, or not being prepared for consultations. A number of chronic pain participants also mentioned that whilst they like to be involved with their healthcare, they did also rely on the healthcare professional's

knowledge or expertise to make some decisions. Chronic pain participants also discussed that they felt that they really had to push and be their own advocate to be involved in their healthcare.

“...my experience has been that I'm having to really fight for that information...I'm having to be my own advocate...you also need to be given the opportunity to talk through options. My experience has been that I haven't been given that opportunity at the start, I have had to ask question after question and request an opportunity to discuss options.”

(P011, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Given the importance of having relevant knowledge about their condition in order to be in a position to engage in SDM (Joseph-Williams et al., 2014; Hawley & Morris, 2017) this suggests that more still needs to be done in helping patients in this. Whilst both groups of participants discussed that they tend to carry out their own research into their health condition or treatment options, it was mostly participants with chronic pain that tended to do this. However, a member of the general population believed that it was important for others to also carry out their own research surrounding their health condition or treatment options.

“I think actually, patient advocacy where you actually going learn yourself, find out as much as you can about how you stay healthy is really important. You have to learn and if you've got a particular condition, say it was arthritis or bone problems, you should go and find out what you need to do to prevent it and then when you get it, what are the best facilities and things that you can do? Other than just medication that might actually make you better.”

(P009, Member of the General Population, Female)

However, both groups of participants acknowledged that it may be more difficult for some individuals to be able to carry out their own research on their health condition, as not everyone will have access to technology and the internet to be able to do so. Taking an active role in making decisions about their health is consistent with the findings of both studies 2 and 3. When asked about their preferred consultation style using Yen et al.'s (2019) single item measure: “How do you think healthcare decisions should be made?”, the vast majority of participants preferred an active consultation style over a passive one, with 94% of participants in study 2 and 92% in study 3 opting for an active consultation style. Active consultation style was derived from the 3 responses where the balance of responsibility leaned more towards the patient. In both studies the most popular choice of the 5 responses was: “I should make the final decision about treatment after seriously considering my healthcare professional's opinion.”, closely followed by “The healthcare professional should share responsibility with me for making the final treatment decision.”. This suggests that the majority of patients accept

that they have an important role to play in making their healthcare decisions, and that the balance of responsibility in making the health-related decision for many patients lies more towards them than the professional. Very few patients agreed that they should make the decision entirely on their own.

Paternalism

Both groups of participants disagreed with paternalism and discussed their experiences and the harms of paternalism. Both groups of participants discussed that they did not feel listened to, felt unhappy, were not given the chance to voice their opinion, that the healthcare professional did not include them in making decisions, were not given choices or information, were made to go along with decisions and they were made to feel small by paternalistic healthcare professionals.

“...there was a long time ago, I remember this is what decades ago, seeing a GP and saying "I've got the flu, doctor" and the reply was "and how many years did you spend at medical school?" So in other words, the impression was, you know, I'm the professional, you're the patient, I'll tell you what you've got...”

(P012, Chronic Pain Participant, Male)

Both groups of participants discussed how paternalistic healthcare professionals acted as if they were the experts and that they knew best because they have the medical knowledge and have been used to telling patients what to do. A few participants, mostly members of the general population said that they found it harder to take part in healthcare decisions in the past or when they were younger. Both groups of participants also discussed how there is a generational difference when it comes to paternalism as older people still believe the doctor knows best and when they were younger, they were encouraged to go along with what the healthcare professional said.

“...my mother's generation didn't ask questions and just did what the doctor said... it can be cultural as well and I've definitely seen that in my own upbringing... when I was a child... and as growing up there was... I would have been encouraged to accept the doctor says rather than ask the doctor a few questions.”

(P007, Member of the General Population, Female)

These reflections are consistent with the results of the previous studies where only 12/195 participants in study 2 and 16/210 in study 3 selected the more paternalistic passive option as their preferred consultation style, showing how the majority of these participants rejected paternalistic perspective

on health care. They are also consistent with the move away from paternalism reflected in the literature (Tonelli & Sullivan, 2019).

The Final Decision

Whilst both groups of participants stated that they made or typically like to make the final healthcare decision, it was mostly chronic pain participants who made the final healthcare decision. Interestingly, whilst members of the general population liked to make the final healthcare decision, two participants with chronic pain were unhappy that the final decision was left to them to make.

“I kind of felt like the GP was just submitting to my request... I guess that has an implication for shared decision-making, because again, the healthcare professional isn't kind of putting across their view on whether or not this is the most appropriate step forward and they're probably going with the path of least resistance and I suppose this can lead to inefficiencies within the service”

(P002, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Again, whilst both groups of participants reported that the healthcare professional made the final healthcare decision, it was mostly chronic pain participants that said the healthcare professional made the final healthcare decision. While most chronic pain participants said they were not happy about the healthcare professional making the final healthcare decision, there were some participants from both groups who were happy that the final healthcare decision was made by the healthcare professional as it helped take some of the burden off of themselves. Two participants with chronic pain also said that if it was a life-or-death situation or if a loved one was in an emergency situation then they would want the healthcare professional to make the final healthcare decision. However, one member of the general population thought that people should never let the healthcare professional make the final healthcare decision.

“They shouldn't be just going to rely on a medical professional go "well I've got this. What you gonna do about it?" I think that's wrong...”

(P009, Member of the General Population, Female)

Additionally, although both groups of participants mentioned making healthcare decisions on behalf of other people, there was slightly more members of the general population who talked about making healthcare decisions on behalf of other people. One member of the general population mentioned representative or parents making decisions on behalf of children or individuals with mental health or learning disabilities. Other members of the general population discussed making decision on behalf of

family members or spouses in terminal decisions. Chronic pain participants said they would want a family member or a healthcare professional to make healthcare decisions on their behalf if they were in an emergency situation or they had Alzheimer's or advanced Dementia.

Engaging in Shared Decision-making

Although both groups of participants said that they take part in SDM, there were slightly more participants with chronic pain that said that they take part in SDM. Participants from both groups stated that they liked to take part in SDM and think others should also take part in SDM. Nearly all participants from both groups said they were happy with their healthcare decision because they engaged in SDM, therefore they felt they were involved in making the decision and understood the decision. Both groups of participants did also highlight that it can be difficult to engage in SDM if the healthcare professional does not give patients the opportunity to engage in SDM or if the healthcare professional does not want to engage in SDM.

"I think when you have someone who is up for that, that makes such a difference in the world but I think if you're faced with someone who doesn't want to get involved, 'cause I would want to do that, absolutely for everything, but if the medical professional doesn't want to do that, you are still on a back foot, it's just not great."

(P009, Member of the General Population, Female)

Two participants with chronic pain that were healthcare professionals also discussed how they like to ensure that they engage in SDM with their patients and it is important that they do engage in SDM with their patients regardless. Participants from both groups also explained that they like to take part in SDM now because of difficult and negative healthcare experiences and negative experiences of SDM. They noted that because they have gone through these negative experiences it has given them the confidence to take part in SDM now.

"I don't know if that in part comes with having a kind of slightly difficult experience with shared decision-making and how... I felt let down by that experience or not considered enough so I kind of look... back on it and I want to make sure that I advocate for myself and take part in shared decision-making and have these conversations about what my choices might be but also alongside what the medical professionals think and what might or might not be best."

(P005, Member of the General Population, Female)

Both groups of participants also mentioned that they would take part in SDM in the future. However, more members of the general population said they felt confident to part in SDM in the future. Although both groups said they felt comfortable taking part in SDM in the future. A couple of members of the general population stated that they actively seek and expect SDM to be the norm for all their healthcare decisions. Some participants from both groups said that SDM is the only way they make all healthcare decisions, and they would never make a healthcare decision without engaging in SDM. One chronic pain participant stated that they would persevere with SDM even if the healthcare professional was not keen to take part in SDM.

7.3.4. COVID-19 on SDM

This theme focuses on the impact that COVID-19 had on SDM and health decisions for participants. Every participant discussed the impact of COVID-19 had on healthcare, whether it was the general and potential impact of COVID-19 or the personal impact COVID-19 had on the participant in relation to their healthcare. Nearly all participants discussed the impact (both positive and negative) of and their experience of remote consultations and how remote consultations had increased compared to in person consultations. Just over half of participants discussed the importance of face-to-face consultations in relation to the relationship with the healthcare professional, non-verbal communication, body language and social cues.

Therefore, this theme was composed of the following sub-themes: “impact of COVID-19”, “remote consultations” and “face-to-face consultations”.

Impact of COVID-19

Both groups of participants discussed the impact of COVID-19 on healthcare. Members of the general population reported that they did not want to go near any hospitals as they were afraid of catching COVID-19 and had either knew someone personally or had heard stories of people catching COVID-19 in hospital and dying from COVID-19. One of these participants had even delayed getting an operation due to fear of catching COVID-19 while in hospital.

“Then I got too scared to have the operation because of the pandemic. I was terrified to go near a hospital...”

(P007, Member of the General Population, Female)

Both groups of participants highlighted the pressures that COVID-19 placed on healthcare as participants with chronic pain discussed delays in access to services and that there were long waiting lists, that one chronic pain participant noted they did not want to add to. Members of the general population were aware that there were lots of patients that healthcare professionals seen in the one day, so they were concerned about appointments being rushed and if there was sufficient time for SDM to take place. The difficulty in trying to see a healthcare professional in person was frequently cited by members of the general population.

“I definitely think it's had an impact for a simple fact is... for the better part of a year to 18 months is you couldn't see your GP face-to-face, it was all over the phone or for some very small instances on a video call... they were extremely rushed off their feet, so shared decision-making has been really impacted by COVID.”

(P005, Member of the General Population, Female)

However, some participants with chronic pain stated that they were still receiving care as normal despite COVID-19. One member of the general population reported a lack of services or options that were previously available before COVID-19. Participants with chronic pain discussed that they still have not received any care or support for one of their health conditions and that appointments have been cancelled and pushed back due to COVID-19.

“I only see her once a year and unfortunately, the next appointments been cancelled and been put back for another year.”

(P012, Chronic Pain Participant, Male)

Remote Consultations

Nearly every participant from both groups discussed the impact of remote consultations on SDM. Whilst both groups of participants highlighted that it may be uncomfortable for patients to discuss health issues over the phone or via Zoom, slightly more members of the general population explained that it may be difficult for patients to talk about health issues over the phone as they do not feel like they have the same level of privacy especially if family members are at home and can overhear the conversation.

“Remote consultations on decision-making, I think...the other aspect is that the patient is not in the medical setting, they're either in their home or other or wherever they're taking their appointment is not in the GPs practices, it's not at the hospital, it's not whatever it may be, and therefore... there's

not the privacy you know, your family might want you to get off the call quickly or agree with whatever it might be. If it's a sensitive or embarrassing subject, you might not want to question it 'cause you don't want the doctor talking more in your home... if you're not actually with the healthcare professional... there's a lot of other social factors that might mean you're not physically, or you're not properly positioned to take part in shared decision-making because of home stresses, people around, you're not comfortable...”

(P005, Member of the General Population, Female)

Both groups of participants discussed how remote consultations had negative impacts on communication with the healthcare professional as they felt more distant, felt it was more difficult to receive information and that things were “getting lost in translation”. Participants with chronic pain also explained that remote consultations had a negative impact on communication as over Zoom there would sometimes be a delay in speech. Additionally, a couple of chronic pain participants discussed the negative impacts of remote consultations on the relationship with the healthcare professional as you do not always get the same healthcare professional, if you’re meeting them for the first time via a remote consultation, if you have not seen what each other look like it can be difficult to build a rapport and relationship with the healthcare professional.

“So when COVID hit, then of course it was all online. So, it's difficult and... you're not always sure who you're going to get to speak to or whether, who it is that might phone you back. So, it's kind of hard to build up a relationship with anyone in those sort of circumstances... the one I'm dealing with now, I've never met because they started after COVID and of course, haven't met anyone face-to-face. So, we've had to try and build up a relationship on the phone. I've never even had a Zoom conversation with him, so he doesn't know what I look like and I don't know what he looks like, so that's quite difficult...”

(P011, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Although one chronic pain participant did say that because there was not a face-to-face appointment then they felt like the healthcare professional listened more. Other participants with chronic pain also highlighted they found remote consultations easier and listed positive aspects such as not needing to travel to appointments, cutting down on waiting times for appointments, contacting a wider range of people with the same condition in support groups, reaching wider areas such as remote communities, provided with more contact with healthcare professionals, convenient when working full-time and helped improve their communication skills.

“I prefer and it has happened due to COVID, but I prefer the way of working just now. It's more convenient for me where a telephone conversation happens as opposed to where you have to go into

the surgery... I mentioned the thing about the phone calls. I... for me, that's been really positive because I work full time... that's convenient for both parties because sometimes you're taking a whole day off work to go for one doctors appointment, and it's not convenient... everybody's lives are really busy. So for me, that was good... I think the phone call part has made this shared decision-making easier because it's forced you to listen, it's forced... as a patient, it's forced me to try and tell the doctor in detail, so that they know what I'm trying to get across."

(P014, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Face-to-Face Consultations

Whilst both groups of participants did discuss the importance of face-to-face consultations, it was primarily participants with chronic pain that discussed the importance of in-person consultations. Both groups, although mostly participants with chronic pain, reflected on the fact that there were more remote consultations and less face-to-face consultations as a result of COVID-19. One member of the general population and most chronic pain participants felt that face-to-face consultations were more positive as it helped to build rapport and a relationship with the healthcare professional whereas remote consultations lacked the human element.

"I was lucky enough to have a face-to-face to get a real feel of him and what he was like as a person too... so that really made me feel better having that face-to-face... and it was positive, it was a positive impact I think meeting him beforehand."

(P004, Member of the General Population, Female)

Although one participant with chronic pain admitted it was more difficult to build a relationship remotely, they did consider they had built a decent relationship over remote consultations. Another participant with chronic pain stated that they were relieved that not all their consultations were face-to-face as it would have been "annoying" to attend so many appointments in a short space of time but did admit that face-to-face consultations are better if you need to show the healthcare professional something physical e.g. a rash.

"I know I have a lot more phone calls with my GP than I used to. It used to be more face-to-face, but that's just been a good thing 'cause I have had to have so much contact with them over the last wee while, it would have been a pain to be there in the flesh every time... I've had... pain and fatigue and things and my energy is quite precious to me at the moment and if every phone call I'd had with the GP had been a face-to-face consultation, that would have had quite a big impact, it's easier just being

able to have... sometimes you want to see them face-to-face, when I had the allergic rash, they were like "no, come in this time", (laughs) so obviously wanted to see that..."

(P013, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Both groups of participants, although slightly more members of the general population also highlighted the importance of non-verbal communication and body language that is easier to read and be picked up on in face-to-face consultations. Although both groups did report that even in face-to-face consultations, wearing face masks also makes it more difficult to read body language, social cues, reactions and emotions which participants thought was potentially dangerous and impacted on mental health. One participant with chronic pain (who was also a healthcare professional) stated she had to remove her face mask because it was difficult to have an emotional conversation while wearing one and a member of the general population said they felt they had to exaggerate everything to get their message across.

"there's a lot to be learned about... empathy and body language. In person how somebody sits, how somebody holds themselves... understanding when they feel comfortable like reading the cues about when they're feeling comfortable, in that situation, when you're talking to them in a way where you're supposed to be engaging with them and sharing something when you don't have that physicality to read from, it can be difficult and people... react very differently on ones in their varying different comfort levels... the last GP locum, he was in a gown. He was gloved. He had a face shield and he had a mask and I'm going there with a mask. So it's a very... it feels like a very impersonal situation to go into, like it's quite an awkward kind of conversation. You're kind of reading... trying to read somebody you've never met before, so you don't even know really know what they actually look like. You're trying to read everything from my eyes and that's not... necessarily easy. There was glare on the shield, so at points you can't even see his eyes properly... so you have to exaggerate everything to get the message across so I think there's an element of that too."

(P006, Member of the General Population, Male)

7.3.5. Participants' Feelings

This theme focuses on participants' feelings they experienced when making their healthcare decisions. Most participants felt uncertain, worried or anxious when making their healthcare decisions. However, most participants felt happy, comfortable or reassured about their healthcare decision. More than half of participants also felt unhappy when making a healthcare decision, sometimes leading to conflicts with the healthcare professional. Additionally, more than half of participants reported having a negative experience when making a healthcare decision. Finally, all participants believed that SDM was

a good thing and most participants felt that SDM was important and should be standard for all healthcare decisions.

Therefore, this theme was composed of the following sub-themes: “uncertainty”, “happy with the decision”, “unhappy with the decision” and “shared decision-making is a positive thing”.

Uncertainty

Most participants from both groups reported feeling uncertain when making their healthcare decision. Participants from both groups felt unsure about going forward with their healthcare decisions, wondering if they had made the right choice. Participants from both groups stated that uncertainty was higher if it was not clear that the benefits outweighed the risks. Participants from both groups also explained that they were uncertain as they did not know what to expect or what was going to happen as they had not had to make those healthcare decisions previously. Two chronic pain participants felt uncertainty around consequences of treatment options and if the treatment options would help them or not. Another two chronic pain participants stated they were uncertain as the healthcare professionals stopped prescribing treatment but did not offer any alternatives.

“...when the doctor tells you there's nothing more they can do, you know, that's the end of the line in a sense from their perspective. So you're just, you know, there's no, nothing further, I mean, you know, so, one was left hanging...”

(P012, Chronic Pain Participant, Male)

Most participants from both groups also reported feeling worried or anxious about their healthcare decisions because of these uncertainties. Participants from both groups felt worried about the potential of things going wrong with their healthcare decisions, with one chronic pain participant describing experiencing internal conflict about having surgery. Two participants with chronic pain were worried about side effects of treatment options and interactions with other medication. Two members of the general population reported that they suffer from anxiety and panic attacks, whilst one chronic pain participant stated feeling nervous before consultations. However, both groups of participants did mention that taking part in SDM and having a good relationship with the healthcare professional helped to reduce the feeling of anxiety. However, both groups of participants reported not having a good relationship with the healthcare professional and one participant with chronic pain said that fighting for information increased anxiety and stress.

“my experience has been that I'm having to really fight for that information and I'm having to do my own research and I'm having to be my own advocate which just adds to the stress of a stage four diagnosis, which I have.”

(P011, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Happy with the Decision

Most participants from both groups said that they were happy with a healthcare decision. Both groups of participants stated that they were happier with decision when they felt they were involved in making the healthcare decision, when they took part in SDM with the healthcare professional as it gave them a sense of ownership and accountability over their own health. This is consistent with study 3 where a strong correlation was found between SDM behaviour and satisfaction with the healthcare decision. Glass et al. (2012) who also found that SDM was positively associated with satisfaction with an individual's healthcare decision. Analysis of individual SDM showed significant correlations for patients being helped in a health care consultation with understanding information, with treatment preference elicitation, and with weighing options thoroughly.

Some participants from both groups were happy with their healthcare decision as it provided them with the best outcome. Both groups of participants said they also felt happy with the healthcare decision as they felt that the communication with the healthcare professional was clear, and they understood all of the available treatment options and the associated risks and benefits of each option.

“...if there's a scale of one to five and five is most satisfied, that's where I am because I felt like I got all of the information, I understood all the options and the outcome was as expected. I mean, even right down to what to expect an hour after the operation, 2 hours, four hours to one day, day two everything was explained to me and the option that I got was the right option for me. So very, very happy.”

(P007, Member of the General Population, Female)

Both groups of participants were also happy with the healthcare decision as they felt they had enough time to make the decision and that the decision could be flexible and change if it needed to be at any time, or if the participant wanted to change their mind, the final decision was “not set in stone” and they could change their mind. Two participants with chronic pain were also happy with their decision as they received aftercare and follow up care after making a final healthcare decision so they did not feel forgotten about or abandoned.

“...at the moment I'm 100% satisfied. I, like I said, the whole frozen shoulder situation, I had two frozen shoulders at the same time, which is highly unusual and the treatment for both has been very successful. I've had follow up Physio after it as well. I've been given loads of aftercare and I don't feel abandoned in anyway. So yeah, yeah I'm really, really happy.”

(P014, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Most participants from both groups also discussed how comfortable or reassured they felt when making healthcare decisions. Both groups of participants felt comfortable or reassured with the healthcare decision as they felt that they were fully informed and fully discussed their treatment options and the potential consequences of the treatment options. Whilst both groups of participants mentioned the relationship with the healthcare professional having an impact on how comfortable or reassured, they felt with healthcare decisions, it was mostly members of the general population who discussed this.

“...sometimes you get a doctor that you're not too comfortable with, in the sense of, you've had past experience of their... what's the word I'm looking for? (wife speaks:) Negligence. (participants laughs) Aye, negligence that, you know, if you're given by the practice or that's who you can see if you want to see it in that space of time, you then say, "well, OK, we'll chance it" but in preference... I would rather make an appointment with the doctor that you have more rapport with and seems to understand your situation better.”

(P012, Chronic Pain Participant, Male)

If participants had a good relationship with the healthcare professional, they felt more comfortable or reassured about their healthcare decision. Whereas, if they did not have a good relationship with the healthcare professional or had not met them previously, then this made them feel less comfortable or reassured in making healthcare decisions. Both groups of participants considered how uncomfortable others might be in discussing health issues over the phone or on using Zoom. Two members of the general population also considered how uncomfortable it may be for some patients to take part in SDM and make healthcare decisions, preferring to let others make that decision instead. One chronic pain participant also reflected on times in the past where they were uncomfortable taking part in SDM and making healthcare decisions.

“I can think of plenty, you know, experiences in the past with healthcare professionals where I wouldn't have felt as confident to, you know, ask questions and things. I might have still done it anyway, I would have tried to it but I wouldn't have necessarily felt as comfortable...”

(P013, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

However, this participant and a member of the general population both said they felt comfortable taking part in SDM in the future and making healthcare decisions.

Unhappy with the Decision

More than half of participants felt unhappy about a healthcare decision they had made and most of these participants were chronic pain participants. Both groups of participants felt unhappy about their healthcare decision as they did not feel that it was a shared decision. Both groups of participants also felt unhappy when it came to making healthcare decisions as they felt that the healthcare professional did not listen, agree with or respect their decision and they did not understand their needs or why they wanted to make a certain decision. Both groups of participants were additionally unhappy with the manner in which the healthcare professionals spoke to them as they were patronising, made throwaway comments, put their own values on the discussion and in one case intimidated the participant.

“...the optometrist I saw before... made me cry and I burst into tears when I came out... her manner was... everything was just wrong about that whole consultation, and she frightened me and when I asked her questions, she left me feeling very vulnerable... she absolutely made me feel... there was something wrong with me that no one had ever found before and she was gonna let me away worrying and scared for the rest of the day... I was scared stupid...”

(P007, Member of the General Population, Female)

Both groups of participants were also unhappy about lack of available treatment options and additionally were unhappy as they felt that the healthcare professionals kept pushing for a treatment option that they did not want or agree with. Both groups of participants expressed unhappiness as they felt they really had to push to receive information or to get the outcome they wanted in their healthcare decision. Two chronic pain patients were also unhappy as they are still waiting for a healthcare professional to action their healthcare decision. In two cases of participants with chronic pain, the unhappiness with the healthcare decision led to conflict with the healthcare professionals.

“The only people who I really had conflict with are the chronic pain service... coming to decisions regarding treatments and them not respecting my views either as a patient or a professional. Just treated me like a wee... a pleb, I felt like a pleb (chuckles) on the pain service. They were really, really the most unemphatic people I've ever come across, and that really wound me up because I was like, "do you even understand chronic pain? You might understand the science, but you have no idea how it affects people's lives at all" and they need to get some empathy, so yeah.”

(P010, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

More than half of participants from both groups also reported having a negative experience in making a healthcare decision. Both groups of participants felt they had a negative experience as they felt dismissed by the healthcare professionals with one member of the general population saying he was laughed at by the healthcare professional for suggesting something. Two participants with chronic pain said they felt they had more negative experiences as being a patient than when working as a healthcare professional. Another two chronic pain participants had negative experiences in making their healthcare decisions as they felt that they were being placed on a set treatment pathway instead of being tailored to or involved in making the healthcare decision.

“So I said "OK, well, why have you suggested this particular treatment, for me?" and the answer was, "we always prescribe that here." So for me, that showed quite clearly that you're not looking at the patient as an individual with individual circumstances around the disease that you've got. You're going down a set treatment pathway and without the patient being in a position to question or have these conversations that you're talking about, in shared decision-making and it's just going to go down... that usual pathway and that's not at all how it should be.”

(P011, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Shared Decision-making is a Positive Thing

All participants from both groups believed that SDM was a good thing. Both groups of participants stated that the main reason they believe that SDM was beneficial was because taking part in SDM helped them to understand their options and to get the best outcomes. Both groups of participants also felt that SDM was a good thing as it gave them a sense of empowerment, ownership, accountability, and confidence in making their healthcare decisions. Again this provides qualitative evidence that links to the quantitative results of study 3, as well as literature on the impact of perceived behavioural control from the TPB (Thompson-Leduc et al., 2015) on engagement in SDM. Both groups of participants also believed that taking part in SDM made them feel happier and more comfortable with their healthcare decisions. Both groups of participants additionally explained that SDM was a positive thing as it made them feel more cared for, listened to respected, valued, supported and seen as an individual with individual health needs.

“So in that way, there's a benefit because you're being listened to and... at every point in the process of getting better, my doctor's been there, on the end of a phone or in person and has helped and the decision has been made between both of us. It's been completely shared, it's been brilliant... at the moment I'm 100% satisfied... I had two frozen shoulders at the same time, which is highly unusual and

the treatment for both has been very successful. I've had follow up Physio after it as well. I've been given loads of aftercare and I don't feel abandoned in anyway. So yeah, yeah I'm really, really happy.”

(P014, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Two participants with chronic pain believed SDM was a good thing as they felt it provided flexibility in their decision-making. Most participants from both groups also felt that SDM was important. Participants with chronic pain also believed that SDM was important as they are asked for their input in making the decision and what matters most to them in making the healthcare decision. Participants from both groups felt that SDM should be the standard and a priority when making healthcare decisions. Both groups of participants also felt that SDM was important as it meant that they were fully informed when making their healthcare decisions and also felt that SDM was important as they felt that it was important for patients to be involved in their healthcare.

“You have to involve the person in the care decisions otherwise, it's not proper healthcare... It's my life, it's my health, I need to be involved. So, it's that straightforward... They need to know that it's important for the person to be listened to and heard, and it ultimately is their body, their health. They need to be involved in the decision-making.”

(P010, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

7.3.6. Barriers

This theme highlights the different barriers that participants felt existed in being able to engage in SDM. Participants discussed how difficulties in accessing appointments with the healthcare professional and in accessing technology to engage in remote consultations were barriers to engaging in SDM. Participants also spoke about hardships they had experienced and how these hardships and moving locations had a negative impact on their mental state which subsequently acted as a barrier to being able to engage in SDM. Participants additionally highlighted how the healthcare professional's attitude can be a barrier to engaging in SDM when the healthcare professional has a negative attitude or is not willing to engage in SDM. Finally, participants discussed how time pressures in GP appointments and waiting times were also barriers to engaging in SDM as there is not enough time to engage in SDM when GP appointments are only ten minutes long.

Therefore, this theme was composed of the following sub-themes: “access”; “hardships and moving locations”; “healthcare professional's attitude” and “time”.

Access

Participants discussed a variety of potential barriers for engaging in SDM, one of which was access. Whilst both groups of participants highlighted access as a barrier, it was mostly chronic pain participants that spoke about difficulty accessing and engaging in SDM. Two participants with chronic pain felt that having access to their medical records, notes and the letters between their healthcare professionals would help them to engage in SDM as these documents would help to outline the decisions that were made, how they were made and would provide more specific information e.g. results from scans. Both groups of participants also mentioned that being able to access a healthcare professional is key for engaging in SDM and that a major barrier is if the patient is unable to access a healthcare professional.

“...well access to the medical profession would be the only, you know, big impact 'cause you know, if you like, they're the gatekeepers for treatment and if you can't get contact with the professional, you're then not going to move forward, unless you've got private healthcare.”

(P012, Chronic Pain Participant, Male)

One participant with chronic pain discussed that it is sometimes difficult to speak to a healthcare professional and that most healthcare consultations are done online or over the phone now because of COVID-19. One member of the general population spoke positively about online self-help or self-referral systems to get access to help quicker as there were no waiting lists. However, a couple of chronic pain participants highlighted that there may be some patients may be excluded because they cannot access, find it difficult to use or do not feel comfortable using digital technology. Although, another two participants with chronic pain also highlighted the positives of digital technology for improving access to more people in support groups or for remote communities to access more healthcare.

Hardships and Moving Locations

Half of participants from both groups discussed experiencing hardships and moving locations and how the stress and anxiety from these events impacted on their mental health and subsequently, their ability to engage in SDM. Both groups of participants discussed how major, life-changing events such as cancer diagnoses, being made redundant and losing their father impacted negatively on their mental state which then prevented them from engaging in SDM as they did not want to or felt like they were not able to think about anything else. Another chronic pain participant also discussed the trauma of losing her daughter and at the time, the pain of losing her daughter made her want anti-depressants to get rid of the pain but with time then realised that this was not the right decision.

"I've been through a lot in my life and there's been times where I've gone... in fact a perfect example, I lost my daughter. She was still born full term and at that point I was like, I went to the doctor, I'm like "I want anti-depressants, I want something, I just want to not be in pain" and the doctor told me that that was not the right decision, "you should, you need to feel some kind of pain, you need to get to grips with this somehow, being on anti-depressants is not going to help this situation"... it absolutely was the right decision. It absolutely was but there was just so much going on in my head and so many things and yeah, absolutely the doctor did the right thing..."

(P014, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Both groups of participants also discussed how moving locations, health boards or GP practices had an impact on being able to engage in SDM. For both groups of participants moving location and health board was a big change and a negative experience, with one participant with chronic pain feeling that they needed to seek help after moving location and one member of the general population struggling to adapt to moving health boards when they were 30 weeks pregnant, as they then had a new midwifery team and consultant. This resulted in a many people not being sure what was happening, where they were supposed to go and only meeting the midwifery team and the consultant a handful of times overall. However, one participant with chronic pain felt it was a positive impact moving GP practices, noting that the quality of service varied between locations and GP practices.

"...within GP practices, I've moved. I was in Ibrox before and now I'm in Cathcart and I can tell that Cathcart is a wealthier area and the GP practice is so much better. Even the pharmacy, the service just... not even the decision-making, but just the administration staff, everybody is so much politer and everybody is listening to me more. So yeah, I think it varies a lot from location to location as well."

(P003, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Healthcare Professional's Attitude

Whilst both groups of participants discussed the healthcare professional's attitude or willingness to engage in SDM as a barrier to taking part in SDM, it was mostly chronic pain participants who spoke about the healthcare professional's attitude as being a barrier to engaging in SDM. Participants from both groups discussed that SDM cannot take place when the healthcare professional is not willing to engage in SDM either through not listening to the patient, feeling that they know best, dismissing the patient, not keen to engage in conversation with the patient, or not providing information or options to the patient.

"...where I've come across, uh, an attitude of the healthcare professional knows best, uhm, it's left me completely switched off... I think when you have someone who is up for that, that makes such a

difference in the world but I think if you're faced with someone who doesn't want to get involved, 'cause I would want to do that, absolutely for everything, but if the medical professional doesn't want to do that, you are still on a back foot, it's just not great... but where you don't get that, I'm not sure you can get shared decision-making, if you don't get somebody that listens.”

(P009, Member of the General Population, Female)

Additionally, two participants with chronic pain discussed how the healthcare professional having a more passive approach to SDM was a barrier for engaging in SDM, as the healthcare professional “just went with” what the patient suggested instead of being more proactive, not putting forward any ideas or their opinion.

“I kind of felt like the GP was just submitting to my request... I guess that has an implication for shared decision-making, because again, the healthcare professional isn't kind of putting across their view on whether or not this is the most appropriate step forward and they're probably going with the path of least resistance and I suppose this can lead to inefficiencies within the service...”

(P002, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Participants with chronic pain felt that some healthcare professionals had become stuck in the habit of not engaging in SDM with their patients. Both groups of participants also highlighted that the way in which the healthcare professional voiced their attitude also impacted on their ability to take part in SDM. Examples included one healthcare professional arguing with the patient, another laughed at a patient for suggesting something and one came across as unempathetic in their approaches to not engaging in SDM with their patients. Two participants with chronic pain also discussed that the healthcare professional's attitude and communication or interpersonal skills were important for engaging in SDM with one chronic pain participant stating that the attitude or willingness of the healthcare professional to engage in SDM was more important than any tools.

“I guess like one thing that I would want to say is that I feel like in order to facilitate successful decision-making, like shared decision-making, I think listening is key. Listening by the clinicians because I feel like that's the main problem that I've faced... So I completely understand why it's difficult to just take the time to listen to the patient, but I think without listening, you know, no matter what fancy tools you're creating for shared decision-making, if the clinician doesn't listen to the patient, it doesn't work...”

(P003, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Time

Every participant from both groups discussed time and how it can be a barrier to engaging in SDM. Participants from both groups felt that they were not given enough time to think about healthcare decisions, they felt the decision was very rushed, they were not given enough information to make the decision and that the decisions were being made in the appointment or consultation by the healthcare professional instead of being able to go home and consider and discuss the options. Whilst both groups of participants mentioned time pressures within the NHS, more participants with chronic pain discussed how GPs only have 10 minutes for appointments and have many patients to see. Both groups of participants discussed the negative impacts that these time pressures have on SDM as there is not enough time to discuss and be given all the information about treatment option, to be listened to, explain symptoms, get a diagnosis and to come to a decision. Therefore, a several participants from both groups felt that there is not enough time to engage in SDM and are left feeling that they want to discuss things further.

"I mean I think it's way less than it should be and I think in reality, if you want to have a proper discussion with a GP, if we use GPs as an example, you'd have to book two appointments because you're in there an average, what 5-7 minutes max... Given that they don't know you, if you're not there for years and they don't know you, I don't know how given you don't know the individual how you get to a shared capacity when you've only got a matter of minutes to listen to their symptoms, diagnose it, and come to a decision and I think in those instances, you're not likely to see shared decision-making, you're likely to see the medical professional going "here's a prescription, thanks a lot, bye."

(P009, Member of the General Population, Female)

Participants from both groups also highlighted that if you do not know the healthcare professional, this can also add time onto the appointment as they need to provide the healthcare professional with more information making it harder to take part in SDM. However, if they know the healthcare professional then they believe they can take part in SDM in the allocated ten minutes for appointments. Participants from both groups also stated that it is quicker and easier for GPs to write a prescription or refer patients onto another service than to engage in SDM. Chronic pain participants also reported how difficult it was to get appointments, that there was long waiting lists for appointments and services, and that some appointments were cancelled or delayed which also meant a delay in making healthcare decisions or receiving treatment.

"...there's a longer term drug that you can take, so I was looking to get started on that and it's takes quite a long time to build up in your system, takes quite a long time to work, so to me, I was keen to get started on it as soon as possible...so I had to wait till I saw the NHS rheumatologist which was a

sort of ten week wait, it wasn't too bad... that's now been several weeks and I've not heard yet whether I can start back on it or not, so I'm kind of just left with no treatment at the moment... just the process of being able to get it and each stage of that decision being actually actioned... and the actual steps happening has just been super drawn out, so since... so that whole process, I'm still sitting here, not having any medication, has been since May and we're yeah, we're now mid-September, so it's just... it's been really long and it's just over a little thing about, you know, prescribing medication, so that's sort of frustrating...”

(P013, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Both groups of participants additionally reported that for surgical healthcare decisions, appointments would be made to have the surgery with the next 10 or 14 days. Participants could only delay the appointment once and after this, if they did not get the surgery, they were not given the option to rearrange within the NHS. Whereas one member of the general population felt that private healthcare was better as they were able to delay things more and take more time to make decisions. Participants from both groups said that they had much longer time in appointments when it was private healthcare (about 45 minutes to an hour) and they felt happier as they felt they had enough time to fully discuss the options, felt that the healthcare professional got to know them better and they were able to engage in SDM. However, there were participants from both groups who felt that despite time pressures, they were still able to engage in SDM and had enough time to think about and make decisions without feeling any pressures.

“...that was obviously just a 10/15-minute consultation but it still felt like it was a joint shared discussion.”

(P009, Member of the General Population, Female)

7.3.7. Facilitators

This theme highlights the different facilitators that participants felt were important for being able to engage in SDM. Participants discussed how being aware of SDM can help facilitate engagement in SDM. Participants also spoke about how being or knowing someone who is a healthcare professional or an academic can be a facilitator for taking part in SDM. Participants additionally highlighted how being prepared for appointments can facilitate SDM. Participants also discussed the importance of tailoring treatment options for each patient in facilitating SDM and explained that having a higher level of knowledge and confidence in making healthcare decisions facilitates SDM. Additionally, participants spoke about the importance of communication with the healthcare professional in facilitating SDM.

Finally, participants highlighted the importance of feeling in control of healthcare decisions for facilitating SDM.

Therefore, this theme was composed of the following sub-themes: “awareness”; “occupation”; “prepared”; “tailored”; “knowledge”; “confidence”; “communication” and “control”.

Awareness

Whilst both groups of participants discussed awareness of SDM as being an important facilitator for taking part in SDM, it was mostly participants with chronic pain who discussed it. Participants from both groups reported having awareness of SDM from previous experiences in making healthcare decisions and believe that it is a positive having awareness of SDM. Participants from both groups also feel that other people should be made aware of SDM. However, it was only participants with chronic pain that highlighted the need for healthcare professionals to be made more aware of SDM.

“I'm hoping healthcare professionals are becoming more aware of the need for it and how it's an integral part of healthcare, they have to be aware of it, it's patient centred, person centred.”

(P010, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

One of these participants with chronic pain also discussed how even though healthcare professionals are aware of SDM and speak about it, they may not know how to carry out SDM.

“...the model of, you know, shared decision-making is something that is spoken about an awful lot, but I don't know that many healthcare professionals know how to do it in practice.”

(P002, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Awareness of SDM was not an important predictor of behaviour in study 3, where participants were asked: “Had you heard of shared decision-making before completing this survey?” with response options of yes (44.3%) or no (55.7%). However, the literature supports the current findings in suggesting that awareness is important. Increasing awareness of a phenomenon is frequently a first step in getting patients on board (Joseph-Williams et al., 2017), and the study 3 results may point to limitations of the question.

Occupation

Half of participants from both groups stated that they were either healthcare professionals, and two of these participants (one from each group) also reported that a close family member was also a healthcare professional. These participants discussed that working as a healthcare professional

increased their awareness of SDM, awareness of risks and consequences in healthcare decisions and increased their health literacy. They also discussed how working as a healthcare professional they believe it is important to implement SDM to support their patients.

“So I would hope that my practice reflects shared decision-making... it's really important to me at every appointment that I check in with the person and check that what I have on my agenda is actually the most important thing for that person in, at that time. So I would hope that I do practice shared decision-making...”

(P002, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

A few participants from both groups also stated that they were more used to being a healthcare professional rather than being a patient and find being a patient more difficult as a result. Half of participants from both groups also reported that they were or had previously been academics. One participant from each group also stated that a spouse was an academic too. Participants from both groups discussed that having the awareness of SDM and believed increased education level or literacy facilitates them in taking part in SDM. Participants from both groups also highlighted how reading academic papers and medical journals help in making healthcare decisions.

“I work at a university and read academic papers daily so, you know, I can decipher the information and make a decision myself as to whether I understand something or feel comfortable with it.”

(P006, Member of the General Population, Male)

Prepared

Most participants from both groups discussed being prepared for healthcare appointments helped facilitate SDM. Participants from both groups liked to prepare questions about the risks, pros and cons regarding their healthcare decision and to read over information before attending healthcare appointments. This made participants feel more encouraged to take part in SDM. Some chronic pain participants also highlighted times where the healthcare professional provided them with information before the appointment or where they felt that the healthcare professional prepared for the appointment, which also facilitated SDM.

“...it was very clear that they had done a lot of work before they phoned me and were able to go through in quite a lot of detail... the way the treatment is taken, the potential side effects, and what, if anything, can be done to mitigate these side effects and that was a very good phone call because the person at the other end, the healthcare professional, had taken time to have all the information ready, so that they could talk it through with me and that is a really good situation to be in when you feel that they have taken that time.”

(P011, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Two members of the general population reported either phoning the healthcare professional back after having an appointment to ask some more questions about their options or taking notes of questions to ask the healthcare professional at the next appointment. However, one participant with chronic pain commented that they do not like to appear too over prepared as they fear the healthcare professional may negatively judge them for “googling too much information”.

“...you try not to look too over prepared I think for these sorts of things. I'm thinking these people are like "Oh no, what's, who's been doctor, you know, Doctor Google here?" sort of thing...”

(P013, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Another participant with chronic pain was concerned that if they had not been prepared before their appointment, that the appointment would have played out differently (without SDM) and sometimes, despite being prepared for appointments, they feel that the healthcare professional had not asked them what they were wanting out of the appointment or what they think might help which they thought was important for facilitating SDM.

Tailored

A few participants with chronic pain discussed how tailoring healthcare options to each individual healthcare decision can help facilitate SDM. Participants with chronic pain highlighted how positive healthcare decisions and consultations felt when the healthcare professional tailored the treatment options or conversation to their specific needs. This desire for tailored treatment is consistent with views of SDM that emphasise the need for the practitioner to find out about the patient (Bomhof-Roordink, et al., 2019) and really take on board the individual characteristics and needs of the individual (Cave, 2020).

Chronic pain participants also discussed the negative impacts of when they felt that the consultation or healthcare decision was not tailored or personalised to their condition or needs and that the healthcare they received was the same for everyone.

“...it was like the there was no personalised care... in that there was no understanding of... I may have not wanted further investigations because of... what had happened previously and... I was more comfortable with letting things take its course than waiting on... because I think healthcare professionals underestimate the pressure of waiting on a waiting list for something... it's very hard to trust somebody who... hasn't really listened or hasn't really explained why they think a particular option is the right way to go and for me... explaining the kind of healthcare thing of “oh, you know, it's in the guidelines, we do it that way,” but it's like how old are the guidelines? (laughs) Are the guidelines

still consistent with best practice or has evidence emerged that would suggest that this isn't actually the right way to go for my kind of population... the risk of being sucked into a... biomedical model that... neglects your roles in life, neglects what you want out of life and just focuses on fixing is really harmful when you have chronic pain because actually I am fine just as I am like just because I have chronic pain doesn't mean that I'm not a whole... it doesn't mean I need fixed..."

(P002, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Two participants with chronic pain also explained that they would like the information that they receive in relation to their healthcare decision and the treatment options to be in a visual format, as they believe that having a visual aid would be helpful to understand the information better rather than just text on paper. Although this research did not continue to focus on decision aids (DAs) after study 1, due to lack of use of DAs in the NHS, this patient's comments suggest that they would find DAs useful and future research should further examine how best to present health-related information to patients.

Knowledge

Knowledge was an important variable in studies 2 and 3 in predicting attitudes to and engagement in SDM, so it was interesting that knowledge was also identified as important in study 4. Nearly every participant from both groups discussed knowledge as being a facilitator for taking part in SDM. Participants from both groups discussed how being equipped with knowledge about the treatment options and being informed of the risks and benefits of each option either through carrying out their own research, speaking to others with the same health condition or by being provided this information from the healthcare professional. Knowledge was described as important for them to be able to engage in SDM, and participants from both groups also felt that they were not being provided with the knowledge necessary for them to be able to make a healthcare decision from their healthcare professionals. This in turn prevented them in being able to take part in SDM and they felt they had to fight to get that information or actively had to seek it out.

"...in my own experience, sometimes I felt that the knowledge wasn't always given to me. And you know, quite often it was something that I had to sort of seek out in order to make decisions."

(P001, Member of the General Population, Female)

A couple of participants from both groups also explained that if they felt they did not have enough knowledge or experience about particular treatment options, then they would feel more likely to "bow to" i.e. rely upon the healthcare professional's knowledge instead of taking part in SDM. Both groups of participants discussed having knowledge about how their health condition impacts on them in

everyday life. However, participants with chronic pain discussed how whilst they may not have the same type of knowledge as the healthcare professionals, they do know how their health condition impacts on them each day and the various circumstances that are important to consider in making a healthcare decision.

“I know myself better than any professionals know me and I know my situation, my home situation, my own personal assets and difficulties...”

(P013, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Participants from both groups also felt as that having increased knowledge from working as a healthcare professional or from having a high education level facilitated them to be able to fully engage in SDM. Most participants from both groups also spoke about how important the healthcare professional’s knowledge and experience is for engaging in SDM. They highly valued the healthcare professional’s medical knowledge regarding health conditions and treatment options, as the healthcare professional has more medical knowledge than them, referring to the healthcare professionals as the experts. Members of the general population felt more reassured or at ease when receiving care from a healthcare professional who had a lot of experience in their health condition.

“I had convinced myself that he was the top eye surgeon for this type of procedure in Scotland... I just trusted him implicitly which helped me relax because one of the things he told me when he met me was how his own track record...he just instilled confidence in me because he talked so much about how many of these he'd done and he just made it seem so routine for him...I wanted the best man for the job and he seemed to be the best man for the job, you know, yeah, or woman, but there was only men in the mix...”

(P007, Member of the General Population, Female)

However, some participants from both groups believed that the healthcare professional were undereducated when it came to certain health conditions and in one case, were being provided with inaccurate information. Chronic pain participants also felt that some healthcare professionals do not always make clear or provide their knowledge or reasoning behind healthcare decisions, because the healthcare professional has the knowledge but does not always feel the need to share that knowledge with their patients. Other chronic pain participants also felt that the more knowledgeable and experienced healthcare professionals sometimes “get stuck in their ways” and become biased, therefore not engaging in SDM.

“I think it's an education thing, I (sighs)... and this is a horrible thing to say, and it may be totally incorrect, but I feel that the doctors are very highly educated people, maybe they don't...maybe they

just don't think because they know what they're doing. They know the knowledge. Maybe they just don't think that other people need to know it and so they don't pass it on to the person who they're talking to. It's maybe not a personality thing, it's maybe just a knowledge thing, I don't know.”

(P014, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Most participants from both groups also highlighted how important they felt it was to be fully informed of the treatment options and the risks and benefits of the treatment options to facilitate engagement in SDM. Whilst more participants from both groups (more so participants with chronic pain), felt fully informed when making their healthcare decision, a few participants from both groups did not feel they were informed enough to engage in SDM. There were some participants from both groups who also expressed concern that other patients may not always be fully informed when making healthcare decisions too. Both groups of participants additionally felt reassured when they were fully informed of their treatment options and the associated risks and benefits of the treatment options.

“So it's just that whole informed consent, you know when I think just that, reassurance of it's not something else going on. It's not... it's just the medication and the way it's reacted or it's, you know, this intervention hasn't hasn't gone exactly how I thought it would, but actually the healthcare professional told me that this was a risk, so that's fine, you know it's just that reassurance, especially when you're living with long term conditions.”

(P002, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Confidence

Most participants from both groups spoke about how important confidence is in being a facilitator for engaging in SDM. Participants from both groups reported they felt confident in being able to make healthcare decisions and engaging in SDM now and in the future. However, participants from both groups also discussed times in the past when they were not as confident in making healthcare decisions and engaging in SDM. Suffering from an illness, chronic pain or mental health, having a negative healthcare experience, fighting for information and not being instilled confidence by the healthcare professional were reasons given by both groups of participants for lacking confidence to take part in healthcare decisions and for engaging in SDM in the past.

“It actually takes quite a lot of courage to do that though, so you have that conversation with the GP, particularly when you're not well, you know, you're talking to me now, you probably see that I'm fairly confident. I wasn't like this two years ago. I was like really crying a lot, upset, had my confidence was eroded and I'd had waves and waves of anxiety, it's horrible.”

(P009, Member of the General Population, Female)

Members of the general population expressed concern about other patients not having the confidence to engage in SDM and healthcare decisions. Participants from both groups felt confident in being able to ask more questions, to challenge the healthcare professional's view, to get a second opinion and to engage in SDM even if it is not offered. Both groups of participants also highlighted how taking part in SDM made them feel happier, more confident and reassured with healthcare decisions.

“Well for me, it's about your confidence in whatever medical decision you're making about your healthcare or whatever, you know, it's reassuring if you're involved in making the decision... when you go on to enact that decision of healthcare or medical decision that you've made, there's a lot more confidence in that... I am a lot more confident and happy with these decisions when I'm taking part in them... once the decision has then been made, I'm more confident in the process of OK, this is what we've decided, this is what I'm going to do, or this is what's going to happen, uhm, I... yeah, I think your confidence in the decision as well is important for following through with your treatment decisions and things or adherence to things and things like that.”

(P005, Member of the General Population, Female)

Participants from both groups felt more confident to take part in SDM when they had a good relationship with the healthcare professional, from having knowledge or being given enough information, understanding the treatment options, from having a previous negative experience and from overcoming an illness.

Communication

Most participants from both groups discussed the importance of communication as being a facilitator for taking part in SDM. Participants from both groups felt it was important to be fully informed about the possible treatment options and the consequences of each treatment option. Participants from both groups also believed that communication and interpersonal skills were more important for healthcare professionals to engage in SDM than technical medical knowledge. Whilst both groups of participants reported having negative communication with a healthcare professional, there was also reports of having positive communication with a healthcare professional. Some participants from both groups reported having both negative and positive communication with a healthcare professional. Two participants with chronic pain highlighted that the communication level varies between different healthcare professionals. Participants from both groups felt that they received better communication from healthcare professionals in private healthcare consultations as there was more time for

communication versus public or NHS-facilitated healthcare. Participants from both groups also highlighted how important listening was to facilitate SDM.

“I guess like one thing that I would want to say is that I feel like in order to facilitate successful decision-making, like shared decision-making, I think listening is key. Listening by the clinicians because I feel like that's the main problem that I've faced... so I completely understand why it's difficult to just take the time to listen to the patient, but I think without listening, you know, no matter what fancy tools you're creating for shared decision-making, if the clinician doesn't listen to the patient, it doesn't work...”

(P003, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Participants from both groups were happier when they felt that they had been listened to by the healthcare professional and when the healthcare professional explained the treatment options and the consequences of each treatment option. However, there were also participants from both groups that did not feel that they were being listened to or understood by the healthcare professional. There were participants from both groups who felt that the communication was not clear from the healthcare professional, they wanted more information about treatment options, they were not given information or they were not asked how they felt or what they wanted out of the appointment. Participants from both groups felt it was important to be asked how they felt about the treatment options, what is important to them and what their concerns are by the healthcare professional, but these were sometimes ignored or not asked. Participants from both groups also highlighted that the manner in which the healthcare professional communicates is also important.

“...her manner was everything was just wrong about that whole consultation, and she frightened me and when I asked her questions, she left me feeling very vulnerable... Yeah, she didn't have the manner with patients... it would be horrible for, you know, what I mean, you'd hate for her to say something to an old person, I'm really, really worried you know, because she did, she made me cry.”

(P007, Member of the General Population, Female)

Participants from both groups also discussed that the willingness of the healthcare professional to communicate information can vary and some healthcare professionals will just decide on what they consider is the best option for the patient, rather than discuss the different treatment options with the patient. Some participants from both groups also felt they had to really push or fight to get information from the healthcare professional or to engage in SDM. Other participants from both groups felt that they had to suggest treatment options as the healthcare professional was not suggesting any. However, some participants from both groups felt happy and reassured with their healthcare decisions as they

had a good relationship with their healthcare professional and felt that the healthcare professional took time to learn more about them. Participants from both groups also felt that communication with the healthcare professional about treatment options increased their understanding and helped to inform them about the treatment options. Participants from both groups additionally found that speaking to their partner, family or others with the same health condition helped in making their healthcare decision.

“So it was helpful to talk through with my husband and my daughters as well, so... but it is ultimately my decision, I know that and they know that so... but it's good to talk through things with people...”

(P011, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Participants from both groups also spoke about the communication that occurred between their different healthcare professionals about their health condition and decision. Additionally, participants from both groups discussed the impact that COVID-19 has had on communication in healthcare. Participants from both groups explained how others may not feel comfortable discussing health issues over the phone, particularly in their own home if other family members can overhear the discussion. Two participants with chronic pain also felt that it was harder to have a conversation over the phone than having an in-person consultation with a healthcare professional. However, two participants with chronic pain discussed the benefits of phone call consultations and preferred to have phone consultations.

Control

Participants from both groups discussed control as a facilitator for engaging in SDM. A member of the general population felt it was important to be in control of making a healthcare decision. A participant with chronic pain explained that in order to engage in SDM and to give control over to the healthcare professional, the patient has to trust the healthcare professional. Another participant with chronic pain found that having the power to make a healthcare decision was beneficial. Participants from both groups discussed how SDM gives the power or control back to patients and that they feel it is important to be in control of their own health and body.

“...well, obviously I think it's really good, because, as a patient myself, it will be, you know, it's my body, so I want to be in charge of my body.”

(P003, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

The importance of participants' experiences of being in control of their decisions in the current qualitative study reflects the findings of study 3, where perceived behavioural control from the TPB was found to be an important predictor of patients' intentions to take part in SDM, their SDM behaviour and their satisfaction with the outcomes of their decision. For SDM to succeed patients have to really feel that they have some control in making the decision, i.e. they feel confident that they can succeed in understanding and carrying out the target behaviours, in this case SDM behaviours. This is also consistent with Thompson-Leduc et al.'s (2015) systematic review of studies based on TPB, where perceived behavioural control was found to be an important variable in several studies.

Two participants with chronic pain felt that their healthcare decision was out of their control. However one participant with chronic pain was glad that the healthcare professional took control of the healthcare decision as they felt they had a high decision burden and did not know much about the health condition. Two members of the general population felt more in control of healthcare decision when they engage in SDM. Both groups of participants discussed how they do not have control over having a health condition or illness but by engaging in SDM, they take back a bit of control by making decisions on how to deal with the health condition. Participants from both groups additionally felt that patients should have responsibility and control over their healthcare.

"I think that it's... people should have a bit of responsibility and control and things over their care and I believe that people take better care of themselves if they do have that sort of buy in or investment or whatever you want to call it, in their own care..."

(P013, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

7.3.8. Important Considerations

This theme highlights various consideration that participants felt were important for enabling them to engage in SDM. Participants discussed how important it was for them to consider their quality of life when making healthcare decisions. Participants also spoke about how culture can influence engagement in SDM. Participants additionally highlighted that there are differences between healthcare professionals in their approach to making healthcare decisions. Finally, participants explained various ways in which SDM can be situational although half of participants did believe that SDM is suitable or can be suitable for all healthcare decisions. Therefore, this theme was composed of the following sub-themes: "quality of life"; "culture"; "differences between healthcare professionals" and "shared decision-making can be situational".

Quality of Life

Most participants from both groups discussed how it was important to consider their quality of life when making healthcare decisions and explained how engaging in SDM improved their quality of life.

“I've had a real example of where shared decision-making was massively beneficial to me, in fact, life changing... you can get a lens that will completely correct your eyesight for the rest of your life... I can see ladybirds on walls... it's transformed my life because it was a proper shared decision and the options were discussed...”

(P007, Member of the General Population, Female)

Half of participants from both groups also spoke about the importance of outcomes when engaging in SDM. Participants from both groups discussed the importance of knowing all the possible outcomes from the different treatment options when making a healthcare decision. Two individuals with chronic pain highlighted that sometimes there is only one outcome as there is only one treatment option available or no treatment options to pursue. Participants from both groups additionally explained how engaging in SDM leads to the best outcomes for patients.

“So if you want the best outcomes for your patients, you have to listen to your patients and you have to involve them in their decision-making.”

(P010, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Culture

About half of participants from both groups discussed the role that culture can play in SDM. Two members of the general population spoke about their culture in relation to making healthcare decisions. One of these participants spoke about how there is more risks and complications associated with their health condition because they are South Asian, but the participant was comforted as the healthcare professional had this knowledge and had consulted with other patients of South Asian background who experienced the same risks. The other member of the general population explained that it is difficult to challenge the healthcare professional as their culture also includes respecting your elders. This member of the population also highlighted the importance of typed words and using software such as Google Translate to learn and communicate in English with healthcare professionals and that it is difficult for those whose first language is not English to speak in order to communicate any health concerns.

“with... increasing numbers of people from refugee groups or asylum groups, uhm in Glasgow especially but you know, in the country generally... they have a heavy reliance on typed words, so they're receiving things on WhatsApp, they're running it through Google Translate to check that they understand what's being said, and then writing it in their own language to then learn and that's how they're, that's how a lot of them are learning. So their typed and written English is far better than their spoken and listened comprehension. Especially when it comes to technical terminology, which medical situations you're going to run into a fair bit, so I think that's definitely a disadvantage...”

(P006, Member of the General Population, Male)

Hawley and Morris (2017) point out that the different needs of patients from different racial and ethnic backgrounds have not been given sufficient consideration in developing models of SDM and this is probably why these patients have less favourable views of SDM.

An individual with chronic pain also briefly mentioned that Ireland has a two-tier healthcare system. This same individual also spoke about how there may be a cultural clash between patients and healthcare professionals as patients do not want to go to appointments, as they believe that the healthcare professional is only interested in prescribing medication whereas healthcare professionals believe that patients only want medication. Participants from both groups additionally discussed the culture change that is required for both patients and healthcare professionals to move away from the traditional paternalistic approach to healthcare and to move towards SDM.

“I think that a lot of it is culture. There's just a... that is an older sort of model of working, more medical model and it's a culture change that has to happen.”

(P013, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Differences between Healthcare Professionals

Every participant from both groups discussed the differences between different healthcare professionals when making healthcare decisions. Both groups of participants felt that each healthcare professional had their own way of working and that different healthcare professionals had different preferences in their way of working. Participants from both groups believed that different types of healthcare professionals engaged in SDM more than others e.g. two participants with chronic pain believed that allied healthcare professionals such as occupational therapists and physiotherapists engaged in SDM more than nurses and doctors. However, another participant with chronic pain believed that nurses were more helpful in providing information than doctors.

“...nurses... I don't know if it's just because of their profession, they're generally very open and want to give you information... I would say the only one who maybe haven't been as helpful as other people are doctors...”

(P014, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Two members of the general population also noted that trainee healthcare professionals were unlikely to make shared decisions. However, both groups of participants explained that even when you see more than one of the same types of healthcare professional, e.g. specialists, there can be differences in that one specialist wants to engage in SDM and the other does not. Further to this, both groups of participants believed that differences between healthcare professionals are due to the individual's personality, empathy, ability to listen and how willing they are to engage in SDM and in conversation rather than their occupation. Both groups of participants also believed that younger healthcare professionals were more likely to engage in SDM than older and more experienced healthcare professionals.

“...maybe the older generation who've been in their roles longer. I think they maybe, sometimes less open to the shared decision-making route... so yes, I think it's something that will take a while to percolate through to all healthcare professionals... age generations, also where you are in the hierarchy, you know, of the medical hierarchy. I think em, sometimes those healthcare professionals who might be in the middle or whatever, a bit more open to the shared decision-making whereas by the time you've reached, you know, higher up the tree, maybe they're not quite so in that mode...”

(P011, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

One member of the general population additionally believed that female healthcare professionals were more likely to engage in SDM than male healthcare professionals. However, two members of the general population prefer and had more positive experiences with older healthcare professionals that were more experienced compared to younger healthcare professionals.

Two individuals with chronic pain who were also healthcare professionals noted the differences they experience when they are a patient and when they are a healthcare professional as they engage in SDM as a healthcare professional but do not feel they are given the opportunity to engage in SDM as a patient and they want the healthcare professionals to be more proactive in making healthcare decisions when they are a patient.

“...unfortunately as a patient on the other side of things, I don't tend to feel like that is a common way of working in services that I access. Personally, I feel like that my service that I work in is probably at one end of a spectrum there... but often my personal experiences have been less, less good, and I find

it a bit challenging because I'm used to working one way and then as a patient I find it, so yeah...I have had an experience with a GP who and I don't know whether just has a more passive kinda style or whether sometimes I think 'cause once the people know you are a health professional, not a nurse, not a doctor, not got medical knowledge, but sometimes I think they sort of then let you kind of take the reins a little bit too much maybe and aren't very proactive themselves in kind of coming up with ideas and stuff and anything... maybe ideas I came up with, they'd be like "Oh yeah, great. Let's try that" but like sometimes you do want them to be a bit more proactive and a wee bit more leading as well."

(P013, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Participants from both groups also felt that private healthcare was better than NHS healthcare as there are significant waitlists in the NHS and there is more time in private appointments for discussion. Two members of the general population additionally believed there were more options available in private healthcare and that there was more engagement in SDM in private healthcare. An individual with chronic pain felt that there were differences between different departments of healthcare i.e. that cancer care included patients in decisions, but they did not feel listened to when seen for mental health. They did however noted this may be due to mental health services being underfunded and mental health not being spoke about as much as other health conditions. The same individual with chronic pain also reported that the quality of healthcare varies by location too between different GP practices.

Shared Decision-making Can Be Situational

Every participant from both groups discussed ways in which engagement in SDM can be situational. Both groups of participants stated that they would like to make the final decision in relation to healthcare choices unless it was a life or death, an emergency situation or if they were unconscious then the healthcare professional would need to make the healthcare decision. Both groups of participants also suggested that being able to take part in SDM can depend on the individual's context, health condition and situation if they are able to make that decision or if they would benefit from SDM. Additionally, both groups of participants discussed that being able to engage in SDM depends on how willing the healthcare professional is to engage in SDM as they can either be passive or paternalistic in their attitude and approach when making healthcare decisions.

"I kind of felt like the GP was just submitting to my request...I guess that has an implication for shared decision-making, because again, the healthcare professional isn't kind of putting across their view on whether or not this is the most appropriate step forward and they're probably going with the path of least resistance and I suppose this can lead to inefficiencies within the service... I think it's very hard

when you're just kind of given a "it's either this option or nothing."... So, uh I think for me, it's very hard if you say to somebody... "we're either going with this or there's nothing"... that isn't actually... I don't feel that's a shared decision for people..."

(P002, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Two individuals with chronic pain also felt that their appointments would have turned out differently if they had not went into them prepared. Participants with chronic pain additionally highlighted that sometimes there only is one outcome or option that is given and in other cases, there are no options which has limits for SDM. Both groups of participants also felt that pressures on services such as time pressures impacts on engagement in SDM as there is not enough time in a 10-minute appointment to think about and make healthcare decisions. Participants with chronic pain additionally explained how having a positive relationship with the healthcare professional can help facilitate SDM but that it is harder to engage in SDM if you do not have a relationship with the healthcare professional. Both groups of participants also explained that if the healthcare professional does not listen to the patient or vice versa then SDM will not work. Two individuals with chronic pain highlighted that sometimes there can be personality clashes between patients and healthcare professionals which can impact on SDM.

"So, I wonder whether it's pressure on a service that's making them less up for shared decision-making or it could be personality clash. I mean, there's so many different factors. The person I saw, we just clashed, so it possibly was a.. what do you call it? Head... butting heads or something? You shouldn't take that out on a patient, even if you do butt heads, you either pass them onto somebody else... there's other ways around it..."

(P010, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Another two individuals with chronic pain discussed how if a patient is not in the right state of mind to make a healthcare decision then this makes it harder for them to engage in SDM and that any healthcare decision that impacts their quality of life e.g. mental health or chronic pain, then they want to engage in SDM and feel that it is more important for patients with long term conditions to engage in SDM. Furthermore, participants with chronic pain spoke about how chronic pain and mental health can negatively impact on their ability to engage in SDM. Both groups of participants also highlighted that there can be limits to SDM for patients that have mental health capacity issues or other capacity issues such as learning disabilities and dementia, although a representative may be able to make a healthcare decision on their behalf in these circumstances. Both groups of participants also reported that some patients do not want to take part in SDM and in some cases may prefer someone else to make a healthcare decision for them. Two individuals with chronic pain explained that some patients

may not feel confident enough to engage in SDM if they do not feel that SDM was encouraged or offered by a healthcare professional.

“No, I wasn't encouraged. No, I had to push. Yeah, definitely and not everyone will... I think I'm quite confident that I would be able to take part in shared decision-making because I would go for that, even if the healthcare professional was not as forth coming, I would definitely persevere with that but I know there'd be a lot of people that might not feel able to do that for whatever reason...”

(P011, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Both groups of participants also reported that some patients do not want to take part in SDM and in some cases may prefer someone else to make a healthcare decision for them. Two individuals with chronic pain explained that some patients may not feel confident enough to engage in SDM if they do not feel that SDM was encouraged or offered by a healthcare professional. Another two participants with chronic pain also highlighted that it is difficult to engage in SDM if they have not been fully informed or been given enough information to make a healthcare decision. However, both groups of participants agreed that if the health decision concerned a new health condition, they did not know much about then they would rely on the healthcare professional to make the healthcare decision. Both groups of participants also felt that if it was clear that the benefits outweigh the risks for a healthcare decision then they would go with the healthcare professional's opinion. Both groups of participants also discussed that if a patient wanted to make a healthcare decision that was potentially harmful for the patient, then the healthcare professional is right to not engage in SDM with the patient. However, half of participants from both groups believed that SDM is suitable in all or most medical scenarios as even patients with limited capacity can still have someone make a decision on their behalf with the healthcare professional and participants from both groups believed that SDM should be the default where possible when making healthcare decisions.

7.3.9. Areas for Improvement

This theme encompasses the different areas participants felt required improvement within healthcare to facilitate engagement in SDM. Participants highlighted their various concerns around SDM. Participants also spoke about ways in which finance can limit patients' ability to take part in SDM. Participants additionally highlighted the multiple pressures that healthcare professionals and the NHS face. Finally, participants discussed the different areas in which healthcare needs improved to allow for SDM to occur.

Therefore, this theme was composed of the following sub-themes: “concerns around shared decision-making”; “finance”; “pressures in the NHS” and “healthcare needs improved”.

Concerns around Shared Decision-making

Around half of participants from both groups voiced their concerns about SDM. Both groups of participants were concerned that, even though healthcare professionals know about SDM, would SDM be carried out correctly and would healthcare professionals know how to carry out SDM in practice. Both groups of participants also voiced concerns around the healthcare professional considering what is best or right for the patient as there is a fine line between supporting patients to make a decision that is right for them and manipulating them into a decision. Additionally, both groups of participants were uncertain if the patient’s views are taken into account and whether the healthcare professional asks what the patient wants out of the appointment.

“...has the healthcare professional actually asked me what do I want out of the... like out of the consultation?”

(P002, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Both groups of participants also were concerned regarding whether healthcare professionals consider the patient’s lifestyle and social factors and how these may impact on the patient’s ability to engage in SDM. Two individuals with chronic pain were concerned that healthcare professionals may follow set treatment pathways or set guidelines for every patient instead of tailoring the decision to factor in the patient’s individual circumstances. Both groups of participants discussed their concerns around patients not being seen due to COVID-19 or they may find it difficult to engage in SDM because of remote consultations. Members of the general population voiced their concerns about not every patient feeling comfortable or confident enough to take part in SDM, therefore the healthcare professional needs to ensure that SDM takes place.

“The difficulty and worry that I have with other people is that not everybody is going to be comfortable or confident enough to do that, so the onus is on healthcare professionals to instigate these conversations and make sure it's a priority because it's difficult for people to challenge or to bring up these thoughts.”

(P005, Member of the General Population, Female)

Two members of the general population also stated their concerns regarding patients that have a mental health condition, learning disabilities or that are not in the right mental state, that these factors

may impact on their capacity to engage in SDM or cause them to not feel comfortable advocating for themselves. An individual with chronic pain additionally was concerned if every patient is fully informed and gives full consent for what they sign up to within health services. A member of the general population also voiced concern over the possibility of healthcare professionals writing prescriptions for patients instead of engaging in SDM as this is quicker and easier in 10-minute appointments, particularly if the healthcare professional does not know the patient. Both groups of participants also expressed their concerns around power dynamics between the healthcare professional and patients as healthcare professionals are regarded as being the top demographics of society and that they know a lot more than patients therefore, it is easy for healthcare professionals to make decisions for patients particularly for younger patients or patients who face multiple deprivation issues instead of engaging them in SDM. These power dynamics also makes it difficult for patients to challenge healthcare professionals.

“...the power dynamics between healthcare providers and their patients... are often not discussed and often strong undertones, especially if you're dealing with... I don't like it, but if you're dealing with the higher up professionals, someone that's at doctor level or consultant level or whatever. If you're dealing in that type of realm of a healthcare decision... it can be really difficult to advocate for yourself and say against these people, that might know a whole lot more than you or whatever...”

(P005, Member of the General Population, Female)

Finance

Half of participants from both groups discussed different financial impacts on SDM. Both groups of participants felt that private healthcare was better than NHS healthcare but noted that private healthcare came with a cost. Two individuals with chronic pain highlighted that they needed to pay for their treatment options as these were not available on the NHS. Another individual with chronic pain believed that mental healthcare was underfunded and did not have enough resources, which in turn limits SDM. Both groups of participants discussed the differences in ability to engage in SDM for patients that are middle class and for patients with deprivation issues.

“There would have been a lot of mothers with other kind of challenges and like it's definitely within the SIMD, it would probably be within the one or two category, you know, so a lot of social... multiple deprivation issues and I got the impression that this is a healthcare professional who had gotten... just gotten used to telling people what to do and I felt that as a... middle class healthcare professional, I

had more insight into what choices I was going to make and why I was making them and I felt like we are in a position of power as healthcare professionals.”

(P002, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Additionally, an individual with chronic pain felt that the quality of healthcare provided was better in wealthier areas or locations. To further highlight the differences between different classes of patients, a member of the general population stated that if they did not have a good job and disposable income, then they might have been left feeling that they received an inferior product and felt disappointed for the rest of their life. Another member of the general population added that in most cases, the NHS will give patients the cheapest treatment option which is not necessarily the best treatment option. An individual with chronic pain also felt that the NHS was underpaid. However, a member of the general population offered a potential solution to save the NHS time and money by allowing the patient to see a healthcare professional that has the right expertise for their health condition instead of the patient initially seeing a healthcare professional that does not have this expertise and then needs to be referred to a healthcare professional that does have the right expertise.

“I think to have nurse practitioners who have certain expertise in different fields... like menopause, that's what should be happening. So you don't even have to see a GP, but you could have a nurse practitioner, but who has a special expertise in menopause and you go and chat to them. It would save so much time and money but uhm, I think we'd have to overhaul the whole way it works.”

(P009, Member of the General Population, Female)

Another member of the general population explained that a big motivator for engaging in SDM for them was to avoid wasting NHS resources and to save money by receiving the right care and best treatment option for them as early as possible.

Pressures in the NHS

Most of participants from both groups discussed the different pressures that exist in the NHS. Participants from both groups felt that there was not enough time in appointments to discuss health concerns with the healthcare professional or for them to support patients to make complex decisions. Both groups of participants also highlighted the long waiting lists in the NHS with participants not wanting to add to this, therefore they sought out private healthcare as the waiting list was shorter. However they worried that other patients with major issues may not see healthcare professionals as result of also trying to avoid adding to the waiting lists. An individual with chronic pain commented that NHS staff were overworked and underpaid. A member of the general population also reported constraints on money and time within the NHS. Both groups of participants also discussed healthcare

professionals being rushed off their feet as there was only one consultant in an entire clinic and GPs see a lot of patients in one day thus this pressure on services left participants wondering if there was any time for SDM to take place.

“...people think that GPs and healthcare professionals are so rushed at the minute, they're so pressed for time...she was definitely rushed but she was... the only consultant in the entire clinic for ante Natal issues...they were extremely rushed off their feet...it's definitely been impacted in that respect that the medical profession has been extremely knocked for six. It's been so busy that the GPs are taking the brunt of stuff that they never would before, so they're rushing. They're seeing like 50/60 people a day. Is there the time for shared decision-making during COVID?”

(P005, Member of the General Population, Female)

However, an individual with chronic pain explained that whilst GPs are overstretched and do not have much time in appointments, at their current GP surgery, they have never felt rushed or “pushed out the door”. Despite the surgery having a long waiting list or a full waiting room, the participant noted their GP took the time they needed to consult with their patients. Although, they also highlighted that there was redeployment of healthcare staff to different areas, taking staff away from where they usually work resulting in people being lost in systems and not having the resources or time to have discussions with patients. Another individual with chronic pain found it difficult to get a GP appointment and that appointments with their consultants had been cancelled and delay due to pressure within the NHS. Both groups of participants also discussed COVID having massive impacts on the ability of the NHS to operate and function normally, many noting that COVID has overwhelmed the NHS and that this would have a big impact on SDM.

“COVID has massive impacts on the ability of the health service to operate and function normally and that in itself, is going to impact greatly on the shared decision-making.”

(P011, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Healthcare Needs Improved

Most participants from both groups discussed the various aspects of healthcare that they feel need improved. Both groups of participants reported that they wanted to discuss treatment options and alternatives more with their healthcare professional, but they felt that they had to fight for information or ask the healthcare professional for information. They also believed they had to be their own advocate and actively seek out SDM and information. Both groups of participants also felt that information and resources should be given automatically by the healthcare professional without

needing to ask and that they should be involved in SDM without needing to ask. Both groups of participants additionally explained that they were not asked what they wanted or for their view on the healthcare decision. Two individuals with chronic pain also reported being dismissed by the healthcare professional. The same two individuals with chronic pain also believed that good relationships between patients and healthcare professionals should be prioritised as soon as possible, as having a negative relationship with the healthcare professional can make the healthcare experience really negative for patients.

“I think we need to prioritise good therapeutic relationships as soon as possible so that people aren't having their power taken away from them at the start of their journey that we then spend years trying to give back to them.”

(P002, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

One of these individuals with chronic pain also explained that longer appointment times are needed in the NHS as not only is it harmful for GPs to pressure them into making complex decisions in 10-minutes, but it is also too short a period to fully engage in SDM. Both groups of participants felt that healthcare professionals need to be more open to engaging in SDM as they have found that it depends on how willing a healthcare professional is to engage in SDM whether it takes place or not. Both groups of participants also felt that they were not included in the decision-making for their healthcare decision, that paternalism occurred instead and that they felt they needed to ask questions to initiate SDM. Both groups of participants also felt that they were not listened to when making their healthcare decisions, but they believed that listening was key for SDM. Both groups of participants additionally discussed the differences in care between locations and different health departments. Two individuals with chronic pain believed that patients are experts in their own body and health and life circumstances therefore they need to be included in SDM. Participants with chronic pain also highlighted the need for healthcare professionals to tailor to the patient and their circumstances as each health condition affects people differently so this needs to be taken into account and patients should be asked how the health condition impacts them and most participants with chronic pain did not feel that the healthcare decision was tailored or personalised.

“So I said "OK, well, why have you suggested this particular treatment, for me?" and the answer was, "we always prescribe that here." So for me, that showed quite clearly that you're not looking at the patient as an individual with individual circumstances around the disease that you've got. You're going down a set treatment pathway and without the patient being in a position to question or have these conversations that you're talking about, in shared decision-making and it's just going to go down... that usual pathway and that's not at all how it should be.”

(P011, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

Two individuals with chronic pain also reported not receiving any care yet or still not being given any information due to COVID-19. Another two individuals with chronic pain stated that their healthcare professional did not like being questioned by patients. Participants from both groups felt pressured into a healthcare decision. Both groups of participants also felt that they were not given information or fully informed what was happening but that the healthcare professional was making the decisions instead and they felt they should have been given more time to make their decision. Additionally, both groups of participants believed that the healthcare professional should initiate conversations and make sure SDM is a priority as it is difficult for patients to challenge or bring up these thoughts. Both groups of participants also stated that they were given information after the decision had already been made. Two individuals with chronic pain explained that there were no treatment options available to them. Both groups of participants reported that their treatment option was discontinued. Two members of the general population felt that the NHS provides the cheapest, not necessarily the best treatment option and that if they went with an NHS treatment option then they would have received an inferior product and would have been left feeling disappointed. Both groups of participants believed that SDM should be standard within healthcare.

“I think the important thing for me is that it's the default, it's where we start and if we have to scale it back, then we scale it back but we try within reason to make it the way that we work. I think that would be great.”

(P006, Member of the General Population, Male)

However, both groups of participants stated that their healthcare professional did not want to engage in SDM and felt that if the healthcare professional had more empathy and knowledge, then they could take part in SDM. Members of the general population reported that the healthcare professional did not discuss information or treatment options. Both groups of participants felt that the healthcare system needs to change across the board and that the paternalistic attitude needs to go. Participants with chronic pain believed that time and culture shifting is required to allow for SDM to happen.

7.4 Discussion

The current study aimed to follow up on the findings from the previous studies in a more detailed qualitative exploration of patients' perceptions of SDM in healthcare decisions. The research question

was: “What are the Scottish general populations and individuals with chronic pain attitudes to and experiences of the SDM process?”

The attitudes of all participants, both the Scottish general population and individuals with chronic pain, to SDM was positive with participants believing that SDM should be standard within healthcare. However, in most cases across both groups, participants did not experience SDM and it was clear that there were differences between healthcare professionals, geographical location and departments in whether SDM occurred. Participants from both groups shared important factors to facilitate SDM.

Support and advice from family, friends, others with the same health condition and from healthcare professionals were important in SDM. Having a good relationship with the healthcare professional and agreement between the patient and the healthcare professional were key factors. Participants also considered the impact of their healthcare decision on others too. Participants felt it was important to be involved with healthcare decisions regarding their health, as well as how they valued their health. They also spoke about how having multiple health conditions can impact on their healthcare decisions and they were able to tell when they needed to see a healthcare professional. How often participants attended appointments and saw healthcare professionals was also highlighted. The most frequently discussed treatment options and health conditions were identified and participants discussed their experience of receiving private healthcare.

Half of participants were actively involved in their healthcare and felt it was important that they were involved in healthcare decisions. Most participants encountered paternalism when making healthcare decisions and spoke about the harms associated with paternalism. Additionally, participants spoke about who made the final healthcare decision: themselves or the healthcare professional. Most participants also discussed taking part in SDM and most participants said they would take part in SDM in the future. Every participant discussed the impact of COVID-19 had on healthcare, whether it was the general, potential impact of COVID-19 or the lived and personal impact COVID-19 had on the participant in relation to their healthcare. Nearly all participants discussed the impact (both positive and negative) of and their experience of remote consultations and how remote consultations had increased compared to in person consultations. Just over half of participants discussed the importance of face-to-face consultations in relation to the relationship with the healthcare professional, non-verbal communication, body language and social cues.

Most participants felt uncertain, worried or anxious when they were in the process of making their healthcare decisions. However, most participants felt happy, comfortable or reassured when they had actually made the decision. More than half of participants also felt unhappy when making a healthcare decision, sometimes leading to conflicts with the healthcare professional. Additionally, more than half

of participants reported having a negative experience when making a healthcare decision. All participants also believed that SDM was a good thing, and most participants felt that SDM was important and should be standard for all healthcare decisions.

Participants discussed how difficulties in accessing appointments with the healthcare professional and in accessing technology to engage in remote consultations were barriers to engaging in SDM. Participants also spoke about hardships they had experienced and how these hardships and moving locations had a negative impact on their mental state which subsequently acted as a barrier to being able to engage in SDM. Participants additionally highlighted how the healthcare professional's attitude can be a barrier to engaging in SDM when the healthcare professional has a negative attitude or is not willing to engage in SDM. They discussed how time pressures in GP appointments and waiting times were also barriers to engaging in SDM as there is not enough time to engage in SDM when GP appointments are only 10-minutes long.

Participants discussed how being aware of SDM can help facilitate engagement in SDM, and also spoke about how being or knowing someone who is a healthcare professional, or an academic, can be a facilitator for taking part in SDM. Participants additionally highlighted how being prepared for appointments can facilitate SDM and the importance of tailoring treatment options for each patient in facilitating SDM. Furthermore, participants explained that having a higher level of knowledge and being confident in making healthcare decisions can facilitate SDM. Additionally, participants spoke about the importance of communication with the healthcare professional in facilitating SDM. Participants also highlighted the importance of feeling in control of healthcare decisions for facilitating SDM.

Participants discussed how important it was for them to consider their quality of life when making healthcare decisions. They also spoke about how culture can influence engagement in SDM and highlighted that there are differences between healthcare professionals in their approach to making healthcare decisions. It was shared how the various ways in which SDM can be situational, although half of participants did believe that SDM is suitable or can be suitable for all healthcare decisions. Participants highlighted their various concerns around SDM, such as how they believed finance can limit patients' ability to take part in SDM. Participants additionally highlighted the multiple pressures that healthcare professionals and the NHS face and the different areas in which healthcare needs improved to allow for SDM to occur.

7.4.1. Differences Between Individuals with Chronic Pain & Members of the General Population

Considerable differences were found between how often some sub-themes were discussed between the two groups. There was a total of 8 sub-themes in which more participants with chronic pain discussed these topics compared to members of the general population: “participants’ health”, “frequency of attending appointments”, “private healthcare”, “active involvement”, “face-to-face consultations”, “access”, “healthcare professional’s attitude” and “awareness”.

Participants with chronic pain felt that it was important to take part in SDM and in decisions regarding their healthcare, as that it would empower them to take the best course of action for their health. Also, as participants with chronic pain felt that the decisions were being made about their health and their body, they needed to be involved in the healthcare decisions. A couple of participants with chronic pain also mentioned that due to having multiple health conditions or due to the effects of taking multiple medication, that they had to take these factors into consideration when making healthcare decisions or decisions that might impact on their health. Participants with chronic pain also explained that because they live with their health conditions, they can feel or know if something is not right in relation to their health and to then contact a healthcare professional as a result.

Participants who experience chronic pain stated that they attended healthcare appointments more frequently as they have multiple health conditions. Some of these participants mentioned attending different hospitals, GPs and being seen by different healthcare professionals such as doctors, nurses, rheumatologists and consultants. Additionally, more participants with chronic pain received private healthcare than members of the general population.

It was mostly participants with chronic pain that were actively involved with their healthcare. Additionally, it was mostly participants with chronic pain that believed it was important for themselves to be involved in decisions around their health as it is their body, and it gave them a sense of ownership in their healthcare. It was mostly participants with chronic pain that also believed it was important for other people to take accountability and to be actively involved in their healthcare too. One participant with chronic pain even described a campaign called the “it’s ok to ask” campaign created by the Scottish Government which encourages patients to ask questions about the benefits, risks and alternatives of treatment options. However, some participants with chronic pain did consider that it may be difficult to be actively involved in healthcare decisions due to pain, mental health, having a bad day, or not being given encouragement, or the opportunity, to engage, or not being prepared for consultations.

A couple of chronic pain participants also mentioned that whilst they like to be involved with their healthcare, they did also rely on the healthcare professional's knowledge or expertise to make some decisions. A couple of chronic pain participants additionally discussed that they felt that they really had to push and be their own advocate to be involved in their healthcare. It was mostly participants with chronic pain that tended to do this.

It was mostly participants with chronic pain that discussed the importance of in person consultations. One participant with chronic pain whilst admitting it is more difficult to build a relationship remotely, they did think they had built a decent relationship remotely. Another participant with chronic pain said that they were relieved that not all their consultations were face-to-face as it would have been annoying to attend so many appointments in a short space of time. They did however admit that face-to-face consultations are better if they needed to show the healthcare professional something e.g. a rash. One participant with chronic pain who was also a healthcare professional stated she had to remove her face mask because it was difficult to have an emotional conversation while wearing one and a member of the general population said they felt they had to exaggerate everything to get their message across.

It was mostly chronic pain participants that spoke about access being a barrier to engaging in SDM. Two participants with chronic pain felt that having access to their medical records, notes and the letters between their healthcare professionals would help them to engage in SDM as these documents would help to outline the decisions that were made, how they were made and would provide more specific information e.g. results from scans. One participant with chronic pain also discussed that it is sometimes difficult to speak to a healthcare professional and that most healthcare consultations are done online or over the phone now because of COVID-19. A couple of chronic pain participants highlighted that there may be some patients may be excluded because they cannot access, find it difficult to use or do not feel comfortable using digital technology. Although, another two participants with chronic pain also highlighted the positives of digital technology for improving access to more people in support groups or for remote communities to access more healthcare.

It was mostly chronic pain participants that spoke about the healthcare professional's attitude as being a barrier to engaging in SDM. Two participants with chronic pain discussed how the healthcare professional having a more passive approach to SDM was also barrier for engaging in SDM, as the healthcare professional "just went with" what the patient suggested instead of being more proactive, not putting forward any ideas or their opinions. Participants with chronic pain also felt that some healthcare professionals had become stuck in the habit of not engaging in SDM with their patients. Two participants with chronic pain additionally discussed that the healthcare professional's attitude

and communication or interpersonal skills were important for engaging in SDM with one chronic pain participant stating that the attitude or willingness of the healthcare professional to engage in SDM was more important than any tools.

It was primarily participants with chronic pain that spoke about awareness of SDM being a key facilitator for engaging in SDM. It was only participants with chronic pain that highlighted the need for healthcare professionals to be made more aware of SDM though. One of these participants with chronic pain also discussed how even though healthcare professionals are aware of SDM and speak about it, they do not know how to carry out SDM.

There was also one sub-theme in which only participants with chronic pain discussed the topic: “tailored”. A few participants with chronic pain discussed how tailoring healthcare options to each individual healthcare decision can help facilitate SDM. Participants with chronic pain also highlighted how positive healthcare decisions and consultations felt when the healthcare professional tailored the treatment options or conversation to their specific needs. Chronic pain participants additionally discussed the negative impacts of when they felt that the consultation or healthcare decision was not tailored or personalised to their condition or needs and that the healthcare they received was the same for everyone.

Two participants with chronic pain also explained that they would like the information that they receive in relation to their healthcare decision and the treatment options to be in a visual format as they believe that having a visual aid would be helpful to understand the information better rather than just text on paper.

7.4.2. Limitations

There were some limitations to the current study. One of the previously discussed limitations described earlier in this chapter was that only 14 out of the 24 participants’ data was analysed and reported for this study. Whilst this provides some ethical issues in relation to not using all participants data, and the researcher acknowledges and greatly appreciates that these participants have given their time and believed that their data was going to be analysed and used for research purposes, the reason for only using the 14 participants data was due to data saturation occurring with these 14 participants, i.e. no new themes or sub-themes were found to be emerging from the remaining 10 participants’ interview transcripts. This was confirmed by carrying out a light touch review of the remaining participants data. Below are example quotes from 4 of the remaining participants’ data which show that the same themes were found in their interview transcripts:

“I think one of the things that would be really helpful is if the doctors, when they're writing up their letters to the GP, if they copied that, if the patient also saw the letter to the GP, and I know actually that some doctors do that, there are some areas in the health service where that happens, and I think that's really, really helpful. Granted, there might be people who never look at the letter or don't want to know what's in it or don't see it but I think for a lot of people that would be useful and it would make them better able to make the choices and make the decisions when it comes to have to do that...there are some GP practices I think that allow patients to have access to their records... there's lots of evidence out there that people can cope with being able to see their medical records, and in fact you could probably pick up all sorts of mistakes and errors that probably creep in that normally you don't get the chance to know what's going on.”

(General Population, Female)

From this quote, it is apparent that the participant believed that patients not having access to their own medical records and any exchanged medical letters is a barrier for SDM. This finding corresponds with the sub-theme “access” under the theme “Barriers”. The participants that had their data analysed and used also spoke about access being a barrier to engaging in SDM and feeling that patients having access to their medical records, notes and the letters between their healthcare professionals would help them to engage in SDM.

“For me personally, it provides me with the feeling that I have some sort of control over the situation, so you know, I have a lifelong illness I need to manage... so having that shared, having that ability to make a decision myself and not having one forced upon me, you know, in order to make it in conjunction with a health care provider. I would say it's been really helpful in terms of giving me a sense of control and to a degree, some objective control over a situation or an illness or whatever that I don't have control over, whether I have that illness or not, but I have control over the progress, the progression of that illness and stuff like that, so it's quite good from that point of view and in terms of having that kind of psychological feeling of ownership over my health care decisions, you know, it's not, yes you're not visiting the health care provider, it's not through choice but I do have choice over how it's managed and that is really important. Whether I exercise that choice in the best way is another matter, but yeah that's probably the most important thing for me.”

(Chronic Pain Participant, Male)

It is clear from this quote that the participant felt that taking part in SDM made them feel more in control of their health and body in healthcare decisions and that feeling in control of their healthcare decisions was an important facilitator for engaging in SDM. Participants that had their data analysed and used also discussed control as a facilitator for engaging in SDM and how SDM gives the power or

control back to patients and that they feel it is important to be in control of their own health and body in the sub-theme “control” under the theme “Facilitators”.

“I just feel it's very, very clinical over the phone, you know, 'cause sometimes there's things that come up that you want to ask but it's better to do it person to person. I mean there was a few things that I wanted to ask at my last consultation that maybe, I felt as if maybe it would be wasting their time talking about it over the phone 'cause they had other people to attend to. Whereas person to person, I can talk to them and say, right, you know, does this usually happen with these drugs and whatever, you know, so yeah. I mean it's been better in person rather than over the phone...Yeah, I would say so because it's difficult to talk about the pros and cons of things when you're sitting on a phone in your own sitting room and you're not actually facing the person and they're telling you all that's involved and it's, I just find it more difficult to do.”

(P019, General Population, Female)

This quote conveys the participant's negative experience of remote consultations on SDM and highlights the importance of face-to-face consultations on SDM. Participants that had their data analysed and used also discussed the impact of remote consultations on SDM and face-to-face consultations in the sub-themes: “remote consultations” and “face-to-face consultations” under the theme “COVID-19 on SDM”. Participants also discussed how remote consultations had negative impacts on communication with the healthcare professional as they felt more distant, felt it was more difficult to receive information and that things were getting lost in translation. Participants additionally also felt that face-to-face consultations were more positive as it helped to build rapport and a relationship with the healthcare professional whereas remote consultations lacked the human element.

“I have normally one forum that... so I have MS and so I would go to an MS forum that I like and I would maybe ask other people with MS what they've done or their experiences and then I would probably discuss it with the healthcare professional... also my partner is included a little bit as well but that's more for some of the practicalities more maybe like travel and other things...”

(P015, Chronic Pain Participant, Female)

In this quote, the participant highlights the importance of being able to connect with patients that experience the same health condition to share information on their experiences and treatments which then helped the participant to take part in SDM with their healthcare professional.

Participants that had their data analysed and used also mentioned that they find it useful to receive advice and support from other people who have the same health condition as them whether that was

from an in-person support group or on Facebook groups in the sub-theme “advice from other people” under the theme “Support from Others”. Participants also mentioned that they would read about other people’s experiences and stories of the same condition and discussed including partners in healthcare decisions too.

Another limitation was that whilst participants from both the general population and participants with chronic pain were interviewed, most participants were females. Therefore, generalisability of results may be limited for males from both groups. Although gender differences in SDM were not found in study 3, there was evidence in the literature that women are more likely to engage in SDM (Shepherd et al., 2011). Hamann et al. (2012); Levinson et al. (2005) and Flynn et al. (2006) all found that women preferred an active consultation style. This is likely due to women frequently attending more than males at GPs and health care provision, where they go for support in relation to female-specific health e.g. contraceptive and pregnancy. Women have also taken an active role in these services for a long time.

Also, information on age and ethnicity was not collected for the current study. Therefore, any possible differences between age and ethnicity groups in members of the general population and participants with chronic pain have not been identified. Additionally, participants were required to have made a healthcare decision so that they could discuss their experience of making the healthcare decision. However, this means that members of the general population and individuals with chronic pain who have not made a healthcare decision could not take part and provide their opinion on or attitude towards SDM, again potentially limiting the generalisability of the results.

Finally, whilst the initial aim of the study was to look at only patients’ views of SDM, half of participants were either healthcare professionals or had a family member who was. However, participants that were healthcare professionals spoke about their perspective and experience of SDM as a patient as well as being a healthcare professional, therefore adding an interesting viewpoint to the results.

7.4.3. Future Research

Ideas for future research could include examining age, gender or ethnicity differences between members of the general population or individuals with chronic pain. Future research could also examine differences in attitudes towards SDM between participants who have and participants who have not made a healthcare decision. Additionally, future research could compare attitudes and experiences of SDM between patients from different health boards in Scotland or between different countries in the UK (e.g. Scotland compared to England etc.). Another potential area for future

research would be to examine differences in attitude or experience of SDM between different chronic pain conditions (e.g. Fibromyalgia compared to arthritis etc.) as SDM may be more appropriate for some health conditions than others.

7.5 Conclusion

The findings of the current study examined individuals with chronic pain and individuals in the Scottish general population attitudes to and experiences of SDM. The attitudes of all participants, both the Scottish general population and individuals with chronic pain, to SDM was positive with participants believing that SDM should be standard within healthcare.

However, in most cases across both groups, participants did not experience SDM, and it was clear that there were differences between healthcare professionals, geographical location and departments in whether SDM occurred. Participants from both groups also shared important factors to facilitate SDM.

The current study was the fourth and final study conducted for this body of work. The next chapter (Chapter 8), the General Discussion and Conclusion, will discuss the findings from studies 1-4 in relation to the aims of the thesis in addition to discussing future implications, original contributions to knowledge, the strengths and limitations of the thesis and ideas for future research before summarising and concluding the thesis.

Chapter 8: General Discussion and Conclusion

8.1 Chapter Introduction

This final chapter starts by demonstrating how the research carried out by the researcher addressed the overarching aims of the thesis. Subsequent subsections demonstrate the contributions made by each of the four studies. Study 1 used qualitative interviews with healthcare professionals to investigate their perceptions of the implementation of shared decision-making (SDM) and decision aids (DAs) in NHS Scotland. Study 2 used a quantitative approach to identify the predictors of acceptance of SDM by individuals with chronic pain. Study 3 used a quantitative approach to identify the predictors of engagement in SDM in the Scottish general population. Study 4 used a qualitative approach to examine the attitudes to and experiences of SDM both in the Scottish general population and in individuals with chronic pain. The chapter then focuses on discussing the original contributions to knowledge and the wider implications of the research. Following this, the strengths and limitations of the thesis are discussed and subsequently ideas for future research are considered. Finally, the thesis is summarised and concluded.

8.2 The Overarching Aims of the Thesis

To recap, SDM is a critically important element of the new model of healthcare quality. Despite the central role of SDM in the government's new model of healthcare quality, the utilisation of SDM within Scotland and the wider UK has been inconsistent (Coulter & Collins, 2011). Efficient SDM is currently not the norm (Creaney, 2019; Carmona et al., 2021), and a lot of patients want to be more involved in their treatment, and to be provided with more information in decisions concerning support, treatment or care than they presently experience (Coulter & Collins, 2011; Driever et al., 2022). However, implementing SDM in practice, such as formal processes, systems, workforce attitudes, behaviours and skills remains a difficult task (Coulter & Collins, 2011). Therefore, whilst the Scottish Government aims to make SDM standard practice in healthcare, successful implementation of SDM and DA is patchy and not currently the norm in Scotland. Consequently, the overarching aim of this thesis was to identify key factors that will facilitate the successful implementation of medical SDM in Scotland.

8.2.1. Aim 1: Investigate the Implementation of Shared Decision-making and Decision Aids in NHS Scotland (Study 1)

Several studies were discussed in the literature review (chapter 2) that looked at the implementation of SDM and DAs in Europe and the UK. In many of these the UK was found to have the lowest score for SDM compared to North American and European countries (Coulter & Ellins, 2006). The UK was also found to have poor implementation of SDM in standard medical practice (Coulter et al., 2011; Bomhof-Roordink et al., 2019). However, no studies could be found which investigated the implementation of SDM and DAs in Scotland specifically.

It is important to look at SDM in Scotland separately because there are several differences in how the NHS in Scotland and the rest of the UK operate (Deeming, 2024). In England, health is governed by primary care trusts and 10 strategic health authorities. In Wales, health is governed by 22 local health boards, local authorities and the National Assembly. In Scotland, health is governed by 14 NHS boards, whereas in Northern Ireland, health is governed by 4 health and social services boards (Sutherland & Coyle, 2009). Greer and Rowland (2007) also highlight the different health priorities in the NHS in the different countries of the UK: England prioritises market and technical policy approaches, where Scotland prioritises collectivism and collaboration, Wales prioritises collectivism and communication, whereas Northern Ireland prioritise neutrality, public health and democratic participation.

Further differences between NHS Scotland and NHS England are that NHS trusts are still in operation in England but were abolished in Scotland in 2004 (Greer, 2004; Stewart, 2004). Free NHS dental and eye checks were brought into Scotland in 2006, and prescription charges were terminated in 2011 but none of these changes have been made in England (Deeming, 2024). Another key difference is that needed personal care is free in Scotland but is means-tested in England (Deeming, 2024). Also important to note is that there is higher public spending on healthcare in Scotland compared to the rest of the UK (Steele & Cylus, 2012). For all of these reasons, and because Scotland's NHS is a separate body from the other public health systems in the UK, it is important to look at the implementation of SDM and DAs in Scotland.

Study 1 used qualitative one-to-one interviews with members of Scottish NHS boards to examine their perceptions of the implementation of SDM and DAs in Scotland. Some health boards did use DAs, with the most cited examples targeted towards cancer, tonsillitis, orthopaedics, gastroenterology and chronic pain. However, it was evident that most health boards did not use DAs. For the health boards that did use DAs, the use of DAs in these health boards was relatively new. The representatives of

most Scottish NHS Boards were of the view that DAs were not successfully implemented and used routinely as standard practice.

In contrast, participants in study 1 viewed SDM as a priority with most healthcare professionals reporting that SDM was being carried out routinely as part of standard practice. This finding aligns with the Scottish Government's aim for SDM to be standard practice in healthcare (Scottish Government, 2016; Smith, 2024), as well as the General Medical Council's instruction that SDM will be standard practice for every healthcare professional for the majority of medical decisions.

However, this finding contrasts with Légaré et al. (2008); Creaney (2019) and Carmona et al.'s (2021) suggestion that successful implementation of SDM was patchy and not currently the norm within the UK, or at least for Scotland. The views expressed by the representatives of the NHS Scotland boards were also shared by the healthcare professionals from Légaré et al.'s (2008) study, as both groups believe that they already carry out SDM, which is common for healthcare professionals when they consider their engagement with SDM (Stevenson et al., 2000) but having this belief can be a barrier to carrying out SDM as healthcare professionals often believe they are sharing decisions to a greater extent than their patients do. Further barriers to the successful implementation of SDM identified by the healthcare professionals included lack of time, lack of awareness of SDM and lack of reviews.

Whilst the healthcare professionals in study 1 believed that SDM is successfully implemented in most health boards in NHS Scotland, no audits on SDM in Scotland had been carried out to confirm that this is the case. Therefore, while healthcare professionals may believe they are conducting SDM appropriately, for example by fully informing patients and eliciting their preferences, it would be useful to examine patients' perspectives on SDM. It may be that the experiences of patients do not match the perceptions of healthcare professionals (Stevenson et al., 2000). Consequently, in subsequent studies in this thesis, attention turned to looking at patients' perceptions of SDM.

To summarise, the findings from study 1 indicated that DAs were not successfully implemented in most health boards in NHS Scotland. Even for the health boards that did use DAs, the implementation of DAs was new, and their impact was relatively unexplored. However, the findings from study 1 also indicated that healthcare professionals thought that SDM was standard practice in most NHS boards in Scotland.

If SDM is to become standard practice, it needs to be accepted both by healthcare professionals and patients. Since the study of the acceptance of SDM by patients has been relatively neglected compared with the study of acceptance of SDM by healthcare professionals, the remainder of this thesis focused on SDM in patients. Studies 2 and 3 adopted a quantitative approach, with study 2 using a survey

completed by patients with chronic pain, while study 3 used a survey completed by members of the Scottish general population. Study 4 adopted a qualitative approach to further explore ideas from studies 2 and 3, using qualitative interviews with both groups of patients.

8.2.2. Aim 2 (Study 2): Investigate the Predictors of Acceptance of SDM by Individuals with Chronic Pain

Study 2 used an online survey completed by individuals with chronic pain to study acceptance of SDM in these patients. Chronic pain patients were chosen because research suggests that SDM may be more useful for healthcare decisions in which there are varied treatment options available and multiple possible decisions (van der Horst, Garvelink, Bos, Stiggelbout, & Pieterse, 2023). This is the case with chronic pain where there are many different treatment options available to these patients. A further reason for choosing chronic pain as a test case was due to the considerable impact that it has on the quality of life for many individuals and their families in Scotland, and on healthcare services. Understanding SDM in patients with chronic pain could be important as it could help in providing an effective tool for patients to better evaluate and identify suitable care options, and to better self-manage their pain (Mann et al., 2013).

At the start of this study it was difficult to find measures of SDM, but the measures chosen were preferred consultation style (active or passive), attitudes towards SDM and knowledge of SDM (Durand et al., 2017) as previous research (Godin & Shephard, 1990; Van Ryn, 1990; Beale & Manstead, 1991; Charles et al., 1997; Joseph-Williams et al., 2014; Thompson-Leduc et al., 2015; & Hawley & Morris, 2017) identified these measures as being important in accepting and facilitating SDM. Attitudes towards SDM was regarded as a key outcome variable in study 2 and was the focus of the primary hypotheses, since attitudes seem to determine acceptance of SDM (Creaney, 2019).

First of all, it was useful to examine the links between the outcome measures of acceptance of SDM: attitudes towards SDM, preferred consultation style and knowledge of SDM. Attitudes towards SDM were linked to the other outcome variables: preferred consultation style and knowledge of SDM, suggesting that attitudes did provide a reasonable measure of acceptance of SDM as initially proposed. Participants' attitudes towards SDM were significantly negatively associated with their preferred consultation style, suggesting that individuals who are more positive about SDM prefer to be more active when making healthcare decisions. This result is in line with Charles et al. (1997) and Carlsen and Aakvik's (2006) findings that there was an association between preferred consultation style and attitudes towards SDM. Participants' knowledge of SDM was also significantly positively associated

with their attitudes towards SDM, indicating that individuals who have more knowledge of SDM will have positive attitudes towards SDM.

However, none of the primary variables that had been identified from the literature as key in relation to attitudes towards SDM was related to participants' attitudes towards SDM, raising a question mark over attitudes as an important variable in SDM. Although, in looking at the secondary hypotheses, three variables were significantly associated with attitudes towards SDM: education level, awareness of SDM and whether participants had made a treatment decision. Consistent with Zeuner et al. (2015), participants who had higher levels of education (university level and above) had significantly more positive attitudes towards SDM than participants who had lower levels of education (college level and below). It seems that patients who had more education would be more likely to know about/understand SDM and its benefits and be more receptive to SDM than those with lower levels of education. In addition, participants who had previously heard about SDM before taking part in the survey had significantly more positive attitudes towards and significantly more knowledge about SDM than participants who hadn't heard of SDM. It makes sense that those who had heard about SDM will be more receptive towards SDM than those who had not. Participants who had made a treatment decision also had significantly more positive attitudes towards and more knowledge of SDM than participants who had not made a treatment decision. This suggests that individuals who had made a treatment decision regarding their chronic pain have more experience of SDM and its benefits and will be more receptive towards SDM. These findings suggest that increasing patients' knowledge and awareness of SDM will help to increase their acceptance of SDM.

Only two factors predicted preferred consultation style: age and preparation for decision-making. Participants under the age of 50 years preferred a passive consultation style, thus they prefer the healthcare professional to make healthcare decisions. This finding was unexpected, and not in line with Hamann et al.'s (2012) finding that younger people preferred a more active consultation style, but a possible explanation is that these younger patients do not have as much experience in making healthcare decisions as patients over the age of 50 years old, and prefer to look to the healthcare professional's medical knowledge and expertise for making the healthcare decision. Individuals who were more prepared to make a healthcare decision also preferred to be passive when making healthcare decisions. This finding seems unexpected as individuals who were more prepared to make a healthcare decision, one would expect to prefer to be more active in their healthcare decisions because they are prepared to make a healthcare decision, but this was not the case for the current study's findings. Perhaps participants who preferred a passive consultation style felt more prepared to make a healthcare decision because they felt confident in the healthcare professionals' opinion and decisions.

Eleven factors were significantly associated with participants' knowledge of SDM: Attitudes towards SDM, awareness of SDM, attending a medical appointment, whether participants had made a treatment decision, participants' baseline pain intensity and breakthrough pain intensity, readiness to change, specifically the subscales: exercise, cognitive control, pacing and decisional conflict. Therefore, with the exception of the links between the outcome variables, the variables that were identified as significant predictors of acceptance of SDM were secondary variables.

Knowledge scores were significantly higher for participants who had previously heard about SDM before taking the survey than participants who had not, indicating that participants that were aware of SDM had significantly more knowledge of SDM than participants that had no awareness of SDM. This finding makes sense as individuals who had heard about SDM before taking the survey will have more awareness of SDM, thus these individuals would have more knowledge about SDM, whilst individuals that hadn't previously heard about SDM before taking the survey will have less awareness of SDM, thus these individuals would have less knowledge about SDM. Participants who had not attended a medical appointment had significantly more knowledge of SDM compared to participants who had attended a medical appointment. This finding was unexpected and not in line with Scherr et al. (2022) who stated that in order for patients to completely take part in SDM, they must have knowledge regarding their treatment options and their health condition and they must possess the skills needed to take part in the medical appointment, suggesting that patients can only experience SDM and so have knowledge of SDM from taking part in SDM in a medical appointment. Although perhaps participants who had not attended a medical appointment referred to other sources of information (such as Google) to acquire knowledge about SDM to control their pain or maybe participants who had attended a medical appointment did not experience SDM in their appointment and thus they had less knowledge of SDM. Knowledge scores were found to be significantly higher for participants who had made a treatment decision than those who had not made a treatment decision, indicating that participants who made a treatment decision had significantly more knowledge of SDM compared to participants who had not made a treatment decision. This finding makes sense as individuals who had made a treatment decision regarding their chronic pain will have more experience of SDM and consequently more knowledge of SDM, whilst individuals who hadn't made a treatment decision about their chronic pain will have less experience of SDM and less knowledge of SDM.

Participants with moderate baseline pain intensity had significantly more knowledge of SDM than participants with severe baseline pain intensity. This finding makes sense as it seems likely that individuals with moderate baseline pain intensity will still be trying to find out more about their condition and ways of reducing and managing their pain, whereas individuals with severe baseline pain intensity maybe feel that they have done all they can but nothing makes any difference to their

pain or would rather the healthcare professional decide their treatment instead. Participants who had severe breakthrough pain intensity had significantly more knowledge of SDM compared to participants who had mild to moderate breakthrough pain intensity. This finding makes sense as individuals with severe breakthrough pain intensity will be more likely to want to experience SDM to manage their pain, thus these individuals would have more knowledge of SDM, whereas individuals with mild to moderate breakthrough pain intensity will be less likely to need to experience SDM to manage their pain, thus these individuals would have less knowledge of SDM. Participants who employed a greater use of adaptive coping behaviours (or less use of maladaptive ones) had more knowledge of SDM. Thus, patients who exercised more to cope with their chronic pain, individuals who used more cognitive control (i.e. diverted their attention, used coping self-statements, re-interpreted sensations, avoided catastrophising and ignored pain) to cope with their chronic pain and patients who paced themselves had more knowledge of SDM. This finding corresponds with Hu et al. (2023) who found in their study that patients who exercised often were more inclined to use SDM, suggesting that patients who exercise frequently will have more knowledge of SDM. Individuals who had more knowledge of SDM also experienced less decisional conflict. This finding makes sense as individuals that experience less decisional conflict in making healthcare decisions probably experience less decisional conflict because they have participated in SDM, therefore these individuals would also have more knowledge of SDM.

Thus, in summary, the predictors of acceptance of SDM for individuals with chronic pain in study 2 (chapter 5) were: being over 50 years old, not being prepared to make a healthcare decision, having a higher education level, being aware of SDM, having made a treatment decision, not attending a medical appointment, experiencing moderate baseline pain intensity, experiencing severe breakthrough pain intensity, being more ready to change, exercising more, exhibiting cognitive control, pacing tasks and experiencing less decisional conflict.

However, the findings also demonstrated that these were perhaps poor measures of acceptance of SDM and highlighted the need for better measures of acceptance of SDM. Thus, the major constraints in study 2 were the validity of the outcome measures used, and the number of variables used, and these limited the utility of the findings in study 2. These constraints were addressed in study 3, where the Theory of Planned Behaviour was introduced as a new theoretical framework and fewer variables were used. In addition, a different demographic of participants was used to gain insight into what the predictors of engagement in SDM are for members of the Scottish general population.

8.2.3. Aim 3 (Study 3): Investigate the Predictors of Engagement in SDM in the Scottish General Population

While study 2 looked at acceptance of SDM for individuals with a specific health condition, it is also important to examine how patients generally engage with SDM. Consequently, study 3 investigated shared decision-making in the Scottish general population. An important theoretical extension to understanding engagement in SDM in study 3 was the introduction of the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) (Ajzen, 1991).

Given the key role of the TPB in study 3, the six primary hypotheses focused on the TPB variables. Four hypotheses focused on intention to engage in SDM as an outcome variable, looking at the impact of attitudes towards SDM, subjective norms and self-efficacy both separately and simultaneously on intention, and two hypotheses focused on engagement in SDM behaviours, looking at the relationship between intention and engagement in SDM, as well as the impact of all 4 variables: attitudes towards SDM, subjective norms, self-efficacy and intention, on engagement in SDM behaviours.

When analysed on their own, attitudes, subjective norms and self-efficacy all predicted participants' intention to engage in SDM, but when the three predictors were all entered simultaneously into a multiple regression, only subjective norms and self-efficacy were significant, with attitudes towards SDM found to be a nearly significant predictor of intention. These results largely correspond with Thompson-Leduc et al.'s (2015) finding that subjective norms, self-efficacy, and attitude were the most frequently identified determinants of healthcare professionals' intention to engage in SDM-related behaviours.

Subjective norms, self-efficacy and intention were also predictors of engagement in SDM behaviour when analysed separately. These results suggest that, consistent with the TPB, patients' engagement in SDM is influenced by what other people close to them think about SDM (subjective norms), how effective they feel they are in engaging in SDM (self-efficacy) and their intention to engage in SDM. The results also reflect Joseph-Williams et al.'s (2014) belief that subjective norms is a key "entry level" factor to SDM and with Durand et al.'s (2014) statement that engagement in shared decision-making requires self-efficacy. The only TPB predictor variable that was not significantly correlated with engagement in SDM was attitudes towards SDM. This finding was unexpected and inconsistent with the claims of Creaney (2019) that fostering positive attitudes towards SDM is crucial for effective engagement in SDM. This finding is worth further exploration and possibly suggests the need to develop a better measure of attitudes towards SDM.

When all four TPB variables (attitudes, subjective norms, self-efficacy and intention) were entered simultaneously as predictors of engagement in SDM behaviour, intention was the strongest predictor, with self-efficacy also significant, but neither attitudes nor subjective norms were significant. The strong influence of intention to engage in SDM reflects Ajzen's (1991) basic prediction of the TPB that the greater the intention to perform a behaviour, the greater the likelihood that the behaviour will be engaged in. Also consistent with the basic model of TPB, self-efficacy, i.e., the extent to which an individual believes that they can effectively engage in SDM, was also found to be a good predictor of engagement in SDM behaviour even after taking account of intention.

Another aim of study 3, tested in the secondary hypotheses, was to identify useful measures of SDM. The TPB analyses had indicated that both intention and engagement in SDM behaviour were useful outcome variables in studying SDM and these were also strongly related to patients' satisfaction with their decision. Those who intend to engage in SDM and those who engage in SDM tend to be more satisfied with the healthcare decision. This is consistent with Siebinga, Driever, Stiggelbout, & Brand (2022) and Shay & Lafata (2015) who also found that patients who have engaged in SDM are more likely to have higher levels of satisfaction. These findings suggest that intention, engagement in SDM behaviours and satisfaction with the healthcare decision are all useful measures of engagement in SDM.

However, preferred consultation was only weakly linked to intention and was unrelated to engagement in SDM behaviour and satisfaction with the healthcare decision, suggesting that preferred consultation style was less useful as a measure of SDM than the TPB variables and satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

Despite this, it was interesting that 94% of the participants in study 2 and 92.4% of the participants in study 3 preferred an active consultation style, indicating that they wanted to be involved in some way in making health decisions. In both study 2 and study 3 the preferred response: "As the patient, I should make the final decision about which treatment I should receive, after seriously considering my healthcare professional's opinion" was the most popular choice.

A further important finding of study 3 was that the participant's relationship with their healthcare professional was the most important predictor of engagement in SDM behaviours and satisfaction with their healthcare decision and the relationship with their healthcare professional was, in fact, an even better predictor than the TPB variables. These results correspond with Deniz et al.'s (2021) finding that the patients' relationship with the healthcare professional positively impacts SDM and demonstrates the healthcare professional-patient relationship as the basis of SDM (Eliacin et al., 2015). These results also correspond with Prip et al. (2018) who found that the patient-healthcare professional relationship

can impact patients' satisfaction with their healthcare and with Qudah & Luetsch (2019) who also found that increased patient satisfaction was associated with positive patient-healthcare professional relationships.

Knowledge of SDM was also weakly correlated with and predicted engagement in SDM behaviour, showing that participants who know more about SDM also engaged in more SDM behaviour. This supports the findings of researchers including Joseph-Williams et al. (2014) and Hawley and Morris (2017) who stated that for SDM to be achieved, patients need to have good knowledge.

When all the significant predictors of engagement in SDM behaviour were entered simultaneously into a regression, relationship with their healthcare professional was the strongest predictor with intention also contributing to the model, statistically significantly predicting engagement in SDM behaviour, whilst self-efficacy, knowledge and subjective norms did not. These results suggest that individuals' relationship with their healthcare professional was the strongest influence for members of the general population in Scotland on taking part in SDM. This result also corresponds with the Scottish Government report (2019) which identified that trusting relationships between patients and the healthcare professional is an important factor in facilitating SDM.

8.2.4. Aim 4 (Study 4): Examine the Scottish General Populations' and Individuals' with Chronic Pain Attitudes to and Experiences of Shared Decision-making

Study 4 aimed to explore in more detail some of the findings from the 2 quantitative studies, using a qualitative approach involving semi-structured interviews, to examine the perceptions and experiences of patients about how successfully SDM is implemented in Scotland. Participants in study 4 included both members of the Scottish general population and individuals with chronic pain.

Thematic analysis revealed that all participants believed that SDM was a good thing, and most participants felt that SDM was important. All participants had positive attitudes to SDM, with most participants believing that SDM should be standard for all healthcare decisions, reflecting the Scottish government's aim for SDM to be standard practice. However, participants across both groups felt that they did not experience SDM, and it was clear that there were differences between healthcare professionals, geographical location and departments in whether SDM occurred. This study adds important evidence about the perceptions of patients that run counter to the views of the healthcare professionals in study 1 who believed that SDM is successfully implemented in most health boards in Scotland.

Most participants encountered paternalism when making healthcare decisions and spoke about the harms associated with paternalism. This is clearly contrary to the basic principles of SDM but aligns with Davis et al. (2010) who found high levels of paternalism within healthcare in the UK. Additionally, participants spoke about who made the final healthcare decision: themselves or the healthcare professional. Whilst both groups of participants reported that the healthcare professional made the final healthcare decision, it was mostly chronic pain participants who said the healthcare professional made the final healthcare decision. Also, whilst most chronic pain participants said they were not happy about the healthcare professional making the final healthcare decision, there were some participants from both groups who were happy that the final healthcare decision was made by the healthcare professional as it helped take some of the burden off them. However, Bomhof-Roordink et al. (2019) found that the healthcare professional and the patient agreeing on the final decision was amongst one of the key components in a majority of SDM models. Most participants also discussed wanting to take part in SDM but highlighted that it can be difficult to engage in SDM if the healthcare professional does not provide patients the opportunity to engage in SDM or if the healthcare professional does not want to engage in SDM. This aligns with Driever et al. (2022) who found that the majority of patients want to be included in decision-making but believe that the healthcare professional makes the healthcare decision more frequently than they would like. Most participants also said they would take part in SDM in the future.

Since the study 4 was carried out during the Lockdowns linked to COVID-19, every participant discussed the impact that COVID-19 had in relation to their healthcare. Abrams et al. (2020) also discussed and noted the challenges and opportunities for delivering healthcare as a result of COVID-19, highlighting an increased need to facilitate participation in SDM. Some challenges that were highlighted included: patient preferences for an in-person consultation instead of a telephone consultation; potential decisional conflict over what treatment is appropriate for different patients introducing variation in essential healthcare; reallocating healthcare interfering with SDM concerning particular options of service which can be offered. Potential opportunities included: a unique chance to implement and study virtual SDM as it is unclear how significantly virtual consultations effect the healthcare professional and patient relationship and the ability to engage in SDM particularly for individuals with low health literacy or for individuals with who are less adept at using technology; possible infrastructure changes which improve healthcare collaboration, opportunities and tools to reach underserved populations; possible benefits of virtual SDM could include reduced travel, lower costs, increased amount of access to services/specialists, reduced access disparities and quality enhancements as a result of increased efficiency in transferring information.

Nearly all participants discussed both positive and negative impacts of remote consultations and how remote consultations had increased compared to in-person consultations following? COVID-19. Abrams et al. (2020) also commented that whilst social distancing and the reallocation of health services can impede preference for a face-to-face consultation, these measures also provide an opportunity to examine and implement virtual SDM processes. Just over half of participants discussed the importance of face-to-face consultations in relation to the relationship with the healthcare professional, non-verbal communication, body language and social cues. Abrams et al. (2020) additionally commented on how these adaptations influence the patients' relationship with their healthcare professional.

Most participants felt uncertain, worried or anxious when they were in the process of making their healthcare decisions. However, most participants felt happy, comfortable or reassured when they had actually made the decision. Glass et al. (2012) also found that taking part in SDM was positively associated with satisfaction with an individual's healthcare decision. However, more than half of participants also felt unhappy when making a healthcare decision, sometimes leading to conflicts with the healthcare professional, highlighting the importance of patients having a good relationship with their healthcare professional. Elwyn et al. also (2012) found that attaining SDM is dependent upon establishing a good relationship between patients and healthcare professionals and Deniz et al. (2021) additionally found that the relationship with the healthcare professional positively impacts on SDM. Additionally, more than half of participants reported having a negative experience when making a healthcare decision.

Participants discussed how difficulties in accessing appointments with the healthcare professional and in accessing technology to engage in remote consultations were barriers to engaging in SDM. Participants also spoke about hardships they had experienced and how these hardships and moving locations had a negative impact on their mental state which subsequently acted as a barrier to being able to engage in SDM. Participants additionally highlighted how the healthcare professional's attitude can be a barrier to engaging in SDM when the healthcare professional has a negative attitude or is not willing to engage in SDM. Joseph-Williams et al. (2017) also stated that a crucial obstacle in all change programmes is to alter attitudes. They agreed that attitudinal change amongst healthcare professionals is needed for SDM to be standard practice. Participants also discussed how time pressures in GP appointments and waiting times were also barriers to engaging in SDM as there is not enough time to engage in SDM when GP appointments are only 10 minutes long. Coulter and Collins (2011) also state that this is a common belief that SDM appointments use more time than appointments in which healthcare professionals alone decide. Although, whilst the appointments themselves might perhaps use a bit more time, the time used involving the patient in the decision

might decrease the overall time used working with a patient who is unhappy or uncertain regarding a decision they were not included in.

Participants discussed how being aware of SDM can help facilitate engagement in SDM. Joseph-Williams et al. (2017) also stated that increasing awareness of a phenomenon is frequently a first step in getting patients on board. Participants also spoke about how being or knowing someone who is a healthcare professional or an academic can be a facilitator for taking part in SDM. Participants additionally highlighted how being prepared for appointments can facilitate SDM. Participants also discussed the importance of tailoring treatment options for each patient in facilitating SDM. This reflects Cave's (2020) sentiment that for SDM to occur, healthcare professionals really must take on board the individual characteristics and needs of the individual. Furthermore, participants explained that having a higher level of knowledge facilitates SDM. Joseph-Williams et al. (2014) also found that patients require knowledge to engage in SDM. Similarly, other researchers (Hawley & Morris, 2017) stated that for SDM to be achieved, patients need to have good knowledge. Participants also discussed that being confident in making healthcare decisions can facilitate SDM. Additionally, participants spoke about the importance of communication with the healthcare professional in facilitating SDM. Participants also highlighted the importance of feeling in control of healthcare decisions for facilitating SDM. This is also consistent with Thompson-Leduc et al.'s (2015) findings where perceived behavioural control was found to be an important variable in several studies.

Participants discussed how important it was for them to consider their quality of life when making healthcare decisions. This is important as the ethos underlying SDM is that the healthcare professional is the expert on their condition, while the patient is the expert on their experiences and expectations of how to manage the condition. Participants also spoke about how culture can influence engagement in SDM. Hawley and Morris (2017) also point out that the different needs of patients from different racial and ethnic backgrounds have not been given sufficient consideration in developing models of SDM. Participants additionally highlighted that there are differences between healthcare professionals in their approach to making healthcare decisions. Participants also explained various ways in which SDM can be situational although half of participants did believe that SDM is suitable or can be suitable for all healthcare decisions. Participants highlighted their various concerns around SDM. Participants also spoke about ways in which finance can limit patients' ability to take part in SDM. Participants additionally highlighted the multiple pressures that healthcare professionals and the NHS face. Participants also discussed the different areas in which healthcare needs improved to allow for SDM to occur.

In summary, the attitudes of the study 4 participants towards SDM were positive with participants believing that SDM should be standard within healthcare. However, most participants felt that they did not experience SDM, and it was clear that there were differences between healthcare professionals, geographical location and departments in whether or not SDM occurred.

8.2.5. Overall Aim: To Identify Key Factors that will Facilitate the Successful Implementation of Medical Shared Decision-making in Scotland

The overall aim of the thesis was to identify key factors that will facilitate medical shared decision-making in Scotland. These factors were identified across the four studies (chapters 4-7).

Study 1 identified time, lack of awareness and lack of reviews as barriers to implementing SDM. This lack of time is also identified in a report produced by the General Medical Council (2020), where doctors across the UK identified a lack of time to understand patients; expectations, capacity and needs/wants as a barrier to engaging in SDM. Joseph-Williams et al. (2014) also found that the most often cited explanation for the lack of uptake of SDM by healthcare professionals is the lack of time in appointments. There is an expectation that discussions to facilitate SDM will add more time onto a pre-existing pressured 10-minute appointment (Légaré & Thompson-Leduc, 2014). However, there is literature which shows that whilst carrying out SDM may add on more time to individual appointments, SDM can frequently reduce the length of overall time spent on healthcare for each patient through more targeted follow-up discussions and appointments (Légaré & Thompson-Leduc, 2014), particularly if patients are provided with information beforehand and attend their appointment prepared. Thus, making time for SDM, increasing awareness of SDM and performing more reviews on SDM will help to facilitate the successful implementation of SDM.

Study 2 examined the impact of a wide range of variables that impacted on SDM in patients with chronic pain. The following variables were found to be important in supporting individuals with chronic pain to accept SDM: participants' attitudes towards SDM, age, preparation for decision-making, preferred consultation style, knowledge of SDM, education level, awareness of SDM, whether participants had made a treatment decision, attendance at a medical appointment, baseline pain intensity, breakthrough pain intensity, readiness to change, exercise, cognitive control, pacing & decisional conflict.

Awareness of SDM was also an important factor for SDM which was discussed in study 1. There is a call for more education to increase awareness of the benefits of SDM, what SDM would look like in

practice and how boards, patients and healthcare professionals can prepare for their new roles (Sign up to Safety Patient Engagement in Patient Safety Group & Ltd, 2016).

The TPB model introduced in study 3 provided a useful perspective on how to engage patients in SDM with subjective norms, self-efficacy and intention to engage in SDM identified as useful variables. The relationship with their healthcare professional and knowledge of SDM were also identified as important influences for members of the Scottish general population to engage in SDM. Knowledge of SDM was additionally found to be an important factor for SDM in study 2. In the Scottish Government report (2019), both healthcare professionals and patients also reported numerous barriers of SDM involving knowledge. Low health literacy was found to be the main knowledge barrier for some patients and was viewed as continuing to be a barrier for better SDM unless changes can occur.

However, participants' attitudes towards SDM, age, preferred consultation style, education level and awareness of SDM were unexpectedly not found to be significant factors for members of the Scottish general population to engage in SDM in study 3 despite these factors being significant in supporting individuals with chronic pain to accept SDM in study 2. A possible explanation could be that perhaps these factors are more important for individuals with chronic pain rather than for members of the Scottish general population for SDM or maybe these factors are of greater importance in accepting SDM instead of being important for engaging in SDM.

Study 4 highlighted that most participants did not experience SDM despite healthcare professionals in study 1 believing that SDM was standard practice for most health boards in Scotland and that there were differences between healthcare professionals, geographical location and departments in whether SDM was carried out. However, in study 3 the mean score for participants' engagement in SDM behaviours was 37.88 out of a possible 54, indicating that in study 3 participants had an average of 70% for engaging in SDM behaviours and in studies 2 and 3 participants that preferred an active consultation style including participants' who believe that "the healthcare professional should share responsibility with me for making the final decision about the treatment I should receive" was 94% of participants in study 2 and 92.4% of participants in study 3. Thus, these results from studies 2 and 3 correspond with Creaney's (2019) findings which highlights that there is an increasing drive in Scotland towards SDM. Although, despite participants' high engagement in SDM behaviours in study 3 and preferring to be actively involved in healthcare decisions in studies 2 and 3, perhaps most of the participants in study 4 did not experience SDM due to their healthcare professionals not engaging in or facilitating SDM with them because of the reported differences between healthcare professionals, geographical location and departments in whether SDM took place. Thus, these findings from study 4 correspond with the Scottish Government (2018) that whilst numerous examples of excellent

practice exist in NHS Scotland, effective SDM between patients and healthcare professionals is not yet standard practice.

Findings from both study 3 and study 4 also highlighted that support and advice from family, friends, others with the same health condition and from healthcare professionals were important in facilitating SDM. This finding also corresponds with the Scottish Government's (2018) research that in order to achieve SDM, there is a need for true collaboration between the patient and the healthcare professional, and the inclusion of carers, families and significant persons needs to be supported. Having a good relationship with the healthcare professional and agreement between the patient and the healthcare professional were also key factors for engagement in SDM in both studies 3 and 4. Having a trusting relationship between patients and healthcare professionals was additionally identified as being an important element to facilitate SDM by Creaney (2019). The Health and Care Experience Survey (2018) also found that there is a want from patients in Scotland for better relationships between patients and healthcare professionals.

Every participant discussed the impact that COVID-19 had on healthcare in study 4, including the impact of remote consultations and how remote consultations were more frequent than in person consultations. Participants also highlighted how in person consultations were important because of body language, non-verbal communication, social cues and for the relationship with the healthcare professional. Murphy et al. (2021) also highlighted that COVID-19 rapidly accelerated a shift to remote consultations (online, telephone and video) in general practice. Worries surrounding the effects of remote consultations have been raised although there is limited research on the impact of remote consultations and the effects of COVID-19 on healthcare. Haier et al. (2022) also found from their systematic review that the literature concerning SDM in remote consultations is sparse and focuses primarily on what the technology can achieve, but not on the extent to which technology can aid the collaboration between healthcare professionals and patients which is necessary for SDM. This could therefore be an area for future research.

Participants also identified that difficulties in accessing medical appointments and in accessing technology to engage in remote consultations were barriers to engaging in SDM. Abrams et al. (2020) also highlighted that COVID-19 has changed the way in which healthcare is delivered but this enables re-evaluation of standard practices and to enhance the effectiveness of management strategies. They also state that through the challenges of COVID-19 and any future challenges, continuous SDM is required with patients and healthcare professionals. They also acknowledge that COVID-19 has created numerous challenges but has also forced healthcare professionals to re-evaluate how to

provide increased high-quality and patient-centred healthcare. Participants also identified that experiencing a negative mental state was a barrier for engagement in SDM.

Healthcare professionals not wanting to take part in SDM or having a negative attitude towards SDM, were also highlighted as being barriers to engaging in SDM. The importance of positive attitudes is emphasised in Creaney's (2019) report which views fostering positive attitudes towards SDM as crucial for implementation and that stakeholders, i.e. healthcare professionals, should foster and promote attitudes which are receptive of SDM. Waiting times and time pressures in consultations were additional barriers which were discussed by participants as they felt that 10 minutes in each appointment is not sufficient to fully engage in SDM. This finding also links back to study 1's finding of time being a barrier to carrying out SDM.

Awareness of SDM was highlighted as being a facilitator of engagement in SDM in study 4. Awareness of SDM was also identified as being important factors for SDM in studies 1 and 2. However, awareness of SDM unexpectedly was not found to be significant for participants' engagement in SDM in study 3. Although, more participants were aware of SDM in studies 1 and 2 (70.8%) than in study 3 (44.3%). Participants also highlighted that being prepared for appointments was a facilitator for SDM. Being prepared to make healthcare decisions was also an important factor for SDM found in study 2. Tailoring treatment options for each patient was also identified as being important in facilitating SDM. Having more knowledge was additionally identified as a facilitator for SDM. This also corresponds with studies 2 and 3's finding that knowledge of SDM is important for acceptance of and engagement in SDM.

Having confidence in making healthcare decisions was also a facilitator for SDM. This finding supports study 3's finding that participants' self-efficacy is important for engaging in SDM. Participants also identified communication with the healthcare professional as being important for facilitating SDM. Participants additionally discussed how feeling in control of healthcare decisions was important for facilitating SDM. This finding also corresponds with Jordan, Joseph-Williams, Edwards, Holland-Hart, & Wood's (2019) finding that when teenagers feel that they are in control of what is happening to them, they act more positively towards being included in decisions and discussions, which can aid SDM. Van Der Ploeg-Dorhout, Van Den Boogaard, Reinders-Messelink, & Van Der Cingel (2024) also found in their study that every patient that experienced collaboration in decisions experienced this as being positive as it made them feel in control. Taking part in SDM made patients feel that their healthcare was their responsibility.

Ways in which culture can impact on engagement in SDM was also discussed. Also, differing examples in which SDM can be situational were discussed by participants despite half of participants belief that SDM can be applicable to all healthcare decisions. These beliefs were also shared with patients across

the UK who felt that it is not always possible or justified to include patients in decision-making because of particular circumstances or characteristics (MORI, 2018). Van der Horst et al. (2023) also identified and discussed ways in which SDM can be situational and in some instances, perhaps not appropriate such as in circumstances where immediate life-saving treatment is required. Examples of this include decisions on acute surgery (Niburski, Guadagno, Mohtashami, & Poenaru, 2020) or CPR for an acutely instable patient (Turnbull, Sahetya, & Needham, 2016). In these instances, delaying the initiation of treatment is potentially harmful. SDM is also regarded as being 'logistically impractical' when a patient is acutely unstable (Turnbull et al., 2016). Finance was also discussed as a potential barrier for some patients to engage in SDM.

Thus, in summary, the key factors that will facilitate the successful implementation of medical SDM in Scotland found across all 4 studies were: time, awareness of SDM, reviews, participants' attitudes towards SDM, age, preparation for decision-making, participants' preferred consultation style, knowledge of SDM, education level, whether participants had made a treatment decision, attendance at a medical appointment, participants baseline pain intensity, participants breakthrough pain intensity, readiness to change, exercise, cognitive control, pacing, decisional conflict, participants' subjective norms, participants' self-efficacy, participants' intention to engage in SDM, participants' relationship with their healthcare professional, support and advice from family, friends, others with the same health condition and from healthcare professionals, remote consultations, face-to-face consultations, non-verbal communication, body language, social cues, accessing appointments with the healthcare professional, accessing technology to engage in remote consultations, mental state, the healthcare professional's attitude, tailoring treatment options for each patient, communication with the healthcare professional, feeling in control of healthcare decisions, culture, SDM being suitable for all healthcare decisions and finance.

8.3 Contributions of Thesis

8.3.1. Original Contributions to Knowledge

Study 1 made an original contribution to knowledge with its focus on Scotland by exploring the use of DAs and SDM in NHS Boards in Scotland. No literature could be found on Scottish healthcare professionals' attitudes to SDM and only one study, based in America, could be found on clinicians' attitudes to SDM in a chronic pain context. The interviews with members of Scottish NHS boards found that, while some Scottish NHS Boards did use DAs, most health boards did not. In contrast, SDM was a priority with most healthcare professionals expressing the view that SDM was being carried out

routinely as part of standard practice. In this way the thesis filled a gap in the literature. Despite the central role of SDM in the Scottish government's new model of healthcare quality, the utilisation of DAs and SDM within the UK has been inconsistent (Coulter & Collins, 2011). No existing literature or resources were found that detailed the use of DAs and SDM in NHS Scotland; all literature concerning DAs and SDM related to NHS England and Wales. Although the MAGIC programme claimed to cover the UK, it did not include Scotland.

A further important contribution to knowledge was the focus in studies 2-4 on patients' attitudes to and engagement with SDM. Previous research, such as Légaré et al. (2008), had focused on healthcare professionals' attitudes to SDM and DAs but, for SDM to be standard practice, it needs to be accepted both by healthcare professionals and patients. Furthermore, no existing literature could be found on the relationship between readiness to change and SDM, yet there are studies discussed previously that show support for SDM and readiness to change for chronic pain patients. In addition, existing studies which use the TPB (Ajzen, 1991) in relation to SDM appear to only use healthcare professionals as participants, whereas the TPB was used to predict patients/members of the general population's engagement in SDM for study 3. In concentrating on patients' attitudes to and engagement with SDM, this thesis extends our knowledge of factors that influence the effectiveness of SDM.

The focus on chronic pain patients in study 2 also addressed a gap in the literature, as no literature was found that looked at acceptance of SDM in a chronic pain context. There are theories and models of decision making in psychology and in healthcare but there are no theories or models which look at or incorporate the acceptance of SDM in a chronic pain context. Therefore, investigating potential factors of acceptance in SDM in chronic pain patients also addressed a gap in the literature.

As far as the researcher is aware, there are also no previous studies which investigate the predictors of engagement in SDM for members of the Scottish general population (study 3). There also is not any previous literature which could be found that examines both individuals with chronic pain and members of the Scottish general population's attitudes towards and experiences of SDM (study 4).

Additionally, in their guidance around facilitating SDM and how to implement it as standard practice, the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (2021) recommended that future research focuses on how SDM differs between different groups of patients and in different healthcare settings; how to encourage patients to engage in SDM and how SDM may be required to be adapted for remote consultations. Thus, the current project also focused on these key areas, looking at general patients as well as chronic pain patients and exploring patients' attitudes to SDM in study 4.

Durand et al. (2017) developed a number of measures of SDM that were adapted for use in studies 2 and 3: participants' preferred consultation style, attitudes to SDM, knowledge of SDM, and SDM

awareness. The items included in these measures were originally created for or aimed at medical students, and these are the first studies that have used these items for patients with chronic pain and for members of the general population in Scotland.

8.3.2. Practical Implications

The research carried out during this PhD thesis has significant practical implications that will help to facilitate the successful implementation of medical SDM in Scotland.

Time was identified as a barrier to carrying out SDM, therefore creating more time in appointments for SDM to take place is of importance. Thus, increasing the allocated time for each appointment may help to implement SDM.

Awareness and knowledge of SDM were also found to be key for the implementation of SDM and in making participants satisfied with their healthcare decision. This shows the importance of increasing both patients and healthcare professionals' awareness and knowledge of SDM. This could be done by incorporating education about SDM as part of healthcare professionals' medical training or in training modules and by perhaps including information regarding SDM on the NHS website or in patient pamphlets at medical sites. The Scottish Government (2018) also suggest increasing training opportunities by embedding SDM into undergraduate education for all healthcare professionals. They also call for the creation of patient/public campaigns to improve individual's understanding, knowledge, confidence and skills to use health information. Additionally, they suggest making training and information on SDM publicly accessible to promote individuals to become actively involved in healthcare decisions. These recommendations are highly consistent with the current findings.

Clark, Rudell, Setiadi, Agrawal & Oliver (2024) also propose that in order for SDM to become standard practice in all healthcare settings, training is required on communicating benefits, risks and consequences, using decision aids and embedding SDM in organisational practices and culture. They also state that organisations should establish that skills, knowledge and confidence to aid SDM are included in all healthcare professionals' induction, training and ongoing professional development. Additionally, they highlight the importance of training to establish culture competence as this is key for the future of SDM. Respecting and understanding cultural beliefs, differences and practices is key for tailoring healthcare plans which align with the patients' preferences and values. Clark et al. (2024) also believe that, as healthcare technology advances, healthcare professionals need to have the skills to integrate and use digital tools (such as DAs) that aid SDM. Another recommendation for training and education to increase patients' awareness or knowledge of SDM is to improve their health literacy

skills. The importance of health literacy for effective SDM is highlighted by Wigfall and Tanner (2018). Muscat, Shepherd, Nutbeam, Trevena & McCaffery (2021) also highlight that there is not much evidence that SDM and health literacy have converged with related practice, except for simplifying SDM tools through improving readability scores of DAs. They suggest that alongside modifying verbal and written information, healthcare professionals should also address patients' capacities and skills. Through aiding the development of general health literacy skills for SDM, patients will possess a transferable set of skills if they want to use it. King et al. (2013) suggested that training through role play, and simulation should be promoted at Board level to develop more opportunities to examine consistent models of 'SDM in practice'. Zeuner et al. (2015) also support this idea and suggest that simulation centres which are currently being used to improve general clinical skills, could be used to practice SDM communication skills.

It was also found that no reviews of SDM were being carried out on healthcare professionals, thus carrying out reviews amongst healthcare professionals to ensure that they are partaking in or are encouraging their patients to engage in SDM would help to successfully implement SDM. Participants' attitudes towards SDM were also important for implementing SDM, specifically if they have positive attitudes towards SDM, therefore highlighting the benefits of SDM to patients would help facilitate SDM. Age was also a significant factor for SDM, specifically patients younger than 50 years old preferred the healthcare professional to make the healthcare decision. Thus, healthcare professionals should specifically focus on ensuring that younger patients take part in SDM or are given the opportunity to engage in SDM.

The more prepared patients felt in making a healthcare decision and the less decisional conflict they experienced, the more accepting they were of SDM, therefore healthcare professionals should help participants to feel more prepared to make their healthcare decision by giving them all of the information they need such as the pros and cons of each treatment option which will also help to reduce their decisional conflict. Preferred consultation style was also important for facilitating SDM, specifically participants who were more active in their healthcare decisions and feeling in control of healthcare decisions was also important, thus healthcare professionals should help to promote patients to be more active and involved in their healthcare decisions, this will also help for patients to feel more in control of their healthcare decisions. Although, most patients in studies 2-4 did prefer an active consultation style which is positive.

Education level was additionally important for SDM, specifically that patients with a higher education level were more likely to take part in SDM, therefore any materials promoting SDM should contain simple information which is appropriate for patients of all educational levels. Whether participants

had made a treatment decision also influenced SDM, specifically patients that had made a treatment decision were more accepting of SDM, thus healthcare professionals should ensure patients that have not yet made a treatment decision or are in the process of making a treatment decision have the opportunity to engage in SDM. Also, participants that attended a medical appointment preferred for the healthcare professional to make the healthcare decision, therefore the healthcare professional should perhaps encourage participants to be more active or involved in their healthcare decision at appointments.

Patients that experience mild to moderate breakthrough pain intensity and that experience severe baseline pain intensity had less knowledge of SDM, thus healthcare professionals should try to inform these patients of SDM and how it can benefit the treatment of their chronic pain. Also, chronic pain patients that adopted a range of adaptive coping mechanisms such as exercise, cognitive control and pacing facilitated SDM, thus healthcare professionals should promote and inform chronic pain patients of these adaptive coping mechanisms to help them manage their chronic pain.

Participants subjective norms and support and advice from family, friends and others with the same health condition and from healthcare professionals are all facilitators of SDM & made participants more satisfied with the healthcare decision, therefore healthcare professionals should try to include and involve patients' family or friends in SDM if that's what the patient wants. Also providing patients with information about support groups or forums for patients with the same health condition can also help facilitate SDM. Participants self-efficacy and intention was additionally important for SDM and for participants to be more satisfied with their healthcare decision, thus helping the patient to feel more confident and able to take part in SDM will help facilitate SDM and the patient's intention to engage in SDM again in the future and to help patients feel satisfied with their healthcare decisions.

The relationship between the healthcare professional and the patient as well as the healthcare professional's attitude and communication with the healthcare professional were also important for SDM and for making the participants satisfied with their healthcare decision, therefore fostering a good relationship and communication with patients, ensuring they have positive attitudes towards their patients and SDM is crucial. Remote consultations and face-to-face consultations were also facilitators of SDM, some patients preferred remote consultations whilst others preferred face-to-face consultations, thus healthcare professionals should check with individual patients what type of appointment they would prefer. Furthermore, accessing appointments with the healthcare professional and accessing technology to engage in remote consultations were important for facilitating SDM, therefore, trying to ensure patients can get an appointment with the healthcare

professional particularly an in-person appointment if patients do not have access to technology to engage in remote consultations is important.

Non-verbal communication, body language and social cues were additionally found to be important for SDM in study 4, therefore the healthcare professional should keep these in mind when in appointments with patients and be as open as possible in these areas. Participants mental state was important for SDM; thus, healthcare professionals should assess a patient's mental state to ensure they can engage in SDM. Tailoring treatment options for each patient also was important for facilitating SDM, therefore healthcare professionals should ensure that treatment options are tailored to each patient and their specific needs. Culture was also important for SDM; thus, healthcare professionals should be mindful of patients' culture and how that may impact on their ability to take part in SDM. Finance was additionally important for SDM, specifically, some patients felt that they were able to engage more in SDM in private healthcare, thus healthcare professionals in the NHS should ensure that SDM occurs regardless of private or public healthcare. Finally, SDM should be suitable for all healthcare decisions, therefore, all healthcare professionals should strive to carry out SDM in all healthcare decisions, where possible.

Therefore, the identification of these key factors (that were identified across the 4 studies) that will facilitate the successful implementation of medical SDM in Scotland can be practically implemented following these suggestions, thus facilitating the successful implementation of SDM in Scotland and potentially in other countries too.

Another major finding was that the TPB was a significant and useful model in predicting participants' engagement in SDM. Therefore, focusing on the components of the TPB and understanding the crucial role of patients' attitudes towards SDM, their subjective norms, self-efficacy and intention in predicting their engagement in SDM and health behaviours is key to help implement SDM. Although, another important practical implication is that more effective and reliable measures of SDM need to be developed and validated as most of the measures of SDM used in the study were not reliable but were used as the range of measures of SDM were limited.

Also, it was found in study 1 that DAs are not successfully implemented and used routinely as standard practice within most Scottish NHS Boards. Clinicians believed that a successful DA should be more visual than having lots of text, favouring images and animated videos over lots of text. It was also agreed that key stakeholders should have a say in the development of a DA or for any medical intervention, so patients and as many various healthcare professionals which are involved in the health condition should all be consulted for their opinions in creating a DA. Information needs to be accessible. Information in a DA needs to be kept simple and understandable for all reading/health

literacy levels. They also need to contain localized Information and signpost to additional resources. Clinicians believed that a possible future decision aid for chronic pain would be useful for patients to self-manage their condition and that the DA should include or list all available treatment options for patients. Thus, incorporating these features into a DA for chronic pain and for DAs in general may help facilitate the successful implementation of DAs in Scotland.

8.4 Strengths and Limitations

An important strength of this thesis was the focus on patients. While study 1 looked at healthcare professionals, studies 2, 3 and 4 focused on patients. While most previous literature on SDM only looked at healthcare professionals as participants (Légaré et al., 2008), there were strong recommendations from the literature and from the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (2021) that future research should focus on patients' understanding of SDM. Thus, the current project focused on patients.

Another strength was the focus on Scottish patients and identifying key factors that would facilitate the successful implementation of SDM in Scotland. Research on SDM in Scotland was sparse in the literature and the research conducted for this thesis addressed this gap in the literature, making an original contribution to knowledge in a Scottish context to aid the successful implementation of SDM in Scotland.

Another key strength of the thesis was the use of a mixed methods approach. Blending quantitative and qualitative methods, the strengths of each method are maximised, and their respective weaknesses are avoided (Tashakkori & Teddlie, 1998). Additionally, mixed methods research aims to supply a more in-depth understanding of a phenomenon which would not have been attainable through utilising a single approach (Morse & Niehaus, 2009; Creswell & Clark, 2011).

There were also limitations within the thesis. The most prominent limitation was that the majority of the measures used particularly in study 2 (and some in study 3) did not have good alpha reliability scores. Although knowledge was linked to a range of variables in study 2, the knowledge scale in particular did not have a good alpha reliability. However, the reason for using these measures was because there were not many reliable measures of SDM or acceptance of SDM available when the researcher conducted the studies. In a review of SDM measures, Ahmad, Tabar, Othman and Abdelrahim (2020) found that the majority of the measures reviewed received a poor score. These authors found that only one measure: the OPTION 12 Scale (Elwyn et al., 2005) was given an excellent rating in all 5 validity ratings in content, structural and criterion validity. Although there were issues

with the measures mostly in study 2, the attitudes towards SDM measure was based on the OPTION 12 scale (Durand et al., 2017). To help overcome the limitation of validity of the measures, the researcher only used items that had acceptable reliability scores when analysing the data and for knowledge of SDM, only items that gave the highest reliability scores were used in analysing the data.

Also, a noted limitation of the thesis was that for studies 2 and 3, due to the nature of the studies, multiple hypotheses testing was carried out. Whilst, the researcher is aware of the problems associated with multiple testing, mainly that through doing this, it is more likely for the researcher to have a false-positive finding (Ranganathan et al., 2016), the researcher still felt it was necessary to test multiple different variables in order to identify which variables impact on the acceptance of SDM in individuals with chronic pain and which variables impact on members of the Scottish general population's engagement in SDM to address the aims of the research, further knowledge and potentially facilitate the successful implementation of SDM. Also, whilst the researchers are additionally aware that the p-values would normally be adjusted for multiple comparisons using the methods outlined in Chen et al. (2017), instead the researchers decided to split the analyses and hypotheses into primary and secondary analyses and hypotheses. Thus, any significant results which are greater than .001 should be interpreted with caution. Additionally, in retrospect, if the analyses were to be carried out again, then the p-values should be adjusted as discussed above since multiple testing was carried out.

Another limitation of the thesis was that not all Scottish NHS health boards took part in the interviews in study 1. Therefore, the researcher may not have captured a complete picture on the implementation of SDM and DAs in Scotland as not all Scottish NHS boards participated in the study. It may be possible that the boards that did not take part in study 1 used or implemented DAs more than the boards that were interviewed. However, the researcher did contact all Scottish NHS boards for recruitment for study 1's interviews but not all NHS boards replied or participated. Although more than half of Scottish NHS boards (8 out of 14) took part in interviews for study 1. There was also the potential for bias in the manner that participants were recruited for the study. By emailing the listed contact detail for each NHS board, it was hoped that one individual from each board who was knowledgeable in the use of decision aids and SDM in their board would be interviewed. Thus, the majority of participants were knowledgeable about or had heard about decision aids and/or shared decision-making. Therefore, there was the potential for bias in that there perhaps could have been more effort to recruit participants who were not knowledgeable about or hadn't heard about decision aids and/or shared decision-making in order to gain a more balanced understanding of the implementation of DAs and SDM in Scottish NHS Boards.

Additionally, there were a few limitations surrounding studies 2 & 3 in relation to generalisability of certain demographic characteristics. Many more females than males that took part in all of the studies. Therefore, generalisability of results may be limited for males from both groups, thus the results are more biased towards females as not many males took part in the studies. Although gender differences in SDM were not found in studies 2 & 3, potentially due to the limited number of males that took part in these studies, there was evidence in the literature that women are more likely to engage in SDM (Shepherd et al., 2011). Hamann et al. (2012), Levinson et al. (2005) and Flynn et al. (2006) all found that women preferred an active consultation style. This is probably because women are more frequent attenders than males at GPs and health care provision, where they go for support in relation to contraceptive and pregnancy. Women have taken an active role in these services for a long time.

Additionally, although there was not a more even distribution in participants that preferred a passive consultation style, this is a positive as this suggests that perhaps more patients prefer to be involved in their healthcare decisions. However, again it does limit generalisability of the results as there may have been more differences found for participants that preferred an active consultation style, thus the results are more biased towards participants with an active consultation style.

Despite there being many participants that had a higher education level for study 3 and few unemployed participants for study 3, these distributions were more even in study 2's participants. Although, as there were more participants that had a higher education level and less participants that were unemployed for study 3, this additionally limits generalisability of results and creates a bias towards these demographics. The results may have been different if more participants with a lower education level and more participants that were unemployed took part in study 3. Additionally, participants were required to have made a healthcare decision in study 4 so that they could discuss their experience of making the healthcare decision, thus members of the general population and individuals with chronic pain who hadn't made a healthcare decision could not take part and provide their opinion on or attitude towards SDM, potentially limiting the generalisability of the results for study 4 and creating a bias as members of the Scottish general population and individuals with chronic pain that have not made a healthcare decision may have had different perceptions and experiences of SDM. However, participants that had and participants had not made a treatment decision took part in studies 2 and 3 and gave their attitudes towards SDM then. Thus, the researchers may be missing an understanding of how males, individuals who suffer with either breakthrough or baseline pain, individuals with a lower education level, individuals who are unemployed, individuals who prefer a passive consultation style and individuals who have not yet made a healthcare decision's view or experience SDM.

Also related to generalisability, a potential limitation for the current thesis was that all participants were Scottish therefore, potentially limiting generalisability of results and creating a possible bias to just the Scottish population.

Furthermore, whilst the initial aim of study 4 was to look at only patients' views of SDM, half of participants or a family member turned out to be healthcare professionals. However, participants who were healthcare professionals spoke about their perspective and experience of SDM as a patient as well as being a healthcare professional, therefore adding an interesting viewpoint to the results.

8.5 Future Research

Based on both the existing literature and the research carried out in the thesis, there are several suggestions for future research. The first suggestion would be to explore the development of better validated measures of SDM. The current studies questioned the value of preferred consultation style as a measure of SDM as it was not strongly related to other variables. However, correlations between the TPB measures and satisfaction with the healthcare decision measures suggested that these were useful measures. Future research should aim to develop and validate better SDM scales and attitudes scales for patients which have acceptable reliability scores. The TPB variables in study 3 would be a good place to start in this.

Advances might also be made by comparing the implementation of SDM and DAs between the different countries within the UK. Previous literature (Coulter & Ellins, 2006; Härter et al., 2017) compared the implementation of SDM across countries but list the UK as an individual country rather than comparing the different countries (Scotland, England, Wales and Northern Ireland) within the UK. Also, as study 1 only asked healthcare professionals generally (regardless of job role) about implementation of SDM and DAs, it may be worthwhile to look at potential differences in the implementation of SDM and DAs between different healthcare professional job roles i.e. GP doctors vs nurses vs physiotherapists etc.

Given the differences noted in this thesis between staff and patients' perceptions of whether SDM is already successfully integrated into practice, it would seem that there is a need for training both for NHS staff and for patients. The Scottish Government (2018) has already suggested increasing training opportunities by embedding SDM into undergraduate education for all healthcare professionals, further highlighting examples of good practice might have a role to play here.

Related to better training is the transformational impact that generative AI is likely to have on SDM in healthcare in the near future. This technology is likely to completely change the way in which some components of healthcare are delivered (Li, Kumar, & Chen, 2023). Given the capacity of generative AI to create content, it may be used to generate targeted knowledge and decision aids for patients with specific conditions. Elwyn, Ryan, Blumkin & Weeks (2024) demonstrated from their case study that AI could facilitate SDM, but they did also state that due to the pace of development, lots of policy and research questions are still to be answered in relation to the impact of AI on SDM.

It is also clear that the impact of the change to remote consultations as a result of COVID-19 has been underexplored. Haier et al. (2022) found from their systematic review that the literature concerning SDM in remote consultations is sparse despite the increase in remote consultations and focuses primarily on what the technology can achieve but not on the extent to which technology can aid the collaboration between healthcare professionals and patients which is necessary for SDM. These issues could be explored in more detail to examine the impact of remote consultation on the practice of SDM.

8.6 Thesis Conclusions

The research carried out in this thesis has focused on factors that impact on SDM in patients, as well as patients' attitudes to and experiences of SDM. The research built on existing theoretical frameworks and empirical literature and adopted a mixed-methods approach, starting with an exploratory qualitative study with members of NHS Scotland, which then informed subsequent quantitative and qualitative studies with patients.

The qualitative findings of study 1 found that, whilst DAs were not widely used, the healthcare professionals felt that SDM was successfully implemented in NHS Scotland. While there was research evidence about staff perceptions of SDM, there was a dearth of evidence on the views of patients. These findings guided the decision to focus on patients in studies 2, 3 and 4.

The quantitative findings of study 2 identified numerous factors that predicted knowledge of SDM, attitudes towards SDM and preferred consultation style, but major constraints with this study were the number of variables used, and the validity of the outcome measures used, and this limited the utility of the findings in study 2. The introduction of the TPB model in study 3 helped to provide a more useful framework for studying SDM, and the TBP variables, intention to engage in SDM and engagement in SDM behaviours, as well as satisfaction with the healthcare decision all emerged as useful outcome measures. The views of others (subjective norms), confidence in one's ability to take part in SDM (self-efficacy) and knowledge of SDM were useful predictor variables, demonstrating a

need for education and training in SDM for both patients and healthcare professionals. The relationship with the healthcare professional (HCP) also proved to be an important variable, highlighting the importance of the relationship between the patient and the HCP for successful engagement in SDM. This is an important finding at a time when a widespread criticism that patients make of their healthcare appointments is that they "see a different person every time".

Study 4 participants confirmed that patients were supportive of and keen to engage in SDM but also highlighted that they often feel that they do not currently have the opportunity to do this. This study also confirmed findings from previous studies such as the importance of awareness, knowledge, confidence, control and the views of others on engagement in SDM. The timeline for the thesis meant that this study was conducting during the COVID-19 lockdowns, and this caused both opportunities for and challenges to engaging in SDM.

Both the qualitative and quantitative studies and ideas discussed in this thesis have highlighted key factors that could help to facilitate the successful implementation of health-related SDM in Scotland. The contradiction between the views of the members of health boards in study 1 that SDM is currently implemented in the NHS in Scotland, and patients' views in study 4 that it is not, suggests that there is still a need to clarify exactly what SDM means for both patients and healthcare staff in order to develop a common understanding. Thus, there is a need to develop more guidance and to educate both staff and patients about what SDM is and how best to practice SDM for healthcare decisions.

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Appendix A: Study 1 Example of Transcript Coding

I: Ok. Em, are the decision aids to be used in consultations or outwith consultations? Or can they be used in both?

P: In both, in both. So, depending on the type of decision aid. If it's an information leaflet, it can be discussed in consultation or provided as supplementary information. Em, a couple of different information decision aid tools we've developed in the past year has been, eh, animated video, so therefore it can be used at the consultation but also provide an alternative, em, decision aid tool that can be accessed at home in the patient's own time.

I: Ok, em, I was wondering if there was any, em, financial incentives or if they're included in company performance targets?

P: No.

I: Ok.

P: No. The- the approach is a person-centred approach and not a financial or performance gain.

I: Ok. Are there audits or reviews carried out on the decision aids and on shared decision-making?

P: Yes.

I: How often are these carried out?

P: So they were carried out initially as a baseline and then with an outpat-, an outcome impact evaluation, em, the work is still relatively new Abbie, so that process is ongoing.

I: Ok. Are shared decision-making and decision aids used routinely as part of standard practice in your board?

P: No, but that is this year's plan. (laughs)

I: Ok (laughs), em, so you think the reason why it's not standard practice is just because it's just new, it's still to be-

P: Well, I think, as I'd said, you know, specific to certain areas, the likes of cancer services or long-term conditions or that, there will be supportive information that provides, you know, shared decision, em, and decision aid tools. For the purpose of realistic medicine, it's still relatively new to the organisation and therefore, in a program to roll it out.

I: Ok, that's fine. Do you think that a decision aid for chronic pain would be useful for patients?

P: Yes, em, if I think about the approach we've had around caring for your, em, throat and it was an animation video we made around tonsil hygiene and having a video accessible in your own home, in your own time, em, it empowers the patient and re-iterates the information, em, that can be forgotten if it's just given to you in a leaflet. You can I-use, lose the- the leaflet or you can forget, em, what information you were given at the time of a consultation. So I believe having aids in different formats that are accessible for you at a convenient time, wherever you are, supports management of that condition.

Appendix B: Thematic Analysis Process Using Worked Examples Study 1

Six stages of Thematic Analysis:

- 1) Data familiarisation,
- 2) Generating initial codes,
- 3) Searching for themes,
- 4) Reviewing themes
- 5) Defining and Naming themes
- 6) Producing a qualitative report

Priority

- 1) **Data familiarisation:** “Anything that's basically, we think something is a good idea and we're, we've spoken to our patients, we can actually facilitate work, then we actually go ahead and do it but we've not actually used any tools to-, to start a service like that.”

“The approach is a person-centred approach and not a financial or performance gain.”

I: “...are there audits or reviews carried out on shared decision-making? P: “Yeah, em, no and I'm not sure how you would do that either...”

- 2) **Generating initial codes:** “Anything that's basically, we think something is a good idea and we're, we've spoken to our patients, we can actually facilitate work, then we actually go ahead and do it but we've not actually used any tools to-, to start a service like that.” - healthcare professionals prefer/favour shared decision-making to decision aids.

“The approach is a person-centred approach and not a financial or performance gain.” – there are no financial or performance-based incentives for partaking in SDM.

I: “...are there audits or reviews carried out on shared decision-making? **P:** “Yeah, em, no and I'm not sure how you would do that either...” – most participants stated that no audits or reviews were carried out on SDM or DAs

3) Searching for themes:

Theme: Priority

Sub-themes: Favour existing practice, incentive and lack of review

4) Reviewing themes:

Theme: Priority

Sub-themes: Favour existing practice and incentive (removed lack of review as doesn't fit)

5) Defining and naming themes: Priority (now changed to Shared decision-making is the top priority), Favour existing practice (now changed to Favour shared decision-making) & Incentive (now changed to Personal & Professional Incentive).

6) **Producing a qualitative report:** The theme “Shared decision-making is the top priority” is composed of 2 sub-themes: Favour shared decision-making and Personal & Professional Incentive. The 2 sub-themes both convey how important SDM was across the different health boards, being the top priority for participants.

Favour Shared Decision-making

Shared decision making (the process/practice of patients and clinicians working in partnership to choose treatments) seemed to be the priority for all healthcare professionals instead of using decision aids (physical “tools” such as an app on a tablet or an information leaflet) to facilitate SDM with most boards reported SDM being carried out routinely as part of standard practice. SDM involves the availability of evidence-based information concerning uncertainties, outcomes and options, together with counselling for decision support and a system for implementing and recording patients' informed preferences (Coulter & Collins, 2011). Therefore, SDM can be carried out by the clinician telling the patient evidence-based information concerning uncertainties, outcomes and options, provide

counselling for decision support and implement and record patients' informed preferences through researching information before the patient arrives, discussing this information with the patient and then taking note of the patient's choice on his/her computer. DAs can aid SDM by presenting this information in a simple format to the patient but DAs are not always needed for SDM to be carried out as the clinician can carry out SDM through skilled conversation with the patient.

Much like the finding of the MAGIC project that "Skills trump tools, attitudes trump all", numerous healthcare professionals had said that whilst the tools (the option grids and decision aids) were useful, the most important thing for them was their/clinicians attitudes to SDM and carrying out SDM i.e. having various conversations with their patients, and the skills and knowledge to aid these conversations.

"Anything that's basically, we think something is a good idea and we're, we've spoken to our patients, we can actually facilitate work, then we actually go ahead and do it but we've not actually used any tools to-, to start a service like that. "

Personal & Professional Incentive

Every board had stated that there were no financial incentives or company targets surrounding carrying out SDM. Many participants believed that it was a crucial part of their job to carry out SDM and that improving patient care through SDM was the real incentive as opposed to monetary rewards or performance targets.

"The approach is a person-centred approach and not a financial or performance gain."

Appendix C: Study 1 Interview Schedule

Opening A. (Establish Rapport): Hello [shake hands] My name is Abbie McGuire, a PhD researcher from the University of the West of Scotland and as a member of an NHS Board, I thought it would be a good idea to interview you, so that I can better understand how decision aids and shared decision making are used in current practice.

B. (Definitions): There may be differing definitions of shared decision-making. Therefore, for clarity and to avoid uncertainty and confusion, the definition which I am using for shared decision-making is:

"Shared decision-making (SDM) is a practice in which patients and clinicians work in partnership to choose treatments, management packages, support packages, or tests based on the patient's informed preferences and clinical evidence. SDM involves the availability of evidence-based information concerning uncertainties, outcomes and options, together with counselling for decision support and a system for implementing and recording patients' informed preferences." (Coulter & Collins, 2011).

There are also some questions regarding shared decision aids. Again, there may be differing definitions of shared decision aids. Therefore, for clarity and to avoid uncertainty and confusion, the definition which I am using for shared decision aids is:

"Decision aids are tools that help people become involved in decision making by making explicit the decision that needs to be made, providing information about the options and outcomes, and by clarifying personal values. They are designed to complement, rather than replace, counselling from a health practitioner." (Ottawa Hospital Research Institute, 2015).

C. (Purpose) I would like to ask you some questions concerning the use of decision aids, features of these aids, evaluation of these aids, examples of best practice decision aids and shared decision making in order to learn more about current practice in the development and design of decision aids and how shared decision making is utilised in practice to help inform the methodology for designing and implementing a shared decision-making aid for chronic pain which will build on existing best practice

D. (Motivation) I hope to use this information to spread, adapt and scale-up the methodology and product for use in NHS Boards.

E. (Timeline) The interview should take about 30-45 minutes.

F. (Responses) For most of the following questions, you are encouraged to provide open responses but I do have a series of prompts for these questions in case you are stuck for a response. Do you have any questions at this time or wish me to explain or elaborate on anything at this point before we begin?

(Transition: Let me begin by asking you some questions regarding the use of decision aids)

Body A. (Topic) Use of decision aids

1. Have you heard of decision aids /are you familiar with them?
2. Do any of your health services use decision aids?
 - a. (If yes or some do move to question 29)
 - b. (If "no") Why do your health services not use decision aids?

Prompts

- Is there not enough funding, Y/N
- No incentives for using them, Y/N
- No training in using shared decision aids, Y/N
- Are their use not regarded as a priority/necessity Y/N
- Or is there any other reason why your health services don't use decision aids? Y/N
- If there is another reason as to why your health services don't use decision aids please explain or elaborate on this.

(Transition to the next topic: I will now ask you some questions regarding your opinion on best practice decision aids) B. (Topic) Best Practice Decision aids

3. What are examples of the best practice decision aid(s) in your opinion and why?

Prompts

For example Elwyn et al. (2013) produced a specific, short decision aid for patients to use whilst in an appointment with their clinician, named Option Grids. They are short tables which summarise each treatment choice on one side of A4 paper, which allows the quick comparison of choices, utilising patients most frequently asked questions. Whilst, the majority of patient decision aids are for patients to use themselves prior to or after appointments and contain a lot of information, the option grids are a shorter alternative to be used by both patient and clinician during an appointment tackling the issue of allotted time for patient appointments. Clinicians also felt that utilising the Option Grids made it

simpler to make clear the different choices available and stated a 'handover' effect, in which patient inclusion in the decision-making process was increased. It was also found that when utilised in a cooperative manner, they also improved patients' voice and confidence, increasing their engagement in cooperative discussions.

Durand, Alam, Grande & Elwyn, (2016) created and assessed the usability, acceptability and accessibility of a picture-based decision aid (to be utilised within clinical appointments) aimed at females of low socioeconomic status (SES) diagnosed with early-stage breast cancer. Every female of low SES recently diagnosed with early-stage breast cancer perceived the Picture Option Grid accessible, usable and acceptable.

Breslin, Mullan & Montori (2008) created a medicinal option decision aid for patients that have type 2 diabetes. They created the decision aid via active collaboration with designers, patients and clinicians, observations of clinical appointments, literature review, and collaborative creation of design criteria. Observations from these methods informed the iterative development of prototypes which were field tested and reviewed in real appointments. The aim of the decision aid was to promote a discussion between the patient and clinician regarding diabetes medication choices. 4 iterations of the decision aid were produced and field-tested prior to attaining issue cards which arranged the data for 5 medications regarding glucose control, weight alterations, hypoglycaemia, side effects, daily routine and self-monitoring. These cards successfully produced discussions during appointments. The cards/decision aid was then named Diabetes Medication Choice and was utilised in a pilot, cluster randomized trial (Mullan, Montori, Shah et al., 2009). The aid explains 5 antihyperglycemic medications, their treatment strains (unfavourable effects, self-monitoring, and administration requirements), and effect on haemoglobin A1c (HbA1c) levels. 21 clinicians were randomized to utilise the decision aid during the clinical appointment and 19 to operate typical care and an information pamphlet. Researchers utilised video analysis and surveys to evaluate post-visit decisional outcomes and pharmacy and medical records to evaluate 6-month HbA1c levels and medication adherence. Compared to the 37 typical care patients, the 48 patients that received the decision aid found the decision aid more beneficial, had increased knowledge and were more included in making decisions regarding diabetes medications.

4. What do you think would make a decision aid an example of best practice?

Prompts

- If the decision aid was shown to improve knowledge,
Y/N

- Increase accurate risk perceptions,
Y/N
- Congruence between the chosen option and informed values,
Y/N
- Reduce decisional conflict as a result of being informed or clear about personal values,
Y/N
- Increase participation in decision making for patients,
Y/N
- Increase participation in decision making for clinicians,
Y/N
- Increase clinician-controlled decision making,
Y/N
- Increase patient-controlled decision making,
Y/N
- Increase shared decision-making,
Y/N
- Reduce adverse events,
Y/N
- Increase patient adherence to treatment option,
Y/N
- Increase patient self-management,
Y/N
- Result in satisfaction with the choice made.
Y/N
- If there is another aspect or outcome which you think would make a decision aid an example of best practice, please explain or elaborate on this.
Y/N

(Transition to the next topic: I will now ask you a few questions about what features you think decision aid should have) C. (Topic) Features of decision aids

5. In your opinion, should decision aids be used in consultations or outwith consultations? Or should decision aids be used both in consultations and outwith consultations?

Prompts

For example Elwyn et al. (2013) produced a specific, short decision aid for patients to use whilst in an appointment with their clinician, named Option Grids. But other decision aids might be for patients to use in the waiting room prior to their appointment or at home after an initial consultation. Or some decision aids can be used both in consultations and outwith for the patient to review options in more detail or to discuss with family or friends before making a final decision.

6. Do you think that decision aids should be primarily for clinicians to use or for patients to use? Or should both patients and clinicians use decision aids?

7. What health conditions do you think decision aids should be used for or would be best suited for?

Prompts

- Asthma,
Y/N
- Diabetes,
Y/N
- Breast Cancer,
Y/N
- Osteoarthritis,
Y/N
- Chronic Pain
Y/N
- Other, if other please specify which health condition you think decision aids should be used
- for or would be best suited for
Y/N

8. Do you think that decision aids should be publicly accessible/available? If "Yes" where do you think these decision aids should be found?

Prompts

- On any website which patients can access such as the NHS website?
Y/N

9. Which formats do you think decision aids should use?

Prompts

- Online/Website,
Y/N
- Paper/Leaflet/Pamphlet,
Y/N
- Option Grids (short tables which summarise each treatment choice on one side of A4 paper, which allows the quick comparison of choices, utilising patients most frequently asked questions)

Y/N
- An app
Y/N
- On a tablet,
Y/N
- DVD,
Y/N
- Pre-recorded videos Y/N
- Other format. If other format please elaborate which formats the decision aids should use.
Y/N

10. Should decision aids be brief or in-depth? Or should brief decision aids have an option to provide more information/go into more depth?

11. Should decision aids be text-based, picture based or contain both text and pictures?

12. On average, how often should decision aids be used?

Prompts

- Daily,
Y/N
- Weekly,
Y/N
- Monthly,
Y/N
- A few times a year,
Y/N
- Annually
Y/N

- Other, if other please elaborate how often decision aids should be used?
Y/N

13. Should decision aids be updated frequently?

a. If “yes” how frequently?

Prompts

- Daily,
Y/N
- Weekly,
Y/N
- Monthly,
Y/N
- A few times a year,
Y/N
- Annually
Y/N
- Other, if other please elaborate how frequently decision aids should be updated
Y/N

b. If not why not?

Prompts

- Not a priority,
Y/N
- Not enough time/resources, Y/N
- Unsure how to update decision aids frequently.
Y/N
- Other, if other please elaborate why decision aids shouldn't be updated frequently?
Y/N

14. Should decision aids meet/follow certain guidelines/criteria such as NICE or GRADE?

15. Which guidelines/criteria should decision aids follow/meet?

Prompts

- NICE,
Y/N
- GRADE,
Y/N
- IPDAS,
Y/N
- Other. If "other" please specify which guidelines/criteria should decision aids follow/meet? Y/N

16. a. Which outcomes/impacts should decision aids have? Generally positive?

Prompts

- Improve knowledge,
Y/N
- Increase accurate risk perceptions,
Y/N
- Increase congruence between the chosen option and informed values,
Y/N
- Reduce decisional conflict as a result of being informed or clear about personal values,
Y/N
- Increase participation in decision making for patients,
Y/N
- Increase participation in decision making for clinicians,
Y/N
- Increase clinician-controlled decision making,
Y/N
- Increase patient-controlled decision making, Y/N
- Increase shared decision-making,
Y/N
- Reduce adverse events,
Y/N
- Increase patient adherence to treatment option,
Y/N
- Increase patient self-management,
Y/N

- Result in satisfaction with the choice made.
Y/N
- Increase patient practitioner communication
Y/N
- If other please elaborate which outcomes/impacts should decision aids have?
Y/N

b. Do you think that there any negatives outcomes/impacts or constraints on use of decision aids?

Prompts

- Increase decisional conflict
Y/N
- Not enough time in consultations to use them
Y/N
- Patient's don't want to use them or unsure of how to use them
Y/N
- Healthcare professionals don't like them/think they're a waste of time
Y/N
- Not enough training on how to use decision aids for staff
Y/N
- Not enough decision aids to use
Y/N
- Promote patient decision making instead of shared decision-making
Y/N
- Their use is irrelevant and ineffective
Y/N
- Patients will want inappropriate/expensive treatments
Y/N
- There's no incentive to use them
Y/N
- They won't be appropriate for those with low health literacy
Y/N

- Other, if other please elaborate which negative outcomes/impacts or constraints on use of decision aids you think there are

Y/N

17. Should decision aids also be used by a patient's relative/guardian/caregiver?

18. Should the use of decision aids and/or the outcome be recorded for other healthcare professionals to see?

Prompt

- Should the use of decision aids and/or the outcome be noted in the patients' health records? Y/N

19. Should decision aids be evaluated with respect to their effectiveness? If "Yes", please provide more information such as details of who should provide this feedback/evaluation, how often this should be given, what the feedback/evaluation measures should be and an example of what this feedback/evaluation should look like.

20. In your opinion, what features should a decision aid have?

Prompts

- Should they be brief or in-depth? Y/N
- Text-based or picture-based?
Y/N
- To be used in appointments or out with consultations?
Y/N
- Should they come in a variety of formats or only in certain formats?
Y/N
- For patient use or clinician use? Updated frequently?
Y/N
- Linked to patient's health records?
Y/N

(Transition to the next topic: I will now ask you a few questions regarding shared decision making) D.
(Topic) Shared decision making

21. Are there any staff incentives for taking part in/carrying out shared decision-making? If so please outline what incentives there are for staff partaking in/carrying out shared decision-making?

Prompts

- Financial incentives
Y/N
- or are they included in company performance targets?
Y/N

22. Are staff trained in carrying out shared decision making? If not, why are they not trained in partaking in shared decision making?

Prompts

- Not enough interest,
Y/N
- Resources
Y/N
- or not a priority?
Y/N

23. Are there audits/reviews carried out on shared decision-making? How often are these audits/reviews carried out?

24. Is shared decision-making used routinely as part of standard practice in your board? If not or in some locations, please explain why and outline what challenges need to be addressed/steps need to be taken to make shared decision-making used routinely as part of standard practice?

Prompts

- Is there no incentives for carrying out shared decision making,
Y/N
- Is there no training on how to carry out shared decision making,
Y/N
- Is it not regarded as a priority/necessity,
Y/N
- Are patients/clinicians attitudes negative towards shared decision making?
Y/N

(Transition to the next topic: I will now ask you a couple of questions regarding your thoughts on the development of a decision aid for chronic pain) E. (Topic) Chronic pain decision aid

25. Do you know of any decision aid for chronic pain?

26. Do you think that a decision aid for chronic pain would be useful for patients to understand all of their treatment options, the associated risks and benefits of each option? And to manage their pain?

27. If so what features do you think it should include?

Prompts

- Should they be brief or in-depth?
Y/N
- Text-based or picture-based?
Y/N
- To be used in appointments or out with consultations?
Y/N
- Should they come in a variety of formats or only in certain formats?
Y/N
- For patient use or clinician use?
Y/N
- Updated frequently?
Y/N
- Linked to patient's health records?
Y/N

28. Do you think that the decision aid for chronic pain should focus on pharmacological treatment options, non-pharmacological treatment options or should it incorporate both options? And why?

Prompts

- Should the decision aid focus on just medication/pain killer options
Y/N
- Should it focus on options such as social prescribing, exercise, cognitive behavioural therapy Y/N
- or should the decision aid include all options?
Y/N

III Closing A. (Summarize) You are very informed in the use of decision aids. You have provided your opinion on what would make a best practice decision aid. You think that in order for shared decision making to be standard practice _____. B (Maintain Rapport) I appreciate the time you took for this interview. Is there anything else you think would be helpful for me to know so that I can successfully design and implement a shared decision-making aid for chronic pain which will build on

existing best practice C. (Action to be taken) I should have all the information I need. Would it be alright to call or email you if I have any more questions? Thanks again. I look forward to reviewing and using this information to inform my research.

29. Which of your health services use decision aids?

Prompts

- General practices,
Y/N
- Hospitals or other services?
Y/N
- If indicated "other services" please specify which health service(s) use decision aids?
Y/N

30. Do all of your health services use decision aids? a) If not all or some do please specify why not all health services use decision aids?

Prompts

- Insufficient funding,
Y/N
- Not appropriate/suitable in all health services
Y/N
- Other reason. If indicated "other reason" please elaborate on why not all health services use decision aids?
Y/N

(Transition to the next topic: I will now ask you a few questions about the features of the decision aids)

B. (Topic) Features of the decision aids

31. Are the decision aids to be used in consultations or outwith consultations? Or can the decision aids be used both in consultations and outwith consultations?

Prompts

For example Elwyn et al. (2013) produced a specific, short decision aid for patients to use whilst in an appointment with their clinician, named Option Grids. But other decision aids might be for patients to use in the waiting room prior to their appointment or at home after an initial consultation. Or some decision aids can be used both in consultations and outwith for the patient to review options in more detail or to discuss with family or friends before making a final decision.

32. Are the decision aids primarily for clinicians to use or for patients to use? Or do both patients and clinicians use the decision aids?

33. What health conditions are the decision aids used for? Are there any for chronic pain?

Prompts

- Asthma,
Y/N
- Diabetes,
Y/N
- Breast Cancer,
Y/N
- Osteoarthritis
Y/N
- Chronic Pain
Y/N
- Other, if other please specify which health condition you think decision aids should be used
- for or would be best suited for
Y/N

34. Are these decision aids publicly accessible/available? If "Yes" or "Some are" where can these decision aids be found?

Prompts

- Are they on any website which patients can access such as the NHS website?
Y/N

35. What formats do the decision aids use?

Prompts

- Online/Website,
Y/N
- Paper/Leaflet/Pamphlet,
Y/N
- Option Grids (short tables which summarise each treatment choice on one side of A4 paper, which allows the quick comparison of choices, utilising patients most frequently

asked questions)

Y/N

- An app
Y/N
- On a tablet,
Y/N
- DVD,
Y/N
- Pre-recorded videos Y/N
- Other format. If other format please elaborate which formats the decision aids use.
Y/N

36. Are the decision aids brief or in-depth? Or do brief decision aids have an option to provide more information/go into more depth?

37. Are the decision aids text-based, picture based or contain both text and pictures?

38. On average, how often are the decision aids used?

Prompts

- Daily,
Y/N
- Weekly,
Y/N
- Monthly,
Y/N
- A few times a year,
Y/N
- Annually
Y/N
- Other, if other please elaborate how often the decision aids are used?
Y/N

39. Are the decision aids updated frequently?

a. If “yes” how frequently?

Prompts

- Daily,
Y/N
- Weekly,
Y/N
- Monthly,
Y/N
- A few times a year,
Y/N
- Annually
Y/N
- Other, if other please elaborate how frequently the decision aids are updated
Y/N

b. If not why not?

Prompts

- Not a priority,
Y/N
- Not enough time/resources, Y/N
- Unsure how to update decision aids frequently.
Y/N
- Other, if other please elaborate why the decision aids aren't updated frequently?
Y/N

40. Do the decision aids meet/follow certain guidelines/criteria such as NICE or GRADE?

41. Which guidelines/criteria do the decision aids follow/meet?

Prompts

- NICE,
Y/N
- GRADE,
Y/N
- IPDAS,
Y/N
- Other. If "other" please specify which guidelines/criteria the decision aids follow/meet?
Y/N

42. a. Which outcomes/impacts do the decision aids have? Are they generally positive?

Prompts

- Improve knowledge,
Y/N
- Increase accurate risk perceptions,
Y/N
- Increase congruence between the chosen option and informed values,
Y/N
- Reduce decisional conflict as a result of being informed or clear about personal values,
Y/N
- Increase participation in decision making for patients,
Y/N
- Increase participation in decision making for clinicians,
Y/N
- Increase clinician-controlled decision making,
Y/N
- Increase patient-controlled decision making, Y/N
- Increase shared decision-making,
Y/N
- Reduce adverse events,
Y/N
- Increase patient adherence to treatment option,
Y/N
- Increase patient self-management,
Y/N
- Result in satisfaction with the choice made.
Y/N
- Increase patient practitioner communication
Y/N
- If other please elaborate which outcomes/impacts the decision aids have?
Y/N

b. Are there any negatives outcomes/impacts or constraints on the use of the decision aids?

Prompts

- Increase decisional conflict
Y/N
- Not enough time in consultations to use them
Y/N
- Patient's don't want to use them or unsure of how to use them
Y/N
- Healthcare professionals don't like them/think they're a waste of time
Y/N
- Not enough training on how to use decision aids for staff
Y/N
- Not enough decision aids to use
Y/N
- Promote patient decision making instead of shared decision-making
Y/N
- Their use is irrelevant and ineffective
Y/N
- Patients want inappropriate/expensive treatments
Y/N
- There's no incentive to use them
Y/N
- They aren't appropriate for those with low health literacy
Y/N
- Other, if other please elaborate which negative outcomes/impacts or constraints on use of decision aids there are
Y/N

43. Can the decision aids also be used by a patient's relative/guardian/caregiver?

44. Are the use of the decision aids and/or the outcome recorded for other healthcare professionals to see?

Prompt

- Is the use of the decision aids and/or the outcome noted in the patients' health records?
Y/N

(Transition to the next topic: I will now ask you some questions regarding your opinion on best practice decision aids) C. (Topic) Best Practice Decision aids

45a. Have the decision aids been evaluated with respect to their effectiveness? If "Yes" or "Some do", please provide more information such as details of who provides this feedback/evaluation, how often this is given, what the feedback/evaluation measures and an example of what this feedback/evaluation looks like.

b. If "Yes" or "Some do", which are the highest rated/evaluated decision aid(s) and why?

c. If "No", what are the best practice decision aid(s) in your opinion and why? Either from the decision aid(s) currently used by your health services or examples of best practice decision aids that are used elsewhere?

Prompts

For example Elwyn et al. (2013) produced a specific, short decision aid for patients to use whilst in an appointment with their clinician, named Option Grids. They are short tables which summarise each treatment choice on one side of A4 paper, which allows the quick comparison of choices, utilising patients most frequently asked questions. Whilst, the majority of patient decision aids are for patients to use themselves prior to or after appointments and contain a lot of information, the option grids are a shorter alternative to be used by both patient and clinician during an appointment tackling the issue of allotted time for patient appointments. Clinicians also felt that utilising the Option Grids made it simpler to make clear the different choices available and stated a 'handover' effect, in which patient inclusion in the decision-making process was increased. It was also found that when utilised in a cooperative manner, they also improved patients' voice and confidence, increasing their engagement in cooperative discussions.

Durand, Alam, Grande & Elwyn, (2016) created and assessed the usability, acceptability and accessibility of a picture-based decision aid (to be utilised within clinical appointments) aimed at females of low socioeconomic status (SES) diagnosed with early-stage breast cancer. Every female of low SES recently diagnosed with early-stage breast cancer perceived the Picture Option Grid accessible, usable and acceptable.

Breslin, Mullan & Montori (2008) created a medicinal option decision aid for patients that have type 2 diabetes. They created the decision aid via active collaboration with designers, patients and clinicians, observations of clinical appointments, literature review, and collaborative creation of design criteria. Observations from these methods informed the iterative development of prototypes which were field tested and reviewed in real appointments. The aim of the decision aid was to promote a discussion between the patient and clinician regarding diabetes medication choices. 4 iterations of the decision

aid were produced and field-tested prior to attaining issue cards which arranged the data for 5 medications regarding glucose control, weight alterations, hypoglycaemia, side effects, daily routine and self-monitoring. These cards successfully produced discussions during appointments. The cards/decision aid was then named Diabetes Medication Choice and was utilised in a pilot, cluster randomized trial (Mullan, Montori, Shah et al., 2009). The aid explains 5 antihyperglycemic medications, their treatment strains (unfavourable effects, self-monitoring, and administration requirements), and effect on haemoglobin A1c (HbA1c) levels. 21 clinicians were randomized to utilise the decision aid during the clinical appointment and 19 to operate typical care and an information pamphlet. Researchers utilised video analysis and surveys to evaluate post-visit decisional outcomes and pharmacy and medical records to evaluate 6-month HbA1c levels and medication adherence. Compared to the 37 typical care patients, the 48 patients that received the decision aid found the decision aid more beneficial, had increased knowledge and were more included in making decisions regarding diabetes medications.

46. In your opinion, what features should a best practice decision aid have?

Prompts

- Should they be brief or in-depth? Y/N
- Text-based or picture-based? Y/N
- To be used in appointments or out with consultations? Y/N
- Should they come in a variety of formats or only in certain formats? Y/N
- For patient use or clinician use? Y/N
- Updated frequently? Y/N
- Linked to patient's health records? Y/N
- Other, if other what features should a best practice decision aid have? Y/N

47. What do you think would make a decision aid an example of best practice?

Prompts

- If the decision aid was shown to improve knowledge,
Y/N
- Increase accurate risk perceptions,
Y/N
- Congruence between the chosen option and informed values,
Y/N

- Reduce decisional conflict as a result of being informed or clear about personal values,
Y/N
- Increase participation in decision making for patients,
Y/N
- Increase participation in decision making for clinicians,
Y/N
- Increase clinician-controlled decision making,
Y/N
- Increase patient-controlled decision making,
Y/N
- Increase shared decision-making,
Y/N
- Reduce adverse events,
Y/N
- Increase patient adherence to treatment option,
Y/N
- Increase patient self-management,
Y/N
- Result in satisfaction with the choice made.
Y/N
- If there is another aspect or outcome which you think would make a decision aid an example of best practice, please explain or elaborate on this.
Y/N

(Transition to the next topic: I will now ask you a few questions regarding shared decision making and decision aids) D. (Topic) Shared decision making and decision aids

48. Are staff trained in carrying out shared decision making and in the use of decision aids? If not, please explain why are they not trained in these areas?

Prompts

- Not enough interest,
Y/N
- Resources
Y/N

- or not a priority?

Y/N

49. Are there any staff incentives for partaking in/carrying out shared decision-making and using decision aids? If so please outline what incentives there are?

Prompts

- Financial incentives

Y/N

- or are they included in company performance targets?

Y/N

50. Are there audits/reviews carried out on the decision aids and on shared decision-making? How often are these audits/reviews carried out?

51. Are shared decision-making and decision aids used routinely as part of standard practice in your board? If not or in some locations, please explain why and outline what challenges need to be addressed/steps need to be taken to make shared decision-making and decision aids used routinely as part of standard practice?

Prompts

- Is there no incentives for carrying out shared decision making and using decision aids,

Y/N

- Is there no training on how to carry out shared decision making and in the use of decision aids,

Y/N

- Are they not regarded as a priority/necessity,

Y/N

- Do patients/clinicians have attitudes negative towards shared decision making and decision aids?

Y/N

(Transition to the next topic: I will now ask you a couple of questions regarding your thoughts on the development of a decision aid for chronic pain) E. (Topic) Chronic pain decision aid

52. Do you know of any decision aids for chronic pain?

53a. Do you think that a decision aid for chronic pain would be useful for patients to understand all of their treatment options, the associated risks and benefits of each option? And to manage their pain?

b. If so what features do you think it should include?

Prompts

- Should they be brief or in-depth? Y/N
- Text-based or picture-based? Y/N
- To be used in appointments or out with consultations? Y/N
- Should they come in a variety of formats or only in certain formats? Y/N
- For patient use or clinician use? Y/N
- Updated frequently? Y/N
- Linked to patient's health records? Y/N

54. Do you think that the decision aid for chronic pain should focus on pharmacological treatment options, non-pharmacological treatment options or should it incorporate both options (and why) ?

Prompts

- Should the decision aid focus on just medication/pain killer options
Y/N
- Should it focus on options such as social prescribing, exercise, cognitive behavioural therapy Y/N
- or should the decision aid include all options?
Y/N

III Closing A. (Summarize) You are very informed in the use of decision aids. You have provided your opinion on what would make a best practice decision aid. You think that in order for shared decision making to be standard practice _____. B (Maintain Rapport) I appreciate the time you took for this interview. Is there anything else you think would be helpful for me to know so that I can successfully design and implement a shared decision-making aid for chronic pain which will build on existing best practice C. (Action to be taken) I should have all the information I need. Would it be alright to call or email you if I have any more questions? Thanks again. I look forward to reviewing and using this information to inform my research.

Appendix D: Study 1 Participant Information Sheet

Participant Information Sheet

Identifying Existing Good Practice in the Development of Shared Decision Aids: Collating Examples of Current Practice in the Design, Use & Implementation of Shared Decision Aids in Scotland's NHS Boards

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

What is the purpose of this study?

The purpose of this study is to identify existing good practice in the development of shared decision aids through gathering examples of current practice in the use, design and implementation of shared decision-making aids in Scotland's NHS Boards. This is necessary because, whilst Shared Decision Making (SDM) is aimed to be standard practice in healthcare within the UK and Decision Aids (DA) should be used to assist the SDM process, successful implementation of SDM and DA is patchy and not currently the norm within the UK due to this gap in knowledge.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen to take part in this study because you are a lead member of a Scottish NHS Board which makes you a key stakeholder for identifying examples of existing good practice in the development of shared decision aids in Scotland's NHS Boards and for gathering your perceptions and views about decision aids including these for chronic pain.

Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form. If you decide to take part you are still free to withdraw up to 2 days after your interview is carried out without giving a reason.

What will happen to me if I take part?

You will be asked to partake in an interview (carried out either over the telephone, face-to-face or via a video conferencing software such as Skype or Webex depending on your preference) which aims to gather examples of current and best practice in designing and implementing shared decision-making aids. The interview will last around 30-45 minutes. The aim of the study and definitions of important terms will be explained before the interview questions are asked and there will be time set aside for answering any questions you may have before and after the interview questions occur.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

There are no direct disadvantages or risks as a result of taking part in this study.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

It cannot be guaranteed that you will experience any direct benefits from taking part in the research, although the responses from the interview may be used to inform the design and implementation of decision aids which would better support/implement standard practice of shared decision making and decision aids within the UK. Following successful evaluation and review, the aim will be to spread, adapt and scale-up the methodology and product for use in other NHS Boards.

Data Protection Privacy Notice

The data controller for this project will be University of the West of Scotland (UWS). The UWS Data Protection Office provides oversight of UWS activities involving the processing of personal data, and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. UWS's Data Protection Officer is Andy Connor and he can also be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk.

Your personal data will be processed for the purposes outlined in this notice. The legal basis that would be used to process your personal data will be the provision of your consent. You can provide your consent for the use of your personal data in this project by completing the consent form that has been provided to you.

Your personal data will be processed so long as it is required for the research project. If we are able to anonymise or pseudonymise the personal data you provide we will undertake this, and will endeavour to minimise the processing of personal data wherever possible.

If you are concerned about how your personal data is being processed, please contact UWS in the first instance at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. If you remain unsatisfied, you may wish to contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). Contact details, and details of data subject rights, are

available on the ICO website at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights/>

What will happen to the results of the research study?

Only anonymised data will be shared outside of the research team. Data will be stored at UWS, either in a locked filing cabinet or on a password protected computer for up to ten years after the study finishes, after which it will be destroyed. The findings from this study will be written up as part of the researcher's PhD thesis, as peer reviewed journal articles, and/or presented at conferences/seminars. All data will be reported anonymously.

Who has reviewed the study?

UWS MCS Ethics Committee. Ethics approval number: 4989.

Contact for further information

If you require any further information please contact:

Researcher:

Abbie McGuire

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street, Paisley, PA1 2BE, UK

Telephone: [REDACTED]

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

Research Supervisor:

Elizabeth Boyle

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street, Paisley, PA1 2BE, UK

Telephone: [REDACTED]

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

Thank you for taking part in this study.

Appendix E: Study 1 Consent Form

RESEARCH INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Title of Project: Identifying Existing Good Practice in the Development of Shared Decision Aids:
Collating Examples of Current Practice in the Design, Use & Implementation of Shared Decision Aids in
Scotland's NHS Boards

Ethics Approval Number: 4989

Investigator(s): Abbie McGuire

Researcher Email: [REDACTED]

Please read the following statements and, if you agree, initial the corresponding box to confirm agreement:

I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.

Initials

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason.

Initials

I consent to the processing of my personal information (interview responses) for the purposes explained to me. I understand that such information will be handled in accordance with all applicable data protection legislation.

Initials

I understand that my data will be treated confidentially and any publication resulting from this work will report only data that does not identify me.

Initials

I agree to having my voice/likeness digitally recorded.

Initials

I freely agree to participate in this study.

Initials

Signatures:

Name of participant (block capitals)

Name of researcher (block capitals)

ABBIE MCGUIRE

Date

Date

Signature

Signature

Appendix F: Study 1 Debrief Sheet

Debriefing Form

Identifying Existing Good Practice in the Development of Shared Decision Aids: Collating Examples of Current Practice in the Design, Use & Implementation of Shared Decision Aids in Scotland's NHS Boards

Thank you taking part in this study. This study aimed to identify existing good practice in the development of shared decision aids through gathering examples of current practice in the use, design and implementation of shared decision-making aids in Scotland's NHS Boards. This is necessary because, whilst Shared Decision Making (SDM) is aimed to be standard practice in healthcare within the UK and Decision Aids (DA) should be used to assist the SDM process, successful implementation of SDM and DA is patchy and not currently the norm within the UK due to this gap in knowledge.

If you would like more information about this research once it is completed, please contact the researcher:

Abbie McGuire

University of the West of Scotland, High Street, Paisley, PA1 2BE, UK

Telephone: [REDACTED]

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

Or my director of studies:

Elizabeth Boyle

University of the West of Scotland,

University of the West of Scotland, High Street, Paisley, PA1 2BE, UK

Telephone: [REDACTED]

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

If you are interested in this area of research, you may wish to read the following references:

- Coulter, A. & Collins, A. (2011). Making shared decision-making a reality: No decision about me, without me. London: The King's Fund.
- Elwyn, G., O'Connor, A. M., Bennett, C., Newcombe, R. G., Politi, M., Durand, M. A., Drake, E., Joseph-Williams, N., Khangura, S., Saarimaki, A., Sivell, S., Stiel, M., Bernstein, S. J., Col, N., Coulter, A., Eden, K., Harter, M., Rovner, M. H., Moumjid, N., Stacey, D., Thomson, R., Whelan, T., van der Weijden, W. T., & Edwards, A. (2009). Assessing the quality of decision support technologies using the International Patient Decision Aid Standards instrument (IPDASi). *PLoS ONE*, 4(3), e4705. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0004705.
- Elwyn, G., Laitner, S., Coulter, A., Walker, E., Watson, P., & Thomson, R. (2010). Implementing shared decision-making in the NHS. *British Medical Journal*, 341, c5146. doi: 10.1136/bmj.c5146.
- Elwyn, G., Lloyd, A., Joseph-Williams, N., Cording, E., Thomson, R., Durand, M., & Edwards, A. (2013). Option Grids: Shared decision making made easier. *Patient Education and Counseling*, 90(2), 207 – 212. doi: 10.1016/j.pec.2012.06.036
- O'Connor, A. M., Rostom, A., Fiset, V., Tetroe, J., Entwistle, V., Llewellyn-Thomas, H., Holmes-Rovner, M., Barry, M., & Jones, J. (1999). Decision aids for patients facing health treatment or screening decisions: systematic review. *British Medical Journal*, 319(7212), 731–734. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.319.7212.731>
- O'Connor, A. M., Bennett, C. L., Stacey, D., Barry, M., Col, N. F., Eden, K. B., Entwistle, V. A., Fiset, V., Holmes-Rovner, M., Khangura, S., Llewellyn-Thomas, H., & Rovner, D. (2009). Decision aids for people facing health treatment or screening decisions. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, 3, Art. No.: CD001431. doi: 10.1002/14651858.CD001431.pub2.
- Stacey, D., Légaré, F., Col, N. F., Bennett, C. L., Barry, M. J., Eden, K. B., Holmes-Rovner, M., Llewellyn-Thomas, H., Lyddiatt, A., Thomson, R., Trevena, L., Wu, J. H. C. (2014). Decision aids for people facing health treatment or screening decisions. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, 1, Art. No.: CD001431. doi: 10.1002/14651858.CD001431.pub4.
- The International Patient Decision Aid Standards Collaboration. (2003). Retrieved from <http://ipdas.ohri.ca/>
- The Ottawa Hospital Research Institute. (2014). *Patient Decision Aids: Implementation Toolkit*. Retrieved from <https://decisionaid.ohri.ca/implement.html>
- The Scottish Government. (2016). *A National Clinical Strategy for Scotland*. Edinburgh, Scotland: The Scottish Government.

If this research has caused you any distress or discomfort and you would like to speak to someone please contact the following sources of support and advice:

UWS Counselling Service

Email: counselling@uws.ac.uk

Phone: 0141 848 3803

Student Link

Elles Building West

University of the West of Scotland, High Street, Paisley, PA1 2BE, UK

If you have any complaints or feel that you have been affected by the study in any way please contact:

Professor Jim McKechnie (Head of Psychology):

Dr Chris O'Donnell (Chair of the Media, Culture and Society Ethics Committee):

Appendix G: Study 2 Survey

Chronic Pain Assessment Questionnaire

Pain is a patient-specific experience that requires ongoing assessment and evaluation, both by patients and their providers. This questionnaire will help assess the two parts of chronic pain that often change over time, persistent baseline and breakthrough pain. Please take a moment to complete this questionnaire.

Part 1: Assessment of Persistent Baseline Pain

1

During the past week, have you had any pain or would you have had pain if not for the treatment you are receiving?

- If Yes, please proceed to the next question.

- If No, your pain profile may not include persistent baseline pain.

2

Is this pain present continuously (most of the day) on most days or would the pain persist if not for the treatment you are receiving?

- If Yes, please proceed to the next question. This is known as persistent baseline pain.

- If No, your pain profile may not include persistent baseline pain.

3

During the past week, on average, how would you rate your baseline pain on a scale of 0 to 10? (Refer to **Figure 1A**)

- If Severe, your baseline pain may be uncontrolled.

- If Mild or Moderate, your baseline pain is controlled.

Highest Level of Education: _____

Patient Information

Attended a medical appointment for chronic pain Not attended a medical appointment for chronic pain

Pain Diagnosis: _____

Age Group: younger than 20 20 - 29 30 - 39

40 - 49 50 - 59 60 - 69 70 or older

Have you made a treatment decision / chosen a treatment option with your healthcare professional?
or

No If Yes, please specify chosen treatment: _____

Sex: Male Female

Race: White British Black African

Indian Chinese

Other (please specify): _____

FIGURE

1a Please rate your baseline pain by circling

the one number that describes your baseline pain on the average during the past week.

Occupation: _____

0-10 Numeric Pain Intensity Scale

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

4 Assess the nature of your baseline pain

- Where do you feel this pain? (Refer to *Figure 1B*)
- How long have you experienced this pain? (in weeks)

- Does anything that you do reduce your pain?

Yes No

If Yes, please describe what reduces your pain:

- Does anything that you do make your pain worse?

Yes No

If Yes, please describe what makes your pain worse:

5 Are you taking opioid medications daily?

If Yes, which opioid(s) are you taking?

How often are you taking it/them?

Please proceed to the next question.

If No, please proceed to the next question.

FIGURE

1b

Where do you feel this pain?

(In the diagram below mark with an "x" the areas where you experience this pain)

Adapted from Portenoy RK, et al. *J Pain*. 2006;7:583-591; Hagen NA, et al. *J Pain Symptom Manage*. 2008;35:136-152; and the clinical practice of Michael J. Brennan, MD.

Part 2: Assessment of Breakthrough Pain

1

Do you have periods during the day when you have temporary episodes of uncontrolled pain (also known as breakthrough pain)?

If Yes, how often?

• What time of day do these episodes occur?

If No, please return this form now.

2 How long does it take from the time you first notice the pain until it is at its worst?

• How long do the episodes last?

• How long does it usually take from the time you take medicine until the pain goes away?

3 How would you rate your breakthrough pain at its worst on a scale of 0 to 10? (Refer to *Figure 2A*)

4

Where do you feel this pain? (Refer to *Figure 2B*)

(In the diagram below mark with an "x" the areas where you experience this pain)

FIGURE

2a

Please rate your baseline pain by circling the one number that describes your baseline pain on the average during the past week.

0-10 Numeric Pain Intensity Scale

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

FIGURE

2b

Where do you feel this pain?

Adapted from Portenoy RK, et al. *J Pain*. 2006;7:583-591; Hagen NA, et al. *J Pain Symptom Manage*. 2008;35:136-152; and the clinical practice of Michael J. Brennan, MD.

6

Do you know what causes these breakthrough pain episodes?

Yes No

- Are the episodes associated with certain activities (for example, gardening, walking)?

Yes No

If Yes, what are these activities? _____

- Does the onset occur with certain bodily functions (for example, coughing, sneezing)?

Yes No

If Yes, what are these bodily functions?

- Does the onset usually occur right before a scheduled dose of your pain medication?

Yes No

7

Are these episodes of breakthrough pain the same type of pain as your usual pain?

Yes No

If No, how do they differ?

Function

8

Do the episodes of breakthrough pain affect your ability to handle daily responsibilities at home or work?

Yes No

If Yes, how often? _____

9

To what extent does avoiding activities due to fear of an episode of breakthrough pain compromise your quality of life?

A little A fair amount A lot

An extreme amount

Medications

10

Does anything help lessen the severity of these episodes of breakthrough pain?

Yes No

• What helps? _____

• What doesn't help? _____

11

Do you take any breakthrough pain medication(s)?

If Yes, complete questions 12 and 13.

If No, please return this form now.

12

In the past 24 hours, how long has it taken for your breakthrough pain medication to begin to take effect?

_____ minutes

13

In the past 24 hours, how satisfied or dissatisfied have you been with how fast your breakthrough pain medication began to reduce your breakthrough pain?

Very satisfied

Satisfied

Neutral

Dissatisfied

Very Dissatisfied

MPRCQ2 Worksheet:

Please use a memorable word or phrase e.g. "blue" for your unique identifier.

Patient Unique Identifier: _____ Date: _____

Section 1:

Instructions. Please write the number that best indicates your intention to use each of the following methods of coping with or managing your pain by using the 1 to 7 rating scale below:

- 1 = I am not doing this now, and am not interested in ever doing it.
- 2 = I might do this someday but I have made no plans to do it.
- 3 = I will probably start doing this sometime (in the next 6 months).
- 4 = I have made plans to start doing this soon (within the next month).
- 5 = I have recently started doing this (within the past month).
- 6 = I have been doing this for a while (more than 1 month but less than 6 months).
- 7 = I have been doing this for a long time (at least 6 months).

Section 1		Score
1	Walk fast, jog, swim (or use an exercise machine) at least 20 minutes 3 times a week or more.	
2	Use imagery to decrease pain.	
3	Distract myself from my pain.	
4	Tell people I am close to what is on my mind.	
5	Stand straight when I carry something heavy.	
6	Tell myself often that I can manage the pain and its effects on my life.	
7	Stretch my muscles (for at least 10 minutes) 3 times a week or more.	
8	Break up tasks into smaller pieces to get more done.	
9	Ignore the pain.	
10	Use correct posture when sitting.	

11	Express my feelings openly.	
12	Exercise for at least 30 minutes 3 times a week or more.	
13	Listen to a relaxation tape to relax.	
14	Work steadily, but at a reasonable pace.	
15	Put the pain in the background.	
16	Reassure myself often that I am managing my pain well.	
17	Alter the pain with my mind to something less unpleasant.	
18	Use slow, deep breathing to relax.	
19	Keep on doing what I want to do despite pain.	
20	Keep my back straight when I am sitting.	
21	Lift weights, do push-ups, or sit-ups (for at least 20 minutes) 3 times per week or more.	
22	Concentrate on a hobby or chore to distract myself from pain.	
23	Think about the pain differently so it is less upsetting.	
24	Disregard the painful sensations.	
25	Pace my activities so I don't get tired too soon.	
26	Alter the pain with my mind so it is less intense.	
27	Let others know what I want and need.	
28	Use my mind to distract myself from the pain.	
29	Lift heavy objects safely by keeping my back straight.	
30	Put the pain sensations out of my thoughts.	
31	Meditate to relax.	
32	Remind myself often that I will feel better in the future.	
33	Ignore the pain sensations.	
34	Exercise the muscles where I hurt (for at least 5 minutes) 3 times a week or more.	

35	Try not to slouch when I am sitting.	
36	Picture calming images to relax.	
37	Keep on doing what I need to do despite pain.	
38	Pace myself so I can keep working slowly and steadily.	
39	Tell myself often that I am doing well despite the pain.	
40	Think about the pain differently so that it hurts less.	
41	Use self-hypnosis to relax.	
42	Disregard the pain.	
43	Tell people I am close to how I feel.	
44	Exercise to increase muscle strength (for at least 20 minutes) 3 times a week or more.	
45	Work at a reasonable pace (not too fast or slow).	
46	Practice relaxing the different muscles in my body.	
47	Bend at the knees instead of the waist when lifting.	
48	Put the pain sensations in the back of my mind.	
49	Pay attention to something else when I hurt.	
50	Not think about how the pain feels.	
51	Stretch the muscles where I hurt (for at least 5 minutes) 3 times a week or more.	
52	Pace myself so that I don't have to take long breaks.	

Section 2:

Instructions. The following questions are slightly different than those that you have already answered. For the remaining questions, please write the number that best indicates your intention to stop using each of the methods of coping with or managing your pain by using the 1 to 7 rating scale below:

- 1 = I am doing this now and am not interested in ever stopping.
- 2 = I might stop this someday, but I have made no plans to stop doing it.
- 3 = I will probably stop doing this sometime (in the next 6 months).
- 4 = I have made plans to stop doing this soon (within the next month).
- 5 = I have recently stopped doing this (sometime in the past month).
- 6 = I have not done this for a while (more than 1 month but less than 6 months).
- 7 = I have not done this for a long time (at least 6 months).

Section 2		Score
53	Ask for help with chores when I hurt.	
54	Think about how bad the pain feels.	
55	Rest when I hurt.	
56	Sit down to rest when I hurt.	
57	Ask for help with cleaning because of my pain.	
58	Tell myself "I can't go on with this pain."	
59	Allow pain to keep me from doing what I need to do.	
60	Think about how overwhelming the pain feels.	
61	Lie down to rest when I hurt.	
62	Ask others for help when I hurt.	
63	Worry about the pain.	
64	Rest because of pain.	
65	Tell myself "I can't stand this pain."	
66	Ask for help with lifting or carrying because of pain.	
67	Let pain prevent me from doing what I need to do.	
68	Allow pain to stop me from doing what I want to do.	
69	Think thoughts that make me feel worse.	

Chronic Pain Patients Attitudes Survey

Shared decision making can be defined as "The conversation that happens between a patient and their healthcare professional to reach a health care choice together" (NHS Shared decision making, 2012).

Q1 How do you think healthcare decisions should be made? (Please select one of the options below)

- As the patient, I should make the final decision about which treatment I should receive.
- As the patient, I should make the final decision about which treatment I should receive after seriously considering my healthcare professional's opinion.
- The healthcare professional should share responsibility with me for making the final decision about the treatment I should receive.
- The healthcare professional should make the final decision about which treatment I should receive after seriously considering my opinion.
- The healthcare professional should make the final decision about which treatment I should receive.

Q2 Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with the following statements.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Shared decision-making can only be done with patients who are sufficiently educated and confident to discuss treatment or screening options with their clinician.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Doing shared decision making is unrealistic because it takes too much time.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Doing shared decision making is low on my priority list.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Physician payment should be based on how well they do shared decision making.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Having resources which summarize the risks and benefits of clinical decisions would be helpful (e.g. patient decision aid).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Patients should trust clinicians to make all decisions on their behalf.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q3 Read the following scenario. Please indicate: which decision style experienced clinicians should adopt in this situation. There are no right or wrong answers. Assume consent is obtained for each patient.

3a) A 45-year-old female presents to the Emergency Department. She requires an urgent emergency surgical intervention but is capable of giving consent.

What should the clinician do in this situation?

- The clinician should use evidence-based information to decide on the best course of action for the patient and inform the patient of their decision.

The clinician should share evidence-based information with the patient, and elicit the patient's preferences, so the patient and clinician can make an informed decision together.

The clinician should share evidence-based information with the patient and allow the patient to make the decision on their own.

The clinician should share evidence-based information with the patient and choose the best course of action for the patient.

3b) A 53-year-old male presents to his primary care clinician for an annual physical exam. The patient asks his provider about the need to screen for colorectal cancer.

What should the clinician do in this situation?

The clinician should use evidence-based information to decide on the best course of action for the patient and inform the patient of their decision.

The clinician should share evidence-based information with the patient, and elicit the patient's preferences, so the clinician and patient can make an informed decision together.

The clinician should share evidence-based information with the patient and allow the patient to make the decision on their own.

The clinician should share evidence-based information with the patient and choose the best course of action for the patient.

Q4 Please indicate whether you feel each of the following statements is TRUE or FALSE.

	True	False
Shared decision-making is a process in which clinicians and patients work together, sharing information about options and preferred outcomes, in order to reach a mutual agreement on the best course of action.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Shared decision-making causes patients to feel uncertain about their decisions.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Shared decision-making increases patient decision regret.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Shared decision-making results in fewer patients choosing major surgery.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q5 Please indicate whether you feel each of the following statements is TRUE or FALSE.

	True	False
Evidence shows that involving patients in making important healthcare decisions increases knowledge.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To promote shared decision making, the clinician will indicate that alternative treatment or management options exist.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To promote shared decision making, the clinician will give information about the pros and cons of options that are considered reasonable (including taking 'no action')	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

To promote shared decision making, the clinician will support the patient in becoming informed and comparing options.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There is no need for the clinician to check the patient's understanding.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
In the shared decision-making process, it is necessary to elicit the patient's preferences.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q6 Please indicate whether you feel each of the following statements is TRUE or FALSE.

	True	False
Whenever possible, the clinician should integrate the patient's preferences in deciding what to do next.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A majority of patients do not want to engage in shared decision making with their clinician.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Even if the patient does not wish to be involved in the decision-making process, it is the clinician's role to encourage the patient to make a decision.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A majority of clinicians do not want to engage in shared decision making with their patients.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q7 Had you heard of shared decision making before completing this survey?

- yes
- no

Q8 Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with the following statement.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
--	----------------	-------	----------	-------------------

I would like to know more about how to do shared decision with health care professionals.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
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Q9 In a clinical encounter, how do you think engaging in shared decision making would affect the length of the visit?

- Decrease the overall length of the visit
- The length of the visit would remain the same
- Increase the overall length of the visit

Q9a If you selected "Decrease the overall length of the visit." How much shorter would the clinical visit be when engaging in shared decision making?

- About 5 minutes shorter, or more
- About 2 minutes shorter
- About 1 minute shorter

Q9b If you selected "Increase the overall length of the visit." How much longer would the clinical visit be when engaging in shared decision making?

- About 5 minutes longer, or more
- About 2 minutes longer
- About 1 minute longer

Q10 How do you think healthcare decisions should be made?

- As the patient, I should make the final decision about which treatment I should receive.
- As the patient, I should make the final decision about which treatment I should receive after seriously considering my healthcare professional's opinion.
- The healthcare professional should share responsibility with me for making the final decision about the treatment I should receive.
- The healthcare professional should make the final decision about which treatment I should receive after seriously considering my opinion.
- The healthcare professional should make the final decision about which treatment I should receive.

Q11 Would you be interested in taking part in testing and giving feedback on a shared decision-making aid for chronic pain in the future?

Yes

No

Q11a If you selected “Yes”, indicating interest in participating in a further study, please enter a valid email address below to be eligible:

Needs Assessment Questionnaire:

Exploring decisions about managing chronic pain

If you have made a treatment decision about your chronic pain please fill out questions 1-26 only. If you have still to make a treatment decision about your chronic pain please fill out questions 27-52 only.

Now that you have agreed to participate in the study, and mentioned that you have made a treatment decision about your chronic pain, I will begin to ask you questions about your current approach to managing your chronic pain, your past experiences making a decision about your chronic pain, and what type of information you would need to make future decisions.

Part I

1. Have you sought the care of / from any of the following health professionals for your chronic pain? Please indicate yes or no to the following list:

Yes No

- | | | |
|--------------------------|--------------------------|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | Acupuncturist |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | GP doctor |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | Chiropractor |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | Dietitian / Nutritionist |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | Emergency room / urgent care centre / walk-in clinic |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | Exercise physiologist / Personal trainer / Health coach |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | Chronic pain specialist |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | Homeopathic doctor |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | Massage therapist |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | Naturopathic doctor |

Nurse / Nurse practitioner

Occupational therapist

Social prescriber

Pharmacist

Physician

Physiotherapist

Surgeon

Other: _____

Part II: Making a Decision

You noted earlier that you made a treatment decision (i.e. decided to start, stop, switch, or not use a specific treatment) about your chronic pain. Please think about the last time you made a decision about managing your chronic pain.

2. Can you tell me what the decision was about?

Please specify: _____

When you were thinking about your options for this recent decision.....

3. Did you feel worried about what could go wrong?

Yes

No

4. Did you feel distressed or upset?

Yes

No

5. Did you feel like you couldn't get the decision off your mind?

- Yes
- No

6. Did you waiver (or keep changing your mind) between the choices that you faced?

- Yes
- No

7. Did you want to delay the decision?

- Yes
- No

8. Did you question what was important to you?

- Yes
- No

9. Did you feel physically or mentally stressed (have tense muscles, a racing heartbeat or difficulty sleeping) about making this decision?

- Yes
- No

10. Were you able to play the role you wanted in the decision?

- Yes
 - No
-

Part III: Preparation for decision making.

When considering this same treatment decision about your chronic pain (i.e. decided to start, stop, switch, or not use a specific treatment):

11 Did you know which options were available to you?

- Yes
- No

12. Did you know the benefits and risks of each option?

- Yes
- Unsure
- No

13. Did you know how likely (the chances of) each of the benefits and harms were?

- Yes
- Unsure
- No

14. Were you clear about which benefits and harms matter most to you?

- Yes
- Unsure
- No

15. Did you choose without pressure from others?

- Yes
- Unsure
- No

16. Did you have enough support and advice to make a choice?

- Yes
- Unsure
- No

17. Did you feel motivated or ready to make the decision?

- Yes
- Unsure
- No

18. Did you feel you had the ability or skill to make this type of decision?

- Yes
- Unsure
- No

19. Did you feel sure about the best choice for you?

- Yes
- Unsure
- No

Part III: Steps in Decision-Making

The following questions ask about the steps you took in considering this same treatment decision about your chronic pain (i.e. decided to start, stop, switch, or not use a specific treatment):

20. Did you have information on the options, and their benefits and harms?

- Yes
- Unsure
- No

21. Did you have information on how likely each of the benefits and harms were to occur?

- Yes
- Unsure
- No

22. Did you get information on what others decide or recommend?

- Yes
- Unsure
- No

22a. If yes, from whom?

- Personal doctor
- Other doctors
- Spouse/partner
- Other (Specify):

23. Did you do anything else to make your decision?

- Yes (Specify):

- Unsure
- No

Part IV Future Decisions

24. If you have to make a future chronic pain treatment decision (i.e. decided to start, stop, switch, or not use a specific treatment), what information would you want? (Check all that apply).

- Information about chronic pain
- Information about drug therapies
- Information about non-drug therapies (such as exercise, acupuncture)
- Help considering the personal importance of the benefits and risks
- Guidance in the steps of making a decision
- Information on what others decide or recommend
- Other (Specify): _____

25. In what format would you prefer this information? *Read list, and check all that apply.*

- Booklets or pamphlets
- Videos/DVDs
- Website
- In a table on one or two sided A4 paper (option grid)
- CD-ROMs
- Television
- Animated videos
- Illustrations
- An app for phones and/or tablets
- Newspapers
- Magazines
- Personal communication with your doctor

- Discussion groups with other people living with chronic pain, including online discussions and social networks
- Information sessions held in your community
- Other (Specify): _____

26. What sources of information would you consider trustworthy? *Read list, and check all that apply.*

- Pharmacies
- Societies (British Pain Society, etc.)
- Medical and health care specialists
- Governments (including health departments)
- Health insurance companies
- Private companies that sell drugs and health products
- Consumer associations
- Not-for-profit companies that produce health information
- Other:

Thank you very much for completing this questionnaire. This information will help us improve educational materials for people facing difficult health care decisions.

Next, I will be creating a pen and paper version of a decision aid that has been developed to help people like yourself understand the different treatment options for chronic pain.

If you wrote your email on the attitudes survey I will email you again after I have created the decision aid to complete another set of questions that will ask about your opinions and for feedback on the decision aid.

Needs Assessment Questionnaire:

Exploring decisions about managing chronic pain

Now that you have agreed to participate in the study, and mentioned that you have yet to make a treatment decision about your chronic pain, I will begin to ask you questions about your current approach to managing your chronic pain, your current experience in making a decision about your chronic pain, and what type of information you would need to make future decisions.

Part I

27. Have you sought the care of / from any of the following health professionals for your chronic pain? Please indicate yes or no to the following list:

- | Yes | No | |
|--------------------------|--------------------------|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | Acupuncturist |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | GP doctor |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | Chiropractor |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | Dietitian / Nutritionist |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | Emergency room / urgent care centre / walk-in clinic |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | Exercise physiologist / Personal trainer / Health coach |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | Chronic pain specialist |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | Homeopathic doctor |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | Massage therapist |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | Naturopathic doctor |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | Nurse / Nurse practitioner |

Occupational therapist

Social prescriber

Pharmacist

Physician

Physiotherapist

Surgeon

Other: _____

Part II: Making a Decision

You noted earlier that you have still to make a treatment decision (i.e. decide to start, stop, switch, or not use a specific treatment) about your chronic pain. Please think about the current decision you may need to make about managing your chronic pain.

28. Can you tell me what the decision is/will be about?

Please specify: _

When you are thinking about your options for this current/future decision.....

29. Do you feel worried about what could go wrong?

- Yes
- No

30. Do you feel distressed or upset?

- Yes
- No

31. Do you feel like you can't get the decision off your mind?

- Yes
- No

32. Do you waiver (or keep changing your mind) between the choices that you face?

- Yes
- No

33. Do you want to delay the decision?

- Yes
- No

34. Do you question what is important to you?

- Yes
- No

35. Do you feel physically or mentally stressed (have tense muscles, a racing heartbeat or difficulty sleeping) about making this decision?

- Yes
- No

36. Do you feel able to play the role you want in the decision?

- Yes
- No

Part III: Preparation for decision making.

When considering this same treatment decision about your chronic pain (i.e. deciding to start, stop, switch, or not use a specific treatment):

37. Do you know which options are available to you?

- Yes
- No

38. Do you know the benefits and risks of each option?

- Yes
- Unsure
- No

39. Do you know how likely (the chances of) each of the benefits and harms are?

- Yes
- Unsure
- No

40. Are you clear about which benefits and harms matter most to you?

- Yes
- Unsure
- No

41. Do you feel able to choose without pressure from others?

- Yes
- Unsure
- No

42. Do you have enough support and advice to make a choice?

- Yes

- Unsure
- No

43. Do you feel motivated or ready to make the decision?

- Yes
- Unsure
- No

44. Do you feel you have the ability or skill to make this type of decision?

- Yes
- Unsure
- No

45. Do you feel sure about the best choice for you?

- Yes
- Unsure
- No

The following questions ask about the steps you are taking in considering this same treatment decision about your chronic pain (i.e. decided to start, stop, switch, or not use a specific treatment):

46. Do you have information on the options, and their benefits and harms?

- Yes
- Unsure
- No

47. Do you have information on how likely each of the benefits and harms are to occur?

- Yes
- Unsure
- No

48. Do you get information on what others decide or recommend?

- Yes
- Unsure
- No

48a. If yes, from whom?

- Personal doctor
 - Other doctors
 - Spouse/partner
 - Other (Specify): _____
-

49. Are you doing anything else to make your decision?

- Yes (Specify): _____
 - Unsure
 - No
-

Part IV Future Decisions

50. If you have to make a future chronic pain treatment decision (i.e. decided to start, stop, switch, or not use a specific treatment), what information would you want? (Check all that apply).

- Information about chronic pain
- Information about drug therapies
- Information about non-drug therapies (such as exercise, acupuncture)
- Help considering the personal importance of the benefits and risks
- Guidance in the steps of making a decision
- Information on what others decide or recommend
- Other (Specify): _____

51. In what format would you prefer this information? *Read list, and check all that apply.*

- Booklets or pamphlets
- Videos/DVDs
- Website
- In a table on one or two sided A4 paper (option grid)
- CD-ROMs
- Television
- Animated videos
- Illustrations
- An app for phones and/or tablets
- Newspapers
- Magazines
- Personal communication with your doctor
- Discussion groups with other people living with chronic pain, including online discussions and social networks
- Information sessions held in your community
- Other (Specify): _____

52. What sources of information would you consider trustworthy? *Read list, and check all that apply.*

- Pharmacies
- Societies (British Pain Society, etc.)
- Medical and health care specialists
- Governments (including health departments)
- Health insurance companies
- Private companies that sell drugs and health products
- Consumer associations
- Not-for-profit companies that produce health information
- Other: _____

Thank you very much for completing this questionnaire. This information will help us improve educational materials for people facing difficult health care decisions.

Next, I will be creating a pen and paper version of a decision aid that has been developed to help people like yourself understand the different treatment options for chronic pain.

If you wrote your email on the attitudes survey I will email you again after I have created the decision aid to complete another set of questions that will ask about your opinions and for feedback on the decision aid.

Appendix H: Study 2 Information Sheet

Participant Information Sheet

Investigating the Influence of Pain and Readiness to Change on Attitudes towards Shared Decision-making in Chronic Pain Patients.

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

What is the purpose of this study?

The purpose of the study is to investigate the predictors of acceptance of shared decision making by patients with chronic pain.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen to take part in this study because you are an individual with chronic pain which makes you a key stakeholder for the current study.

Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form. If you decide to take part you are still free to withdraw only up until the point that the questionnaire is submitted without giving a reason by

contacting a member of the research team with the unique identifier you will create and give as part of the study.

What will happen to me if I take part?

You will be asked to fill out 4 surveys either online or paper versions. The time to complete all questionnaires will take around 30-40 minutes. The questionnaires will ask for some demographic information and assess your pain type, duration, intensity, persistent baseline level and breakthrough levels of pain, readiness to change, attitudes to shared decision making and your decisional needs. You can keep these documents and fill them out at home in your own time. Individuals who take a paper copy of the surveys will need to either post me their completed surveys and consent form or scan and email them to me when finished. Contact details for both of these methods can be found on page 2.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

There are no disadvantages of taking part, however there are some questions which ask you to report on your chronic pain. Due to the nature of the topic, reflecting on your chronic pain and wellbeing may be difficult and upsetting. If the study raises any concerns for you about your chronic pain, you should contact your health care provider or speak to a family member or friend. Alternatively, you may wish to contact a chronic pain helpline. See: www.painconcern.org.uk for helplines in the UK. You will also find chronic pain support and advice contact information at the end of the study on the debrief sheet.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

It cannot be guaranteed that you will experience any direct benefits from taking part in the research, although the responses from the interview may be used to inform the design and implementation of a decision aid for chronic pain which would better support/implement standard practice of shared decision making and decision aids within the UK and also help patients with chronic pain with their treatment. Following successful evaluation and review, the aim will be to spread, adapt and scale-up the methodology and product for use in other NHS Boards.

Data Protection Privacy Notice

The data controller for this project will be University of the West of Scotland (UWS). The UWS Data Protection Office provides oversight of UWS activities involving the processing of personal data, and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. UWS's Data Protection Officer is Andy Connor and he can also be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk.

Your personal data will be processed for the purposes outlined in this notice. The legal basis that would be used to process your personal data will be the provision of your consent. You can provide your consent for the use of your personal data in this project by completing the consent form that has been provided to you. Your personal data will be processed so long as it is required for the research project. If we are able to anonymise or pseudonymise the personal data you provide we will undertake this, and will endeavour to minimise the processing of personal data wherever possible.

If you are concerned about how your personal data is being processed, please contact UWS in the first instance at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. If you remain unsatisfied, you may wish to contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). Contact details, and details of data subject rights, are available on the ICO website at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights/>

What will happen to the results of the research study?

Only anonymised data will be shared outside of the research team. Data will be stored at UWS, either in a locked filing cabinet or on a password protected computer for up to ten years after the study finishes, after which it will be destroyed. The findings from this study will be written up as part of the researcher's PhD thesis, as peer reviewed journal articles, and/or presented at conferences/seminars. All data will be reported anonymously.

Who has reviewed the study?

UWS MCS Ethics Committee. Ethics approval number: 2019-8446-6985

Contact for further information

If you require any further information please contact:

Researcher: Abbie McGuire

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley,

PA1 2BE

UK

Telephone: [REDACTED]

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

Research Supervisor:

Elizabeth Boyle

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley,

PA1 2BE

UK

[REDACTED]

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

Appendix I: Study 2 Consent Form

RESEARCH INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Title of Project: Investigating the Influence of Pain and Readiness to Change on Attitudes towards Shared Decision-making in Chronic Pain Patients.

Ethics Approval Number: 2019-8446-6985

Investigator(s): Abbie McGuire

Researcher Email: Abbie.McGuire@uws.ac.uk

Please read the following statements and, if you agree, initial the corresponding box to confirm agreement:

I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.

Initials

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw only up until the point that the questionnaire is submitted without giving any reason.

Initials

I consent to the processing of my personal information (survey responses) for the purposes explained to me. I understand that such information will be handled in accordance with all applicable data protection legislation.

Initials

I understand that my data will be treated confidentially and any publication resulting from this work will report only data that does not identify me.

Initials

I freely agree to participate in this study.

Initials

Signatures:

Name of participant (block capitals):

Name of researcher (block capitals):

ABBIE MCGUIRE

Date

Date

Signature

Signature

Appendix J: Study 2 Debrief Sheet

Debriefing Form

Investigating the Influence of Pain and Readiness to Change on Attitudes towards Shared Decision-making in Chronic Pain Patients.

Thank you taking part in this study. This study aimed to investigate the predictors of acceptance of shared decision-making (SDM) by patients with chronic pain. The study specifically examined if differences in the type of pain suffered by patients with chronic pain, persistent baseline level and breakthrough levels of pain and differences in patients' readiness to change influenced their attitudes to SDM. I also wanted to gather information from chronic pain patients on their decisional needs (i.e. what they want/need from a chronic pain decision aid such as what information they would want regarding treatment of their condition and what format they would prefer this information to be in).

It is expected that patients who experience more severe baseline pain, more frequent breakthrough levels of pain and patients who exhibit decreased readiness to change will have more negative attitudes to shared decision making but that they will be the patients who would benefit the most from shared decision making and from using a decision aid for chronic pain. The ultimate aim/value of the research is to examine/determine what factors influence the acceptance of SDM in patients with chronic pain and to incorporate this information into a DA for chronic pain as, in addition to having a considerable impact on the quality of life for many individuals and their families in Scotland, the condition also has a substantial impact on society, the healthcare services and on economic costs. Joosten et al. (2008) found that SDM improved longer term outcomes in several studies that explored both mental and physical health conditions. Positive impacts were observed on patient's adherence to plans, satisfaction, knowledge and well-being. Bieber et al. (2004) looked at the effects of SDM in patients with Fibromyalgia syndrome which is an exemplary condition of chronic widespread pain. They found that patients' readiness to enrol in physical activities, to take analgesics, and to participate in psychotherapeutic elements were most likely to be raised through SDM. It promotes self-management and independence which are crucial for chronic pain patients to treat their pain. By giving patients a full understanding of their problems and greater responsibility for making choices, it also helps to reduce over-use of medical interventions. (Picker Institute Europe, 2010).

If you would like more information about this research once it is completed, please contact the researcher:

Abbie McGuire

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley,

PA1 2BE

UK

Telephone: [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

Or my director of studies:

Elizabeth Boyle

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley,

PA1 2BE

UK

Telephone: [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

If you are interested in this area of research, you may wish to read the following references:

- Coulter, A. & Collins, A. (2011). Making shared decision-making a reality: No decision about me, without me. London: The King's Fund.

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If this research has caused you any distress or discomfort and you would like to speak to someone please contact the following sources of support and advice:

- Pain Concern (0300 123 0789)
- The Samaritans (116 123) or NHS 24 (111) for urgent support

If you have any complaints or feel that you have been affected by the study in any way please contact:

Professor Jim McKechnie (Head of Psychology):

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

Or

Nicola McGuigan (Chair of Education & Social Sciences ethics committee):

[REDACTED]

Appendix K: Non-significant Secondary Results Study 2

Non-Significant Secondary Hypotheses

As explained in Chapter 5, there were numerous secondary hypotheses that were tested and to help keep the findings concise, only the significant results for the tests performed on the secondary variables were reported in Chapter 5. The non-significant results of the analyses involving the secondary hypotheses can be viewed in this Appendix.

Hypotheses Related to the Primary Variables

In this section, non-significant analyses which were performed on the secondary hypotheses related to the primary variables are presented.

Baseline Pain Intensity

S H1 PAIN. The Impact of Participants' Baseline Pain Intensity on Preferred Consultation Style

Table K1 below shows participants' active or passive preference for involvement as a function of participants' baseline pain intensity.

Table K1

Preference for Involvement by Participants' Baseline Pain Intensity

	Active	Passive
Mild	24	2
Moderate	80	5
Severe	79	5

A logistic regression was performed to ascertain the effects of participants' baseline pain intensity on the likelihood that participants prefer an active or passive consultation style. The logistic regression model was not statistically significant, $\chi^2(2) = .116, p = .944$. The model explained 0.2% (Nagelkerke R^2) of the variance in preferred consultation style and correctly classified 93.8% of cases. Therefore, participant's baseline pain intensity did not predict their preferred consultation style.

Readiness to Change

S H3 READINESS. The Impact of Participants' Readiness to Change on Preferred Consultation Style

A point-biserial correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between participants' readiness to change and preferred consultation style. The correlation between readiness to change and preferred consultation style was not statistically significant ($rpb = .045, n = 195, p = .530$). Therefore, participants' readiness to change was not significantly associated with their preferred consultation style.

Decisional Needs

Decisional Needs: Decisional Conflict

S H5 DECISION. The Impact of Participants' Decisional Conflict on Preferred Consultation Style

A point-biserial correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between decisional conflict and preferred consultation style. The correlation between decisional conflict and preferred consultation style was not statistically significant ($rpb = -.057, n = 195, p = .215$). Therefore, decisional conflict was not significantly associated with participants' preferred consultation style.

Decisional Needs: Preparation for Decision-making

S H8 DECISION. The Impact of Participants' Preparation for Decision-making on Knowledge of SDM

A Pearson correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between participants' preparation for decision-making and knowledge of SDM. The correlation between participants' preparation for decision-making and knowledge of SDM, was not statistically significant ($r = .099$, $n = 195$, $p = .086$). Therefore, participants' preparation for decision-making was not significantly associated with participants' knowledge of SDM.

Additional Secondary Hypotheses

In this section, the non-significant analyses which were performed on the remaining secondary hypotheses are presented.

Additional Pain Variables

Additional analyses were carried out on three further pain-related variables: participants' breakthrough pain intensity, their type of pain and their duration of pain on participants' acceptance of SDM. However, only one of these additional pain analyses were significant: participants' breakthrough pain intensity on their knowledge of SDM. The remaining non-significant pain analyses are presented.

Breakthrough Pain Intensity

S H9 PAIN. The Impact of Participants' Breakthrough Pain Intensity on Attitudes towards SDM

As is shown in Table K2 below, the mean scores for attitudes towards SDM was 3.00 (SD=0.00) for participants that had mild to moderate breakthrough pain and 2.62 (SD=0.65) for participants that had severe breakthrough pain.

Table K2

Participants' Attitudes towards SDM by Participants' Breakthrough Pain Intensity

	No. of Participants	Mean	Standard Deviation
Mild to Moderate	8 (4.1%)	3.00	0.00

Severe	149 (76.4%)	2.62	0.65
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To assess if there was a difference in attitudes towards SDM for the participants who had mild to moderate breakthrough pain intensity and who had severe breakthrough pain intensity, independent t-tests were performed. No significant difference was found between groups for attitudes towards SDM scores [$T(155) = 1.625, p = .106$], indicating that participants' breakthrough pain intensity was not related to their attitudes towards SDM.

S H10 PAIN. The Impact of Participants' Breakthrough Pain Intensity on Preferred Consultation Style

Table K3 below shows participants' active or passive preference for involvement as a function of participants' breakthrough pain intensity.

Table K3

Preference for Involvement by Participants' Breakthrough Pain Intensity

	Active	Passive
Mild to Moderate	7	1
Severe	139	10

A logistic regression was performed to ascertain the effects of participants' breakthrough pain intensity on the likelihood that participants prefer an active or passive consultation style. The logistic regression model was not statistically significant, $\chi^2(1) = .325, p = .568$. The model explained 0.5% (Nagelkerke R^2) of the variance in preferred consultation style and correctly classified 93.0% of cases. Therefore, participant's breakthrough pain intensity did not predict their preferred consultation style.

Type of Pain

S H12 PAIN. The Impact of Participants' Type of Pain on Attitudes towards SDM

As is shown in Table K4 below, the mean scores for attitudes towards SDM was 2.70 (SD=0.66) for participants that had persistent baseline pain, 2.70 (SD=0.48) for participants that had breakthrough

pain, 2.64 (SD=0.65) for participants that had both types of pain and 3.00 (SD=0.00) for participants that had neither type of pain.

Table K4

Participants' Attitudes towards SDM by Participants' Type of Pain

	No. of Participants	Mean	Standard Deviation
Persistent Baseline Pain	37 (19.0%)	2.70	0.66
Breakthrough Pain	10 (5.1%)	2.70	0.48
Both	146 (74.9%)	2.64	0.65
Neither	2 (1.0%)	3.00	0.00

To assess whether there were differences in attitudes towards SDM between the different pain type groups, a one-way ANOVA was performed. No statistically significant differences were found between the pain groups for attitude scores ($F(3,191) = .312, p = .817$), indicating that the type of pain experienced by the participant did not impact on their attitudes towards SDM.

S H13 PAIN. The Impact of Participants' Type of Pain on Preferred Consultation Style

Table K5 shows participants' active or passive preference for involvement as a function of participants' type of chronic pain.

Table K5

Preference for Involvement by Participants' Type of Pain

	Active	Passive
Persistent Baseline Pain	36	1
Breakthrough Pain	9	1
Both	136	10
Neither	2	0

A logistic regression was performed to ascertain the effects of participants' type of pain on the likelihood that participants prefer an active or passive consultation style. The logistic regression model was not statistically significant, $\chi^2(3) = 1.545, p = .672$. The model explained 2.1% (Nagelkerke R^2) of the variance in preferred consultation style and correctly classified 93.8% of cases. Therefore, participant's type of pain did not predict their preferred consultation style.

S H14 PAIN. The Impact of Participants' Type of Pain on Knowledge of SDM

As is shown in Table K6 below, the mean scores for knowledge of SDM was 4.70 (SD=1.05) for participants that had persistent baseline pain, 4.20 (SD=1.48) for participants that had breakthrough pain, 4.48 (SD=0.93) for participants that had both types of pain and 4.00 (SD=1.41) for participants that had neither type of pain.

Table K6

Participants' Knowledge of SDM by Participants' Type of Pain

	No. of Participants	Mean	Standard Deviation
Persistent Baseline Pain	37 (19.0%)	4.70	1.05
Breakthrough Pain	10 (5.1%)	4.20	1.48
Both	146 (74.9%)	4.48	0.93
Neither	2 (1.0%)	4.00	1.41

To assess whether there were differences in knowledge of SDM between the different pain type groups, a one-way ANOVA was performed. No statistically significant differences were found between the pain groups for knowledge scores ($F(3,191) = 1.022, p = .384$), indicating that the type of pain experienced by the participant did not impact on their knowledge of SDM.

Pain Duration

S H15 PAIN. The Impact of Participants' Pain Duration on Attitudes towards SDM

A Pearson correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between pain duration and attitudes towards SDM. The correlation between pain duration and attitudes towards SDM, was not statistically significant ($r = -.022$, $n = 185$, $p = .764$). Therefore, participants' pain duration was not significantly associated with their attitudes towards SDM.

S H16 PAIN. The Impact of Participants' Pain Duration on Preferred Consultation Style

Table K7 below shows participant's active or passive preference for involvement means and standard deviations as a function of participant's pain duration (in weeks).

Table K7

Means (and Standard Deviations) for Preference for Involvement by Participants' Pain Duration

	Active (N = 174)	Passive (N = 11)
Pain Duration (Weeks)	926.22 (4757.44)	367.64 (457.79)

A point-biserial correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between participants' pain duration and preferred consultation style. The correlation between pain duration and preferred consultation style was not statistically significant ($r = -.029$, $n = 185$, $p = .698$). Therefore, participants' pain duration was not significantly associated with their preferred consultation style.

S H17 PAIN. The Impact of Participants' Pain Duration on Knowledge of SDM

A Pearson correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between pain duration and knowledge of SDM. The correlation between pain duration and knowledge of SDM, was not statistically significant ($r = .005$, $n = 185$, $p = .948$). Therefore, participants' pain duration was not significantly associated with their knowledge of SDM.

Additional Readiness to Change Variables

To explore the relationships between the individual subscales of the readiness to change questionnaire with participants' acceptance of SDM in more detail, correlations and regressions were carried out between all subscales. Significant correlations were found between the exercise, cognitive control and pacing sub-scales and knowledge of SDM, but no other correlations were significant. The remaining non-significant readiness to change subscale analyses are presented.

Exercise

S H18 READINESS. The Impact of Participants' Exercise on Attitude towards SDM

A Pearson correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between exercise and attitude towards SDM. The correlation between exercise and attitude towards SDM, was not statistically significant ($r = .022$, $n = 195$, $p = .380$). Therefore, exercise was not significantly associated with participants' attitudes towards SDM.

S H19 READINESS. The Impact of Participants' Exercise on Preferred Consultation Style

A point-biserial correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between exercise and preferred consultation style. The correlation between exercise and preferred consultation style was not statistically significant ($r_{pb} = -.037$, $n = 195$, $p = .304$). Therefore, exercise was not significantly associated with participants' preferred consultation style.

Avoiding Pain Contingent Rest

S H21 READINESS. The Impact of Participants' Avoiding Pain Contingent Rest on Attitude towards SDM

A Pearson correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between avoiding pain contingent rest and attitude towards SDM. The correlation between avoiding pain contingent rest and attitude towards SDM, was not statistically significant ($r = -.035$, $n = 195$, $p = .316$). Therefore, avoiding pain contingent rest was not significantly associated with participants' attitudes towards SDM.

S H22 READINESS. The Impact of Participants' Avoiding Pain Contingent Rest on Preferred Consultation Style

A point-biserial correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between avoiding pain contingent rest and preferred consultation style. The correlation between avoiding pain contingent rest and preferred consultation style was not statistically significant ($r_{pb} = .051, n = 195, p = .239$). Therefore, avoiding pain contingent rest was not significantly associated with participants' preferred consultation style.

S H23 READINESS. The Impact of Participants' Avoiding Pain Contingent Rest on Knowledge of SDM

A Pearson correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between avoiding pain contingent rest and knowledge of SDM. The correlation between avoiding pain contingent rest and knowledge of SDM, was not statistically significant ($r = -.031, n = 195, p = .335$). Therefore, avoiding pain contingent rest was not significantly associated with participants' knowledge of SDM.

Assertive Communication

S H24 READINESS. The Impact of Participants' Assertive Communication on Preferred Consultation Style

A point-biserial correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between assertive communication and preferred consultation style. The correlation between assertive communication and preferred consultation style was not statistically significant ($r_{pb} = .059, n = 195, p = .206$). Therefore, assertive communication was not significantly associated with participants' preferred consultation style.

S H25 READINESS. The Impact of Participants' Assertive Communication on Attitude towards SDM

A Pearson correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between assertive communication and attitude towards SDM. The correlation between assertive communication and attitude towards SDM, was not statistically significant ($r = -.011, n = 195, p = .882$). Therefore, assertive communication was not significantly associated with participants' attitudes towards SDM.

S H26 READINESS. The Impact of Participants' Assertive Communication on Knowledge of SDM

A Pearson correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between assertive communication and knowledge of SDM. The correlation between assertive communication and knowledge of SDM, was not statistically significant ($r = .046$, $n = 195$, $p = .526$). Therefore, assertive communication was not significantly associated with participants' knowledge of SDM.

Task Persistence

S H27 READINESS. The Impact of Participants' Task Persistence on Attitude towards SDM

A Pearson correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between task persistence and attitude towards SDM. The correlation between task persistence and attitude towards SDM, was not statistically significant ($r = .009$, $n = 195$, $p = .905$). Therefore, task persistence was not significantly associated with participants' attitudes towards SDM.

S H28 READINESS. The Impact of Participants' Task Persistence on Preferred Consultation Style

A point-biserial correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between task persistence and preferred consultation style. The correlation between task persistence and preferred consultation style was not statistically significant ($r_{pb} = -.016$, $n = 195$, $p = .826$). Therefore, task persistence was not significantly associated with participants' preferred consultation style.

S H29 READINESS. The Impact of Participants' Task Persistence on Knowledge of SDM

A Pearson correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between task persistence and knowledge of SDM. The correlation between task persistence and knowledge of SDM, was not statistically significant ($r = .110$, $n = 195$, $p = .126$). Therefore, task persistence was not significantly associated with participants' knowledge of SDM.

Relaxation

S H30 READINESS. The Impact of Participants' Relaxation on Attitude towards SDM

A Pearson correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between relaxation and attitude towards SDM. The correlation between relaxation and attitude towards SDM, was not statistically significant ($r = .055$, $n = 195$, $p = .444$). Therefore, relaxation was not significantly associated with participants' attitudes towards SDM.

S H31 READINESS. The Impact of Participants' Relaxation on Preferred Consultation Style

A point-biserial correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between relaxation and preferred consultation style. The correlation between relaxation and preferred consultation style was not statistically significant ($r_{pb} = -.051, n = 195, p = .477$). Therefore, relaxation was not significantly associated with participants' preferred consultation style.

S H32 READINESS. The Impact of Participants' Relaxation on Knowledge of SDM

A Pearson correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between relaxation and knowledge of SDM. The correlation between relaxation and knowledge of SDM, was not statistically significant ($r = .075, n = 195, p = .297$). Therefore, relaxation was not significantly associated with participants' knowledge of SDM.

Cognitive Control

S H33 READINESS. The Impact of Participants' Cognitive Control on Attitude towards SDM

A Pearson correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between cognitive control and attitude towards SDM. The correlation between cognitive control and attitude towards SDM, was not statistically significant ($r = .014, n = 195, p = .844$). Therefore, cognitive control was not significantly associated with participants' attitudes towards SDM.

S H34 READINESS. The Impact of Participants' Cognitive Control on Preferred Consultation Style

A point-biserial correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between cognitive control and preferred consultation style. The correlation between cognitive control and preferred consultation style was not statistically significant ($r_{pb} = .071, n = 195, p = .322$). Therefore, cognitive control was not significantly associated with participants' preferred consultation style.

Pacing

S H36 READINESS. The Impact of Participants' Pacing on Attitude towards SDM

A Pearson correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between pacing and attitude towards SDM. The correlation between pacing and attitude towards SDM, was not statistically significant ($r = -.018$, $n = 195$, $p = .802$). Therefore, pacing was not significantly associated with participants' attitudes towards SDM.

S H37 READINESS. The Impact of Participants' Pacing on Preferred Consultation Style

A point-biserial correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between pacing and preferred consultation style. The correlation between pacing and preferred consultation style was not statistically significant ($rpb = .012$, $n = 195$, $p = .866$). Therefore, pacing was not significantly associated with participants' preferred consultation style.

Avoiding Asking for Assistance

S H39 READINESS. The Impact of Participants' Avoiding Asking for Assistance on Attitude towards SDM

A Pearson correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between avoiding asking for assistance and attitude towards SDM. The correlation between avoiding asking for assistance and attitude towards SDM, was not statistically significant ($r = -.064$, $n = 195$, $p = .372$). Therefore, avoiding asking for assistance was not significantly associated with participants' attitudes towards SDM.

S H40 READINESS. The Impact of Participants' Avoiding Asking for Assistance on Preferred Consultation Style

A point-biserial correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between avoiding asking for assistance and preferred consultation style. The correlation between avoiding asking for assistance and preferred consultation style was not statistically significant ($rpb = .026$, $n = 195$, $p = .715$). Therefore, avoiding asking for assistance was not significantly associated with participants' preferred consultation style.

S H41 READINESS. The Impact of Participants' Avoiding Asking for Assistance on Knowledge of SDM

A Pearson correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between avoiding asking for assistance and knowledge of SDM. The correlation between avoiding asking for assistance and

knowledge of SDM, was not statistically significant ($r = -.065$, $n = 195$, $p = .368$). Therefore, avoiding asking for assistance was not significantly associated with participants' knowledge of SDM.

Proper Body Mechanics

S H42 READINESS. The Impact of Participants' Proper Body Mechanics on Attitude towards SDM

A Pearson correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between proper body mechanics and attitude towards SDM. The correlation between proper body mechanics and attitude towards SDM, was not statistically significant ($r = .031$, $n = 195$, $p = .672$). Therefore, proper body mechanics was not significantly associated with participants' attitudes towards SDM.

S H43 READINESS. The Impact of Participants' Proper Body Mechanics on Preferred Consultation Style

A point-biserial correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between proper body mechanics and preferred consultation style. The correlation between proper body mechanics and preferred consultation style was not statistically significant ($r_{pb} = .077$, $n = 195$, $p = .287$). Therefore, proper body mechanics was not significantly associated with participants' preferred consultation style.

S H44 READINESS. The Impact of Participants' Proper Body Mechanics on Knowledge of SDM

A Pearson correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between proper body mechanics and knowledge of SDM. The correlation between proper body mechanics and knowledge of SDM, was not statistically significant ($r = .131$, $n = 195$, $p = .067$). Therefore, proper body mechanics was not significantly associated with participants' knowledge of SDM.

Demographic Variables

Demographic variables that might influence acceptance of SDM include age, gender, education level and employment status. In this section, non-significant analyses performed on the demographic variables are presented.

Age

S H45 AGE. The Impact of Participants' Age Group on Attitudes towards SDM

As Table K8 shows below, the mean scores for participants' attitudes towards SDM was 2.60 (SD=0.68) for participants aged under 50 years old and 2.73 (SD=0.58) for those aged 50 years or older.

Table K8

Participants' Attitudes towards SDM by Age Group

	No. of Participants	Mean	Standard Deviation
Under 50 years old	107 (54.9%)	2.60	0.68
50+ years old	88 (45.1%)	2.73	0.58

To assess if there was a difference in participants' attitudes towards SDM as a result of their age group, an independent t-test was performed. No difference was found between age groups for participants' attitudes towards SDM [$T(193) = -1.401, p = .163$], indicating that participants' age group was not related to their attitudes towards SDM.

S H47 AGE. The Impact of Participants' Age Group on Knowledge of SDM

As Table K9 below shows, the mean scores for participants' knowledge of SDM was 4.39 (SD=1.02) for participants aged under 50 years old and 4.64 (SD=0.94) for participants aged 50 years and older.

Table K9

Participants' Knowledge of SDM by Age Group

	No. of Participants	Mean	Standard Deviation
Under 50 years old	107 (54.9%)	4.39	1.02
50+ years old	88 (45.1%)	4.64	0.94

To assess if there was a difference in participants' knowledge of SDM as a result of their age group, an independent t-test was performed. No difference was found between age groups for participants' knowledge of SDM [$T(193) = -1.727, p = .086$], indicating that participants' age group was not related to their knowledge of SDM.

Gender

S H48 GENDER. The Impact of Gender on Attitudes towards SDM

As shown in Table K10 below, attitudes towards SDM for females was 2.67 (SD=0.63) and for males was 2.58 (SD=0.70).

Table K10

Participants' Attitudes towards SDM by Participants' Gender

	No. of Participants	Mean	Standard Deviation
Female	169 (87.5%)	2.67	0.63
Male	26 (13.3%)	2.58	0.70

To assess if there was a difference in attitudes towards SDM for female and male participants, an independent samples t-tests were performed. The independent samples t-test showed that this difference was not significant [$T(193) = .677, p = .499$], that is there was no gender difference in patients' attitudes towards SDM.

S H49 GENDER. The Impact of Gender on Preferred Consultation Style

Preference for involvement in medical decision-making with respect to gender can be seen in Table K11 below.

Table K11

Preference for Involvement by Participant's Gender

	Active	Passive	Total
Male	24	2	26
Female	159	10	169
Total	183	12	195

A chi-square test of independence was performed to examine the relation between participant's gender and preference for involvement. The relation between these variables was not significant, X^2

(1, $N = 195$) = .123, $p = .363$, indicating that preference for a more active role in SDM was not related to participants' gender.

S H50 GENDER. The Impact of Gender on Knowledge of SDM

As shown in Table K12 below, knowledge of SDM for females was 4.52 (SD=0.98) and for males was 4.38 (SD=1.02).

Table K12

Participants' Knowledge of SDM by Participants' Gender

	No. of Participants	Mean	Standard Deviation
Female	169 (87.5%)	4.52	0.98
Male	26 (13.3%)	4.38	1.02

To assess if there was a difference in knowledge of SDM for female and male participants, an independent samples t-tests were performed. The independent samples t-test showed that this difference was not significant [$T(193) = .654$, $p = .257$], that is there was no gender difference in patients' knowledge of SDM.

Education Level

S H52 EDLEVEL. The Impact of Education Level on Preferred Consultation Style

Preference for involvement in medical decision-making as a function of level of education grouping can be seen in Table K13 below.

Table K13

Preference for Involvement by Education Grouping Level of Participants

	Active	Passive	Total
Further or Higher Education Degree	108	9	117
High School or Some Further/Higher Education	75	3	78

Total	183	12	195
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A chi-square test of independence was performed to examine the relation between participant education grouping level and preference for involvement. The relation between these variables was not significant, $\chi^2 (1, N = 195) = 1.199, p = .137$, indicating that preference for a more active role in SDM was not related to the education grouping of the individual.

S H53 EDLEVEL. The Impact of Education Level on Knowledge of SDM

As shown in Table K14 below, knowledge of SDM for participants with a higher education level was 4.54 (SD=0.99) and for participants with a lower education level was 4.45 (SD=0.99).

Table K14

Participants' Knowledge of SDM by Participants' Highest Education Level

	No. of Participants	Mean	Standard Deviation
Lower education level	78 (40.0%)	4.45	0.99
Higher education level	117 (60.0%)	4.54	0.99

To assess if there was a difference in knowledge of SDM for participants with a higher education level and participants with a lower education level, independent t-tests were performed. No difference was found between groups for knowledge of SDM scores [$T(193) = -.621, p = .535$], indicating that participants' highest education level was not related to their knowledge of SDM.

Employment Status

S H54 EMPLOY. The Impact of Employment Status on Attitudes towards SDM

As is shown in Table K15 below, the mean scores for attitudes towards SDM was 2.68 (SD=0.60) for those in employment and 2.63 (SD=0.68) for those not in employment.

Table K15

Participants' Attitudes towards SDM by Employment Status

	No. of Participants	Mean	Standard Deviation
Employed	98 (50.3%)	2.68	0.60
Not in Employment	97 (49.7%)	2.63	0.68

To assess if there was a difference in attitudes towards SDM for participants in employment and participants not in employment, independent t-tests were performed. No significant difference was found between groups for attitudes towards SDM scores [$T(193) = .595, p = .277$], indicating that participants employment status was not related to participants' attitudes towards SDM.

S H55 EMPLOY. The Impact of Employment Status on Preferred Consultation Style

Preference for involvement in medical decision-making as a function of participants' employment status can be seen in Table K16 below.

Table K16

Preference for Involvement by Participant's Employment Status

	Active	Passive
Employed	91	7
Unemployed	92	5

A chi-square test of independence was performed to examine the relation between participant's employment status and preference for involvement. The relation between these variables was not significant, $\chi^2(1, N = 195) = .334, p = .282$, indicating that preference for a more active role in SDM was not related to participants' employment status.

S H56 EMPLOY. The Impact of Employment Status on Knowledge of SDM

As is shown in Table K17 below, the mean scores for knowledge of SDM was 4.56 (SD=0.94) for those in employment and 4.44 (SD=1.03) for those not in employment.

Table K17

Participants' Knowledge of SDM by Participants' Employment Status

	No. of Participants	Mean	Standard Deviation
Employed	98 (50.3%)	4.56	0.94
Not in Employment	97 (49.7%)	4.44	1.03

To assess if there was a difference in knowledge of SDM for participants in employment and participants not in employment, independent t-tests were performed. No significant difference was found between groups for knowledge of SDM scores [$T(193) = .834, p = .203$], indicating that participants employment status was not related to participants' knowledge of SDM.

Health Related Variables

In addition to demographic variables, a number of health-related variables that might also impact on the acceptance of SDM were considered. These include awareness of SDM, whether participants had made a treatment decision or not regarding their chronic pain and attendance at medical appointments. In this section, non-significant analyses performed on the health variables are presented.

Awareness of SDM

S H58 AWARE. The Impact of Participants' Awareness of SDM on Preferred Consultation Style

Table K18 shows participants' active or passive preference for involvement as a function of participants' awareness of SDM.

Table K18

Preference for Involvement by Awareness of SDM

	Active	Passive

Previous Awareness of SDM	128	10
No Previous Awareness of SDM	55	2

A logistic regression was performed to ascertain the effects of participants' awareness of SDM on the likelihood that participants prefer an active or passive consultation style. The logistic regression model was not statistically significant, $\chi^2(1) = 1.081, p = .298$. The model explained 1.5% (Nagelkerke R^2) of the variance in preferred consultation style and correctly classified 93.8% of cases. Therefore, participants' awareness of SDM did not predict their preferred consultation style.

Made a Treatment Decision

S H61 TREATMENT. The Impact of Whether Participants Had Made a Treatment Decision on Preferred Consultation Style

Table K19 shows participants' active or passive preference for involvement as a function of whether participants had made a treatment decision.

Table K19

Preference for Involvement by Whether Participants Had Made a Treatment Decision

	Active	Passive
Made a treatment decision	136	10
Not made a treatment decision	47	2

A chi-square test of independence was performed to examine the relation between whether participants had made a treatment decision and preference for involvement. The relation between these variables was not significant, $\chi^2(1, N = 195) = .487, p = .485$, indicating that preference for a more active role in SDM was not related to whether participants had made a treatment decision.

Attendance at a Medical Appointment

S H63 ATT. The Impact of Attending a Medical Appointment on Attitudes towards SDM

As is shown in Table K20 below, the mean scores for attitudes towards SDM was 2.66 (SD=0.63) for participants that attended a medical appointment for their chronic pain and 2.64 (SD=0.84) for participants that did not attend a medical appointment for their chronic pain.

Table K20

Participants' Attitudes towards SDM by Attendance of a Medical Appointment

	No. of Participants	Mean	Standard Deviation
Attended a medical appointment	181 (92.8%)	2.66	0.63
Did not attend a medical appointment	14 (7.2%)	2.64	0.84

To assess if there was a difference in attitudes towards SDM for the participants who attended medical appointments and who did not attend medical appointments, independent t-tests were performed. No significant difference was found between groups for attitudes towards SDM scores [$T(193) = 0.082$, $p = .935$], indicating that participants' attendance of medical appointments was not related to their attitudes towards SDM.

S H64 ATT. The Impact of Participants' Attendance of a Medical Appointment on Preferred Consultation Style

Table K21 shows participants' active or passive preference for involvement as a function of attending a medical appointment. Since there were no patients in the group who had a passive preference and did not attend a medical appointment it was not appropriate to carry out chi square analysis.

Table K21

Preference for Involvement by Attendance of a Medical Appointment

	Active	Passive
Attended a medical appointment	169	12
Did not attend a medical appointment	14	0

Appendix L: Study 3 Survey

Investigating the Predictors of Engagement in Shared Decision-making in the General Population

Definition of Shared Decision-Making (SDM)

What is Shared Decision-Making (SDM)?

Shared Decision-making (SDM) can be defined as “the conversation that happens between a patient and their healthcare professional to reach a health care choice together (NHS shared decision making, 2012).

Participant Information

Healthcare Information

How frequently do you attend medical appointments/see a medical consultant? *

- Daily
- Weekly
- Fortnightly
- Monthly
- Every few months
- Every six months
- Yearly
- Every few years

Other (please specify):

How would you rate your health? *

Excellent

Very good

Good

Fair

Poor

Demographic Information

What is your age (years)? *

Please select your sex: *

Male

Female

What country were you born in? *

What country do you currently live in? *

What is your occupation? *

What is your highest level of education? *

Healthcare Attitude Survey

1) How do you think healthcare decisions should be made? (Please select one of the options below) *

- As the patient, I should make the final decision about which treatment I should receive.
- As the patient, I should make the final decision about which treatment I should receive after seriously considering the healthcare professional's opinion.
- The healthcare professional should share responsibility with me for making the final decision about the treatment I should receive.
- The healthcare professional should make the final decision about which treatment I should receive after seriously considering my opinion.
- The healthcare professional should make the final decision about which treatment I should receive.

2) Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with the following statements regarding healthcare decisions: *

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Disagree Strongly
Shared decision-making can only be done with patients who are sufficiently educated and confident to discuss treatment or screening options with their clinician.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Doing shared decision making is unrealistic because it takes too much time.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Doing shared decision making is low on my priority list.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Physician payment should be based on how well they do shared decision making.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Having resources which summarize the risks and benefits of clinical decisions would be helpful (e.g. patient decision aid).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Patients should trust clinicians to make all decisions on their behalf.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

3) Read the following scenario. Please indicate: which decision style experienced clinicians should adopt in this situation. There are no right or wrong answers. Assume consent is obtained for each patient.

3a) A 45-year-old female presents to the Emergency Department. She requires an urgent emergency surgical intervention but is capable of giving consent.

What should the clinician do in this situation? *

- The clinician should use evidence-based information to decide on the best course of action for the patient and inform the patient of their decision.
- The clinician should share evidence-based information with the patient, and elicit the patient's preferences, so the patient and clinician can make an informed decision together.
- The clinician should share evidence-based information with the patient and allow the patient to make the decision on their own.
- The clinician should share evidence-based information with the patient and choose the best course of action for the patient.

3b) A 53-year-old male presents to his primary care clinician for an annual physical exam. The patient asks his provider about the need to screen for colorectal cancer.

What should the clinician do in this situation? *

- The clinician should use evidence-based information to decide on the best course of action for the patient and inform the patient of their decision.
- The clinician should share evidence-based information with the patient, and elicit the patient's preferences, so the clinician and patient can make an informed decision together.
- The clinician should share evidence-based information with the patient and allow the patient to make the decision on their own.
- The clinician should share evidence-based information with the patient and choose the best course of action for the patient.

4) Please indicate whether you feel each of the following statements is TRUE or FALSE. *

True	False
Shared decision-making is a process in which clinicians and patients work together, sharing information about options and preferred outcomes, in order to reach a mutual agreement on the best course of action.	<input type="radio"/>
Shared decision-making causes patients to feel uncertain about their decisions.	<input type="radio"/>
Shared decision-making increases patient decision regret.	<input type="radio"/>
Shared decision-making results in fewer patients choosing major surgery.	<input type="radio"/>

5) Please indicate whether you feel each of the following statements is TRUE or FALSE. *

True	False
Evidence shows that involving patients in making important healthcare decisions increases knowledge.	<input type="radio"/>
To promote shared decision making, the clinician will	<input type="radio"/>

indicate that alternative treatment or management options exist.

To promote shared decision making, the clinician will give information about the pros and cons of options that are considered reasonable (including taking 'no action')

To promote shared decision making, the clinician will support the patient in becoming informed and comparing options.

There is no need for the clinician to check the patient's understanding.

In the shared decision-making process, it is necessary to elicit the patient's preferences.

6) Please indicate whether you feel each of the following statements is TRUE or FALSE. *

True

False

Whenever possible, the clinician should integrate the patient's preferences in deciding what to do next.

A majority of patients do not want to engage in shared decision making with their clinician.

Even if the patient does not wish to be involved in the decision-making process, it is the clinician's role to encourage the patient to make a decision.

A majority of clinicians do not want to engage in shared decision making with their patients.

7) Had you heard of shared decision making before completing this survey? *

yes

no

8) How do you think healthcare decisions should be made? *

As the patient, I should make the final decision about which treatment I should receive.

As the patient, I should make the final decision about which treatment I should receive after seriously considering opinion.

The healthcare professional should share responsibility with me for making the final decision about the treatment.

The healthcare professional should make the final decision about which treatment I should receive after seriously

- The healthcare professional should make the final decision about which treatment I should receive.

Subjective Norms

Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with the following statements in relation to your healthcare: *

	Strongly Disagree						Strongly Agree
	-3	-2	-1	0	+1	+2	+3
Most people who are important to me would recommend that I engage in shared decision-making	<input type="radio"/>						
Most people who are important to me would think it preferable for me to engage in shared decision-making	<input type="radio"/>						
Most people who are important to me are in favor of me engaging in shared decision-making	<input type="radio"/>						

Perceived Behavioural Control (Self-Efficacy)

Please show how confident you feel in doing these things by selecting the number from 0 (not at all confident) to 4 (very confident) for each item listed below.

I feel confident that I can *

	Not at all confident					Very Confident
	0	1	2	3	4	
1) Get the facts about the healthcare choices available to me	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2) Get the facts about the benefits of each choice	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3) Get the facts about the risks and side effects of each choice	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4) Understand the information enough to be able to make a choice	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
5) Ask questions without feeling dumb	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
6) Express my concerns about each choice	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
7) Ask for advice	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
8) Figure out the choice that best suits me	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
9) Handle unwanted pressure from others in making my choice	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

10) Let the clinic team know what's best for me

11) Delay my decision if I feel I need more time

The Patient-Doctor Relationship

You will read nine statements that a person can make about his/her Health Care Professional (HCP). Please choose the appropriateness of each statement for your HCP by marking one number per statement. The meaning of the numbers is as follows:

1 = not at all appropriate

2 = somewhat appropriate

3 = appropriate

4 = mostly appropriate

5 = totally appropriate *

	1	2	3	4	5
1 My HCP helps me	<input type="radio"/>				
2 My HCP has enough time for me	<input type="radio"/>				
3 I trust my HCP	<input type="radio"/>				
4 My HCP understands me	<input type="radio"/>				

5 My HCP is dedicated to help me

6 My HCP and I agree on the nature of my medical symptoms

7 I can talk to my HCP

8 I feel content with my HCP's treatment

9 I find my HCP easily accessible

Intention

Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with the following statement in relation to your healthcare: *

Strongly							Strongly
Disagree							Agree
-3	-2	-1	0	+1	+2	+3	

I intend to engage in shared decision-making

Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with the following statement in relation to your healthcare: *

Very Unlikely							Very Likely
-3	-2	-1	0	+1	+2	+3	

To me, to engage in shared decision-making would be

Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with the following statement in relation to your healthcare: *

Very Low							Very High
-3	-2	-1	0	+1	+2	+3	

I believe that my chances to engage in shared decision-making are

Medical Decision in the Last Year

Have you attended a medical appointment and made a medical/treatment decision in the last year? *

yes

no » continue with Page « Debrief Sheet »

Behaviour (Shared decision-making)

Please indicate which health complaint/problem/illness the consultation was about:

Please indicate which decision was made:

Completely Strongly Somewhat Somewhat Strongly Completely
disagree Disagree Disagree Agree Agree Agree

My doctor made clear
that a decision needed to be made

My doctor wanted to
know exactly how I want
to be involved in making
the decision

My doctor told me that
there are different

options for treating my
medical condition

My doctor precisely
explained the
advantages and
disadvantages of the
treatment options

My doctor helped me
understand all the
information

My doctor asked me
which treatment option I
preferred

My doctor and I
thoroughly weighed the
different treatment
options

My doctor and I selected
a treatment option
together

My doctor and I reached
an agreement on how to
proceed

Nine statements related to the decision-making in your last medical consultation are listed below. For each statement please indicate how much you agree or disagree. *

Satisfaction with Healthcare Decision

You have made a medical decision concerning your healthcare with a healthcare professional. Answer the following questions about the decision. Please indicate to what extent each statement is true for you AT THIS TIME. Use the following scale to answer the questions. 1 = strongly disagree 2 = disagree 3 = neither agree nor disagree 4 = agree 5 = strongly agree *

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
1. I am satisfied that I was adequately informed about the issues important to the decision.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2. The decision that was made was the best decision possible for me personally.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3. I am satisfied that the decision was consistent with my personal values.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4. I expect to successfully carry out (or continue to carry out) the decision that was made.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
5. I am satisfied that this was my decision to make.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
6. I am satisfied with the decision.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Appendix M: Study 3 Information Sheet

Participant Information Sheet

Investigating the Predictors of Engagement in Shared Decision-making in the General Population

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

What is Shared Decision-Making (SDM)?

Shared Decision-making (SDM) can be defined as “the conversation that happens between a patient and their healthcare professional to reach a health care choice together (NHS shared decision making, 2012).

What is the purpose of this study?

The purpose of this study is to investigate the predictors of engagement in Shared Decision-making (SDM) in the general population.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen to take part in this study because you are a member of the general population that may have attended a medical appointment and made a medical/treatment decision in the last year which makes you a key stakeholder for the current study.

Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form. If you decide to take part you are still free to withdraw only up until the point that the questionnaire is submitted without giving a reason by contacting a member of the research team with the unique identifier you will create and give as part of the study.

What will happen to me if I take part?

You will be asked to fill out an online survey. The time to complete the survey will take around 10-20 minutes. The survey will ask for some demographic information and assess your preferred consultation style, attitudes toward SDM, knowledge of SDM, SDM awareness, self-efficacy in engaging in SDM, your relationship with your healthcare professional, subjective norms towards SDM and intention to engage in SDM.

One of the health questions will ask if you have made a medical/treatment decision in the last year. If you respond "yes", the survey will then also assess your engagement in SDM and satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

There are no disadvantages of taking part, however there are some questions which ask you to reflect on your health. Due to the nature of the topic, reflecting on your health may be difficult and upsetting. If the study raises any concerns for you about your health, you should contact your health care provider or speak to a family member or friend. Alternatively, you may wish to contact a helpline: The Samaritans (116 123) or NHS 24 (111) for urgent support.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

It cannot be guaranteed that you will experience any direct benefits from taking part in the research, although the responses from the survey may be used to better support/implement standard practice of shared decision making within the UK.

Data Protection Privacy Notice

The data controller for this project will be University of the West of Scotland (UWS). The UWS Data Protection Office provides oversight of UWS activities involving the processing of personal data, and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. UWS's Data Protection Officer is Andy Connor and he can also be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk.

Your personal data will be processed for the purposes outlined in this notice. The legal basis that would be used to process your personal data will be the provision of your consent. You can provide your consent for the use of your personal data in this project by completing the consent form that has been provided to you.

Your personal data will be processed so long as it is required for the research project. If we are able to anonymise or pseudonymise the personal data you provide we will undertake this, and will endeavour to minimise the processing of personal data wherever possible.

If you are concerned about how your personal data is being processed, please contact UWS in the first instance at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. If you remain unsatisfied, you may wish to contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). Contact details, and details of data subject rights, are available on the ICO website at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights/>

What will happen to the results of the research study?

Only anonymised data will be shared outside of the research team. Data will be stored at UWS on a password protected computer for up to ten years after the study finishes, after which it will be destroyed. The findings from this study will be written up as part of the researcher's PhD thesis, as

peer reviewed journal articles, and/or presented at conferences/seminars. All data will be reported anonymously.

Who has reviewed the study?

UWS School of Education & Social Science Ethics Committee. Ethics approval number:

Contact for further information

If you require any further information please contact:

Researcher:

Abbie McGuire

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley,

PA1 2BE

UK

Telephone: [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

Research Supervisor:

Elizabeth Boyle

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley,

PA1 2BE

UK

Telephone: [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

Thank you for taking part in this study.

Appendix N: Study 3 Consent Form

Participant Consent Form

Please read the following statements and, if you agree, tick the corresponding box to confirm agreement:

I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for this study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions (via email) and have had these answered satisfactorily. *

yes

no » continue with finish the survey

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw only up until the point that the questionnaire is submitted without giving any reason. *

yes

no » continue with finish the survey

I consent to the processing of my personal information (survey responses) for the purposes explained to me. I understand that such information will be handled in accordance with all applicable data protection legislation. *

yes

no » continue with finish the survey

I understand that my data will be treated confidentially and any publication resulting from this work will report only data that does not identify me. *

yes

no » continue with finish the survey

I freely agree to participate in this study. *

yes

no » continue with finish the survey

Please enter a unique ID (a memorable word or phrase e.g. “blue”) in the box below for your unique identifier. This will be for you only in case you wish to have your data deleted. You may want to keep this safe in case you change your mind about participating. This is used because your data will be anonymised and not linked to any personal information (such as name or email). *

Appendix O: Study 3 Debrief Sheet

Debriefing Form

Investigating the Predictors of Engagement in Shared Decision-making in the General Population

Thank you taking part in this study. This study aimed to identify the predictors of engagement in Shared Decision-making (SDM) in the general population. This is necessary because, whilst Shared Decision Making (SDM) is aimed to be standard practice in healthcare within the UK, successful implementation of SDM is patchy and not currently the norm within the UK. Identifying the predictors of engaging in SDM may be used to better support/implement standard practice of shared decision making within the UK.

If you would like more information about this research once it is completed, please contact the researcher:

Abbie McGuire

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley,

PA1 2BE

UK

Telephone: [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

Or my director of studies:

Elizabeth Boyle

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley,

PA1 2BE

UK

Telephone: [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

If you are interested in this area of research, you may wish to read the following references:

- Ajzen, I. (2011). The theory of planned behaviour: reactions and reflections.
- Coulter, A. & Collins, A. (2011). Making shared decision-making a reality: No decision about me, without me. London: The King's Fund.
- Elwyn, G., Laitner, S., Coulter, A., Walker, E., Watson, P., & Thomson, R. (2010). Implementing shared decision-making in the NHS. *British Medical Journal*, 341, c5146. doi: 10.1136/bmj.c5146.
- Elwyn, G., Frosch, D., Thomson, R., Joseph-Williams, N., Lloyd, A., Kinnersley, P., Cording, E., Tomson, D., Dodd, C., Rollnick, S., Edwards, A., & Barry, M. (2012). Shared decision making: a model for clinical practice. *Journal of general internal medicine*, 27(10), 1361-1367.
- Joseph-Williams, N., Lloyd, A., Edwards, A., Stobbart, L., Tomson, D., Macphail, S., Dodd, C., Brain, K., Elwyn, G., & Thomson, R. (2017). Implementing shared decision making in the NHS: lessons from the MAGIC programme. *Bmj*, 357, j1744.
- The Scottish Government. (2016). *A National Clinical Strategy for Scotland*. Edinburgh, Scotland: The Scottish Government.

- Thompson-Leduc, P., Clayman, M. L., Turcotte, S., & Légaré, F. (2015). Shared decision-making behaviours in health professionals: a systematic review of studies based on the Theory of Planned Behaviour. *Health Expectations*, 18(5), 754-774.

If this research has caused you any distress or discomfort and you would like to speak to someone please contact the following sources of support and advice:

- The Samaritans (116 123) or NHS 24 (111) for urgent support

If you have any complaints or feel that you have been affected by the study in any way please contact:

Professor Jim McKechnie (Head of Psychology):

██████████

████████████████████

Or

Iain McPhee (Chair of the School of Education and Social Sciences Ethics Committee):

████████████████████

Appendix P – Non-Significant Study 3 Secondary Analyses Results

Non-Significant Secondary Hypotheses

As explained in Chapter 6, there were numerous secondary hypotheses that were tested and to help keep the findings concise, only the significant results for the tests performed on the secondary variables were reported in Chapter 6. The non-significant results of the analyses involving the secondary variables can be viewed in this Appendix.

Relationships Between the Outcome Variables

The theory of planned behaviour was introduced into this study in the hope that the theory would provide a good framework for thinking about shared decision-making and that intention to engage and engagement in SDM behaviour would provide better measures of SDM than other measures used to assess engagement in SDM. We have already seen that intention was a moderate predictor of engagement in SDM behaviour. However, it was also useful to examine the relationship between the four outcome variables used in the study: intention to engage in SDM, engagement in SDM behaviour, preferred consultation style and satisfaction with the healthcare decision to establish how good they are as measures of engagement in SDM. Correlations between the outcome variables are shown in Table P1 below.

Table P1

Correlations between all Outcome Variables

	Preferred Consultation Style	Intention	SDM behaviour	Satisfaction
Preferred Consultation Style	1			
Intention	-.242**	1		

SDM behaviour	-.087	.448**	1	
Satisfaction	.026	.440**	.729**	1

Preferred consultation style

- **S H2 OV:** Participants who have higher scores for engagement in SDM will prefer an active consultation style.

A point-biserial correlation was run to determine the relationship between participants' preferred consultation style and engagement in shared decision-making. As shown in Table P1 above, there was a negative correlation between engagement and participants' preferred consultation style, which was not statistically significant ($r_{pb} = -.087$, $n = 146$, $p = .295$). This result was unexpected as it suggests that preference for an active or passive consultation style is unrelated to engagement in shared decision-making.

Satisfaction with the Healthcare Decision

- **S H5 OV:** Participants who prefer an active consultation style will have higher scores for satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

A point-biserial correlation was run to determine the relationship between participants' preferred consultation style and their satisfaction with the healthcare decision. As displayed in Table P1 above, the correlation between participants' satisfaction with the healthcare decision and their preferred consultation style was not statistically significant ($r_{pb} = .026$, $n = 146$, $p = .757$). Similarly, this result was unexpected as it suggests that preference for an active or passive consultation style is unrelated to satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

The TPB Variables as Predictors of Engagement in SDM Behaviours, Preferred Consultation Style and Satisfaction with the Healthcare Decision

The next set of secondary analyses that was carried out looked at the links between the TPB predictor variables (attitudes, subjective norms and self-efficacy) and engagement in SDM, preferred consultation style and satisfaction with the healthcare decision as outcome variables. While the correlation between these variables together and engagement in SDM behaviours was examined as a

primary hypothesis, it was useful to also explore these relationships individually. Table P2 below shows the correlations between these variables.

Table P2

Correlations between the TBP variables and the Outcome Variables

	Attitude	Subjective norm	Self-efficacy	SDM Behaviour	PCS	Satisfaction
Attitude	1					
Subjective norm	.295**	1				
Self-efficacy	.137*	.404**	1			
SDM Behaviour	.154	.251**	.331**	1		
PCS	-.238**	-.250**	-.061	-.087	1	
Satisfaction	.010	.219**	.226**	.729**	.026	1

To further explore the relationships between the theory of planned behaviour variables and the outcome variables, a series of regressions were also carried out.

Attitudes Towards SDM

- **S H6 ENGAGE:** Attitudes towards SDM will predict engagement in SDM.

Although the correlation between attitudes and engagement in SDM behaviour was not significant, a linear regression was carried out to investigate this relationship further. The results of the regression indicated that the model explained 2.4% of the variance and that the model was not a significant predictor of engagement in SDM behaviour, $F(1,144) = 3.518, p = .063$, although this result is marginal. Participants' attitudes did not statistically significantly predict their engagement in SDM behaviour ($B = .154, p = .063$), based on a two-tailed test.

- **S H8 SAT:** Attitudes towards SDM will predict satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

A linear regression was also carried out to investigate whether participants' attitudes towards SDM could significantly predict their satisfaction with the healthcare decision. The results of the regression indicated that the model explained 0.0% of the variance and that the model was not a significant predictor of satisfaction with the healthcare decision, $F(1,144) = 0.013, p = .908$. Participants' attitudes did not statistically significantly predict their satisfaction with the healthcare decision ($B = .010, p = .908$).

Self-efficacy

- **S H13 PCS:** Participants who have higher self-efficacy scores will prefer an active consultation style.

A point-biserial correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between participants' self-efficacy and preferred consultation style. As shown in Table P2 above, the correlation between self-efficacy and preferred consultation style was not statistically significant ($r = -.061, n = 210, p = .188$). Therefore, participants' self-efficacy scores were not significantly associated with their preferred consultation style.

Demographic Variables

Age

The first demographic variable that was tested in the current study was participants' age. Correlations were carried out to examine how participants' age were related to their engagement in SDM behaviour, preferred consultation style and satisfaction with the healthcare decision. As Table P3 below shows, none of the outcome variables: engagement in SDM behaviour, preferred consultation style and satisfaction with the healthcare decision were significantly correlated with age.

Table P3

Correlations between Age & Outcome Variables

	Age	SDM Behaviour	Preferred Consultation Style	Satisfaction with the Healthcare Decision
Age	1			
SDM Behaviour	.080	1		
Preferred Consultation Style	-.092	-.087	1	
Satisfaction with the Healthcare Decision	-.003	.729**	.026	1

- **S H15 ENGAGE:** Younger participants will have higher scores for engagement in shared decision-making.

A Pearson correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between age and SDM Behaviour. As shown in Table P3 above, the correlation was not statistically significant ($r = .080$, $n = 146$, $p = .168$), showing that, contrary to our prediction, younger participants did not have higher scores for engagement in SDM.

- **S H16 PCS:** Younger participants will prefer an active consultation style.

A point-biserial correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between participants' age and preferred consultation style. As displayed in Table P3 above, the correlation between age and preferred consultation style was not statistically significant ($r = -.092$, $n = 210$, $p = .093$). Therefore, participants age was not significantly associated with their preferred consultation style.

- **S H17 SAT:** Older participants will have higher scores for satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

A Pearson correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between age and satisfaction with their healthcare decision. As shown in Table P3 above, the correlation was not statistically significant ($r = -.003$, $n = 146$, $p = .487$), suggesting that older participants were not more satisfied with the healthcare decision.

Gender

The second demographic variable that was tested in the current study was participants' gender. Independent samples t-tests and a chi-square test of independence were carried out to examine how participants' gender was related to their engagement in SDM behaviour, preferred consultation style and satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

- **S H18 ENGAGE:** Female participants will have higher scores for engagement in SDM.

As Table P4 shows below, the mean scores for SDM Behaviour was 37.86 (SD=11.36) for female participants and 37.93 (SD=10.11) for male participants.

Table P4

Engagement in SDM behaviour by Gender

	No. of Participants	Mean	Standard Deviation
Female	118 (80.8%)	37.86	11.36
Male	28 (19.2%)	37.93	10.11

To assess whether there was a difference in engagement in SDM behaviour for female and male participants, independent t-tests were performed. No significant difference was found between groups in engagement in SDM behaviour scores [$T(144) = .027$, $p = .489$], indicating that participants' gender did not impact on their engagement in SDM Behaviour.

- **S H19 PCS:** Female participants will prefer an active consultation style.

Preference for involvement in medical decision-making with respect to gender can be seen in Table P5 below.

Table P5

Preference for Involvement by Participant's Gender

	Active (N = 194)	Passive (N = 16)
Male	41	5
Female	153	11

A chi-square test of independence was performed to examine the relation between participant's gender and preference for involvement. The relation between these variables was not significant, $\chi^2(1, N = 210) = .884, p = .347$, indicating that preference for a more active role in consultations was not related to participants' gender.

- **S H20 SAT:** Male participants will have higher scores for satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

As shown in Table P6 below, satisfaction with the healthcare decision for females was 24.17 (SD=5.75) and for males was 24.50 (SD=3.83).

Table P6

Satisfaction with the Healthcare Decision by Gender

	No. of Participants	Mean	Standard Deviation
Female	118 (80.8%)	24.17	5.75
Male	28 (19.2%)	24.50	3.83

An independent samples t-test showed that this difference was not significant [$T(144) = .289, p = .386$], i.e., there was no gender difference in patients' satisfaction with their healthcare decision.

Education Level

The next demographic variable that was tested in the current study was participants' education level. Independent samples t-tests and a chi-square test of independence were carried out to examine how participants' education level was related to their engagement in SDM behaviour, preferred consultation style and satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

- **S H21 ENGAGE:** Participants with higher levels of education will have higher scores for engagement in SDM.

As is shown in Table P7 below, the mean score for SDM behaviour was 37.97 (SD=10.89) for those with a post-secondary education level and 36.84 (SD=12.03) for those with no post-secondary education level.

Table P7

Participants Engagement in SDM by Participants Highest Education Level

	No. of Participants	Mean	Standard Deviation
Post-secondary education level	120 (82.8%)	37.97	10.89
No post-secondary education level	25 (17.2%)	36.84	12.03

To assess if there was a difference in engagement in SDM behaviour in relation to level of education, independent samples t-tests were performed. No significant difference was found between groups in their SDM behaviour scores [$T(143) = -.462, p = .322$], indicating that participants' highest education level was not related to their engagement in SDM behaviour.

- **S H22 PCS:** Participants with higher levels of education will prefer an active consultation style.

Preference for involvement in medical decision making as a function of level of education grouping can be seen in Table P8 below.

Table P8

Preference for Involvement by Education Grouping Level of Participants

	Active (N = 194)	Passive (N = 16)
Further or Higher Education Degree	127	11
High School or Some Further/Higher Education	67	5

A chi-square test of independence was performed to examine the relation between participant education grouping level and preference for involvement. The relation between these variables was not significant, $\chi^2 (1, N = 210) = 0.071, p = .790$, indicating that preference for a more active role in SDM was not related to the education grouping of the individual.

- **S H23 SAT:** Participants with a higher education level will have lower scores for satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

As shown in Table P9 below, satisfaction with the healthcare decision for participants with a higher education level was 24.06 (SD=5.76) and for participants with a lower education level was 24.55 (SD=4.77).

Table P9

Satisfaction with the Healthcare Decision by Highest Education Level

	No. of Participants	Mean	Standard Deviation
Higher education level	95 (65.1%)	24.06	5.76
Lower education level	51 (34.9%)	24.55	4.77

To assess if there was a difference in satisfaction with the healthcare decision for participants with a higher education level and participants with a lower education level, an independent samples t-tests was performed. No difference was found between groups for satisfaction with the healthcare decision scores [$T(144) = -.515, p = .304$], indicating that satisfaction with the healthcare decision was not impacted by participants' highest education level.

Employment Status

The final demographic variable that was tested in the current study was participants' employment status. Independent samples t-tests and a chi-square test of independence were carried out to examine how participants' employment status was related to their engagement in SDM behaviour, preferred consultation style and satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

- **S H24 ENGAGE:** Employment status will be associated with engagement in shared decision-making.

As is shown in Table P10 below, the mean scores for SDM behaviour were 37.23 (SD=12.65) for those in employment and 38.45 (SD=9.53) for those not in employment.

Table P10

Participants' Engagement in SDM Behaviour by Employment Status

	No. of Participants	Mean	Standard Deviation
Employed	69 (47.3%)	37.23	12.65
Not in Employment	77 (52.7%)	38.45	9.53

To assess if there was a difference in engagement in SDM behaviour for participants in employment and participants not in employment, independent t-tests were performed. No significant difference was found between groups for engagement in SDM behaviour scores [$T(144) = -.664, p = .508$], indicating that employment status was not related to participants' engagement in SDM behaviour.

- **S H25 PCS:** Participants who are employed will prefer an active consultation style.

Preference for involvement in medical decision making as a function of participant's employment status can be seen in Table P11 below.

Table P11

Preference for Involvement by Participant's Employment Status

	Active	Passive
Employed	91	7
Unemployed	103	9

A chi-square test of independence was performed to examine the relation between participant's employment status and preference for involvement. The relation between these variables was not significant, $\chi^2(1, N = 210) = .059, p = .808$, indicating that preference for a more active role in SDM was not related to participants' employment status.

- **S H26 SAT:** Employment status will be associated with satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

As is shown in Table P12 below, the mean scores for satisfaction with the healthcare decision was 23.57 (SD=6.14) for those in employment and 24.83 (SD=4.65) for those not in employment.

Table P12

Engagement in SDM by Employment Status

	No. of Participants	Mean	Standard Deviation
Employed	69 (47.3%)	23.57	6.14
Not in Employment	77 (52.7%)	24.83	4.65

To assess if there was a difference in satisfaction with the healthcare decision for participants in employment and participants not in employment, independent t-tests were performed. No significant difference was found between groups [$T(144) = -1.413, p = .160$], indicating that participants' employment status was not related to participants' satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

Health-related Variables

Frequency of Attending Medical Appointments

The first health-related variable that was tested in the current study was participants' frequency of attending a medical appointment. A logistic regression, one-way ANOVA and an independent samples t-test were carried out to examine how participants' frequency of attending a medical appointment were related to their engagement in SDM behaviour, preferred consultation style and satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

- **S H27 ENGAGE:** Engagement in SDM will differ based on the frequency of attending medical appointments.

Table P13 below shows the number and percentage of participants in each category relating to the frequency of attending a medical appointment along with the mean scores and standard deviations for SDM behaviour. The majority of participants attended medical appointments every few months (43.2%).

Table P13

Engagement in SDM Behaviour by Participants' Frequency of Attending a Medical Appointment

	No. of Participants	Mean	Standard Deviation
Weekly	2 (1.4%)	36.50	24.75
Fortnightly	5 (3.4%)	37.00	15.12
Monthly	8 (5.5%)	42.25	8.29
Every Few Months	63 (43.2%)	38.57	10.67
Every Six Months	22 (15.1%)	39.95	10.23
Yearly	33 (22.6%)	35.58	11.16
Every Few Years	10 (6.8%)	35.50	14.07
Other	3 (2.1%)	32.00	9.64

To assess whether there were differences in engagement in SDM behaviour as a result of frequency of attending medical appointment groups, a one-way ANOVA was performed with frequency of attending a medical appointment as the independent variable and engagement as the dependent variable. There was no effect of frequency of attending medical appointment groups for engagement in shared decision-making ($F(7,145) = .711, p = .663$), indicating that participants' engagement in SDM was not related to their frequency of attending medical appointments.

- **S H28 PCS:** Participants' frequency of attending medical appointments will predict their preferred consultation style.

Table P14 below shows participants' active or passive preference for involvement as a function of frequency of attending a medical appointment.

Table P14

Participants' Preferred Consultation Style by Participants' Frequency of Attending a Medical Appointment

	Active	Passive
Weekly	4	0
Fortnightly	6	0
Monthly	7	1
Every Few Months	73	5
Every Six Months	31	0
Yearly	45	6
Every Few Years	22	2
Other	6	2

A logistic regression was performed to ascertain the effects of participants' frequency of attending a medical appointment on the likelihood that participants prefer an active or passive consultation style. The logistic regression model was not statistically significant, $\chi^2(7) = 10.249, p = .175$. The model explained 11.4% (Nagelkerke R^2) of the variance in preferred consultation style and correctly classified

92.4% of cases. Therefore, participant’s frequency of attending a medical appointment did not predict their preferred consultation style.

- **S H29 SAT:** Participants who attend medical appointments more frequently will have higher scores for satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

As is shown in Table P15 below, the mean scores for satisfaction with the healthcare decision was 24.26 (SD=5.62) for participants who frequently attend medical appointments and 24.21 (SD=5.22) for participants who infrequently attend medical appointments.

Table P15

Satisfaction with the Healthcare Decision by Frequency of Attending Medical Appointments

	No. of Participants	Mean	Standard Deviation
Frequently attend medical appointments	78 (53.4%)	24.26	5.62
Infrequently attend medical appointments	68 (46.6%)	24.21	5.22

To assess if there was a difference in satisfaction with the healthcare decision for participants who frequently attended medical appointments compared with those who infrequently attended medical appointments, an independent t-test was performed. No significant difference was found between groups for satisfaction with the healthcare decision scores [$T(144) = 0.056, p = .478$], indicating that participants’ frequency of attending medical appointments was not related to their satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

Self-rated Health

The next health-related variable that was tested in the current study was participants’ self-rated health. Independent samples t-tests and a chi-square test of independence were carried out to examine how participants’ self-rated health was related to their engagement in SDM behaviour, preferred consultation style and satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

- **S H30 ENGAGE:** Participants who have better self-rated health will have higher scores for engagement in SDM.

As is shown in Table P16 below, the mean score for SDM behaviour was 38.32 (SD=10.57) for those with a better self-rated health and 36.57 (SD=12.56) for those with poorer self-rated health.

Table P16

SDM behaviour by Participants' Self-rated Health Groups

	No. of Participants	Mean	Standard Deviation
Better Self-rated Health	109 (74.7%)	38.32	10.57
Poorer Self-rated Health	37 (25.3%)	36.57	12.56

To assess if there was a difference in engagement in SDM for the groups of participants who were in better and poorer self-rated health, independent t-tests were performed. No significant difference was found between groups for engagement in SDM scores [$T(144) = 0.830, p = .204$], indicating that participants self-rated health status was not related to participants' engagement in SDM.

- **S H31 PCS:** Participants who have better self-rated health will prefer an active consultation style.

Table P17 below shows participants' active or passive preference for involvement as a function of participants' self-rated health groups.

Table P17

Preference for Involvement by Participants' Self-rated Health Groups

	Active	Passive
Better Self-rated Health	150	13
Poorer Self-rated Health	44	3

A chi-square test of independence was performed to examine the relation between participant's self-rated health and preference for involvement. The relation between these variables was not significant, $\chi^2 (1, N = 210) = .131, p = .717$, indicating that preference for a more active role in consultations was not related to participants' self-rated health.

- **S H32 SAT:** Participants who have better self-rated health will have higher scores for satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

As is shown in Table P18 below, the mean scores for satisfaction with the healthcare decision was 24.39 (SD=5.24) for participants who had better self-rated health and 23.76 (SD=5.98) for participants who had poorer self-rated health.

Table P18

Satisfaction with the Healthcare Decision by Self-rated Health Groups

	No. of Participants	Mean	Standard Deviation
Better Self-rated Health	109 (74.7%)	24.39	5.24
Poorer Self-rated Health	37 (25.3%)	23.76	5.98

To assess if there was a difference in satisfaction with the healthcare decision for the groups who were in better and poorer self-rated health, independent t-tests were performed. No difference was found between groups for satisfaction with the healthcare decision scores [$T(144) = 0.617, p = .269$], indicating that participants' satisfaction with the healthcare decision did not differ as a result of their self-rated health status.

Variables from Study 2

Knowledge of SDM

The first variable from study 2 that was tested in the current study was participants' knowledge of SDM. A logistic regression was carried out to examine if participants' knowledge of SDM predicted their preferred consultation style.

- **S H37 PCS:** Knowledge of SDM will predict preferred consultation style.

Table P19 below shows participants' active or passive preference for involvement means and standard deviations as a function of participant's knowledge of SDM.

Table P19

Means (and standard deviations) for Preference for Involvement by Knowledge of SDM

	Active (N = 194)	Passive (N = 16)
Knowledge of SDM	4.30 (1.07)	4.00 (1.15)

A logistic regression was performed to ascertain the effects of participants' knowledge of SDM on the likelihood that participants prefer an active or passive consultation style. The logistic regression model was not statistically significant, $\chi^2(1) = 1.121, p = .290$. The model explained 1.3% (Nagelkerke R^2) of the variance in preferred consultation style and correctly classified 92.4% of cases. Therefore, participant's knowledge of SDM did not predict their preferred consultation style.

Awareness of SDM

The final variable from study 2 that was tested in the current study was participants' awareness of SDM. Independent samples t-tests and a logistic regression were carried out to examine how participants' awareness of SDM was related to their engagement in SDM behaviour, preferred consultation style and satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

- **S H39 ENGAGE:** Participants who have previous awareness of SDM will engage more in shared decision-making.

As Table P20 below shows, the mean score for SDM behaviour was 39.10 (SD=11.22) for those with a previous awareness of SDM and 36.72 (SD=10.92) for those with no previous awareness of SDM.

Table P20

Engagement in SDM Behaviour by Awareness of Shared Decision-making

	No. of Participants	Mean	Standard Deviation
Previous Awareness of SDM	71 (48.6%)	39.10	11.22
No Previous Awareness of SDM	75 (51.4%)	36.72	10.92

To assess if there was a difference in engagement in SDM behaviour as a result of previous awareness of SDM, an independent t-test was performed. No difference was found between groups for engagement in SDM behaviour scores [$T(144) = 1.298, p = .098$], indicating that whether or not participants had previously been aware of SDM was not related to their engagement in SDM behaviour.

- **S H40 PCS:** Awareness of SDM will predict preferred consultation style.

Table P21 below shows participants' active or passive preference for involvement as a function of participants' awareness of SDM.

Table P21

Preference for Involvement by Participants' Awareness of SDM

	Active	Passive
Previous Awareness of SDM	89	4
No Previous Awareness of SDM	105	12

A logistic regression was performed to ascertain the effects of participants' awareness of SDM on the likelihood that participants prefer an active or passive consultation style. The logistic regression model was not statistically significant, $\chi^2(1) = 2.758, p = .097$. The model explained 3.1% (Nagelkerke R^2) of the variance in preferred consultation style and correctly classified 92.4% of cases. Therefore, participant's awareness of SDM did not predict their preferred consultation style.

- **S H41 SAT:** Participants who have previous awareness of SDM will be more satisfied with the healthcare decision.

As is shown in Table P22 below, the mean scores for satisfaction with the healthcare decision was 24.44 (SD=5.31) for participants who had previous awareness of SDM and 24.04 (SD=5.55) for participants who had no previous awareness of SDM.

Table P22

Satisfaction with the Healthcare Decision by Awareness of Shared Decision-making

	No. of Participants	Mean	Standard Deviation
Previous Awareness of SDM	71 (48.6%)	24.44	5.31
No Previous Awareness of SDM	75 (51.4%)	24.04	5.55

To assess if there was a difference in satisfaction with the healthcare decision for participants who had previous awareness of SDM and for participants who had no previous awareness of SDM, an independent t-test was performed. No significant difference was found between groups for satisfaction with the healthcare decision scores [$T(144) = .441, p = .330$], indicating that participants' previous awareness of SDM was not related to their satisfaction with the healthcare decision.

Appendix Q: Study 4 Interview Schedule (General Population)

Interview Schedule Study 4 – General Population

Opening A. (Establish Rapport): Hello, my name is Abbie McGuire. I am a PhD student at the University of the West of Scotland where I am carrying out research into shared decision-making in health decisions. As part of this research, I am interviewing members of the general population in Scotland and who have made a treatment decision regarding their healthcare about their views on and experiences of shared decision making. You have been selected to take part as a member of the general population in Scotland.

B. (Obtain consent) Before we proceed, I'd just like to confirm that you have read the information sheet and consent form for this study and that you consent to being audio and video recorded for this interview.

C. (Definitions): There may be differing definitions of shared decision-making. Therefore, for clarity and to avoid uncertainty and confusion, the definition which I am using for shared decision-making is:

Shared Decision-making (SDM) can be defined as “the conversation that happens between a patient and their healthcare professional to reach a health care choice together (NHS shared decision making, 2012).

D. (Purpose) I would like to ask you some questions concerning your views and experience of shared decision making in order to learn more about how shared decision making is used in practice and what factors are important for taking part in shared decision-making.

E. (Motivation) I hope to use this information to aid the successful implementation of SDM in Scottish NHS Boards.

F. (Timeline) The interview should take about 45-60 minutes.

G. (Responses) For all of the following questions, you are encouraged to provide as much detail as possible but I do have a series of prompts for these questions that might help you to think in more detail in case you are stuck for a response. Do you have any questions at this time or wish me to explain or elaborate on anything at this point before we begin?

(Transition: Let me begin by asking you some questions regarding your feelings towards shared decision-making)

Body A. (Topic) Feelings towards SDM

1. Can you tell me your feelings about shared decision-making.

prompts

- Can you tell me what you know about SDM?
- Can you tell me about how you usually like to make most healthcare decisions? When it comes to making decisions about your healthcare, do you talk this through with anyone?
- Can you tell me what factors may encourage or prevent you from taking part in SDM?
- How suitable do you think SDM is for all health conditions/medical decisions? Why?

(Transition: I will now move onto asking you some questions regarding how SDM can be beneficial for you)

Body B. (Topic) Benefits of SDM

2. How could shared decision-making be beneficial for you?

prompt

- How does your *health condition* (if mentioned) impact on your ability to take part in SDM?

(Transition: I will now move onto asking you questions regarding the decision-making process for your last treatment decision)

Body C. (Topic) Processes used in SDM

Think back to the last time you had to make a treatment decision in relation to your healthcare.

3. Can you tell me how you found the decision-making process from start to finish?

prompts

- Tell me about your discussion of the possible treatment options with the healthcare professional.
- Tell me about your discussion of the risks, benefits and potential consequences of each treatment option with the healthcare professional.
- Tell me how the healthcare professional may have learned more about you because of making this treatment decision.
- Tell me how the information you were given was tailored to your decision/location/health condition.
- Tell me about how the final decision made.
- Tell me about any other people that may have been involved in making the decision.
- Tell me how encouraged were you to take part in making the decision?
- Tell me about your personal preferences being considered in making the decision.
- Tell me about how much time was given to think about the decision.
- Tell me about how much you and the healthcare professional agreed on the final treatment decision.
- Tell me about any conflict or uncertainty you experienced in making the decision.
- Tell me about your relationship with your healthcare professional.
- Tell me how the relationship with your healthcare professional may have impacted on the decision that was made.
- Tell me how satisfied you are with the decision that was made.

Body E. (Topic) Engaging in SDM in the Future

(Transition: I will now move onto asking you some questions regarding future participation in shared decision-making.)

4. How do you feel about taking part in shared decision-making in the future?

prompts

- Tell me about the likelihood that you will take part in shared decision-making in the future? Why?
- Tell me about your confidence in being able to take part in shared decision-making. Why?
- Tell me about how satisfied you would be with final treatment decisions because of taking part in shared decision-making. Why?
- Tell me which healthcare professionals do you think are more likely to take part in shared decision-making? Why?

Body F. (Topic) Covid-19 Impact on SDM

(Transition: Finally, I will now move onto asking you some questions regarding the possible impact of COVID-19 on SDM)

5. Tell me about the impact you think COVID-19 had had or will have on shared decision-making.

prompt

- Tell me about the impact that remote consultations have had on shared decision-making.

Closing A. (Summarize) You have provided your opinion on shared decision-making. (Maintain Rapport) I appreciate the time you took for this interview. Is there anything else you think would be

helpful for me to know so that I can successfully implement shared decision-making into standard practice? C. (Action to be taken) I should have all the information I need. Would it be alright to email you if I have any more questions? Thanks again. I look forward to reviewing and using this information to inform my research.

Appendix R: Study 4 Interview Schedule (Chronic Pain)

Interview Schedule Study 4 – Chronic Pain

Opening A. (Establish Rapport): Hello, my name is Abbie McGuire. I am a PhD student at the University of the West of Scotland where I am carrying out research into shared decision-making in health decisions. As part of this research, I am interviewing individuals with chronic pain that have made a treatment decision regarding their healthcare and who live in Scotland about their views on and experiences of shared decision-making. You have been selected to take part as an individual with chronic pain living in Scotland.

B. (Obtain consent) Before we proceed, I'd just like to confirm that you have read the information sheet and consent form for this study and that you consent to being audio and video recorded for this interview.

C. (Definitions): There may be differing definitions of shared decision-making. Therefore, for clarity and to avoid uncertainty and confusion, the definition which I am using for shared decision-making is:

Shared Decision-making (SDM) can be defined as “the conversation that happens between a patient and their healthcare professional to reach a health care choice together (NHS shared decision making, 2012).

D. (Purpose) I would like to ask you some questions concerning your views and experience of shared decision making in order to learn more about how shared decision making is used in practice and what factors are important for taking part in shared decision-making.

E. (Motivation) I hope to use this information to aid the successful implementation of SDM in Scottish NHS Boards.

F. (Timeline) The interview should take about 45-60 minutes.

G. (Responses) For all of the following questions, you are encouraged to provide as much detail as possible but I do have a series of prompts for these questions that might help you to think in more detail in case you are stuck for a response. Do you have any questions at this time or wish me to explain or elaborate on anything at this point before we begin?

(Transition: Let me begin by asking you some questions regarding your feelings towards shared decision-making)

Body A. (Topic) Feelings towards SDM

1. Can you tell me your feelings about shared decision-making.

prompts

- Can you tell me what you know about SDM?
- Can you tell me about how you usually like to make most healthcare decisions? When it comes to making decisions about your healthcare, do you talk this through with anyone?
- Can you tell me what factors may encourage or prevent you from taking part in SDM?
- How suitable do you think SDM is for all health conditions/medical decisions? Why?

(Transition: I will now move onto asking you some questions regarding how SDM can be beneficial for you)

Body B. (Topic) Benefits of SDM

2. How could shared decision-making be beneficial for you?

prompt

- How does your chronic pain impact on your ability to take part in SDM?

(Transition: I will now move onto asking you questions regarding the decision-making process for your last treatment decision)

Body C. (Topic) Processes used in SDM

Think back to the last time you had to make a treatment decision in relation to your healthcare.

3. Can you tell me how you found the decision-making process from start to finish?

prompts

- Tell me about your discussion of the possible treatment options with the healthcare professional.
- Tell me about your discussion of the risks, benefits and potential consequences of each treatment option with the healthcare professional.
- Tell me how the healthcare professional may have learned more about you because of making this treatment decision.
- Tell me how the information you were given was tailored to your decision/location/health condition.
- Tell me about how the final decision made.
- Tell me about any other people that may have been involved in making the decision.
- Tell me how encouraged were you to take part in making the decision?
- Tell me about your personal preferences being considered in making the decision.
- Tell me about how much time was given to think about the decision.
- Tell me about how much you and the healthcare professional agreed on the final treatment decision.
- Tell me about any conflict or uncertainty you experienced in making the decision.
- Tell me about your relationship with your healthcare professional.
- Tell me how the relationship with your healthcare professional may have impacted on the decision that was made.
- Tell me how satisfied you are with the decision that was made.

Body E. (Topic) Engaging in SDM in the Future

(Transition: I will now move onto asking you some questions regarding future participation in shared decision-making.)

4. How do you feel about taking part in shared decision-making in the future?

prompts

- Tell me about the likelihood that you will take part in shared decision-making in the future? Why?
- Tell me about your confidence in being able to take part in shared decision-making. Why?
- Tell me about how satisfied you would be with final treatment decisions because of taking part in shared decision-making. Why?
- Tell me which healthcare professionals do you think are more likely to take part in shared decision-making? Why?

Body F. (Topic) Covid-19 Impact on SDM

(Transition: Finally, I will now move onto asking you some questions regarding the possible impact of COVID-19 on SDM)

5. Tell me about the impact you think COVID-19 had had or will have on shared decision-making.

prompt

- Tell me about the impact that remote consultations have had on shared decision-making.

Closing A. (Summarize) You have provided your opinion on shared decision-making. (Maintain Rapport) I appreciate the time you took for this interview. Is there anything else you think would be helpful for me to know so that I can successfully implement shared decision-making into standard practice? C. (Action to be taken) I should have all the information I need. Would it be alright to email you if I have any more questions? Thanks again. I look forward to reviewing and using this information to inform my research.

Appendix S: Study 4 Information Sheet (General Population)

Participant Information Sheet

A Qualitative Study of Attitudes to and Experiences of Shared Decision-making in Individuals Experiencing Chronic Pain and in the General Population.

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

What is the purpose of this study?

The purpose of the study is to examine individuals with chronic pain and members of the general population's views on and experiences of shared decision-making.

What is Shared Decision-Making (SDM)?

Shared Decision-making (SDM) can be defined as “the conversation that happens between a patient and their healthcare professional to reach a health care choice together (NHS shared decision making, 2012).

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen to take part in this study because you are a member of the general population in Scotland that has made a treatment decision regarding your healthcare.

Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part, you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to electronically sign a consent form. If you decide to take part, you are still free to withdraw at any time during the interview and up to 7 days after your interview is carried out without giving a reason by contacting a member of the research team.

What will happen to me if I take part?

You will be asked to partake in an interview (carried out over Zoom) which aims to gather individuals with chronic pain and members of the general population's views on shared decision-making. The interview will last around 45-60 minutes. There will be time set aside for answering any questions you may have before and after the interview questions occur.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

There are no disadvantages of taking part, however there are some questions which ask you to reflect on your healthcare experiences. Due to the nature of the topic, reflecting on your health or your healthcare experiences may be difficult and upsetting. If the study raises any concerns for you about your health, you should contact your health care provider or speak to a family member or friend. Alternatively, you may wish to contact a helpline: The Samaritans (116 123) or NHS 24 (111) for urgent support.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

It cannot be guaranteed that you will experience any direct benefits from taking part in the research, although the responses from the survey may be used to better support/implement standard practice of shared decision-making within the UK.

Data Protection Privacy Notice

The data controller for this project will be University of the West of Scotland (UWS). The UWS Data Protection Office provides oversight of UWS activities involving the processing of personal data, and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. UWS's Data Protection Officer is Andy Connor and he can also be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk.

Your personal data will be processed for the purposes outlined in this notice. The legal basis that would be used to process your personal data will be the provision of your consent. You can provide your consent for the use of your personal data in this project by completing the consent form that has been provided to you.

Your personal data will be processed so long as it is required for the research project. If we are able to anonymise or pseudonymise the personal data you provide we will undertake this, and will endeavour to minimise the processing of personal data wherever possible.

If you are concerned about how your personal data is being processed, please contact UWS in the first instance at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. If you remain unsatisfied, you may wish to contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). Contact details, and details of data subject rights, are available on the ICO website at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights/>

What will happen to the results of the research study?

Only anonymised data will be shared with and outside of the research team. Data will be stored at UWS on a password protected computer for up to ten years after the study finishes, after which it will be destroyed. The findings from this study will be written up as part of the researcher's PhD thesis, as peer reviewed journal articles, and/or presented at conferences/seminars. All data will be reported anonymously.

Who has reviewed the study?

UWS School of Education & Social Science Ethics Committee. Ethics approval number: 2021-16430-13876

Contact for further information

If you require any further information please contact:

Researcher:

Abbie McGuire

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley,

PA1 2BE

UK

Telephone: [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

Research Supervisor:

Dr Elizabeth Boyle

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley,

PA1 2BE

UK

Telephone: [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

Thank you for taking part in this study.

Appendix T: Study 4 Information Sheet (Chronic Pain)

A Qualitative Study of Attitudes to and Experiences of Shared Decision-making in Individuals Experiencing Chronic Pain and in the General Population.

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

What is the purpose of this study?

The purpose of the study is to examine individuals with chronic pain and members of the general population's views on and experiences of shared decision-making.

What is Shared Decision-Making (SDM)?

Shared Decision-making (SDM) can be defined as “the conversation that happens between a patient and their healthcare professional to reach a health care choice together (NHS shared decision making, 2012).

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen to take part in this study because you are an individual with chronic pain that lives in Scotland and that has made a treatment decision regarding your healthcare.

Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part, you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to electronically sign a consent form. If you decide to take

part you are still free to withdraw at any time during the interview and up to 7 days after your interview is carried out without giving a reason by contacting a member of the research team.

What will happen to me if I take part?

You will be asked to partake in an interview (carried out over Zoom) which aims to gather individuals with chronic pain and members of the general population's views on shared decision-making. The interview will last around 45-60 minutes. There will be time set aside for answering any questions you may have before and after the interview questions occur.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

There are no disadvantages of taking part, however there are some questions which ask you to reflect on your chronic pain. Due to the nature of the topic, reflecting on your chronic pain and healthcare experiences may be difficult and upsetting. If the study raises any concerns for you about your chronic pain, you should contact your health care provider or speak to a family member or friend. Alternatively, you may wish to contact a chronic pain helpline. See: www.painconcern.org.uk for helplines in the UK. You will also find chronic pain support and advice contact information at the end of the study on the debrief sheet.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

It cannot be guaranteed that you will experience any direct benefits from taking part in the research, although the responses from the interview may be used to support/implement standard practice of shared decision-making within the UK which may also help individuals with chronic pain with their treatment.

Data Protection Privacy Notice

The data controller for this project will be University of the West of Scotland (UWS). The UWS Data Protection Office provides oversight of UWS activities involving the processing of personal data, and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. UWS's Data Protection Officer is Andy Connor and he can also be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk.

Your personal data will be processed for the purposes outlined in this notice. The legal basis that would be used to process your personal data will be the provision of your consent. You can provide your consent for the use of your personal data in this project by completing the consent form that has been provided to you.

Your personal data will be processed so long as it is required for the research project. If we are able to anonymise or pseudonymise the personal data you provide we will undertake this, and will endeavour to minimise the processing of personal data wherever possible.

If you are concerned about how your personal data is being processed, please contact UWS in the first instance at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. If you remain unsatisfied, you may wish to contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). Contact details, and details of data subject rights, are available on the ICO website at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights/>

What will happen to the results of the research study?

Only anonymised data will be shared with and outside of the research team. Data will be stored at UWS, either in a locked filing cabinet or on a password protected computer for up to ten years after the study finishes, after which it will be destroyed. The findings from this study will be written up as part of the researcher's PhD thesis, as peer reviewed journal articles, and/or presented at conferences/seminars. All data will be reported anonymously.

Who has reviewed the study?

UWS School of Education & Social Science Ethics Committee. Ethics approval number: 2021-16430-13876

Contact for further information

If you require any further information please contact:

Researcher:

Abbie McGuire

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley,

PA1 2BE

UK

Telephone: [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

Research Supervisor:

Dr Elizabeth Boyle

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley,

PA1 2BE

UK

Telephone: [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

Thank you for taking part in this study.

Appendix U: Study 4 Consent Form

Participant Consent Form

Title of Project: A Qualitative Study of Attitudes to and Experiences of Shared Decision-making in Individuals Experiencing Chronic Pain and in the General Population.

Ethics Approval Number: 2021-16430-13876

Investigator(s): Abbie McGuire

Researcher Email:

Please read the following statements and, if you agree, select the corresponding box to confirm agreement:

I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for this study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions (via email) and have had these answered satisfactorily.

yes

no

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time during the interview and up to 7 days after my interview is carried out without giving any reason.

yes

no

I consent to the processing of my personal information (interview responses) for the purposes explained to me. I understand that such information will be handled in accordance with all applicable data protection legislation.

yes

no

I understand that my data will be treated confidentially and any publication resulting from this work will report only data that does not identify me.

yes

no

I consent to being video and audio recorded as part of this study.

yes

no

I freely agree to participate in this study.

yes

no

Signatures:

Name of participant (block capitals):

Name of researcher (block capitals):

ABBIE MCGUIRE

Date:

Date:

Signature:

Signature: Abbie McGuire

Or my director of studies:

Elizabeth Boyle

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley,

PA1 2BE

UK

Telephone: [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

If you are interested in this area of research, you may wish to read the following references:

- Bomhof-Roordink, H., Gärtner, F. R., Stiggelbout, A. M., & Pieterse, A. H. (2019). Key components of shared decision-making models: a systematic review. *BMJ open*, *9*(12), e031763.
- Coulter, A. & Collins, A. (2011). *Making shared decision-making a reality: No decision about me, without me*. London: The King's Fund.
- Joseph-Williams, N., Lloyd, A., Edwards, A., Stobbart, L., Tomson, D., Macphail, S., Dodd, C., Brain, K., Elwyn, G., & Thomson, R. (2017). Implementing shared decision making in the NHS: lessons from the MAGIC programme. *Bmj*, *357*, j1744.
- Thompson-Leduc, P., Clayman, M. L., Turcotte, S., & Légaré, F. (2015). Shared decision-making behaviours in health professionals: a systematic review of studies based on the Theory of Planned Behaviour. *Health Expectations*, *18*(5), 754-774.

If this research has caused you any distress or discomfort and you would like to speak to someone please contact the following sources of support and advice:

- The Samaritans (116 123) or NHS 24 (111) for urgent support

If you have any complaints or feel that you have been affected by the study in any way please contact:

Professor Jim McKechnie (Head of Psychology):

██████████

████████████████████

Or

Iain McPhee (Chair of the School of Education and Social Sciences Ethics Committee):

████████████████████

Appendix W: Study 4 Debrief Sheet (Chronic Pain)

Debriefing Form

A Qualitative Study of Attitudes to and Experiences of Shared Decision-making in Individuals Experiencing Chronic Pain and in the General Population.

Thank you taking part in this study. This study aimed to examine individuals with chronic pain and members of the general population's views on and experiences of shared decision-making. Shared Decision-making (SDM) can be defined as “the conversation that happens between a patient and their healthcare professional to reach a health care choice together (NHS shared decision making, 2012). Examining individuals with chronic pain and members of the general population's views on shared decision-making is necessary because, whilst Shared Decision Making (SDM) is aimed to be standard practice in healthcare within the UK, successful implementation of SDM is patchy within the UK as there isn't yet an agreed standard model of SDM. Identifying individuals with chronic pain and members of the general population's views on shared decision-making SDM may be used to better support/implement standard practice of shared decision-making within the UK.

If you would like more information about this research once it is completed, please contact the researcher:

Abbie McGuire

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley,

PA1 2BE

UK

Telephone: [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

Or my director of studies:

Elizabeth Boyle

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley,

PA1 2BE

UK

Telephone: [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

If you are interested in this area of research, you may wish to read the following references:

- Bomhof-Roordink, H., Gärtner, F. R., Stiggelbout, A. M., & Pieterse, A. H. (2019). Key components of shared decision making models: a systematic review. *BMJ open*, *9*(12), e031763.
- Coulter, A. & Collins, A. (2011). Making shared decision-making a reality: No decision about me, without me. London: The King's Fund.
- Joosten, E. A., DeFuentes-Merillas, L., De Weert, G. H., Sensky, T., Van Der Staak, C. P. F., & de Jong, C. A. (2008). Systematic review of the effects of shared decision-making on patient satisfaction, treatment adherence and health status. *Psychotherapy and psychosomatics*, *77*(4), 219-226.
- Joseph-Williams, N., Lloyd, A., Edwards, A., Stobbart, L., Tomson, D., Macphail, S., Dodd, C., Brain, K., Elwyn, G., & Thomson, R. (2017). Implementing shared decision making in the NHS: lessons from the MAGIC programme. *Bmj*, *357*, j1744.

If this research has caused you any distress or discomfort and you would like to speak to someone, please contact the following sources of support and advice:

Pain Concern (0300 123 0789)

The Samaritans (116 123) or NHS 24 (111) for urgent support

If you have any complaints or feel that you have been affected by the study in any way please contact:

Professor Jim McKechnie (Head of Psychology):

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

Or

Iain McPhee (Chair of the School of Education and Social Sciences Ethics Committee):

[REDACTED]